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Multiuser Detection for DS-CDMA Systems over Generalized-K Fading Channels using Particle Swarm Optimization

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ABSTRACT

In direct sequence-code division multiple accesses systems (DS-CDMA), the signals are transmitted over multipath channels that introduce fading. Multipath fading along with multiple access interference and inter-symbol interference degrades the system performance. Further, simultaneous presence of multipath fading and shadowing leads to worsening of wireless channels. Moreover, experimental results have confirmed the presence of impulsive noise in wireless mobile communication channels. This paper presents a robust multiuser detection technique for DS-CDMA systems over generalized-K (GK) fading channels in the presence of impulsive noise. Robust M -decor relating detector to demodulate binary phase shift keying (BPSK) signals is implemented by using the particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm. The PSO algorithm is used to obtain optimum M -estimates by minimizing an objective function, which is a sum of less rapidly increasing function of residuals. Simulation results are provided to show the evolutionary behavior and efficacy of the proposed M -estimator in comparison with linear decor relating detector, the Huber and the Hampel estimator based detectors.

Keywords: CDMA, influence function, maximal ratio combiner, M -estimator, multiuser detection, Nakagami fading, particle swarm optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent research has explored the potential benefits of evolutionary optimization algorithms and their application to multiuser detection (MUD) for direct-sequence code division multiple access (DS-CDMA) systems [1]-[4]. An adaptive robust MUD technique for CDMA by implementing Huber's M -estimator using genetic algorithm (GA) is presented in [3] and shown that it is robust against heavy-tailed impulsive noise. Recently, particle swarm

Optimization (PSO) algorithm has been applied for the MUD [4] to detect received data bit by optimizing an objective function.

The generalized-K (GK) fading channel has been received considerable attention as it can provide a good fit to different fading environments such as Nakagami- m and Rayleigh-Lognormal [5]. Experimental results have confirmed the presence of heavy-tailed impulsive noise in outdoor mobile

communication channels, in radar and sonar systems and in indoor wireless communication channels [6]. Hence, this paper presents the implementation and performance analysis of proposed based M-estimator [7], [10], which performs well in the heavy-tailed impulsive noise, using PSO algorithm.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider an L-user synchronous CDMA system, where each user transmits information by modulating a PN sequence over a single-path GK fading channel. The received signal over one symbol duration can be modeled as [8]

$$r(t) = \Re \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} b_l(i) \alpha_l(t) e^{j\phi(t)} s_l(t - iT_s - \tau_l) \right\} + n(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\Re\{\cdot\}$ denotes the real part, M is the number of data symbols per user in the data frame of interest, T_s is the symbol interval, $\alpha_l(t)$ is the time-varying fading gain of the l^{th} user's channel, $\phi(t)$ is the time-varying phase of the l^{th} user's channel, $b_l(i)$ is the i^{th} bit of the l^{th} user, $s_l(t)$ is the normalized signaling waveform of the l^{th} user and $n(t)$ is assumed as a zero-mean complex two-term non-Gaussian noise [9].

For synchronous case (i.e., $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = \dots = \tau_L = 0$), assuming that the fading process for each user varies at a slower rate that the magnitude and phase can taken to be constant over the duration of a bit, the received signal can be expressed in matrix notation as [9]

$$\underline{r}(i) = \underline{A}\underline{\theta}(i) + \underline{w}(i) \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{r}(i) \triangleq [r_1(i), \dots, r_N(i)]^T$,

$\underline{w}(i) \triangleq [w_1(i), \dots, w_N(i)]^T$ and

$\underline{\theta}(i) \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} [b_1(i)g_1(i), \dots, b_L(i)g_L(i)]^T$. Here, $w_n(i)$ is a sequence of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) complex random variables whose in-phase and quadrature components are independent non-Gaussian random variables, $g_l(i)$ is the l^{th} channel fading coefficient and

$\underline{A} \triangleq [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_L]$ with $a_l \triangleq [a_1^l, a_2^l, \dots, a_N^l]$.

It is assumed that the signal of each user arrives at the receiver through an independent, single-path fading channel. For the shadowed fading channels, $\alpha_l(i)$ are i.i.d. random variables with GK distribution given by [12]

$$p_\alpha(\alpha_l) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(\mu)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \right)^{m+\mu} \alpha_l^{\frac{m+\mu}{2}-1} K_{m-\mu} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \alpha_l \right) \quad (3)$$

where, m is the Nakagami fading parameter that determines the severity of the fading, μ represents the shadowing levels, Ω_0 is the average SNR in a shadowed fading channel, $K_\xi(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function [9]

In M-estimates, unknown parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_L$ are solved by minimizing a sum of function, $\rho(\cdot)$ of the residuals [9]

$$\hat{\theta} = F(\theta_l(i)) = \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{C}^L} \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \rho \left[\Re \left(r_n(i) - \sum_{l=1}^L [A]_{nl} \theta_l(i) \right) \right] + \rho \left[\Im \left(r_n(i) - \sum_{l=1}^L [A]_{nl} \theta_l(i) \right) \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

where $\rho(\cdot)$ represents a specific penalty function that is symmetric positive-definite with a unique minimum at zero, and is chosen to be less increasing than square, $r_n(i)$ and $\theta_l(i)$ are the n^{th} and l^{th} elements of the vectors $\underline{r}(i)$ and $\underline{\theta}(i)$ respectively, $[A]_{nl}$ is the nl^{th} element of the matrix \underline{A} , and $\Im(\cdot)$ denotes imaginary part. This paper considers the modified-Hampel based M-estimator to implement an M-decorrelating detector with penalty function [7]

$$\rho_{MH}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x^2}{2} & \text{for } |x| \leq a \\ \frac{a^2}{2} - a|x| & \text{for } a < |x| \leq b \\ -\frac{ab}{2} \exp \left(1 - \frac{|x|^2}{b^2} \right) + d & \text{for } |x| > b \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where a, b and d are constants that depend on the robustness of the estimator [7].

III. PSO BASED M-DECORRELATING DETECTOR

PSO is a swarm intelligence method for global optimization modeled after the social behavior of bird flocking and fish schooling [4]. In PSO algorithm the solution search is conducted using a population of individual particles, where each particle represents a candidate solution to the optimization problem (3). Each particle keeps track of the position of its individual best solution (called as \mathbf{p}_{d}^{best}), $\mathbf{p}_{d}^{best} = [p_{d_1}^{best}, \dots, p_{d_L}^{best}]$ and the overall global best solution (called as \mathbf{g}^{best}), $\mathbf{g}^{best} = [g_1^{best}, \dots, g_L^{best}]$ among p bests of all the particles in the population represented as $\mathbf{p}_d^{it} = [p_{d_1}^{it}, \dots, p_{d_L}^{it}]$, where \mathbf{p}_d^{it} is the dth particle in the itth iteration, $d = 1, 2, \dots, N_p$, $it = 1, 2, \dots, N_{it}$, N_p is the number of particles, and N_{it} is the maximum number of iterations. Corresponding to each position, the particle velocity is $\mathbf{v}_d^{it} = [v_{d_1}^{it}, \dots, v_{d_L}^{it}]$ [2], [4]. The steps involved in the PSO based M-decorrelating detector's implementation are [2], [3], [4]:

Step 1: Compute the decorrelating detector output,

$\mathbf{\theta}^0 = \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{r}$. Here, $\mathbf{R} (\triangleq \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A} / N)$ is the normalized cross-correlation matrix of signature waveforms of all users.

Step 2: Initialization: The output of decorrelating detector is taken as input first particle $\mathbf{d}_1^0 = \mathbf{\theta}_1^0$.

Step 3: Fitness evaluation: The objective function (3) is used to find the fitness vector by substituting residuals. Local best position \mathbf{p}_d^{best} is recorded by looking at the history of each particle and the particle with lowest fitness is taken as \mathbf{g}^{best} of the population.

Step 4: Update the inertia weight by using the decrement function $w^{it} = \beta w^{it-1}$, where $\beta < 1$ is the decrement constant.

Step 5: Update the particle velocity by using the relations

$$\mathbf{v}_d^{it+1} = w^{it+1} \times \mathbf{v}_d^{it} + \overbrace{c_1 \times \mu_1 \times (\mathbf{p}_d^{best} - \mathbf{p}_d^{it})}^{\text{privatethinking of the particle}} + \overbrace{c_2 \times \mu_2 \times (\mathbf{g}^{best} - \mathbf{p}_d^{it})}^{\text{socialthinking of the particle}} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_d^{it+1} = \mathbf{p}_d^{it} + \mathbf{v}_d^{it+1} \quad (7)$$

where c_1 and c_2 are the acceleration constants representing the weighting of the stochastic acceleration terms to pull the particle to \mathbf{p}_{best} and \mathbf{g}_{best} . μ_1 and μ_2 are random numbers that are uniformly distributed between 0 and 1. Particle position is updated according to (6). Particle velocity is limited by the maximum velocity $\mathbf{v}^{max} = [v_1^{max}, \dots, v_2^{max}]$.

Step 6: The individual best particle position is

$$\text{updated by following rule: } \begin{cases} \text{if } F(\mathbf{p}_d^{it}) \leq F(\mathbf{p}_d^{best}) \\ \text{then } \mathbf{p}_d^{best} = \mathbf{p}_d^{it} \end{cases}$$

Step 7: \mathbf{g}^{best} is the global best particle position among all the individual best particle positions \mathbf{p}_d^{it} at the itth iteration such that $F(\mathbf{g}^{best}) \leq F(\mathbf{p}_d^{it})$.

Step 8: The above steps are repeated until the maximum number of iterations has been reached.

The computed \mathbf{g}^{best} value is used to evaluate average probability of error of BPSK demodulator, over GK fading channel, by an approximate expression given by

$$\overline{P_e^1} = F \cdot \frac{1}{2} \alpha^{-0.5l} \beta^{-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{1+d+l}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{1-d+l}{2}\right) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{\beta^2}{8\alpha}\right) W_{-0.5l,d}\left(\frac{\beta^2}{4\alpha}\right) \quad (8)$$

where m is the Nakagami fading parameter that determines the severity of the fading, μ represents the shadowing levels, Ω_0 is the average SNR in a shadowed fading channel

$$F = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(\mu)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}}\right)^{m+\mu}, \quad d = m - \mu, \quad l = \frac{m+\mu}{2} - 1,$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{v^2 [R^{-1}]_{11}} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = 2 \sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \quad \text{and} \quad W_{\lambda,\gamma}(\cdot) \text{ is the}$$

Whittaker function [13].

TABLE I. PSO PARAMETERS USED FOR SIMULATION

Parameter	Value
Number of particles, N_p	20
Maximum number of iterations, N_{it}	100
Acceleration constants c_1 and c_2	2
Maximum velocity of the particles $ v_l^{max} $ for all users	2
Initial inertial weight, w	1
Decrement constant, β	0.99

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the performance of M-decorrelating detector is presented by computing (7) for for different values of fading parameters and shadowing levels with least-squares, Huber, Hampel and modified-Hampel penalty functions. The PSO parameters used for simulation are presented in Table I. The value of g^{best} is computed for specified penalty functions and is used to compute the average probability of error (7) of BPSK signals. In Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, the average probability of error versus the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) corresponding to the user 1 under perfect power control of a synchronous DS-CDMA system with six users ($L = 6$) and processing gain, $N = 31$ is plotted for moderate impulsiveness ($\epsilon = 0.01$) of noise, $m = 1, \mu = 1$. Similarly, the average probability of error is plotted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 with highly impulsive noise ($\epsilon = 0.1$) and $m = 1, \mu = 1$. These simulation results show that the decorrelating detector with proposed estimator based detector performs well even in highly impulsive noise when compared to least-squares, Huber and Hampel estimator based detectors.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Multuser detection technique for DS-CDMA systems over GK fading channels using PSO was presented in this paper. An objective function, which is a sum of less rapidly increasing function of residuals, was used to obtain optimum estimates. An M-decorrelator is implemented with different influence functions. Simulation results shows that the proposed M-decorrelator performs better when

compared to least-squares, Huber and Hampel estimator based detectors.

Fig.1 Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M-estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31, \epsilon = 0.01, m = 1, \mu = 1$.

Fig.2 Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M-estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31, \epsilon = 0.01, m = 2, \mu = 2$.

Fig.3 Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and

proposed M-estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$, $m = 1$, $\mu = 1$.

Fig.4 Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M-estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$, $m = 2$, $\mu = 2$.

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A Novel methods of ICI self Cancellation Scheme in OFDM System

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ABSTRACT

In OFDM System the Frequency offset in wireless communication systems distort the Orthogonality between subcarriers resulting in Inter Carrier Interference(ICI). This Paper presents a new scheme for ICI self cancellation which is simple and convenient technique. It utilize data allocation and combining of (λ_{so}, μ_{so}) on to a pair of symmetrically placed subcarriers to reduce the ICI. In proposed scheme we are maximizing CIR performance for a normal frequency offset ε . In this method the CIR performance is about more than 20dB better than that of normal OFDM for Small values of frequency offset ε and having same bandwidth efficiency for larger Doppler frequency. Simulation results show that comparing proposed scheme with standard OFDM system and conventional ICI self cancellation. In simulation results we found that the performance of proposed scheme is better than the standard OFDM system and conventional ICI self cancellation.

Keywords: ICI, CIR, OFDM, CFO, etc...

I. INTRODUCTION

The orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is a form of multi-carrier modulation technique OFDM transmission [1] achieves high spectral efficiency by splitting a high-rate data stream into several lower-rate streams which are mapped onto mutually overlapping subcarriers and transmitted simultaneously. By inserting a cyclic prefix of length larger than the maximum channel delay spread, the inter symbol interference can be easily avoided and the demodulation of OFDM signals can be realized by a one-tap equalizer. Motivated by these attractive properties, OFDM has been widely adopted in transmission standards such as Digital Video Broadcasting (DVB) [2], Wireless LAN, WiMAX, and so on.

The disadvantages of an OFDM system [5]:

1. Higher transmitter output back off is required in comparison to a single carrier system, because of the high peak-to-average power ratio of an OFDM system.

2. As a parallel transmission technique, OFDM is more sensitive to carrier frequency offset (CFO) and tone interference than that of a single carrier system.

CFO introduces the ICI which degrade the overall system performance The ICI effect can be effectively mitigated by the conventional ICI self-cancellation schemes. The average carrier-to-interference power ratio (CIR) [3] is used as the ICI level indicator, and a theoretical CIR expression is derived for the proposed scheme.

In ICI self cancellation scheme the performance degrades at high frequency offset, in conjugate cancellation scheme[10] which improve CIR at very low frequency offset and its performance decreases as carrier frequency offset greater than 0.25, in Phase Rotated Conjugate Cancellation (PRCC) it requires continues carrier frequency offset(CFO) estimation and feedback circuitry which increases the hardware complexity[9]. In this paper we propose a sub optimal approach to find sub optimal values (λ_{so}, μ_{so}) in which data is modulated at two

symmetrical placed sub carriers i.e, k^{th} and $N-1-k^{\text{th}}$ and utilizes a data allocation of $(1, -\lambda_{so})$ and subcarriers are combine with weights $(1, -\mu_{so})$. (λ_{so}, μ_{so}) are suboptimal values and are independent of normalized frequency offset ε . it does not require any CFO estimation or feedback circuitry and hence eliminates the requirement of complex the hardware circuitry.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the mathematical model of a regular OFDM system and ICI self cancellation scheme are described in Section II. Analysis of the proposed system is discussed in Section III. Section IV presents the simulation results and some discussion on them. Finally, some conclusions are given in Section V.

II. STANDARD OFDM SYSTEM

A. OFDM System model

The discrete time baseband OFDM symbol after the IFFT block at the transmitter can be expressed as

$$x[n] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X(k) e^{j2\pi n k / N}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad (1)$$

here N is the total numbers of subcarriers and $X(k)$ is the modulated data symbol transmitted on k^{th} subcarrier. At the receiver, the time-domain received signal suffering from a frequency offset and an Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) can be written as

$$y[n] = x[n] e^{j\frac{2\pi n \varepsilon}{N}} + w[n], \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad (2)$$

ε represents the frequency offset normalized by the frequency spacing of two subcarriers and $w[n]$ is a zero-mean AWGN. After the Fast Fourier transform (FFT) block, the frequency domain signal at the k^{th} subcarrier is given as

$$Y(k) = X(k)S(0) + \sum_{l=0, l \neq k}^{N-1} X(l)S(l-k) + W(k), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad (3)$$

Where $W(k)$ is the DFT of $w[n]$ and $S(l-k)$ is referred as ICI weighting coefficient i.e

$$S(l-k) = e^{j\pi(l+\varepsilon-k)\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)} \frac{\sin(\pi(l+\varepsilon-k))}{N \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{N}(l+\varepsilon-k)\right)} \quad (4)$$

The CIR at the k^{th} subcarrier is

$$CIR_o = \frac{|S(0)|^2}{\sum_{l=0, l \neq k}^{N-1} |S(l-k)|^2} \quad (5)$$

from the above equation the CIR as a function of the normalized frequency offset ε and N , however CIR varies little as a function of N therefore CIR only depend on normalized frequency offset ε

The block diagram of the above description is given below

Fig1. Block diagram of the proposed scheme

B. PHASE SHIFT KEYING

The most popular M-PSK modulation techniques include BPSK, QPSK, 16-PSK and 256-PSK. Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) Quadrature Phase Shift Keying has twice the bandwidth efficiency of BPSK, and the phase of the carrier takes on one of four equally spaced values, such as $0, \pi/2, \pi$ and $3\pi/2$, where each value of phase corresponds to a unique pair of message bits.

The QPSK signal may be defined as

$$S_{QPSK}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{T_s}} \cos\left[2\pi f_c t + (i-1)\frac{\pi}{2}\right] \quad \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq T_b, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

Where T_s is the symbol duration and is equal to twice the bit period. In QPSK two successive bits are combined this combination of two bits forms four distinct symbols. When symbol is change to next symbol the phase of the carrier changed by 45° ($\pi/4$ radians). The table (1) shows symbol and their phase shifts

TABLE-1
RELATION BETWEEN THE INPUT SYMBOLS
AND THE PHASE SHIFTS

Information Bits M_i , Mq	Phase Shifts π
11	$\pi/4$
01	$3\pi/4$
00	$-3\pi/4$
10	$-\pi/4$

C. ICI self cancellation scheme

i) Modulation

From the conclusion of Section II, it is impossible to reduce the ICI unless the ε value is decreased. but for smaller values of ε bandwidth efficiency will be reduced since symbol length is reduced therefore guard interval will be large.

So the idea of ICI cancellation [4] is, for the majority of subcarriers the difference between symmetrically placed ICI coefficients are very small [7]. Therefore if a complex data pair ex:(a,-a) is modulated onto two symmetrically placed subcarriers ,then the ICI generated by these subcarrier will be significantly cancelled out.

Assume that the transmitted data symbols are constrained

$$X(N-1) = -X(0), \dots, X(N-1-k) = -X(k)$$

so the k^{th} subcarrier is repeated at the $N-1-k^{\text{th}}$ subcarrier with opposite polarity.

The received data signal at the k^{th} subcarrier is given by

$$Y'(k) = \sum_{l=0}^{\frac{N-1}{2}} X(l)(S(l-k) - S(l+1-k)) + W(k) \quad (6)$$

and on $N-1-k^{\text{th}}$ subcarrier

$$Y'(N-1-k) = \sum_{l=0}^{\frac{N-1}{2}} X(l)(S(l+k+1-N) - S(k-l)) + W(N-1-k) \quad (7)$$

here the ICI coefficient is defined as

$$S'(l-k) = S(l-k) - S(l+1-k) \quad (8)$$

from the equation(6), it takes only half of the N values, so the number of interference signals are reduced to half and the ICI signals are much smaller than in equation (3) so the number of ICI signals and amplitudes of ICI coefficients have been reduced, such modulation is called ICI cancelling modulation.

ii) Demodulation

In this each signal at the $N-1-k^{\text{th}}$ subcarrier is multiplied by “ -1” and then summed with the one at the k^{th} subcarrier. Then the resultant data sequence is

$$Y''(k) = Y'(k) - Y'(N-1-k) \quad (9)$$

thus CIR of conventional ICI self cancellation scheme can be written as

$$CIR_c = \frac{|-S(-N-1-2k) + 2S(0) - S(1-N+2k)|^2}{\sum_{\substack{l=0 \\ l \neq k}}^{\frac{N-1}{2}} |S(l-k) - S(N-1-l-k) - S(l+k+1-N) + S(k-l)|^2} \quad (10)$$

III. PROPOSED SCHEME

In general at the transmitter a data allocation $(1, -\lambda)$ is used at symmetrical subcarriers i.e

$$X(N-1) = -\lambda X(0), \dots, X(N-1-k) = -\lambda X(k)$$

now the received data at the k^{th} subcarrier is

$$Y'(k) = \sum_{l=0}^{\frac{N-1}{2}} X(l)(S(l-k) - \lambda S(l+1-k)) + W(k) \quad (11)$$

so the received data with combination of k^{th} and $N-1-k^{\text{th}}$ subcarriers with $(1, -\mu)$

$$Y''(k) = Y'(k) - \mu Y'(N-1-k) \quad (12)$$

thus the CIR of this optimal scheme is

$$CIR_p = \frac{|-\mu S(-N+1+2k) + (1+\lambda\mu)(S(0) - \lambda S(-1+N+2k))|^2}{\sum_{\substack{l=0 \\ l \neq k}}^{\frac{N-1}{2}} |S(l-k) - \mu S(-N+1+l+k) - \lambda S(-l-k-1+N) + \mu \lambda S(k-l)|^2} \quad \dots(13)$$

the optimal values λ and μ have been found by using Nelder Mead Simplex Algorithm(NMSA)[8]. These optimal values are calculated for $\varepsilon \in [0.03, 0.25]$ at a very small interval of $\nabla \varepsilon$ which results in maximize the CIR for given ε . but the drawback is for every ε , there is unique optimal values and always this require a continuous CFO estimation this increase in hardware complexity for each pair of optimal values the CIR has been calculated which forms a CIR v_{xx} matrix[6] i.e, the elements in the matrix as the form like $CIR_p(\varepsilon_v, \lambda_{ov}, \mu_{ov})$.

$$\text{where, } v = \frac{\varepsilon_H - \varepsilon_L}{\nabla \varepsilon} + 1 \quad (14)$$

ε_H and ε_L are the lowest and highest possible values and $\nabla\varepsilon$ which results in maximize the CIR for given ε .

here $\varepsilon_H = 0.25, \varepsilon_L = 0.03$ and $\nabla\varepsilon = 0.02$ so that $v=12$ to avoid the above drawbacks sub-optimal pair (λ_{so}, μ_{so}) has been found by using the following criterion

$$(\lambda_{so}, \mu_{so}) = \max_{\lambda_o, \mu_o} \left[p - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^p (p - CIR(\varepsilon_j, \lambda_o, \mu_o))}{v} \right] \quad (15)$$

where p is the maximum CIR of a particular row of the matrix and second term is mean deviation of the CIR of that row from the peak (p) of that row, so here these sub-optimal values (λ_{so}, μ_{so}) independent of normalized frequency offset ε in the proposed method these values are $\lambda_{so} = 0.6164$ and $\mu_{so} = 1.0351$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here we have considered an OFDM system with $N=64$ subcarriers and we are using MPSK modulation with $M=4$ is used to modulate each of the subcarrier. The simulation using MATLAB software are performed to evaluate CIR and BER performance.

Fig.2.CIR versus Normalized frequency offset for various ICI cancellation schemes

As from the figure 2 the CIR performance of proposed system provides a gain of more than 8dB at $\varepsilon = 0.10$ over conventional scheme. But for

$\varepsilon \in [0.03, 0.08]$ the proposed scheme CIR is slightly aggravated than conventional scheme

Fig.3. BER comparison for various schemes. The graph showing the results BER versus Eb/No (dB).

The BER performance of proposed scheme is very much improved than standard OFDM system.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigate the sub-optimal ICI self cancellation scheme for combating the impact of ICI on OFDM system. The proposed scheme provides significant CIR improvement, without increasing the hardware complexity and removes the requirement of CFO estimation

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Soft Switching Cascaded DC-DC Converter with High Voltage Gain

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ABSTRACT

Increased energy demands and global rising pollution awareness has resulted in significant growth in field of sustainable energy, hence much of the research work is focused on green power technologies. Renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic (PV) cell and fuel cell are characterized by low voltage and high current output and have strict current ripple requirement. Hence as an important power electronic interface DC-DC converter plays vital role in distributed generation (DG) system/hybrid system to have lower input current ripple and high output DC link voltage. Therefore, in this work, it is aimed to develop a high gain high efficiency DC-DC converter as a power electronic interface for a renewable energy sources. A zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) dc-dc converter with high voltage gain is proposed. It consists of a ZVS boost converter stage and a ZVS half-bridge converter stage and two stages are merged into a single stage. The ZVS boost converter stage provides a continuous input current and ZVS operation of the power switches. The ZVS half-bridge converter stage provides a high voltage gain. The principle of operation and system analysis are presented. Theoretical analysis and performance of the proposed converter were verified on a 100 W experimental prototype operating at 108 kHz switching frequency.

Keywords: Boost converter, coupled inductor, high voltage gain, reverse recovery, zero-voltage switching.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, dc-dc converters with steep voltage ratio are usually required in many industrial applications. For example, the front-end stage for clean-energy sources, the dc back-up energy system for an uninterruptible power supply (UPS), high-intensity discharge lamps for automobile headlamps, and, finally, the telecommunications industry [1]–[3]. The conventional boost converters cannot provide such a high dc voltage gain, even for an extreme duty cycle. It also may result in serious reverse-recovery problems and increase the rating of all devices. As a result, the conversion efficiency is degraded and the electromagnetic interference (EMI) problem is severe under this situation [4]. In order to increase the conversion efficiency and voltage gain, many modified boost converter topologies have been investigated in the past decade [5]. In dc-dc converters with high voltage gain, there are several

requirements such as high voltage gain low reverse-recovery loss, soft-switching characteristic, low-voltage stress across the switches, electrical isolation, continuous input current, and high efficiency. In order to meet these requirements, various topologies are introduced. In order to extend the voltage gain, the boost converters with coupled inductors are proposed in [6] and [7]. The voltage gain is extended but continuous input current characteristic is lost and the efficiency is degraded due to hard switching of power switches. In [8], a step-up converter based on a charge pump and coupled

Inductor is suggested. Its voltage gain is around 10 but its efficiency is not high enough due to the switching loss. In [9], a high-step-up converter with coupled inductors is suggested to provide high voltage gain and a continuous input current. However, its operating frequency is limited due to

the hard switching of the switches. In [10], a new boost converter with a ripple free input current was suggested. In the new boost converter, an extra LC circuit with coupled inductors was utilized. The ripple component of the input current was reduced by carefully designing the parameters of the coupled inductor. Coupled inductor can serve as a transformer to extend the voltage gain in non-isolated DC/DC converters. The coupled inductor has two windings. The primary winding serves as the similar function as the filter inductor. The second winding operates as a voltage source in series to the power branch. The voltage gain can be extended by a proper turns ratio design of the coupled inductor. However, the efficiency could not be improved due to the switching losses of the power switch. To increase the efficiency and power conversion density, the soft-switching technique is required in DC/DC converters. In [11]–[16], various soft-switching techniques are suggested. Generally, there is a tradeoff between soft-switching Characteristic and high voltage gain. It is because an inductor that is related with soft-switching limits the voltage gain.

In order to solve these problems, a zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) dc–dc converter with high voltage gain is proposed. As shown in Fig. 1, it consists of a ZVS boost converter stage to make the input current continuous and provide ZVS functions. In Fig. 2 ZVS boost converter and ZVS half-bridge converter stage to provide high voltage gain and continuous input current, soft switching operation. Since single power processing stage can be a more efficient and cost-effective solution, both stages are merged and share power switches to increase the system efficiency and simplify the structure. Since both stages have the ZVS function, ZVS operation of the power switches can be obtained with wider load variation. Moreover, due to the ZVS function of the boost converter stage, the design of the half-bridge converter stage can be focused on high voltage gain. Therefore, high voltage gain is easily obtained. ZVS operation of the power switches reduces the switching loss during the switching transition and improves the overall efficiency. The theoretical analysis is verified by a 100W experimental prototype with 24–396 V conversion.

II. Analysis of Proposed Converter

A ZVS boost converter with a coupled inductor is proposed. The ZVS characteristic of the proposed

boost converter reduces the switching losses and raises the overall efficiency. Moreover, since the ZVS characteristic is achieved by adding an additional winding to the boost inductor, there is only one magnetic component. The reverse-recovery of the auxiliary diode is alleviated due to the leakage inductance of the coupled inductor. The theoretical analysis is verified by a 100W experimental prototype with 24V-to-86V conversion.

ZVS DC-DC Converters with high voltage gain was proposed in this project which consists of ZVS Boost converter and ZVS Half bridge converter. Analysis of the proposed converter with design parameters are shown below.

Fig.1 ZVS Boost Converter

Fig.2 Proposed soft-switching dc–dc converter with high voltage gain

The equivalent circuit of the proposed converter is shown in Fig.2 The ZVS boost converter stage consists of a coupled inductor L_c , the lower switch Q_1 , the upper switch Q_2 , the auxiliary diode D_a , and the dc-link capacitor C_{dc} . The diodes D_{Q1} and D_{Q2} represent the intrinsic body diodes of Q_1 and Q_2 . The capacitors C_{Q1} and C_{Q2} are the parasitic output capacitances of Q_1 and Q_2 . The coupled inductor L_c is modeled as the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} , the leakage inductance L_{k1} , and the ideal transformer

that has a turn ratio of 1:n1 ($n_1 = N_{s1}/N_{p1}$). The ZVS half-bridge converter stage consists of a transformer T, the switches Q1 and Q2, the output diodes Do1 and Do2, the dc blocking capacitors C_{B1} and C_{B2}, and the output capacitor C_o. The transformer T is modeled as the magnetizing inductance L_{m2}, the leakage inductance L_{k2}, and the ideal transformer that has a turn ratio of 1:n2 ($n_2 = N_{s2}/N_{p2}$). The theoretical waveforms of the proposed converter are shown in Fig. 3. The switches Q1 and Q2 are operated asymmetrically and the duty ratio D is based on the switch Q1. The operation of the proposed converter in one switching period T_s can be divided into seven as shown in Fig. 4. Just before Mode 1, the upper switch Q2, the auxiliary diode Da, and the output diode D_{o1} are conducting. The magnetizing current i_{m1} of L_c arrives at its minimum value I_{m12} and the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} arrives at its maximum value I_{Da}. The current i_L has its maximum value I_{L1}.

Fig.3 Equivalent circuit of the proposed soft-switching dc-dc converter

Mode 1 [t₀, t₁]: At t₀, the upper switch Q₂ is turned OFF. Then, the capacitor C_{Q2} starts to be charged and the voltage V_{Q2} across Q₂ increases toward V_{dc}. Simultaneously, the capacitor C_{Q1} is discharged and the voltage v_{Q1} across Q₁ decreases toward zero. With an assumption that the output capacitances C_{Q1} and C_{Q2} of the switches are very small and all the inductor currents are not changed, the transition time interval T_{t1} can be considered as follows

$$T_{t1} = t_1 - t_0 = \frac{(C_{Q1} + C_{Q2}) V_{dc}}{I_{L1} + (n_1 + 1) I_{Da} - I_{m12}} \quad (1)$$

Mode 2 [t₁, t₂]: At t₁, the voltage V_{Q1} across the lower switch Q₁ becomes zero and the body diode D_{Q1} is turned ON. Then, the gate signal for Q₁ is applied. Since the current has already flown through the body diode D_{Q1} and the voltage V_{Q1} is

maintained as zero before the switch Q₁ is turned ON, the zero-voltage turn-ON of Q₁ is achieved. Since the voltage v_{p1} across the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} is V_{in}, the magnetizing current i_{m1} increases linearly from its minimum value I_{m2} as follows:

$$i_{m1}(t) = I_{m12} + \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m1}} (t - t_1) \quad (2)$$

Since the voltage v_{Lk1} across the leakage inductance L_{k1} is -(n₁V_{in}+V_{dc}), the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} linearly decreases from its maximum value I_{Da} as follows:

$$i_{Da}(t) = I_{Da} - \frac{n_1 V_{in} + V_{dc}}{L_{k1}} (t - t_1) \quad (3)$$

From (2) and (3), the input current i_{in} is determined as follows:

$$i_{in}(t) = i_{m1}(t) - i_{p1}(t) = i_{m1}(t) - n_1 i_{Da}(t) = I_{m12} - n_1 I_{Da} + n_1 \frac{n_1 V_{in} + V_{dc}}{L_{k1}} (t - t_1) + \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m1}} (t - t_1) \quad (4)$$

Since v_{p2} is -(V_{dc}-V_{CB1}) and v_{Lk2} is V_{CB2}+n₂V_{in}, the magnetizing current i_{m2} and the diode current i_{Do1} are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = I_{m21} - \frac{V_{dc} - V_{CB1}}{L_{m2}} (t - t_1) \quad (5)$$

$$i_{Do1}(t) = -i_{CB2}(t) = I_{Do1} - \frac{V_{CB2} + n_2 V_{in}}{L_{k2}} (t - t_1) \quad (6)$$

In this mode, the primary current i_{p2}, the coupled inductor current i_L, and the switch current i_{Q1} can be obtained from

$$i_{p2}(t) = n_2 i_{CB2}(t) \quad (7)$$

$$i_L(t) = i_{m2}(t) - i_{p2}(t) \quad (8)$$

$$i_{Q1}(t) = i_{in}(t) - i_{Da}(t) - i_L(t) \quad (9)$$

Mode 3 [t₂, t₃]: At t₂, the current i_{CB2} changes its direction. The output diode current i_{Do1} decreases to zero and the diode D_{o1} is turned OFF. Then the output diode D_{o2} is turned ON and its current increases linearly. Since the current changing rate of D_{o1} is controlled by the leakage inductance L_{k2} of the transformer T, its reverse-recovery problem is alleviated. Since V_{p2} is the same as in Mode 2 and V_{Lk2} is n₂V_{in}+V_{CB2}-V_o, the current i_{m2} and the diode current i_{Do2} are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = i_{m2}(t) - \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m2}} (t - t_2) \quad (10)$$

$$i_{D02}(t) = i_{CB2}(t) = \frac{V_{CB2} + n_2 V_{in} - V_O}{L_{k2}} (t - t_2) \quad (11)$$

The currents i_{p2} , i_L , and i_{Q1} can be obtained from the same relations in Mode 2. In this mode, the voltages V_{p1} and V_{Lk} are equal to those in Mode 2. Therefore, the magnetizing current i_{m1} , the auxiliary current i_{Da} , and the input current i_{in} change with the same slopes as in Mode 2.

Mode 4 [t3, t4]: At t3, the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} decreases to zero and the diode Da is turned OFF. Since the changing rate of the diode current i_{Da} is controlled by the leakage inductance L_{k1} of the coupled inductor L_c its reverse recovery problem is alleviated. Since the voltage v_{p1} across the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} is the input voltage V_{in} the magnetizing current i_{m1} increases linearly with the same slope as in Modes 2 and 3 as follows:

$$i_{m1}(t) = i_{m1}(t_3) + \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m1}} (t - t_3) \quad (12)$$

Since the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} is zero, the input current i_{in} is equal to the magnetizing current i_{m1} . At the end of this mode, the magnetizing current i_{m1} arrives at its maximum value I_{m11} . Since the voltages V_{p2} and V_{Lk2} are not changed in this mode, the slopes of the current i_{m2} , i_{CB2} , and i_L are not changed.

Mode 5 [t4, t5]: At t4, the lower switch Q1 is turned OFF. Then, the capacitor C_{Q1} starts to be charged and the voltage V_{Q1} across Q1 increases toward V_{dc} . Simultaneously, the capacitor C_{Q2} is discharged and the voltage V_{Q2} across Q2 decreases towards zero. With the same assumption as in Mode 1, the transition time interval T_{t2} can be determined as follows:

$$T_{t2} = t_5 - t_4 = \frac{(C_{Q1} + C_{Q2}) V_{dc}}{I_{L2} + I_{m11}} \quad (13)$$

Mode 6 [t5, t6]: At t5, the voltage V_{Q2} across the upper switch Q2 becomes zero and the body diode D_{Q2} is turned ON. Then, the gate signal is applied to the switch Q2. Since the current has already flown through the body diode D_{Q2} and the voltage V_{Q2} is maintained as zero before the turn-ON of the switch Q2, the zero-voltage turn-ON of Q2 is achieved. Since the voltage V_{p1} across the magnetizing inductance

L_{m1} is $-(V_{dc} - V_{in})$, the magnetizing current i_{m1} decreases linearly from its maximum value I_{m11} as follows:

$$i_{m1}(t) = I_{m11} - \frac{V_{dc} - V_{in}}{L_{m1}} (t - t_5) \quad (14)$$

Since the voltage V_{Lk1} across the leakage inductance L_k is $n_1 (V_{dc} - V_{in})$, the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} linearly increases from zero as follows:

$$i_{Da}(t) = \frac{n_1 (V_{dc} - V_{in})}{L_{m1}} (t - t_5) \quad (15)$$

From (14) and (15), the input current i_{in} is determined as

$$i_{in}(t) = I_{m11} - \frac{(V_{dc} - V_{in})}{L_{m1}} (t - t_5) - n_1^2 \frac{(V_{dc} - V_{in})}{L_{k1}} (t - t_5) \quad (16)$$

Since the voltage V_{p2} is $V_{CB1} (= D V_{in} / (1 - D))$ and V_{Lk2} is $-(V_O - V_{CB2} + n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D))$, the magnetizing current i_{m2} and the diode current i_{D02} are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = -I_{m22} + \frac{D V_{in}}{L_{m2}(1 - D)} (t - t_5) \quad (17)$$

$$i_{D02}(t) = i_{CB2}(t) = I_{D02} - \frac{V_O - V_{CB2} + (n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D))}{L_{k2}} (t - t_5) \quad (18)$$

Mode 7 [t6, t7]: At t6, the current i_{CB2} changes its direction. The output diode current i_{D02} decreases to zero and the diode D_{02} is turned OFF. Then the output diode D_{01} is turned ON and its current increases linearly. Similar to D_{01} , the current changing rate of D_{02} is controlled by the leakage inductance L_{k2} of the transformer T and its reverse-recovery problem is alleviated. Since v_{p2} is the same as in Mode 6 and V_{Lk2} is $V_{CB2} - n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D)$, the current i_{m2} and the diode current i_{D02} are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = i_{m2}(t_6) + \frac{D V_{in}}{L_{m2}(1 - D)} (t - t_6) \quad (19)$$

$$i_{D01}(t) = -i_{CB2}(t) = \frac{V_{CB2} - (n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D))}{L_{k2}} (t - t_6) \quad (20)$$

The currents i_{p2} and i_L can be obtained from the same relations in Mode 2. In this mode, the voltages V_{p1} and V_{Lk1} are equal to those in Mode 6. Therefore, the magnetizing current i_{m1} , the auxiliary current i_{Da} , and the input current i_{in} change with the same slopes as in Mode 2.

Fig.4 Theoretical waveforms

Fig.5 Modes of Operation

III. CHARACTERISTIC AND DESIGN PARAMETERS:

1. Voltage Gain of the Boost Converter Stage:

Referring to the voltage waveform V_{p1} in Fig. 4, the volt second balance law gives

$$V_{in}DT_s - (V_{dc} - V_{in})(1 - D)T_s = 0. \quad (21)$$

From (21), the voltage gain of the proposed ZVS boost converter stage is obtained by

$$\frac{V_{dc}}{V_{in}} = \frac{1}{1 - D} \quad (22)$$

Which is the same as that of the conventional CCM boost converter.

2. Auxiliary Diode Current Reset Timing Ratio d_1 :

By applying the volt-second balance law to the voltage waveform V_{Lk1} , the auxiliary diode current reset timing ratio d_1 is

$$d_1 = \frac{n_1 D(1 - D)}{n_1(1 - D) + 1} \quad (23)$$

3. Maximum Auxiliary Diode Current I_{Da} :

From Modes 6 and 7, the maximum auxiliary diode current I_{Da} is obtained by.
$$I_{Da} = \frac{n_1 D V_{in} T_s}{L_{k1}} \quad (24)$$

4. DC-Blocking Capacitor Voltage V_{CB1} :

Referring to the voltage waveform v_{p2} in Fig. 4, the volt second balance law gives

$$V_{CB1}(1 - D)T_s - (V_{dc} - V_{CB1})DT_s = 0 \quad (25)$$

From (22) and (25), the dc-blocking capacitor voltage V_{CB1} is obtained by

$$V_{CB1} = \frac{D V_{in}}{1 - D} \quad (26)$$

5. Maximum Output Diode Currents I_{Do1} and I_{Do2} :

From Modes 2 and 7, the maximum output diode current I_{Do1} can be written as follows:

$$I_{Do1} = \frac{n_2 V_{in} + V_{CB2}}{L_{k2}} d_2 T_s = -V_{CB2} + \frac{(n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D))}{L_{k2}} \quad (27)$$

$$I_{Do2} = \frac{n_2 V_{in} + V_{CB2} - V_o}{L_{k2}} (D - d_2) \quad (28)$$

$$T_s = V_o - V_{CB2} + \frac{(n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D))}{L_{k2}} d_3 T_s \quad (29)$$

6. Output Voltage V_o of the Half-Bridge Converter Stage:

From (27) and (29), the dc-blocking capacitor voltage V_{CB2} and the output voltage V_o can be derived as follows:

$$V_{CB2} = \frac{D - d_2 - (D/(1 - D))d_3}{1 - D + d_2 - d_3} \cdot n_2 V_{in} \quad (30)$$

$$V_o = \frac{D - d_2 - (D/(1 - D))d_3}{(D - d_2 + d_3)(1 - D + d_2 - d_3)} \cdot n_2 V_{in} \quad (31)$$

7. Output Diode Current Reset Timing Ratios d_2 and d_3 :

Since the average value of the current i_{CB2} should be zero, the following relation can be obtained:

$$(1 - D + d_2 - d_3) I_{Do1} = (D - d_2 + d_3) I_{Do2} \quad (32)$$

From (27) to (32), the relation between d_2 and d_3 is obtained by

$$\frac{d_2}{d_3} = \frac{D}{1 - D} \quad (33)$$

Since the average value of the current i_{m2} is zero, its peak values I_{m21} and I_{m22} have the same value as follows:

$$I_{m21} = I_{m22} = \frac{D V_{in} T_s}{2 L_{m2}} \quad (34)$$

From Fig.4, the output current I_o can be represented by

$$I_o = (1 - D + d_2 - d_3) \frac{I_{Do1}}{2} = (D - d_2 + d_3) \frac{I_{Do2}}{2} \quad (35)$$

From (27), (28), (33), and (37), d_2 and d_3 are obtained by

$$d_2 = \alpha D \quad (36)$$

$$d_3 = \alpha(1 - D) \quad (37)$$

$$\alpha = 1/2 \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{8L_{k2}I_o}{n_2V_{in}DT_s}} \right) \quad (38)$$

8. Voltage Gain M of the Proposed DC-DC Converter:

From (22), (31), (36), and (37), the voltage gain M of the proposed converter is given by

$$M = \frac{V_o}{V_{in}} = \frac{n_2 D(1 - 2\alpha)}{(D(1 - 2\alpha) + \alpha)(1 - \alpha - (1 - 2\alpha)D)} \quad (39)$$

9. Input Current Ripple:

The input current ripple Δi_{in} can be written by

$$\Delta i_{in} = I_{m11} - I_{m12} + n_1 I_{Da} = \frac{n_1^2 L_{m1} + L_{k1}}{L_{m1} L_{k1}} \cdot DV_{in} T_s \quad (40)$$

To reduce the input current ripple below a specific value I^* , the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} should satisfy the following condition:

$$L_{m1} > \frac{1}{(I^* / DV_{in} T_s) - (n_1^2 / L_{k1})} \quad (41)$$

10. ZVS Conditions:

As is seen in Fig. 3, both the boost converter stage and the half-bridge converter stage have ZVS function. From Fig. 3, the ZVS condition for Q2 is given by

$$I_{m11} + I_{L2} = I_{m11} + I_{m22} + n_2 I_{Do2} > 0. \quad (42)$$

Since the current values I_{m11} , I_{m22} , and I_{Do2} have positive values, the ZVS condition for Q2 is always satisfied. Similarly, for ZVS of Q1, the following condition should be satisfied:

$$I_{m21} + n_2 I_{Do1} + (n_1 + 1) I_{Da} - I_{m12} > 0 \quad (43)$$

The terms I_{m21} and $n_2 I_{Do1}$ are from the half-bridge converter stage and the terms $(n_1 + 1) I_{Da}$ and I_{m12} are from the boost converter stage. If the boost converter stage is designed to satisfy the above inequality (43) regardless of the status of the half bridge converter stage, ZVS of the proposed converter is always accomplished. In this case, the leakage inductance L_{k1} of the coupled inductor L_c should satisfy the following condition

$$L_{k1} < \frac{(n_1 + 1) n_1 DV_{in} T_s}{P_o / V_{in}} \quad (44)$$

Where P_o is the output power and the minimum value I_{m12} of the magnetizing current i_{m1} is approximated as P_o / V_{in} .

Fig.6 Measured Efficiency

Fig.7 MATLAB Simulation circuit

Simulation Results:

Fig 8.1 I_{in} , I_{Da} , V_{Q1} Waveforms

Fig 8.2 V_{Q1} , I_{Q1} , V_{GS1} Waveforms

Fig 8.6 Output voltage Waveform

Fig 8.3 I_L , V_{Q1} , I_{CB1} Waveforms

Fig 8.4 I_{D02} , I_{D01} , V_{Q1} Waveforms

Fig 8.5 I_{Q2} , V_{GS2} , V_{Q2} Waveforms

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig.9 Hardware Implementation

A 100W prototype of the proposed converter is made and tested. The power circuit setup is shown in Fig 4.1. Various parameters used in designing the power circuit are as shown the Table 1 Specifications of prototype.

Parameter	Value
Power	100W
V_{in}	24V
V_{out}	396V
Coupled inductor(L_c) L_{m1} / L_{lk1}	800 μ H / 16.75 μ H
Transformer(T) L_{m2} / L_{lk2}	474 μ H / 170 μ H
C_{dc} (Electrolytic capacitor)	470 μ F/100V
Inductor Core for coupled inductor(L_c)	ETD49
Inductor Core for transformer(T)	ETD44
$N_1, N_2(L_c)$	90, 45turns
$N_1, N_2(T)$	22, 132turns
D_{01}, D_{02}	MUR460(2)
C_{B1}	6.6 μ F
C_{B2}	2.2 μ F
C_o Electrolytic capacitor	220 μ F
Q_1, Q_2	IRF640N
D_a	MUR460

The power is tested in laboratory with the diode bridge rectifier output as input to the converter. Power to control circuit is given from regulated power supply. The waveforms are captured from the oscilloscope and the results are shown in the following section.

V. CONCLUSION

A ZVS dc-dc converter with high voltage gain was suggested. It can achieve ZVS turn-ON of two power switches while maintaining CCM. In addition, the reverse-recovery characteristics of the output diodes were significantly improved by controlling the current changing rate with the use of the leakage inductance of the transformer. The proposed converter presents a higher efficiency and a wider ZVS region compared to other soft-switching converters due to the ZVS boost converter stage. Therefore, the proposed ZVS boost converter is suitable for industrial applications that require a step-up function and a continuous input current characteristic.

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SVM based Multispectral Remote Sensing Image Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Methods of Detection of Multi spectral remote sensing Images are becoming more popular due to the progresses in spatial resolution of satellite imagery. This paper presents detection of multispectral remote-sensing images corrupted by noise using Support Vector Machines. First enhancement of color separation of satellite image using decorrelation stretching is carried out and then the regions are grouped into a set of classes using Support Vector Machines. Simulation results are provided to demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed method for detection of Multi spectral remote sensing Images.

Key Words— Decorrelation, LANDSAT imagery, Spatial resolution, Support Vector Machines.

I. INTRODUCTION

The process of image segmentation (such as pixel based, contour based, region based, model based, color based and hybrid, etc.) is defined as the search for homogenous regions in an image and later the classification of these regions. It also means the partitioning of an image into meaningful regions based on homogeneity or heterogeneity criteria [1]. Multispectral image delivers a great source of data for studying spatial and temporal changeability of the environmental factors. It can be utilized in a number of applications which consists of reconnaissance, making of mapping products for military and civil use, assessment of environmental damage, nursing of land use, radiation level check, urban planning, growth directive, soil test and crop outcome increment. One major area where we use multispectral image is in the process of classification and mapping of vegetation over large spatial scales, as the remote sensing data delivers very good coverage, mapping and classification of land cover features like vegetation, soil, water and forests. This behaves like a replacement for the normal classification techniques, which necessitates expensive and time-intensive field surveys.

Purposes of classification of LANDSAT images is to identify Land use and land cover (LULC) Vegetation types, Geologic terrains, Mineral exploration, Alteration mapping, etc. LANDSAT 7 was launched in April, 1999. LANDSAT carries two multispectral sensors. The first is the *Multi-Spectral Scanner* (MSS) which acquires imagery in four Spectral bands: blue, green, red and near infrared. The second is the *Thematic Mapper* (TM) which collects seven bands: blue, green, red, near-infrared, two mid-infrared and one thermal infrared. The MSS has a spatial resolution of 80 meters, while that of the TM is 30 meters. Both sensors image a 185 km wide swath, passing over each day at 09:45 local time, and returning every 16 days. With LANDSAT 7, support for TM, imagery is to be continued with the addition of a co-registered 15 m panchromatic band [4].

Multispectral image classification can be considered as a combined project of both image processing and classification methods. Usually, image classification, in the process of remote sensing is the method of referring pixels or the basic units of an image to the classes. It is mostly likely to create groups of similar

pixels found in image data into classes that match the informational categories of user interest by matching the pixels to one another and to those of the said identity. Many techniques of image classification have been introduced and numerous areas like image analysis and pattern recognition use the vital term, classification.

Image segmentation is a process of partitioning image pixels based on selected image features. The pixels that belong to the same region must be spatially connected and have the similar image features. If the selected segmentation feature is color, an image segmentation process would separate pixels that have distinct color feature into different regions, and, simultaneously, group pixels that are spatially connected and have the similar color into the same region.

Classification of multispectral remotely sensed data is computed with a special attention on uncertainty computation in the land-cover maps. An efficient technique for classifying the multispectral satellite images into land cover and land use sectors using SVM. The proposed classification technique comprises of segmentation using clustering technique, training data selection for SVM and classification using trained SVM. Multispectral images cannot be fed directly into the SVM for training and testing. The input image is subjected to a set of pre-processing so that the image gets transformed suitably for segmentation.

This paper deals with statistical cluster analysis in the potential presence of contaminations. Detection of multispectral remote-sensing images corrupted by noise using Support Vector Machines is proposed in this paper.. Simulation results are provided to demonstrate the effectiveness of proposed algorithm.

I. Proposed Pixel Analysis with SVM

Support Vector Machines (SVM) [16] is a statistical learning based classification system. The SVM sections the classes with respect to a decision surface that maximizes the margin between the classes. The surface is normally known as the optimal hyperplane

and the data points closest to the optimal hyper plane are known as the support vectors. These support vectors are the most important elements of the training set. Some deviations of SVM are: 1) the SVM can be modified to make it a nonlinear classifier by the employment of nonlinear kernels and 2) a multiclass classifier can be made by clubbing a large number of binary SVM classifiers (making a binary classifier for every possible pair of classes). For multiclass classification, the pair wise classification strategy is regularly made use of. The result of the SVM classification is the decision values of each pixel for each of the class.

The learning set $D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is given as input to a binary SVM classifier. The latter is among the most popular supervised kernel-based classifiers available in the literature. Compared to standard classification methods, it relies on the margin maximization principle that makes it less sensitive to over fitting problems [11]. During the classification stage, a spectral-change map is generated by classifying the remaining pixels in the DI as change or no change. The decision for assigning each pixel is made according to the following decision uncton:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i \in S} \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b^* \quad (3)$$

where $K(.,.)$ is a kernel function.

The set S is a subset of the indices $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ corresponding to the nonzero Lagrange multipliers α_i 's which define the so-called support vectors, and b^* is the ambient noise.

II. Simulation Results

Various experiments were carried out using SVM based image analysis for LANDSAT images and results are summarized in Fig1 to Fig 4. In Fig 5, error analysis of the proposed SVM method is shown and these results demonstrate that multispectral remote sensing image corrupted with noise analysis can be carried out with to maximum accuracy.

Fig1.(a) & (b) Original Image & its Histogram, (c) & (d) Decoorelated Image & its Histogram

Fig2.(a) & (b) Objects in cluster 1 (multi spectral remote sensing Image without noise is considered) & its Histogram, (c) & (d) Objects in cluster 1 (multi spectral remote sensing Image with noise is considered) & its Histogram.

fig 3.(a) & (b) Objects in cluster 2 (multi spectral remote sensing Image without noise is considered) & its Histogram, (c) & (d) Objects in cluster 2 (multi spectral remote sensing Image with noise is considered) & its Histogram.

fig 4. (a) & (b) Objects in cluster 3 (multi spectral remote sensing Image without noise is considered) & its Histogram, (c) & (d) Objects in cluster 3 (multi spectral remote sensing Image with noise is considered) & its Histogram.

Fig5. Error Analysis for the considered 3 clusters (Blue, Green, Red indicates cluster 1, cluster 2 and cluster3, respectively).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, SVM based algorithm for detection of Multi Spectral Remote sensing Images corrupted with noise is proposed analyzed. Simulation results are also provided, which demonstrate the efficiency of proposed algorithm for image analysis for extracting and updating geographical information though considered LANDSAT Images are corrupted with noise.

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Robust Blind Video Watermarking Algorithm

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I. INTRODUCTION

Digital watermarking is a means to embed copyright information into a digital multimedia data such as image, audio, video, etc. Usually, watermarks can be embedded in the spatial or the transform domain of the original multimedia data and in most cases, watermarks should be perceptually unnoticeable and robust to retrieve from the protected multimedia data.

In video watermarking, watermark can be embedded in spatial domain and transform domain like DCT, DFT and DWT. Now we consider the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), which could be a desirable transform for watermarking. Traditionally, SVD is employed in image compression and other signal processing scenarios. In recent papers and SVD based image watermarking algorithms are proposed, declaring that their watermarking algorithms are blind. But as described in the two algorithms need the singular values or the orthogonal matrices for retrieving. Note that once the singular values are modified, the order of singular values may be different, which causes incorrect detection of the watermarks. So we must get the position information of the modified singular values in advance. Since these two algorithms need cover work relevant information for watermark retrieving, they cannot be used in video watermarking applications considering the usage storage of the cover work relevant information. This paper, a novel SVD based blind video watermarking algorithm is proposed. Considering the visible quality and robustness, the watermarks are embedded in specially selected singular values, and the original order can be maintained in our algorithm.

Experiments demonstrate the algorithm's good robustness to MPEG-2, shifting, small rescaling, and

median filtering, etc. The watermarking algorithm is described in section 2. The experiments are presented in Section 3, and the conclusion and the future work in Section 4.

2. Algorithm and implementation Basic idea

The theoretical analysis of the singular values of an image suffering geometric distortions is provided in:

The matrix and its transpose have the same non-zero singular values. The matrix and its row-flipped or column-flipped have the same non-zero singular values.

The non-zero singular values of matrix are the constant ratios to its scaled matrix (which is row or column repeated several times).

Where r is the rank of matrix A .

Because of above properties, SVD can be used for watermarking against geometrical distortions. The key

2.2 Watermark embedding

Before the watermark embedding, the original binary watermark sequence must be modulated as a sequence consisting of "1" (modulated from "1") and "-1" (modulated from "0"). In order to keep the order of singular values and robustness to some attacks such as MPEG-2,

The watermark embedding process is as follows:

a). Apply SVD to the whole cover frames
 $A = U \Sigma V^T$. The of the cover frames.

b). Modify the singular values of the cover frames according to the robustness and visibility:

Because the largest singular values are more important to the image quality, and the smallest

singular values are more sensitive to the noise, we choose the middle singular values to embed the watermarks.

c). Get the frame $A' = U' V T$ where r is the rank of

The watermark extracting process is as follows:

a). Apply SVD to whole watermarked frame $A' : A' = U' V T$, and the $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_L$ are the si values of image.

b). Extract the watermarks from the singular values:

3. Experimental results and analysis

The watermarks are the basic M-sequence. In our experiments, it is 880 bits in length. And the videos for tests are MPEG-2 standard test sequences i.e. "Mobile", "Boating" and "Racing". All the video sequences conform to PAL standard with the resolution of 720x576. There are 220 frames in each video sequence.

Watermarks are embedded in the luminance channel of the video frames. The watermark intensity is 0.48 and 4 bits is embedded in each frame at the 3rd, 5th, 7th and 9th SVD coefficients. Assuming the coefficient for watermarking to be i ($1 \leq i \leq 576$), we find in our experiments that if $i \in [1, 40]$, the watermarked video algorithm can achieve a good robustness.

The proposed algorithm was tested by, ' diagram ('1, '2, L 'r) attacks of MPEG-2 compression, shifting, rescaling and median filtering. Figure 1 to A'. Figure 6 show the original and watermarked video frame of "Mobile" "Boating" and "Racing". Table 1 shows the PSNR (Peak Signal Noise Ratio) of the first 25 watermarked frames of "Mobile".

Table 2 shows the performance against these attacks
2.3 Watermark extraction.

According to the results in Table 1 and 2, our algorithm has a good robustness especially to MPEG-2 compression, even when the compression ratio is 4Mbits/s. Besides, we can see that it is well robust to shifting, and median filtering. If we embedded one bit each frame, the algorithm is also robust to rotation and rescaling.

4. Conclusions

As described above, our algorithm is robust to most attacks like MPEG-2 compression, rescaling, shifting, filtering, etc. Moreover it does not need any information in the detection process while other algorithms [10-11] need the information of singular values. In our future work, we will improve the algorithm to gain better performance against other attacks like rotation, cropping, etc.

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Environment Monitoring and device control using arm based Embedded Controlled Sensor network

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ABSTRACT

This paper mainly deals with integrating the embedded technology in the Agriculture field. It is done using the Wireless Sensor Nodes (WSN) technology with the help of microcontroller. Wireless Sensor Nodes (WSN) has become very popular technology in the recent past years. This paper describes about the one of the enhancement which can be implemented in WSN system to increase the communication distance between the nodes. In this paper, we consider applications, where sensing data are generally collected at an intermediate node which in turn sends the data to mobile using GSM technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the twenty first century, there is revolution of the sensor networks which have also come up with various applications like surveillance, traffic control, environmental and wildlife monitoring, agricultural application, home automation and industrial process control [1]. Embedded controlled sensor networks (ECSN) are mainly designed to be application-specific so that the energy consumption is minimum as the battery-powered nodes demand life-time of Several months or even a few years. The architecture of a typical embedded controlled sensor network is shown in figure 2.

The available technologies are Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Wi-Max, wireless mobile Ad-hoc network (WMANET), UMB, wireless HART, Bluetooth and ZigBee. Embedded sensor networks are formed by communicating over wireless links without using a fixed networked infrastructure controlled by microcontroller. Zigbee is the name for a short-range, low-power, low-cost, and low-data-rate wireless multi-hop networking technology. Block diagram of ECSN consists of a master circuit which is connected to number of sub networks consisting of the various slaves. Master circuit is connected by a personal Computer which can be controlled by the internet. Wireless technologies for environmental monitoring and device control in homes offers many benefits to the users.

2. METHODOLOGY

Environment monitoring and device control allows new level of comfort in homes and it can also manage the energy consumption efficiently which in turns promotes the saving. Remote controlling of the devices offers many advantages to senior citizens and people with disabilities which helps them in being more autonomous and increasing quality of life. In Addition to remote control, monitoring temperature, flood and carbon monoxide in homes is

also a major concern. There is a severe need to monitor temperature or gases as they can be costly and deadly. A monitored low temperature sensor warns about freezing temperatures inside house. Also if the boiler, washer or pipes leaks in the home, it can cause considerable damage.

Guangming Song (etc) [2] developed a wireless-controllable power outlet system. Researchers have worked on home automation and environmental monitoring system in the past but in the existing systems cost is high, size is an issue and they are difficult to maintain. The proposed system is cost effective and controlled by user friendly embedded systems. The block diagram of the proposed system is as shown in figure 2. In this proposed system, we have designed one master module which consists of microcontroller, GSM module and Zigbee module. Three slave modules are designed using 8-bit microcontroller and Zigbee module. Remote control circuit is designed to control the various devices of home for short distance communication. GSM module is used for long distance control of devices and monitoring of environment of home. In master system, we have used ARM7 based LPC2148 microcontroller. LPC2148 is 32/16 bit microcontroller with embedded high speed flash memory of 512 KB. For GSM communication we have used STM300, which is a tri-band GSM/GPRS engine. The STM 300 is integrated with the AT commands and are developed to use TCP/IP protocol easily, which is

very useful for data transfer applications. GSM uses AT commands via its serial interface to control the devices. Zigbee technology is used for wireless personal area networking. Zigbee technology offers simplicity and a cost effective approach to building, construction and remodeling with wireless technology.

The circuit diagram of the master network designed using the ARM microcontroller, GSM module and Zigbee module is as shown below in figure 3.

In slave module we have used 89C51 microcontroller along with zigbee module and sensors for monitoring the environment. The various sensors which are connected with the slave module are gas sensor, humidity sensor, temperature sensor. The devices which are to be controlled remotely can be connected with the slave module.

Mobile Section:

Hardware Requirements

- ARM7 LPC2129 Microcontroller
- PIC Microcontroller
- Zigbee
- Temperature, Humidity and LDR sensors
- GSM modem
- Max232
- LCD

Software Requirements

- Keil C Compiler
- MPLab Microcontroller
- Embedded C

Advantages

- Remote monitoring is possible from anywhere in the field.
- Continuous surveillance is done through monitoring section.

Applications

- It can be implemented in Paddy fields

Existing System

At present there many system which are used to help the farmers in agriculture field. But all these system has one important drawback that is limited distance. Hence we are going for proposed system where we use GSM technology.

Proposed System

Here we have three sections. In the Sensor section it has LDR, humidity and temperature to monitor the agriculture Parameters. It has Zigbee module which will transmit the data to the intermediate section. In the intermediate section we have a Zigbee module and a GSM modem. The Zigbee module will receive the data from the Sensor section and Analyses it. If the value gets abnormal it will send the message to the farmer's mobile.

Block Diagram Sensor Section:

CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates designing of embedded controlled sensor networks used for controlling the home devices as well as monitoring the environmental parameters. The features of GSM and Zigbee are explored to design the system for long distance as well as short distance.. Embedded controlled sensor networks have proven themselves to be a reliable solution in providing remote control and sensing for indoor environmental monitoring systems. Three commercial sensors had been integrated with the system to monitor and compute the level of existence of CO gas, temperature and humidity in atmosphere using information and communication technologies.

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Design and comparison of path delay for various Parallel Prefix Adders

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ABSTRACT

Parallel-prefix adders (also known as carry tree Adders) are known to have the best performance in VLSI designs. This paper investigates five types of carry-tree adders (the Kogge-Stone, sparse Kogge-Stone, spanning tree adder, brentkung adder, hanCarlson adder and spanning tree adder) and compares them to the simple Ripple Carry Adder (RCA) and Carry Skip Adder (CSA). These designs of varied bit-widths were implemented on a Xilinx Spartan 3E FPGA. Due to the presence of a fast carry-chain, the RCA designs exhibit better delay performance up to 128 bits. The carry-tree adders are expected to have a speed advantage over the RCA as bit widths approach 256. This paper proposes the hardware implementation of VLSI architecture for different parallel prefix adders. The coding is done in Verilog HDL and the FPGA synthesis is done using Xilinx Spartan library.

Keywords: Parallel prefix adders, VLSI Architecture, FPGA, RCA, and CSA.

I. INTRODUCTION

To humans, decimal numbers are easy to comprehend and implement for performing arithmetic. However, in digital systems, such as a microprocessor, DSP (Digital Signal Processor) or ASIC (Application-Specific Integrated Circuit), binary numbers are more pragmatic for a given computation. This occurs because binary values are optimally efficient at representing many values. Binary adders are one of the most essential logic elements within a digital system. In addition, binary adders are also helpful in units other than Arithmetic Logic Units (ALU), such as multipliers, dividers and memory addressing.

Therefore, binary addition is essential that any improvement in binary addition can result in a performance boost for any computing system and, hence, help improve the performance of the entire system. The major problem for binary addition is the carry chain. As the width of the input operand

increases, the length of the carry chain increases. Figure 1.1 demonstrates examples of an 8-bit binary add operation and how the carry chain is affected. This example shows that the worst case occurs when the carry travels the longest possible path, from the least significant bit (LSB) to the most significant bit (MSB). In order to improve the performance of carry-propagate adders, it is possible to accelerate the carry chain, but not eliminate it. Consequently, most digital designers often resort to building faster adders when optimizing computer architecture, because they tend to set the critical path for most computations.

Figure 1.1: Binary Adder Example.

The binary adder is the critical element in most digital circuit designs including digital signal processors (DSP) and microprocessor data path units. As such, extensive research continues to be focused on improving the power delay performance of the adder. In VLSI implementations, parallel-prefix adders are known to have the best performance.

Reconfigurable logic such as Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) has been gaining in popularity in recent years because it offers improved performance in terms of speed and power over DSP-based and microprocessor based solutions for many practical designs involving mobile DSP and telecommunications applications and significant reduction in development time and cost over Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) designs. Two n bit operands using a radix-4 Booth recording multiplier requires approximately $n/(2m)$ clock cycles to generate the least significant half of the final product, where m is the number of Booth recoder adder stages. Thus, a large propagation delay is associated with this case.

II. CARRY – PROPAGATE ADDER

Binary carry-propagate adders have been extensively published, heavily attacking problems related to carry chain problem. Binary adders evolve from linear adders, which have a delay approximately proportional to the width of the adder, e.g. ripple-carry adder (RCA), to logarithmic-delay adder, such as the carry-look ahead adder (CLA).

There are some additional performance enhancing schemes, including the carry-increment adder and the Ling adder that can further enhance the carry chain, however, in Very Large Scale Integration(VLSI) digital systems, the most efficient way of offering binary addition involves utilizing parallel-prefix trees, this occurs because they have the regular structures that exhibit logarithmic delay.

Parallel-prefix adders compute addition in two steps: one to obtain the carry at each bit, with the next to compute the sum bit based on the carry bit. Unfortunately, prefix trees are algorithmically slower than fast logarithmic adders, such as the carry propagate adders, however, their regular structures

promote excellent results when compared to traditional CLA adders.

PARALLEL-PREFIX STRUCTURES

To resolve the delay of carry-look ahead adders, the scheme of multilevel-look ahead adders or parallel-prefix adders can be employed. The idea is to compute small group of intermediate prefixes and then find large group prefixes, until all the carry bits are computed. These adders have tree structures within a carry-computing stage similar to the carry propagate adder. However, the other two stages for these adders are called pre-computation and post-computation stages. In pre-computation stage, each bit computes its carry

Generate/propagate and a temporary sum. In the prefix stage, the group carry generate/propagate signals are computed to form the carry chain and provide the carry-in for the adder below. $G_{i:k} = G_{i:j} + P_{i:j}$. $G_{j-1:k} P_{i:k} = P_{i:j}$. $P_{j-1:k}$ In the post-computation stage, the sum and carry-out are finally produced. The carry-out can be omitted if only a sum needs to be produced. $s_i = t_i \wedge G_{i-1} \text{ cout} = g_{n-1} + p_{n-1} _ G_{n-2:-1}$ where $G_{i-1} = c_i$ with the assumption $g_{-1} = c_{in}$. The general diagram of parallel-prefix structures is shown in Figure 1, where an 8-bit case is illustrated. All parallel-prefix structures can be implemented with the equations above; however, Equation can be interpreted in various ways, which leads to different types of parallel-prefix trees. For example, Brent-Kung is known for its sparse topology at the cost of more logic levels. There are several design factors that can impact the performance of prefix structures. Such as Radix/Valency Logic Levels, Fan-out, Wire tracks

Figure.1: 8-bit Parallel-Prefix Structure

III. BUILDING PREFIX STRUCTURES

Parallel-prefix structures are found to be common in high performance adders because of the delay is logarithmically proportional to the adder width. Such structures can usually be

divided into three stages, pre-computation, prefix tree and post-computation. An example of an 8-bit parallel-prefix structure is shown in Figure 2. In the prefix tree, group generate/propagate are the only signals used. The group generate/propagate equations are based on single bit generate/propagate, which are computed in the pre-computation stage. $g_i = a_i \cdot b_i$ $p_i = a_i \oplus b_i$ where $0 < i < n$. $g_{-1} = c_{in}$ and $p_{-1} = 0$. Sometimes, p_i can be computed with OR logic instead of an XOR gate. The OR logic is mandatory especially when Ling's scheme is applied.

Here, the XOR logic is utilized to save a gate for temporary sum t_i . In the prefix tree, group generate/propagate signals are computed at each bit. $G_{i:k} = G_{i:j} + P_{i:j} \cdot G_{j-1:k}$ $P_{i:k} = P_{i:j} \cdot P_{j-1:k}$

1:k More practically, the above equation can be expressed using a symbol "o" denoted by Brent and Kung. Its function is exactly the same as that of a black cell. That is $(G_{i:k}; P_{i:k}) = (G_{i:j}; P_{i:j}) \circ (G_{j-1:k}; P_{j-1:k})$ or $G_{i:k} = (g_i; p_i) \circ (g_{i-1}; p_{i-1}) \circ \dots \circ (g_k; p_k)$ $P_{i:k} = p_i \cdot p_{i-1} \cdot \dots \cdot p_k$ The "o" operation will help make the rules of building prefix structures. In the post-computation, the sum and carry-out are the final output. $s_i = p_i \oplus G_{i-1:-1}$ $c_{out} = G_{n-1:-1}$ where "-1" is the position of carry-input.

The generate/propagate signals can be grouped in different fashion to get the same correct carries. Based on different ways of grouping the generate/propagate signals, different prefix architectures can be created. Figure 3 shows the definitions of cells that are used in prefix structures, including black cell and gray cell. Black/gray cells implement the above two equations, which will be heavily used in the following discussion on prefix trees.

Figure 2: Sklansky Parallel-Prefix

Figure 3: Cell Definitions.

IV. CARRY-TREE ADDER DESIGNS

Parallel prefix adders also known as carry tree adders they pre-compute propagate and generate signals. These signals are combined using fundamental carry operator (fco).

$$(g1, p1) \circ (g2, p2) = (g1+g2.p1, p1.p2)$$

Due to associative law of the fundamental carry operator these operators can be combined in different ways to form various adder structures. For example 4 bit carry look ahead generator is given by

$$C4 = (g4, p4) \circ [(g3, p3) \circ [(g2, p2) \circ (g1, p1)]]$$

Now in parallel prefix adders allow parallel operation resulting in more efficient tree structure for this 4 bit example.

$$C4 = [(g4, p4) \circ (g3, p3)] \circ [(g2, p2) \circ (g1, p1)]$$

It is a key advantage of tree structured adders is that the critical path due to carry delay is of order $\log_2 N$ for N bit wide adder. So the arrangement of the prefix network gives rise to various families of adders.

For this study the focus is on Kogge-Stone, Sparse Kogge stone, Brent Kung, Han-Carlson and Spanning tree adders for 16 bit width. Here we designate black cell as BC and grey cell as GC. Here we designate BC as the black cell which generates the ordered pair in equation. The gray cell (GC) generates the left signal only. The interconnect area is known to be high, but for an FPGA with large routing overhead to begin with, this is not as important as in a VLSI implementation.

KOGGE STONE ADDER

Kogge-Stone adder is one among the parallel prefix adders. This has regular layout which makes them favored adder in electronic technology. It has the minimum fan-out. A 16 bit Kogge stone adder is shown in the figure 4.

The maximum fan-out is 2 in all the logic levels for all width Kogge-stone prefix trees. The key of building any prefix tree is to implement the equation according to the specific features and apply the rules above described in the previous section.

The number of stages for a Kogge stone adder is calculated by \log_2 power N. no of cells is calculated as $N (\log_2 \text{ power } N - 1) + 1$. It consists of 34 BC's and 15 GC's and buffers are given. For 64 bit adder it consists of 6 stages.

No of cells are 321 cells in which 258 BC's and 63 GC's.

Figure 4: 16-bit Kogge-Stone Adder

SPARSE KOGGE STONE ADDER

Figure 5: 16-bit Sparse Kogge-Stone Adder.

The Sparse Kogge stone adder consists of several small ripple carry adders on its lower part, a carry tree is on its upper part. It terminates with ripple carry adders. Number of carries

Generated is less in this adder compared to Kogge stone adder. The function of grey cells and black cells is same as discussed in previous sections. Figure 5 shows the block diagram of 16 bit Sparse Kogge Stone adder. Like the sparse Kogge-Stone adder, this design terminates with a 4- bit RCA. As the FPGA uses a fast carry-chain for the RCA, it is interesting to compare the Performance of this adder with the sparse Kogge-Stone and regular Kogge-Stone adders.

BRENT KUNG ADDER

Figure 6: 16-bit Brent Kung Adder.

Brent Kung adder is one among the parallel prefix adders. Which has low number of cells and it is power efficient. Number of cells in the adder is defined by $2(N-1)-\log_2$ power N. Number of bits are defined by N. it consists of 11 BC's and 15 GC's. A simple tree structure could be formed if only the carry at every power of two positions is computed .it consists of inverse carry tree is added to compute intermediate carries. Figure 6shows Block diagram of Brent Kung 16 bit adder.

For 64 bit adder it consists of 11 stages. No of cells are 120 cells in which 57 BC's and 63 GC's.

HAN-CARLSON ADDER

This adder is the mix of Brent-Kung and Kogge stone adders .it has the maximum fan-out of 2. The Block

Diagram of 16 bit Han-Carlson adder is shown in the figure 7

Figure 7: 16-bit Han Carlson Adder.

SPANNINGTREEADDER

Figure 8: 16-bit Spanning tree Adder.

Another carry-tree adder known as the spanning tree carry-lookahead (CLA) adder is also examined .Like the sparse Kogge-Stone adder, this design terminates with a 4- bit RCA. As the FPGA uses a fast carry-chain for the RCA, it is interesting to compare the performance of this adder with the sparse Kogge-Stone and regular Kogge-Stone adders. Also of interest for the spanning-tree CLA is its testability features.

V. RESULTES

The adders to be studied were designed with varied bit widths up to 16 bits and coded in Verilog HDL. The functionality of the designs was verified via simulation with ModelSim. The Xilinx ISE 12.2 software was used to synthesize the designs onto the Spartan 3E FPGA. The simulated adder delays

obtained from the Xilinx ISE synthesis reports are shown below Table.1. However, according to the synthesis reports, the delay with the logic only makes the regular Kogge-Stone slightly faster

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF PATH DELAYS FOR DIFFERENT PARALLEL PREFIX ADDERS

ADDERS	PATH DELAY
sparsekoggestone	18.261ns
spanningtree	19.372NS
koggestone	13.418ns
hancarlson	15.450ns
brentkung	19.397ns

Maximum combinational path delay: 13.418ns

BRENTKUNG16

Maximum combinational path delay: 19.397ns

SPANNINGTREE

Maximum combinational path delay: 19.372ns

HANCARLSON16

Maximum combinational path delay: 15.450ns

SPARSEKOGGESTONE16

VI. CONCLUSION

Both measured and simulation results from this study have shown that parallel-prefix adders are not as effective as the simple ripple-carry adder at low to moderate bit widths. This is not unexpected as the Xilinx FPGA has a fast carry chain which optimizes the performance of the ripple carry adder. However, contrary to other studies, we have indications that the carry-tree adders eventually surpass the performance of the linear adder designs at high bit-widths, expected to be in the 128 to 256 bit range. This is important for large adders used in precision arithmetic and cryptographic applications where the addition of numbers on the order of a thousand bits is not uncommon. Because the adder is often the critical element which determines to a large part the cycle time and power dissipation for many digital signal processing and cryptographically implementations, it would be worthwhile for future FPGA designs to include an optimized carry path to enable tree based adder designs to be optimized for place and routing. This would improve their performance similar to what is found for the RCA. We plan to explore possible FPGA

Architectures that could implement a "fast-tree chain" and investigate the possible trade-offs involved. The built-in redundancy of the Kogge-Stone carry-tree structure and its implications for fault tolerance in FPGA designs is being studied. The testability and possible fault tolerant features of

The spanning tree adders are also topics for future research. These Hardware Architectures are useful for any number bits with little bit extension of Hardware.

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FPGA Implementation of Fast Elliptic Curve Cryptography using Itoh-Tsujii algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This paper primarily focuses on designing a high-performance Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) architecture and implementations of ECC over $GF(2^{163})$ provides the better security with less key size. Three complex instructions were used to reduce the latency by reducing the overall number of instructions, and a new combined algorithm, based on Lopez-Dahab algorithm, was developed to perform point doubling and point addition. Itoh-Tsujii inversion algorithm was used in the last stage of point multiplication and it is very fastest inversion algorithm compared to other algorithms. Itoh-Tsujii inversion algorithm is a very efficient algorithm for hardware implementation mainly due to reducing the multiplication and squaring operation.. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) recommended five efficient binary field key sizes [163,233,283,409,571]. In this paper ECC curve over $GF(2^{163})$ is shown, which achieves a point multiplication time of 24.3ns at 94.5 MHz on a Xilinx Virtex-2 pro FPGA.

Index Terms- Itoh-Tsujii inversion algorithm, Galois Field (GF), Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC), field-programmable gate array (FPGA).

I. INTRODUCTION

Quadratic equations are studied extensively within mathematics throughout a student's high school and college careers. The standard form for these equations in the variable x is given by $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$, parabolas and hyperbolas are studied in geometry, and surfaces such as hyperboloids and parabolic, given by $(x/a)^2 + (z/b)^2 + (y/c)^2 = 1$ and $(x/a)^2 + (y/b)^2 = z$ respectively. All of these are quadratic equations. Security provided to the Public key using these concepts in ancient days. What is beyond quadratics? For example, there are elliptic curves, which are of the form $y^2 = x^3 + ax^2 + bx + c$.

First introduced in the 1980s, elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) has become popular due to its smaller key sizes and the efficient ECC algorithms are two main reasons compared to existing public key algorithms such as RSA [1]. This superiority translates to equivalent security levels with smaller keys, bandwidth savings, and faster implementations [1], making ECC very appealing. So, to break the security provided to the device using ECC is very difficult, due to its higher degree and more number of variables. They are considered to be particularly

suitable for implementation on platforms with constrained storage and fast specifications. Purpose of Elliptic curve cryptography provides more security, cost efficiency faster implementations, lower power consumption, lower memory and smaller key size. Standards for ECC have been adopted by IEEE, ANSI, and NIST. Attacks on such devices are considered serious threats due to the physical characteristics of these devices and their use in potentially environments. Attacks seek to break the security of these devices through observing their power consumption trace or computations timing. Thus, designers of such systems strive to introduce algorithms and architectures that are not only efficient, but also attack resistant.

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The advantages of software implementations of ECC include ease of use, upgrade, portability, low development cost and flexibility. Their main disadvantages are their lower performance and limited ability to protect private keys compared to hardware implementations. Hardware implementations particularly for public key computations provide better security and offer improved speed and higher security, because they cannot be read or modified by an outside attacker as easily as software implementations.

Several recent FPGA-based hardware implementations of ECC have achieved high-performance throughput. Various acceleration techniques have been used, usually based on parallelism or pre computation.

The work introduced by Orlando and Paar [2] is based on the Montgomery method for computing KP developed by Lopez and Dahab [3] and operates over a single field. A point multiplication over GF (2¹⁶³) is performed in 210 microseconds, using a Galois field multiplier with eleven-cycle latency. The implementation from Lutz and Has an [1] implements some of these techniques achieving a point-multiplication time of 75µs over GF (2¹⁶³), using a Galois field multiplier with a four-cycle latency. An ECC processor capable of operating over multiple Galois fields was presented by Gura, *et al.* [4], which performs a point multiplication over GF (2¹⁶³) in 143µs, using a Galois field multiplier with three-cycle latency. Rodriguez, *et al.* [5] introduced

an FPGA implementation that performs DBL and ADD in parallel, containing multiple instances of circuits to perform the arithmetic functions. It would appear that the inversion required for coordinate conversion at the end of the point multiplication is not performed, as a result the overall performance is let down by quite a low clock frequency (46.5 MHz).

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. ECC using lopez-dahab algorithm

ECC is performed over one of two underlying Galois fields: prime order fields GF (p) or characteristic two fields GF (2^m). Both fields are considered to provide the same level of security [3], but arithmetic in GF (2^m) will be the focus of this paper because it can be implemented in hardware more efficiently using modulo-2 arithmetic. An elliptic E curve over the field GF (2^m) is the set of solutions to the equation (1)

$$y^2 + xy = x^3 + ax + b \quad (1)$$

Where a, b ∈ GF (2^m), b≠0.

Let P₁=(x₁, y₁) ∈ E and P₂=(x₂, y₂) ∈ E, then Summing the two points is P₁+P₂=P₃=(x₃, y₃) ∈ E, Where

$$x_3 = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{y_1 + y_2}{x_1 + x_2} \right)^2 + \frac{y_1 + y_2}{x_1 + x_2} + x_1 + x_2 + a, & P_1 \neq P_2 \\ x_1^2 + \frac{b}{x_1^2}, & P_1 = P_2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$y_3 = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{y_1 + y_2}{x_1 + x_2} \right) (x_1 + x_3) + x_3 + y_1, & P_1 \neq P_2 \\ x_1^2 + \left(x_2 + \frac{y_1}{x_1} \right) (x_3) + x_3, & P_1 = P_2 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Hence, when P₁=P₂ we have the point-doubling operation (DBL), and when P₁≠P₂ we have the point-adding operation (ADD). These operations in turn constitute the crux of any ECC-based algorithm, known as point multiplication or scalar multiplication KP. Galois field multiplier for m=163 i.e, GF (2¹⁶³), the standard recommended curve irreducible polynomial is f(x)= x¹⁶³ + x⁷ + x⁶ + x³ +1. The advantage of choosing Galois field multiplier is for

security. Galois field produces better security for Elliptic curve cryptography.

There are two types of coordinate system, affine coordinate system and Projective coordinate system. Affine coordinate system is a normal coordinate system which consists of divisions (inversion) operations takes more multiplication operations. Another method to compute the point addition and point doubling is to use projective coordinates $P = (X, Z)$. This method has the advantage to save the inversion which is the hardest to compute operation. So we need only one inversion to back conversion. In order to use this method, the coordinates must be converted.

Converting of affine coordinate system to Projective coordinate system is by replacing point $P(x, y)$ to $P(X, Z)$ by using Lopez-Dahab projective coordinate system algorithm. Converting of Projective to Affine coordinate system in last stage of point multiplication called coordinate conversion using Itoh- Tsujii inversion algorithm.

In [3], procedures to perform DBL and ADD are derived from efficient formulas which use only the -coordinate of the points. In the projective coordinate version of the formulas, the x-coordinate of P_i is represented by $\frac{x_i}{z_i}$, for $i \in \{1,2,3\}$; the corresponding DBL and ADD computations are shown in (4) and (5), respectively, and are used in the projective coordinate point multiplication algorithm shown in Algorithm 1

$$x(2P_i) = X_i^4 + b \cdot Z_i^4$$

$$z(2P_i) = Z_i^2 \cdot X_i^2$$

$$Z_3 = (X_1 \cdot Z_2 + X_2 \cdot Z_1)^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$X_3 = x \cdot Z_3 + (X_1 \cdot Z_2)(X_2 \cdot Z_1) \dots (5)$$

Algorithm 1: Lopez-Dahab Point Multiplication.

Input: An integer $k \geq 0$ and a base point $P=(x, y) \in E$.

Output: $Q = KP$.

If $k = 0$ or $x = 0$ then output $(0, 0)$ and stop.

Set $k \leftarrow (k_{1-1}, k_{1-2}, \dots, k_0)$

Set $X_1 \leftarrow x, Z_1 \leftarrow 1, X_2 \leftarrow x^4 + b \cdot Z_2 \leftarrow x^2$.

For j from $l-2$ down to 0 do

 If $k_j = 1$ then

 ADD(X_1, Z_1, X_2, Z_2), DBL(X_2, Z_2)

 Else

 ADD(X_2, Z_2, X_1, Z_1), DBL(X_1, Z_1) .

 Return ($Q = \text{Proj } 2\text{Aff}(X_1, Z_1, X_2, Z_2)$).

Multipliers are usually implemented using one of three approaches: bit-serial, bit-parallel, or digit-serial. Bit-serial multipliers [7], [8] are small, but they require m steps to perform a multiplication. Bit-parallel multipliers [6], [8]–[10] are large but perform a multiplication in a single step.

B. ECC using new combined algorithm

Squaring is a special case of multiplication, and it is only a little more complex than reduction modulo the irreducible polynomial. Refer to [9] for efficient architectures to perform polynomial basis squaring, which only require combinational logic. Itoh–Tsujii inversion algorithm is based on Fermat’s little theorem and is used to compute the inversion at the end of the point multiplication. The algorithm uses addition chains to reduce the required number of multiplications, but it contains exponentiations that must be performed through repeated squaring operations—as many as 64 repeated squaring operations for the field $GF(2^{163})$. It was shown in [1], that relatively low latencies can be achieved using this algorithm if repeated squaring can be performed efficiently. Hence, a third application-specific instruction will be used to perform repeated squaring (RESQR) in order to accelerate the Itoh–Tsujii Inversion algorithm. Using these instructions, a combined algorithm to perform point doubling and point addition can be developed, which has only nine arithmetic instructions, shown in Algorithm 2.

This point addition and point doubling is performed using *new combined algorithm* as shown below.

Input: x-coordinates X_1/Z_1 for P_1 and X_2/Z_2 for P_2 curve Parameter b ;

Output: x-coordinates X_1/Z_1 for $P_1 + P_2$ and X_2/Z_2 for $2P_2$

```

T1 <----- MUL (X2, Z1)
T2 <-----MULAD (X1, Z2)
Z1 <----- RESQ (T2)
T3 <-----MULSQ (Z2, Z2)
Z2 <----- MULSQ(X2, Z2)
T1 <-----MUL (T1, T2)
X1 <-----MULAD (Z3, x)
X2 <-----MULSQ (X2, Z2)
X2 <-----MULAD (T3,b)
    
```

The main aim of the algorithm is to perform DBL and ADD using complex instruction set which reduce the

number of instructions and perform multiple tasks in a single instruction. Three new instructions were introduced in algorithms that are MULAD, MULSQ, and RESQ. DBL and ADD are derived from efficient formulas which use only the x-coordinate of the points.

C. ECC using itoh–tsujii inversion algorithm

When m is odd,

$$a^{2^{(m-1)-1}} = (a^{2^{(m-1)/2-1}})^{2^{(m-1)-1}} \cdot a^{2^{(m-1)/2-1}}$$

When m is even

$$a^{2^{(m-1)-1}} = a(a^{2^{(m-2)-1}})^2$$

$$tmp1 = a^{2^{2-1}} = a \cdot a^2$$

$$tmp2 = a^{2^{4-1}} = tmp1 \cdot (tmp1)^{2^2}$$

$$tmp3 = a^{2^{5-1}} = a \cdot (tmp2)^2$$

$$tmp4 = a^{2^{10-1}} = tmp3 \cdot (tmp3)^{2^5}$$

$$tmp5 = a^{2^{20-1}} = tmp4 \cdot (tmp4)^{2^{10}}$$

$$tmp6 = a^{2^{40-1}} = tmp5 \cdot (tmp5)^{2^{20}}$$

$$tmp7 = a^{2^{80-1}} = tmp6 \cdot (tmp6)^{2^{40}}$$

$$tmp8 = a^{2^{81-1}} = a \cdot (tmp7)^2$$

$$tmp9 = a^{2^{162-1}} = tmp8 \cdot (tmp8)^{2^{81}}$$

$$a^{-1} = 2^{2^{163-2}} = (tmp9)^2$$

Tmp1 to tmp9 are 163-bit registers used to store temporary data for inversion operations. Suppose A^{2^s} form represents s-bit rotate shift.

This inversion process is used in last stage of point multiplication shown in Fig (1). Itoh-suji inversion algorithm is very fastest inversion algorithm compared to other algorithms. Mainly it reduces the multiplication and squaring operations. So, it is used as a very efficient algorithm for hardware implementation.

Fig 1: BLOCK DIAGRAM OF ECC

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To have a realistic platform the proposed methodology is implemented on a Xilinx virtex-2 pro FPGA. The architectures have been authored in VHDL and its synthesis was done with Xilinx ISE foundation 9.1i has been used for performing, mapping, placing and routing. For Behavioral simulation shown in Fig 2 Modelsim6.0 has been used. The synthesis tool was configured to optimize for area and high effort considerations The unit was synthesized using devices from the Xilinx Virtex-2pro FPGA family. Table 1 reports the device utilization for realizing ECC architecture.

TABLE I
DEVICE UTILIZATION (XC2Vp2)

ITEM	AMOUNT	UTILIZATION (%)
Number of slices	6516	14
Number of Flip-Flops	6583	7
Number of 4 i/p LUTs	8265	9
Number of bonded IOBs	839	72
Number of GCLs	1	16

Proposed Architecture Result:

Fig 2: Behavioral simulation result of the Elliptic curve Cryptography

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper focussed on a high-performance ECC has been implemented using FPGA technology. A combined algorithm to perform DBL and ADD was developed based on the Lopez and Dahab Point multiplication algorithm. The data path was pipeline achieved a point multiplication time of 24.3ns on Virtex-2 Pro device ff1696-5 and implementations of ECC over GF (2^{163}) performs the better security with less key size.

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BIOGRAPHY

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Secure transmission in downlink cellular network with cooperative Jammer

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ABSTRACT

A mobile jammer is a device which is used to jam signals of cell phone from receiving signals from base stations. Mobile jammer is used majorly where the disturbances that are occurred with the cell phones. So, in this paper we are designing a new Mobile Jammer unit which is capable of blocking the cell phone working not the signal receiving from Base Station, which make effective use of the situation where jammers actually used. This was implemented using FPGA by interfacing Mobile Device, RF Transmitter and RF Receiver and LCD Unit.

Keywords: Jammers, Mobile Jammer, FPGA, RF Transmitter, RF Receiver, LCD.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cell phones are everywhere these days. According to the Cellular Telecommunications and Internet Association, almost 195 million people in the United States had cell-phone service in October 2005. And cell phones are even more ubiquitous in Europe.

The mobile phone or mobile, also called a wireless, cellular phone, cell phone, cell or hand phone (HP), is a long-range, portable electronic device used for mobile communication that uses a network of specialized base stations known as cell sites.

In addition to the standard voice function of a telephone, current mobile phones may support many additional services, and accessories, such as SMS for text messaging, email, packet switching for access to the Internet, and MMS for sending and receiving photos and video. Most current mobile phones connect to a cellular network of base stations (cell sites), which is in turn interconnected to the public switched telephone network (PSTN) (the exception is satellite phones). Cell phones are basically handheld two-way radios. And like any radio, the signal can be disrupted, or jammed.

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Inside a Digital Cell Phone

If you take a basic digital cell phone apart, you find that it contains just a few individual parts:

- An amazing circuit board containing the brains of the phone
- An antenna
- A liquid crystal display (LCD)
- A keyboard (not unlike the one you find in a TV remote control)
- A microphone
- A speaker
- A battery

Jamming Basics:

Disrupting a cell phone is the same as jamming any other type of radio communication. A cell phone works by communicating with its service network through a cell tower or base station. Cell towers divide a city into small areas, or cells. As a cell-phone user drives down the street, the signal is handed from tower to tower. A jamming device transmits on the same radio frequencies as the cell phone, disrupting the communication between the phone and the cell-phone base station in the tower. Cell Phone Jammer is an instrument to prevent cellular

Need & History of Jammers

The rapid proliferation of cell phones at the beginning of the 21st century to near ubiquitous status eventually raised problems, such as their potential use to invade privacy or contribute to academic cheating. In addition, public backlash was growing against the disruption cell phones introduced in daily life. While older analog cell phones often suffered from poor reception and could even be disconnected by simple interference such as high frequency noise, increasingly sophisticated digital phones have led to more elaborate counters. Cell phone jamming devices are an alternative to more expensive measures against cell phones, such as Faraday cages, which are mostly suitable as built in protection for structures.

They were originally developed for law enforcement and the military to interrupt communications by criminals and terrorists. Some were also designed to foil the use of certain remotely detonated explosives. The civilian applications were apparent, so over time many companies originally contracted to design jammers for government use switched over to sell

phone from receiving and transmitting the mobile signals to the base station. Mobile Cell Phone Jammer can block all kinds of mobile phones ringing sound at all places such as church, mosque, library, Movie Theater and meeting room. You just buy it and just attach it at some place. And you will never hear the bell sound of mobile phone any more.

Fig: Mobile Jamming

these devices to private entities. Since then, there has been a slow but steady increase in their purchase and use, especially in major metropolitan areas. As with other radio jamming, cell phone jammers block cell phone use by sending out radio waves along the same frequencies that cellular phones use.

This causes enough interference with the communication between cell phones and towers to render the phones unusable. On most retail phones, the network would simply appear out of range. Most cell phones use different bands to send and receive communications from towers (called frequency division duplexing, FDD).

Jammers can work by either disrupting phone to tower frequencies or tower to phone frequencies. Smaller handheld models block all bands from 800 MHz to 1900 MHz within a 30-foot range (9 meters). Small devices tend to use the former method, while larger more expensive models may interfere directly with the tower. The radius of cell phone jammers can range from a dozen feet for pocket models to kilometers for more dedicated units. The TRJ-89 jammer can block cellular communications for a 5-mile (8 km) radius.

Less energy is required to disrupt signal from tower to mobile phone than the signal from mobile phone to the tower (also called base station), because the base station is located at larger distance from the jammer than the mobile phone and that is why the signal from the tower is not as strong.

Older jammers sometimes were limited to working on phones using only analog or older digital mobile phone standards. Newer models such as the double and triple band jammers can block all widely used systems (CDMA, iDEN, GSM, et al.) and are even very effective against newer phones which hop to different frequencies and systems when interfered with. As the dominant network technology and frequencies used for mobile phones vary worldwide, some work only in specific regions such as Europe or North America. Some Cell Phone Jammers have been introduced to some State Prisons in the United States. Cell phones that have been sneaked into prison pose a security risk for guards and property owners living nearby.

Problems in Existing Jammers

Envisage a situation where you are essaying to dial 911 and cannot get through because someone has a cell phone jammer with him. Otherwise, you want to call the police to avoid a robbery in your building but the robber has a cell phone jammer with him. So, what could you do in such a dangerous situation? Jamming devices utilized with some thoughts may be much more useful than just a method of enjoyment. To remove these hazards a new efficient type of mobile jammer is proposed using FPGA. In this new design we are going to disable the keypad, MIC, speaker, will be only disabled by using the FPGA & we doing it using a 400MHz frequency which has an public license so there is no need of licensing.

Some of the Common Problems are listed below:

- The person didn't even get the notification of a call or message when he is in the jammer coverage area.
- The person cannot be contacted for some urgent information also.
- Nearly the mobile phone will be in Switch Off state.
- There will not be any notification that the user mobile has been jammed.

Proposed System Design

In most countries, it is illegal for private citizens to jam cell-phone transmission, but some countries are allowing businesses and government organizations to install jammers in areas where cell-phone use is seen as a public nuisance. In December 2004, France legalized cell-phone jammers in movie theaters, concert halls and other places with performances. France is finalizing technology that will let calls to emergency services go through. India has installed jammers in parliament and some prisons. It has been reported that universities in Italy have adopted the technology to prevent cheating. Students were taking photos of tests with their camera phones and sending them to classmates.

Alternatives to Cell Phone Jamming

While the law clearly prohibits using a device to actively disrupt a cell-phone signal, there are no rules against passive cell-phone blocking. That means using things like wallpaper or building materials embedded with metal fragments to prevent cell-phone signals from reaching inside or outside the room. Some buildings have designs that block radio signals by accident due to thick concrete walls or a steel skeleton.

Companies are working on devices that **control a cell phone** but do not "jam the signal." One device sends incoming calls to voicemail and blocks outgoing calls. The argument is that the phone still works, so it is technically not being jammed. It is a legal gray area that has not been ruled on by the FCC as of April 2005.

Cell-phone alters are available that indicate the presence of a cell-phone signal. These have been used in hospitals where cell-phone signals could interfere with sensitive medical equipment. When a signal is detected, users are asked to turn off their phones.

For a less technical solution, Caudal Partners, a design firm in Chicago, has launched the SHHH, the **Society for Handheld Hushing**. At its Web site, you can download a note to hand to people conducting annoying cell-phone conversations, expressing your lack of interest in what they're talking about.

Block Diagram

Figure 1: Mobile Jammer General Block Diagram

FPGA

A **Field-programmable Gate Array (FPGA)** is an integrated circuit designed to be configured by the customer or designer after manufacturing—hence "field-programmable". The FPGA configuration is generally specified using a hardware description language (HDL), similar to that used for an application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) (circuit

diagrams were previously used to specify the configuration, as they were for ASICs, but this is increasingly rare). FPGAs can be used to implement any logical function that an ASIC could perform. The ability to update the functionality after shipping, partial re-configuration of the portion of the design^[1] and the low non-recurring engineering costs relative to an ASIC design (notwithstanding the generally higher unit cost), offer advantages for many applications.

FPGAs contain programmable logic components called "logic blocks", and a hierarchy of reconfigurable interconnects that allow the blocks to be "wired together"—somewhat like many (changeable) logic gates that can be inter-wired in (many) different configurations. Logic blocks can be configured to perform complex combinational functions, or merely simple logic gates like AND and XOR. In most FPGAs, the logic blocks also include memory elements, which may be simple flip-flops or more complete blocks of memory.

In addition to digital functions, some FPGAs have analog features. The most common analog feature is programmable slew rate and drive strength on each output pin, allowing the engineer to set slow rates on lightly loaded pins that would otherwise ring unacceptably, and to set stronger, faster rates on heavily loaded pins on high-speed channels that would otherwise run too slow. Another relatively common analog feature is differential comparators on input pins designed to be connected to differential signaling channels. A few "mixed signal FPGAs" have integrated peripheral Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs) and Digital-to-Analog Converters (DACs) with analog signal conditioning blocks allowing them to operate as a system-on-a-chip. Such devices blur the line between an FPGA, which carries digital ones and zeros on its internal programmable interconnect fabric, and field-programmable analog array (FPAA), which carries analog values on its internal programmable interconnect fabric.

RF ENCODER AND DECODER

General Encoder and Decoder Operations

The Holtek HT-12E IC encodes 12-bits of information and serially transmits this data on receipt of a Transmit Enable, or a LOW signal on pin-14 /TE. Pin-17 the D_OUT pin of the HT-12E serially

transmits whatever data is available on pins 10, 11, 12 and 13, or D0, D1, D2 and D3. Data is transmitted at a frequency selected by the external oscillator resistor.

By using the switches attached to the data pins on the HT-12E, as shown in the schematic, we can select the information in binary format to send to the receiver. The receiver section consists of the Ming RE-99 and the HT-12D decoder IC. The DATA_IN pin-14 of the HT-12D reads the 12-bit binary information sent by the HT-12E and then places this data on its output pins. Pins 10,11,12 and 13 are the data out pins of the HT-12D, D0,D1,D2 and D3.The HT-12D receives the 12-bit word and interprets the first 8-bits as address and the last 4-bits as data. Pins 1-8 of the HT-12E are the address pins. Using the address pins of the HT-12E, we can select different addresses for up to 256 receivers. The address is determined by setting pins 1-8 on the HT-12E to ground, or just leaving they open. The address selected on the HT-12E circuit must match the address selected on the HT-12D circuit (exactly), or the information will be ignored by the receiving circuit.

When the received addresses from the encoder matches the decoders, the Valid Transmission pin-17 of the HT-12D will go HIGH to indicate that a valid transmission has been received and the 4-bits of data are latched to the data output pins, 10-13. The transistor circuit shown in the schematic will use the VT, or valid transmission pin to light the LED. When the VT pin goes HIGH it turns on the 2N2222 transistor which in turn delivers power to the LED providing a visual indication of a valid transmission reception.

Controlling the Project with a FPGA

Using these RF transmitter & receiver circuits with a FPGA would be simple. We can simply replace the switches used for selecting data on the HT-12E with the output pins of the FPGA. Also we can use another output pin to select TE, or transmit enable on the HT-12E. By taking pin-14 LOW we cause the transmitter section to transmit the data on pins 10-13.

To receive information simply hook up the HT-12D output pins to the FPGA. The VT or valid transmission pin of the HT-12D could signal the

FPGA to grab the 4-bits of data from the data output pins. If you are using a FPGA with interrupt capabilities, use the VT pin to cause a jump to an interrupt vector and process the received data.

The HT-12D data output pins will LATCH and remain in this state until another valid transmission is received. **NOTE:** You will notice that in both schematics each of the Holtek chips have resistors attached to pins 15 and 16. These resistors must be the exact values shown in the schematic. These resistors set the internal oscillators of the HT-12E/HT-12D. It is recommended that you choose a 1% resistor for each of these resistors to ensure the correct circuit oscillation.

Range of Operation

The normal operating range using (only) the LOOP TRACE ANTENNA on the transmitter board is about 50 feet. By connecting a quarter wave antenna using 9.36 inches of 22 gauge wire to both circuits, you can extend this range to several hundred feet. Your actual range may vary due to your finished circuit design and environmental conditions. The transistors and diodes can be substituted with any common equivalent type. These will normally depend on the types and capacities of the particular loads you want to control and should be selected accordingly for your intended application.

RF DETAILS

The TWS-434 and RWS-434 are extremely small, and are excellent for applications requiring short-range RF remote controls. The transmitter module is only 1/3 the size of a standard postage stamp, and can easily be placed inside a small plastic enclosure. TWS-434: The transmitter output is up to 8mW at 433.92MHz with a range of approximately 400 foot (open area) outdoors. Indoors, the range is approximately 200 foot, and will go through most walls.....

Figure 2: RF 434 MHz Transmitters. Modulation: ASK

The TWS-434 transmitter accepts both linear and digital inputs can operate from 1.5 to 12 Volts-DC, and makes building a miniature hand-held RF transmitter very easy. The TWS-434 is approximately the size of a standard postage stamp.

Figure 3: RF-434 Pin Diagram

TWS-434RF Receiver operates at 433.92MHz Frequency and at Voltage: 4.5V~5.5V and Bit-rate: 0.2kbps-4kbps

Fig: 4 Receiver Pin configurations

LCD Display

More FPGA devices are using 'smart LCD' displays to output visual information. The following discussion covers the connection of a 16x2 LCD display to a PIC FPGA. LCD displays designed around Hitachi's LCD HD44780 module, are inexpensive, easy to use, and it is even possible to produce a readout using the 8 x 80 pixels of the display. Hitachi LCD displays have a standard ASCII set of characters plus Japanese, Greek and mathematical symbols.

For a 8-bit data bus, the display requires a +5V supply plus 11 I/O lines. For a 4-bit data bus it only requires the supply lines plus seven extra lines. When the LCD display is not enabled, data lines are

tri-state which means they are in a state of high impedance (as though they are disconnected) and this means they do not interfere with the operation of the FPGA when the display is not being addressed.

Reading data from the LCD is done in the same way, but control line R/W has to be high. When we send a high to the LCD, it will reset and wait for instructions. Typical instructions sent to LCD display after a reset are: turning on a display, turning on a cursor and writing characters from left to right. When the LCD is initialized, it is ready to continue receiving data or instructions. If it receives a character, it will write it on the display and move the cursor one space to the right. The Cursor marks the next location where a character will be written. When we want to write a string of characters, first we need to set up the starting address, and then send one character at a time. Characters that can be shown on the display are stored in data display (DD) RAM. The size of DDRAM is 80 bytes.

Fig 5: Pictures of our Proposed Mobile jammer

CONCLUSION

Our projected Mobile jammer is functioning utterly while not moving the signals from the network. In order that the user will be able to get the notifications relating to Calls and messages (SMS, MMS). The notifications regarding the calls are given to the user. If there's any imperative decision as we will get the notification we will leave from the coverage space and use our mobile because it is. No would like of licensing. Implementation of our freshly designed jammers is straightforward. As we tend to square measure employing a FPGA, our hardware will be changed whenever we would like. Will be enforced wherever silence to be maintained. Future modifications square measure attainable simply. Misuse of mobiles will be restricted. So our Mobile jammers will offer higher potency with lower misuses.

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Efficient BISR strategy for Embedded SRAM with Selectable Redundancy using MARCH SS algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an efficient BISR strategy which consists of a Built-In Self-Test (BIST) module, a Built-In Address-Analysis (BIAA) module and a Multiplexer (MUX) module. The BISR is designed flexible that it can provide four operation modes to SRAM users. Each fault address can be saved only once is the feature of the proposed BISR strategy. In BIAA module, fault addresses and redundant ones form a one-to-one mapping to achieve a high repair speed. Besides, instead of adding spare words, rows, columns or blocks in the SRAMs, users can select normal words as redundancy. The selectable redundancy brings no penalty of area and complexity and is suitable for compiler design.

Keywords: Built-In Self-Test (BIST) , Built-In Address-Analysis (BIAA) , SRAM, BISR

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the area occupied by embedded memories in System-on-Chip (SoC) is over 90%, and expected to rise up to 94% by 2014 [1]. Thus, the performance and yield of embedded memories will dominate that of SoCs. However, memory fabrication yield is limited largely by random defects, random oxide pinholes, random leakage defects, gross processing and assembly faults, specific processing faults, misalignments, gross photo defects and other faults and defects.

To increase the reliability and yield of embedded memories, many redundancy mechanisms have been proposed [3-6]. In [3-5] both redundant rows and columns are incorporated into the memory array. In [6] spare words, rows, and columns are added into the word-oriented memory cores as redundancy. All these redundancy mechanisms bring penalty of area and complexity to embedded memories design. Considered that compiler is used to configure SRAM

for different needs, the BISR had better bring no change to other modules in SRAM. To solve the problem, a new redundancy scheme is proposed in this paper. Some normal words in embedded memories can be selected as redundancy instead of adding spare words, spare rows, spare columns or spare blocks.

Memory test is necessary before using redundancy to repair. Designs for test (DFT) techniques proposed in 1970 improve the testability by including additional circuitry. The DFT circuitry controlled through a BIST circuitry is more time-saving and efficient compared to that controlled by the external tester (ATE) [7]. However, memory BIST does not address the loss of parts due to manufacturing defects but only the screening aspects of the manufactured parts [8]. BISR techniques aim at testing embedded memories, saving the fault addresses and replacing them with redundancy. In [9], the authors proposed a new memory BISR strategy applying two serial redundancy analysis

(RA) stages. [10] Presents an efficient repair algorithm for embedded memory with multiple redundancies and a BISR circuit using the proposed algorithm. All the previous BISR techniques can repair memories, but they didn't tell us how to avoid storing fault address more than once. This paper proposes an efficient BISR strategy which can store each fault address only once.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II outlines SRAM fault models, test algorithms and BIST design. Section III introduces the proposed BISR strategy. We present the details of the proposed BISR strategy including the architectures, procedures and the features. In section IV, the experimental results are reported. Finally, Section V concludes this paper.

II. FAULT MODELS, TEST ALGORITHMS AND BIST

A fault model is a systematic and precise representation of physical faults in a form suitable for simulation and test generation [11]. Applying the reduced functional model, SRAM faults can be classified as follows in [12].

AF ---- ADDRESS FAULT

ADOF ---- ADDRESS DECODER OPEN FAULTS

CF ---- COUPLING FAULTS

CFIN ---- INVERSION COUPLING FAULTS

CFID ---- IDEMPOTENT COUPLING FAULTS

BF ---- BRIDGE COUPLING FAULTS

CFST ---- STATE COUPLING FAULTS

DRF ---- DATA RETENTION FAULTS

SAF ---- STUCK-AT FAULTS

SOF ---- STUCK OPEN FAULTS

TF ---- TRANSITION FAULTS

The details of the fault models can be referred in [12]. They are the foundations of the memory test. An Efficient and economical memory test should provide the best fault coverage in the shortest test time [13]. BIST is used to test memories in the paper and its precision is guaranteed by test algorithms. The algorithms in most common use are the March tests. March tests have the advantage of short test time but good fault coverage. There are many March tests such as March C, March C-, March C+, March 3

and so on. TABLE I compares the test length, complexity and fault coverage of them. 'n' stands for the capacity of SRAM.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT MARCH TESTS

Algorithms	Test length	Complexity	Fault coverage
March C	11n	O(n)	AF, SAF, TF, CFin, CFid, and CFst
March C-	10n	O(n)	AF, SAF, TF, CFin, CFid, and CFst
March C+	14n	O(n)	AF, SAF, TF, SOF, CFin, and CFid
March 3	10n	O(n)	AF, SAF, SOF, and TF

As shown in TABLE I, March C- has better fault coverage than March 3 and shorter test time than March C and March C+. So March C- has been chosen as BIST algorithm in this paper. Its algorithm steps are as follows:

1. Up - write 0
2. Up - read 0, write 1
3. Up - read 1, write 0
4. Down - read 0, write 1
5. Down - read 1, write 0
6. Down - read 0

In above steps, "up" represents executing SRAM addresses in ascending order while "down" in descending order. The BIST module in the paper refers to the MBISR design of Mentor Graphics. It mainly consists of a BIST controller, a test vector generator, an address generator and a comparator. It can indicate when memory test is done and whether there is fault in memory.

III. PROPOSED BISR STRATEGY

Redundancy Architecture

The proposed SRAM BISR strategy is flexible. The SRAM users can decide whether to use it by setting a signal. So the redundancy of the SRAM is designed to be selectable. In another word, some normal words in SRAM can be selected as redundancy if the SRAM needs to repair itself. We call these words Normal-Redundant words to distinguish them from the real normal ones. We take a 64 × 4 SRAM for example, as shown in Figure 1. There are 60 normal words and 4 Normal-Redundant words. When the BISR is used, the Normal-Redundant words are

accessed as normal ones. Otherwise, the Normal-Redundant words can only be accessed when there are faults in normal words.

In this case, the SRAM can only offer capacity of 60 words to users. This should be referred in SRAM manual in details.

Figure 1. Architecture of redundancy in SRAM

This kind of selectable redundancy architecture can save area and increase efficiency. After BISR is applied, other modules in SRAM can remain unchanged. Thus the selectable redundancy won't bring any problem to SRAM compiler.

Overall BISR Architecture

Figure 2. Proposed BISR Architecture

The architecture of the proposed BISR strategy is shown in Figure 2. It consists of three parts: BIST module, BIAA module and MUX module. We call the SRAM with BISR a system. The BIST module uses March C- to test the addresses of the normal words in SRAM. It detects SRAM failures with a comparator that compares actual memory data with expected data. If there is a failure (compare = 1), the current address is considered as a faulty address. The BIAA module can store faulty addresses in a memory named Fault_A_Mem. There is a counter in BIAA that counts the number of faulty addresses. When BISR is used (bist_h = 1), the faulty addresses can be replaced with redundant addresses to repair the SRAM. The inputs of SRAM in different operation modes are controlled by the MUX module. In test mode (bist_h = 1), the inputs of SRAM are generated in BISR while they are equal to system inputs in access mode (bist_h = 0).

BISR procedure

Figure 3 shows the proposed BISR block diagram. The BISR starts by resetting the system (rst_l = 0). After that if the system work in test mode, it goes into TEST phase. During this phase, the BIST module and BIAA module work in parallel. The BIST use March C- to test the normal addresses of SRAM. As long as any fault is detected by the BIST module, the faulty address will be sent to the BIAA module. Then the BIAA module checks whether the faulty address has been already stored in Fault-A-Mem. If the faulty address has not been stored, the BIAA stores it and the faulty address counter adds 1. Otherwise, the faulty address can be ignored. When the test is completed, there will be two conditions. If there is no fault or there are too many faults that overflow the redundancy capacity, BISR goes into COMPLETE phase. If there are faults in SRAM but without overflows, the system goes into REPAIR&TEST phase. The same as during TEST phase, the BIST module and BIAA module work at the same time in REPAIR&TEST phase. The BIAA module replaces the faulty addresses stored in Fault-A-Mem with redundant ones and the BIST module tests the SRAM again. There will be two results: repair fail or repair pass. By using the BISR, the users can pick out the SRAMs that can be repaired with redundancy or the ones with no fault.

Figure 3. Block Diagram of BISR

Features of the BISR

Firstly, the BISR strategy is flexible. TABLE II lists the operation modes of SRAM. In access mode, SRAM users can decide whether the BISR is used base on their needs. If the BISR is needed, the Normal-Redundant words will be taken as redundancy to repair fault. If not, they can be accessed as normal words.

TABLE II. SRAM OPERATION MODES

Modes	Repair selection	Operation
Test mode (test_h=1)	Default: repair (bistr_h=1)	Access normal words. Repair faults and test.
	Don't repair (bistr_h=0)	Access normal words. Test only.
Access mode (test_h=0)	Repair (bistr_h=1)	Access normal words. Repair faults and write/read SRAM.
	Don't repair (bistr_h=0)	Access Normal- Redundant and normal Words. Write/read SRAM only.

Secondly, the BISR strategy is efficient. On one hand, the efficiency reflects on the selectable redundancy which is described as flexible above. No matter the BISR is applied or not, the Normal-Redundant words are used in the SRAM. It saves area and has high utilization. On the other hand, each fault address can be stored only into Fault-A-Mem. As said before, March C- has 6 steps. In another word, the addresses will be read 5 times in one test. Some faulty addresses can be detected in more than one step. Take Stuckat-0 fault for example, it can be

detected in both 3rd and 5th steps. But the fault address shouldn't be stored twice. So we propose an efficient method to solve the problem in BIAA module. Figure 4 shows the flows of storing fault addresses. BIST detects whether the current address is faulty. If it is, BIAA checks whether the Fault-A-Mem overflows. If not, the current fault address should be compared with those already stored in Fault-A-Mem. Only if the faulty address isn't equal to any address in Fault-A-Mem, it can be stored. To simplify the comparison, write a redundant address into Fault-A-Mem as background. In this case, the fault address can be compared with all the data stored in Fault-A-Mem no matter how many fault addresses have been stored.

Figure 4. Flows of Storing Fault Addresses

At last, the BISR strategy is high-speed. As shown in Figure 4, once a fault address is stored in Fault-A-Mem, it points to a certain redundant address. The fault addresses and redundant ones form a one-to-one mapping. Using this method, the BISR can quickly get the corresponding redundant address to replace the faulty one.

MARCH SS ALGORITHM

March tests have the advantage of short testing time with good fault coverage. The proposed MARCH algorithm is MARCH C-. Extension for this algorithm is MARCH SS. The algorithm steps are as follows.

1. Up – write 0
2. Up – read 0, read 0, write 0, read 0, write 1
3. Up – read 1, read 1, write 1, read 1, write 0
4. Down – read 0, read 0, write 0, read 0, write 1
5. Down – read 1, read 1, write 1, read 1, write 0
6. Down – read 0

The faults that are covered in the MARCH C-Algorithm are Address Faults (AF), Stuck At Faults (SAF), Transition Faults (TF), Inversion Coupling Faults (CFin), Idempotent Coupling Faults (CFid), State Coupling Faults (CFst).

Some such newly defined fault models are Write Disturb Fault (WDF), Transition Coupling Fault (Cft), Deceptive Read Disturb Coupling Fault (Cfdrd). Another class of faults called Dynamic faults which require more than one operation to be performed sequentially in time in order to be sensitized has also been defined. These new faults cannot be easily detected by established tests like March C-, rendering it insufficient/ inadequate for today’s and the future high speed memories. More appropriate test algorithms like March SS have been developed to deal with these new fault models like Deceptive Read Destructive fault (DRDF), Write disturb fault (WDF), etc.,

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed BISR was designed at RT level and it was synthesized to gate-level using Xilinx ISE simulator. The p simulation results show that the frequency of SRAM with BISR is at least 150MHz. The SRAM was implemented based on a Xilinx ISE. The 32 addresses from H’FE0 to H’FFF were selected as Normal-Redundant addresses. To verify the function of BISR, a Stuck-at-0 fault was set in the SRAM. Figure 5 shows the layout view of the SRAM with BISR circuitry. BISR brings about 20% area penalties.

CONCLUSIONS

An efficient BISR strategy for SRAM IP with selectable redundancy has been presented in this paper. It is designed flexible that users can select operation modes of SRAM. The BIAA module can avoid storing fault addresses more than once and can repair fault address quickly. The function of BISR has been verified by the post simulation. The BISR can work at up to 150MHz at the expense of 20% greater area.

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Performance Analysis of Dual-Hop Relaying Systems

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ABSTRACT

This paper quantifies the impact of hardware impairments on dual-hop relaying, for both amplify-and-forward and decode-and-forward protocols. The outage probability (OP) in these practical scenarios is a function of the effective end-to-end signal-to-noise-and-distortion ratio (SNDR). This paper derives new closed-form expressions for the exact and asymptotic OPs, accounting for hardware impairments at the source, relay, and destination. A similar analysis for the ergodic capacity is also pursued, resulting in new upper bounds. In particular, it is proved that for high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), the end-to-end SNDR converges to a deterministic constant, coined the SNDR ceiling, which is inversely proportional to the level of impairments.

Keywords: Amplify-and-forward, decode-and-forward, dual-hop relaying, outage probability

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of relay nodes for improving coverage, reliability, and quality-of-service in wireless systems has been a hot research topic over the past decade, both in academia [2]–[4] and in industry [5], [6]. This is due to the fact that, unlike macro base stations, relays are low-cost nodes that can be easily deployed and, hence, enhance the network agility. The vast majority of works in the context of relaying systems make the standard assumption of ideal transceiver hardware. Recent works in information theory have demonstrated that non-ideal hardware severely affects multi-antenna systems; more specifically, proved that there is a finite capacity limit at high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), while provided a general resource allocation framework where existing signal processing algorithms are redesigned to account for impairments. Despite the importance of transceiver hardware impairments, their impact on one-way relaying has only been partially investigated; bit error rate simulations were conducted in for amplify-and-forward (AF) relaying, while derived expressions for the bit/symbol error rates considering only non-linear ties or I/Q imbalance, respectively. Most recently elaborated on the impact of I/Q

imbalance on AF relaying and suggested novel digital baseband compensation algorithms. In this paper, we follow a different line of reasoning *by* providing a detailed performance analysis of dual-hop relaying systems in the presence of aggregate transceiver impairments, both for AF and decode-and-forward (DF) protocols.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The dual-hop relaying where a source communicates with a destination through a relay; see Fig. 1(a). There is no direct link between the source and the destination (e.g., due to heavy shadowing), but the results herein can be extended to that scenario as well. Contrary to most prior works, we consider a generalized system model that accounts for transceiver hardware impairments. This model is described in the following subsections and the block model is shown in Fig. 1(b).

(a) Classical dual-hop relaying with ideal transceiver

(b) Generalized dual-hop relaying with hardware impairments

Fig.1. Block diagram of AF/DF relaying

Consider a generalized system model for single-hop transmission that originates from [8]–[11]. Suppose an information signal $s \in \mathbb{C}$ is conveyed over a flat-fading wireless channel $h \in \mathbb{C}$ with additive noise $v \in \mathbb{C}$. This channel can, for example, be one of the subcarriers in a multi-carrier system based on orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM). The received signal is conventionally modeled as:

$$y = hs + v \quad (1)$$

Where h , s , and v are statistically independent.

Detailed distortion models are available for different sources of impairments (e.g., I/Q imbalance, HPA non-linearities, and phase-noise); see [8] for a detailed description of hardware impairments in OFDM systems and related compensation algorithms. However, the combined influence at a given flat fading subcarrier is often well-modeled by a generalized channel model, where the received signal becomes

$$y = h(s + \eta_t) + \eta_r + v \quad (2)$$

While η_t, η_r are distortion noises from impairments in the transmitter and receiver, respectively. The distortion noises are defined as $\eta_t \sim CN(0, k_t^2 P)$, $\eta_r \sim CN(0, k_r^2 P|h|^2)$ which is a model that has been supported and validated by many theoretical investigations and measurements.

A System Model:

Relaying with Non-Ideal Hardware

Consider the dual-hop relaying scenario in Fig. 1. Let the transmission parameters between the source and the relay have subscript 1 and between relay and destination have subscript 2. The received signals at the relay and destination are

$$y_i = h_i(s_i + \eta_i) + v_i \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (3)$$

Where $s_1, s_2 \in \mathbb{C}$ are the transmitted signals from the source and relay, respectively, with average signal power $P_i = E_{s_i}\{|s_i|^2\}$. The channel magnitudes $|h_i|$ are modeled as independent but non-identically distributed Nakagami- m varieties, such that the channel gains $\rho_i \triangleq |h_i|^2 \sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha_i, \beta_i)$. These are Gamma distributed with integer shape parameters $\alpha_i \geq 1$ and arbitrary scale parameters $\beta_i > 0$. In this case, the cumulative distribution functions (cdfs) and probability distribution functions (pdfs) of the channel gains ρ_i are

$$F_{\rho_i}(x) = 1 - \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha_i-1} \frac{e^{-\frac{x}{\beta_i}} (\frac{x}{\beta_i})^j}{j!} \quad x \geq 0$$

$$f_{\rho_i}(x) = \frac{x^{\alpha_i-1} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta_i}}}{\Gamma(\alpha_i) \beta_i^{\alpha_i}} \quad x \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

For $i = 1; 2$. Note that most of the analysis in this paper is generic and applies for any fading distribution. The choice of Nakagami- m fading is only exploited for deriving closed-form expressions for quantities such as the OP and ergodic capacity. For any fading distribution, the quantity.

$$\text{SNR}_i = \frac{P_i E_{\rho_i}\{\rho_i\}}{N_i} \quad (5)$$

Is referred to as the average SNR, for $i = 1; 2$. The average fading power is $E_{\rho_i}\{\rho_i\} = \alpha_i \beta_i$ under Nakagami- m fading.

B. End-to-End SNDR:

Amplify-and-Forward Relaying The information signal s_1 should be acquired at the destination. In the AF relaying protocol, the transmitted signal s_2 at the relay is simply an amplified version of the signal y_1 received at the relay: $s_2 = G y_1$ for some amplification factor $G > 0$. With non-ideal (ni) hardware, as described by (6), the received signal at the destination is now obtained as

$$y_2 = h_2 G_{ni} (h_1 (s_1 + \eta_1) + v_1) + h_2 \eta_2 + v_2$$

$$= G_{ni} h_1 h_2 s_1 + G_{ni} h_1 h_2 \eta_1 + G_{ni} h_2 \eta_2 + v_2 \quad (6)$$

Where the amplification factor G_{ni} is selected at the relay to satisfy its power constraint. The source needs no channel knowledge. If the relay has instantaneous

knowledge of the fading channel, h_1 , it can apply variable gain relaying with $G^v = \sqrt{\frac{P_2}{E_{s_1, v_1} \eta_2 \{|y_1|^2\}}}$

Otherwise, fixed gain relaying with $G^f = \sqrt{\frac{P_2}{E_{s_1, v_1} \eta_2 \{|y_1|^2\}}}$ can be applied using only

statistical channel information. For fixed and variable gain relaying, G_{ni} reads respectively as

$$G_{ni}^f = \sqrt{\frac{P_2}{P_1 E_{\rho_1} (\rho_1 (1+k_1^2)) + N_1}} \quad (7)$$

$$G_{ni}^v = \sqrt{\frac{P_2}{P_1 \rho_1 (1+k_1^2) + N_1}} \quad (8)$$

Where $E_{\rho_1} = \{\rho_1\} \alpha_1 \beta_1$ for Nakagami m -fading, Note that variable gain relaying has always an output power of P_2 at the relay, whilst for fixed gain relaying this varies with the channel gain of the first hop. This, in turn, affects the variance of the distortion noise η_2 for the second hop, which by definition is $E\{\eta_2^2\} = k_2^2 G_{ni}^2 E_{s_1, v_1} \{|y_1|^2\}$ for AF relaying. This reduces to the simple expression $k_2^2 P_2$ for variable gain relaying, while it becomes $(G_{ni}^f k_2^2 (P_1 \rho_1 (1+k_1^2)) + N_1)$ for fixed gain relaying. After some algebraic manipulations (e.g., using the expressions for G_{ni}^v) the end-to-end SNDRs for fixed and variable gain relaying are obtained as

$$\gamma_{ni}^{AF-f} = \frac{\rho_1 \rho_2}{\rho_1 \rho_2 d + \rho_2 (1+k_2^2) + \frac{N_2}{P_2} + \frac{N_1}{P_1 (G_{ni}^f)^2}} \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma_{ni}^{AF-v} = \frac{\rho_1 \rho_2}{\rho_1 \rho_2 d + \rho_2 (1+k_2^2) + \frac{N_2}{P_2} + \frac{N_1}{P_1 P_2}} \quad (10)$$

The relay then has a long-term power constraint $P_2 = E\{|G^f y_1|^2\}$ where expectation is taken over signal, noise, and channel fading realizations.

C. End-to-End SNDR: Decode-and-Forward Relaying

In the DF relaying protocol, the transmitted signal s_2 at the relay should equal the original intended signal s_1 . This is only possible if the relay is able to decode the signal (otherwise the relayed signal is useless); thus, the effective SNDR is the minimum of the SNDRs between 1) the source and relay; and 2) the

relay and destination. We assume that the relay knows h_1 and the destination knows h_2 , along with the statistics of the receiver and distortion noises. With non-ideal hardware as described by the effective end-to-end SNDR becomes

$$\gamma_{ni}^{DF} = \min\left(\frac{P_1 \rho_1}{P_1 \rho_1 k_1^2 + N_1}, \frac{P_2 \rho_2}{P_2 \rho_2 k_2^2 + N_2}\right) \quad (11)$$

and does not require any channel knowledge at the source. In the special case of ideal hardware (i.e., $k_1^2 = k_2^2 = 0$), (11) reduces to the classical result from [2]; that is

$$\gamma_{id}^{DF} = \min\left(\frac{P_1 \rho_1}{N_1}, \frac{P_2 \rho_2}{N_2}\right) \quad (12)$$

Just as for AF relaying, the SNDR expression with DF relaying is more complicated in the general case with hardware impairments.

III. OUTAGE PROBABILITY ANALYSIS

This section derives new closed-form expressions for the exact OPs under the presence of transceiver impairments. These results generalize the well known results in the literature, which rely on the assumption of ideal hardware. The OP is denoted by $P_{out}(x)$ and is the probability that the channel fading makes the effective end-to-end SNDR fall below a certain threshold, x , of acceptable communication quality. Mathematically speaking, this means that

$$P_{out}(x) = (\gamma \leq x) \quad (13)$$

where γ is the effective end-to-end SNDR.

IV. RESULTS ANALYSIS

In this section, the theoretical results are validated by a set of Monte-Carlo simulations. Furthermore, the concepts of SNDR and capacity ceilings and the practical design guidelines of

A. Different Channel Fading Conditions

First, we consider the impact of hardware impairments on the OP, $P_{out}(x)$, for two different thresholds: $x = 2^2 - 1 = 3$ and $x = 2^5 - 1 = 31$. Keeping in mind that the relay communication occupies two time slots, these correspond to rates of 1 and 2.5 bits/channel use, respectively.

We consider a symmetric scenario with fixed levels of impairments of $k_1 = k_2 = 0:1$, independent Nakagami- m fading channels with $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 2$, and the same average SNR at both channels. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the OP as a function of the average SNR for AF and DF relaying, respectively. The curves in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 were generated by the analytical expressions in Theorems 1 and 2 and show perfect agreement with the marker symbols which are the results of Monte-Carlo simulations.

As shown in these figures, there is only a minor performance loss caused by transceiver hardware impairments in the low threshold case of $x = 3$. However, there is a substantial performance loss when the threshold is increased to $x = 31$. More precisely, AF relaying (with either variable or fixed gain) and DF relaying experience losses of around 5 dB and 2 dB in SNR, respectively, for $x = 31$. The DF protocol is thus more resilient to hardware impairments, which was expected since the distortion noise of the first hop does not carry on to the second hop in this protocol. Fig. 4 that it is better to have a strong first hop and a weak second hop than vice versa.

This is explained by the amplification of noise in the AF protocol; however, this effect disappears for variable gain AF relaying and DF relaying, which is easily seen from the symmetric SNDR. Further, we illustrate the existence of SNDR ceilings. To this end, we consider a fixed average SNR of 30 dB at both channels and independent Nakagami- m fading channels with $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 2$. Fig. 5 shows the OP, $P_{out}(x)$, as a function of the threshold x (in dB) using either ideal hardware or hardware with impairments of level $k_1 = k_2 = 0:15$. For low thresholds, the OPs for AF (with fixed or variable gain) and DF are only slightly degraded by hardware impairments.

Fig: 2 Outage probability $P_{out}(x)$ for AF relaying with ideal hardware and with hardware impairments of $k_1 = k_2 = 0:1$.

Fig: 3. Outage probability $P_{out}(x)$ for DF relaying with ideal hardware and with hardware impairments of $k_1 = k_2 = 0:1$.

Fig:4. Outage probability $P_{out}(3)$ for fixed gain AF relaying with ideal hardware and with hardware impairments of $k_1 = k_2 = 0:1$.

Different shape parameters α_1 ; α_2 are considered in the fading distributions and different asymmetric SNRs: $SNR_1 = \mu SNR_2$. The strongest channel has an SNR of 20 dB.

Fig:5 Outage probability $P_{out}(x)$ for AF and DF relaying for different thresholds x . As proved in Corollary 1, there exist SNDR ceilings under transceiver hardware impairments.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Physical transceiver hardware introduces impairments that distort the emitted and received signals in any communication system. While the impact of individual hardware impairments (e.g., phase noise, I/Q imbalance, and HPA non-linearities) have been well investigated in the corresponding literature, it is the aggregate impact of all hardware impairments and the respective compensation algorithms that determine the practical system performance. Motivated by this, we considered a generalized impairment model that has been validated in prior works for single-hop communications and applied it on flat-fading dual-hop relaying, considering both AF and DF protocols. Our analytical and numerical results manifested that the performance of dual-hop relaying is notably affected by these hardware impairments, particularly when high achievable rates are required.

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A ZVS Dual-Input Converter With Hybrid Power Sources

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to develop a high-efficiency converter with two input power sources for a distributed power generation mechanism. The proposed converter can boost the varied voltages of different power sources in the sense of hybrid power supply to a stable output dc voltage for the load demand. An auxiliary circuit in the proposed converter is employed for achieving turn-ON zero-voltage switching (ZVS) of all switches. According to various situations, the operational states of the proposed converter can be divided into two states including a single power supply and a dual power supply. In the dual power-supply state, the input circuits connected in series together with the designed pulse width modulation can greatly reduce the conduction loss of the switches. In addition, the effectiveness of the designed circuit topology and the ZVS properties are verified by experimental results, and the goal of high-efficiency conversion can be obtained.

Key Words: DC–DC converter, hybrid power supply, high- efficiency power conversion, zero-voltage switching (ZVS).

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to protect the natural environment on the earth, the development of clean energy [1]–[3] without pollution has the major representative role in the last decade. By accompanying the permission of Kyoto Protocol, clean energies, such as fuel cell (FC), photovoltaic (PV), wind energy, etc., have been rapidly promoted. Due to the electric characteristics of clean energies, the generated power is critically affected by the climate or has slow transient responses, and the output voltage is easily influenced by load variations. [4]. Thus, a storage element is necessary to ensure proper operation of clean energies. Batteries or super capacitors are usually taken as storage mechanisms for smoothing output power, start-up transition, and various load conditions [5], [6]. The corresponding installed capacity of clean energies can be further reduced to save the cost of system purchasing and power supply. For these reasons, hybrid power conversion systems (PCS) have become one of interesting research topics for engineers and scientists at present.

Based on power electronics technique, the diversely developed power conditioners including dc–dc converters and dc–ac inverters are essential components for clean-energy applications. Generally, one power source needs a dc–dc converter either for raising the input voltage to a certain band or for regulating the input voltage to a constant dc-bus voltage. However, conventional converter structures have the disadvantages of large size, complex topology, and expensive cost. In order to simplify circuit topology, improve system performance, and reduce manufacturing cost, multi-input converters have received more attentions in recent years.

The method for synthesizing multi-input converters was inspired by adding an extra pulsating voltage or a current source to a converter with an appropriate connection. Wai et al. [11], [12] presented multi-input converters with high step-up ratios, and the goal of high-efficiency conversion was obtained. However, these topologies are not economic for the non isolated applications because of the complexity with numbers of electrical components. Tao et al. [13] and Matsuo et al. [14] utilized multi winding-type transformers to

accomplish the power conversion target of multi-input sources. Although these topologies were designed based on time-sharing concept, the complexity of driving circuits will be increased by the control techniques in [13] and [14]. Marchesoni and Vacca [15] investigated a newly designed converter with the series-connected input circuits to achieve the goal of multiple input power sources. The installation cost of the converter with few components was certainly reduced. The feature of [15] is that the conduction losses of switches can be greatly reduced, especially in the dual power supply state. Unfortunately, the hard-switching problem and the huge reverse-recovery current within the output diode degrade the conversion efficiency as a traditional boost converter [6]. Kwasinski [16] discussed the evolution of multiple input converters from their respective single-input versions. Based on several assumptions, restrictions, and conditions, these analyses indicate some feasible and unfeasible frameworks for multiple input developments. Li et al. [17] investigated a set of basic rules for generating multiple-input converter topologies, and systematically generated two families' of multiple-input converters. Qian et al. [18] designed a novel converter topology with four power ports including two sources, one bidirectional storage port, and one isolated load port. The zero-voltage switching (ZVS) can be achieved for four main switches. In this study, a high-efficiency ZVS dual-input converter is investigated, and this converter directly utilizes the current source type applying to both input power sources. Based on the series-connected input circuits and the

designed pulse width modulation (PWM) driving signals, the conduction loss of the switches can be greatly reduced in the dual power-supply state. Lee et al. [19] performed zero-current-transition dc-dc converters without additional current stress and conduction loss on the main switch during the resonance period of the auxiliary cell. The auxiliary cell provides zero-current-switching turn-OFF for all active switches and minimizes the reverse recovery problem of the main diode. The modified type of this representative auxiliary cell in [19] is introduced into the proposed dual-input converter to reduce the reverse-recovery currents of the diodes.

An auxiliary circuit with a small inductor operated in the discontinuous conduction mode (DCM) is utilized for achieving turn-ON ZVS of all the switches, and the huge reverse-recovery current of the output diode in the traditional boost converter can be removed via the utilization of an auxiliary inductor series connected with a diode. Consequently, the proposed dual-input converter can efficiently convert two power sources with different voltages to a stable dc-bus voltage. According to the power dispatch, this converter could be operated at two states including a single power-supply state and a dual power-supply state. This study is organized into four sections. Following the introduction in Section I, the topology and operation of the proposed high-efficiency dual-input converter are presented in Section II. In Section III, experimental results are provided to validate the effectiveness of the proposed converter. Conclusions are drawn in Section IV.

II. TOPOLOGY AND OPERATION OF DUAL-INPUT CONVERTER

Fig. 1 shows the circuit topology of the proposed ZVS dualinput converter. It contains four parts including a primary input circuit, a secondary input circuit, an auxiliary circuit, and an output circuit. The major symbol representations are summarized as follows. V_1 and I_1 denote the primary input voltage and current, respectively. V_2 and I_2 exhibit the secondary input voltage and current, respectively. SP_1 , SP_2 , TP_1 , and TP_2 express the power ON/OFF switches and their driving signals produced by the power management. C_i , L_i , S_i , and T_i ($i = 1, 2$) represent individual capacitors, inductors, switches, and driving signals in the primary and secondary input circuit, respectively. C_a , L_a , $Da1$, and $Da2$ are the auxiliary capacitor, inductor, and diodes

Fig. 1. Circuit topology of high-efficiency dual-input converter.

Fig. 2. Equivalent circuit.

of the auxiliary circuit. S_a and T_a are the auxiliary switch and its driving signal, which is generated by the PWM. C_o , V_o , I_o , and R_o describe the output capacitor, voltage, current, and equivalent load, respectively. For the convenience of analyses, the simplified equivalent circuit is depicted in Fig. 2, and the directional definition of significant voltages and currents are labeled in this figure. The simplification in Fig. 2 is compliant with the following assumptions:

- 1) all power switches and diodes have ideal characteristics without considering voltage drops when these devices are conducted;
- 2) the capacitors C_a and C_o are large enough so that the voltage ripples due to switching are negligible and could be taken as constant voltage sources V_a and V_o ; and
- 3) the power ON/OFF switches SP 1 and SP 2 are omitted. According to different power conditions, the operational states of the proposed converter can be divided into two states including a single power-supply state with only one input power source and a dual power-supply state with two input power sources.

The powers produced by the voltage sources V_1 and V_2 are referred as P_1 and P_2 , respectively, while the power consumed by the load is referred as P_o . If the condition of $P_1 > P_o$ ($P_2 > P_o$) holds, the switch SP 1 (SP 2) turns ON to supply the power with a single input power source V_1 (V_2). On the contrary, the switches SP 1 and SP 2 turn ON to supply the power with two input power sources if the conditions of $P_1 > P_o$ and $P_2 > P_o$ fail. The detailed operational stages are described as follows.

A. Single Power-Supply State

By turning off one power ON/OFF switch SP 1 or SP 2 for cutting off the connection between the power source and the converter, the other input power source V_2 or V_1 can supply alone for supporting the

output demand. The primary input power supply is considered, for example, to explain how to operate in this state, i.e., the switch SP 2 is always turned OFF and the switch S2 is triggered all the while for minimizing the conduction loss. The switching period is defined as T_s . d_1 and d_a denote the duty cycles of the switch S1 and S_a , respectively. d_{dc} and d_{dcm} present the duty cycles of the dead time and the freewheeling time of the auxiliary inductor. Note that the

Fig. 3. Characteristic waveforms in single power-supply state.

auxiliary inductor is designed to operate in the DCM. The characteristic waveforms and topological modes of the single power-supply state are depicted in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. The complete operation modes in a switching period of the converter are discussed as follows.

Mode 1 [$t_0 - t_1$]: At t_0 , the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} returned to zero. The switch S1 is continuously conducted and the auxiliary switch S_a is still turned OFF. The primary inductor L_1 is linearly charged by the primary input voltage V_1 . The auxiliary switch voltage v_{Sa} is equal to the auxiliary capacitor voltage V_a .

Mode 2 [$t_1 - t_2$]: At t_1 , the switch S1 is turned OFF, the switch voltage v_{S1} is rising to the auxiliary capacitor voltage V_a , and the auxiliary switch voltage v_{Sa} is decreasing to zero. The body diode of the auxiliary switch S_a is conducted for receiving the

primary inductor current i_{L1} to charge the auxiliary capacitor. Therefore, the switch current i_{Sa} is negative. Besides, the auxiliary inductor current linearly increases, and its slope is dependent on the auxiliary inductor voltage v_{La} , which is equal to $V_a - V_o$. Continuously, the primary auxiliary diode $Da1$ is conducted.

Mode 3 [$t_2 - t_3$]: At t_2 , the auxiliary switch Sa is turned ON with ZVS because the body diode has been already conducted for carrying the primary inductor current i_{L1} . After the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} increases to be larger than the primary inductor current i_{L1} , the auxiliary switch current i_{Sa} becomes positive. The discharging current from the auxiliary capacitor together with the primary inductor current i_{L1} releases the stored energy to the output voltage V_o . During modes 2 to 3 ($t = t_1 - t_3$), the time interval can be written as $(d_d + d_a)T_S$. The auxiliary inductor current i_{La} and the primary inductor current i_{L1} can be expressed as where I_{L2} is the average value of the secondary inductor current i_{L2} , and Δi_{L2} is the corresponding peak-to-peak current ripple. At t_3 , the local maximum value of the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} can be calculated as

$$i_{La}(t) = \frac{(V_a - V_o)(t - t_1)}{L_a} \quad (1)$$

$$i_{L1}(t) = (I_{L1} + 0.5\Delta i_{L1}) + \frac{(V_1 - V_a)(t - t_1)}{L_1} \quad (2)$$

where I_{L1} is the average value of the primary inductor current i_{L1} , and Δi_{L1} is the corresponding peak-to-peak current ripple. Note that, the time interval ($t_1 - t_2$) in mode 2 is extremely short so that it could be regarded as the same time in Fig. 4. At t_3 , the maximum values of the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} can be calculated as

$$i_{La}(t_3) = \frac{(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_a)T_S}{L_a} \quad (3)$$

According to (2), the current ripple Δi_{L1} can be rewritten as

$$\Delta i_{L1} = \frac{(V_a - V_1)(d_d + d_a)T_S}{L_1} \quad (4)$$

Mode 4 [$t_3 - t_4$]: At t_3 , the auxiliary switch Sa is turned OFF. Because the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} is greater than the primary inductor current i_{L1} , the parasitic capacitor of the auxiliary switch Sa is charged by the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} so that the auxiliary switch voltage v_{Sa} rises. At the same time, the energy stored in the parasitic capacitor of the switch $S1$ will release to the output voltage V_o via the inductor current i_{La} so that the switch voltage v_{S1} decreases. The switch current i_{Sa} falls down to zero and the switch voltage v_{Sa} rises to the auxiliary capacitor voltage V_a . The body diode of the switch $S1$ is conducted for carrying the differential current without strain. Besides, the auxiliary inductor voltage v_{La} is equal to $-V_o$, and the current i_{La} linearly decreases. The energy stored in the auxiliary inductor La starts to discharge into the output voltage V_o as freewheeling.

Mode 5 [$t_4 - t_5$]: At t_4 , the switch $S1$ is turned ON with ZVS upon the condition that the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} is still larger than the primary inductor current i_{L1} . The auxiliary inductor current i_{La} continuously decreases with the slope $-V_o/L_a$. After the current i_{La} is smaller than the primary inductor current i_{L1} , the switch current i_{S1} is positive. During modes 4 to 5 ($t = t_3 - t_5$), the time interval can be written as $(d_d + d_{dem})T_S$. The auxiliary inductor current i_{La} and the primary inductor current i_{L1} can be expressed as

$$i_{La}(t) = \frac{[(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_a)T_S - V_o(t - t_3)]}{L_a} \quad (5)$$

$$i_{L1}(t) = (I_{L1} - 0.5\Delta i_{L1}) + \frac{V_1(t - t_3)}{L_1} \quad (6)$$

Mode 6 [$t_5 - t_6$]: At t_5 , the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} is equal to zero. Substituting $i_{La}(t_5) = 0$ into (7), the relation between the voltages V_a and V_o can be derived as

$$(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_a) = V_o(d_d + d_{dem}) \quad (7)$$

Fig. 4. Topological modes in single power-supply state.

In this mode, the parasitic capacitor of the primary auxiliary diode Da1 is charged by the output voltage Vo with a small reverse-recovery current.

Mode 7 [t6 -t7]: At t6 , the diode voltage vDa1 is rising to the output voltage Vo , the secondary auxiliary diode Da2 is conducted for receiving the auxiliary inductor current iLa to charge the auxiliary capacitor voltage Va , and then the auxiliary inductor current iLa returns to zero. In the single power-supply state with the primary input power, the switch SP 2 is always turned OFF and the switch S2 is triggered all the while. It means that the switch S2 works as a synchronous rectifier for avoiding the current to flow through its body diode and reducing the power losses in modes 2-7 in Fig. 4.

According to the volt-second balance theory [20], the voltage-second production of the primary inductor L1 in a switching period should be equal to zero. Thus, one can obtain

$$V_1(d_1 + d_d)T_S + (V_1 - V_a)(d_a + d_d)T_S = 0 \quad (8a)$$

$$V_1 = V_a(d_a + d_d). \quad (8b)$$

Assume that the dead-time duty cycle dd is much smaller than the duty cycle of the switch d1 ; the summation of the duty cycles d1 and da approaches

to 1. The relationships of (7) and (8b) can be represented as

$$V_o = \frac{(1 - d_1)V_a}{(1 + d_{dec} - d_1)} \quad (9a)$$

$$V_1 = (1 - d_1)V_a \quad (9b)$$

$$\frac{V_o}{V_1} = \frac{1}{(1 + d_{dec} - d_1)}. \quad (9c)$$

Because the average current of the output capacitor Co should be zero over a switching period for a constant output voltage Vo, the balance equation can be expressed via (3) as

$$\frac{0.5(V_a - V_o)(1 - d_1)T_S(1 - d_1 + d_{dec})}{L_a} = \frac{V_o}{R_o}. \quad (10)$$

From the algebraic operation via (9) and (10), the duty cycle and the voltage gain of the converter can be derived as

$$d_{dec} = 0.5(1 - d_1) \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{8L_a}{R_o T_S (1 - d_1)^2}} - 1 \right] \quad (11a)$$

$$V_o = \frac{2V_1}{(1 - d_1) \left[1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{8L_a}{R_o T_S (1 - d_1)^2}} \right]}. \quad (11b)$$

By the similar derivation process, the voltage gain of the single power-supply state with the secondary input power source also can be represented as

$$V_a = \frac{V_2}{(1 - d_2)} \quad (12a)$$

$$V_o = \frac{2V_2}{(1 - d_2) \left[1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{8L_a}{R_o T_S (1 - d_2)^2}} \right]} \quad (12b)$$

where d_2 denotes the duty cycle of the switch S_2 .

B. Dual Power-Supply State

When the proposed converter is operated in the dual powersupply state with two input power sources, it can be taken as a superposition process of the primary and secondary input circuits. In this state, the summation of duty cycles d_1 and d_2 should be greater than 1, i.e., each of duty cycles d_1 and d_2 is securely greater than 0.5. Moreover, the symbols d_{a1} and d_{a2} denote the first and the second duty cycles of the switch S_a , respectively. d_{dcm1} and d_{dcm2} present the first and the second duty cycles of the freewheeling times of the auxiliary inductor. The auxiliary inductor is also designed to operate in the DCM. In order to explain the operational principle in the dual powersupply state easily, the following theoretical analysis is based on the assumption of $i_{L1} > i_{L2} > |i_{L1} - i_{L2}|$, where $|\cdot|$ is the absolute operator. The characteristic waveforms and topological modes of the dual power-supply state are depicted in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. Note that the time intervals in modes 2, 4, 9, and 11 are extremely short so that each interval could be regarded as the same time in Fig. 5. The operation modes in this state are discussed as follows.

Mode 1 [$t_0 - t_1$]: At t_0 , the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} returned to zero. The switches S_1 and S_2 are continuously conducted. The auxiliary switch S_a is still turned OFF. The inductors L_1 and L_2 are linearly charged by the input voltages V_1 and V_2 , respectively.

Mode 2 [$t_1 - t_2$]: At t_1 , the switch S_2 is turned OFF, the switch voltage v_{S2} is rising to the auxiliary capacitor voltage V_a , and the auxiliary switch voltage v_{Sa} is decreasing to zero. The body diode of the auxiliary switch S_a is conducted for receiving the secondary inductor current i_{L2} to charge the

auxiliary capacitor. Therefore, the switch current i_{Sa} is negative. Besides, the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} linearly increases, and the slope is dependent on the auxiliary inductor voltage v_{La} , which is equal to $V_a - V_o$. Continuously, the primary auxiliary diode Da_1 is conducted.

$$i_{La}(t) = \frac{(V_a - V_o)(t - t_1)}{L_a} \quad (13)$$

Mode 3 [$t_2 - t_3$]: At t_2 , the auxiliary switch S_a is turned ON with ZVS. After the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} increases to be larger than the secondary inductor current i_{L2} , the auxiliary switch current i_{Sa} becomes positive. The discharging current from the auxiliary capacitor together with the secondary inductor current i_{L2} releases the stored energy to the output voltage V_o . During modes 2 to 3 ($t = t_1 - t_3$), the time interval can be written as $(d_d + d_{a2})T_S$. The auxiliary inductor current i_{La} and the secondary inductor current i_{L2} can be expressed as

$$i_{L2}(t) = (I_{L2} + 0.5\Delta i_{L2}) + \frac{(V_2 - V_a)(t - t_1)}{L_2} \quad (14)$$

where I_{L2} is the average value of the secondary inductor current i_{L2} , and Δi_{L2} is the corresponding peak-to-peak current ripple. At t_3 , the local maximum value of the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} can be calculated as

$$i_{La}(t_3) = \frac{(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_{a2})T_S}{L_a} \quad (15)$$

According to (14), the current ripple Δi_{L2} can be represented as

$$\Delta i_{L2} = \frac{(V_a - V_2)(d_d + d_{a2})T_S}{L_2} \quad (16)$$

In addition, applying Kirchhoff's current law, the current loop equation is given by $i_{L1} = i_{S1} + i_{L2}$. The switch current i_{S1} can be expressed as $i_{L1} - i_{L2}$, and it is positive so far due to the current relationship $i_{L1} > i_{L2}$. By the topological design and switching mechanism, the conduction loss of the switch S_1 sustaining all the primary inductor current i_{L1} can be effectively reduced, especially in the low-voltage high-current clean-energy applications.

Mode 4 [t3 –t4]: At t3 , the auxiliary switch Sa is turned OFF. Because the auxiliary inductor current iLa is greater than the secondary inductor current iL2 , the parasitic capacitor of the auxiliary switch Sa is charged by the auxiliary inductor current iLa, and the auxiliary switch voltage vSa rises.

At the same time, the energy stored in the parasitic capacitor of the switch S2 will release to the output voltage Vo via the inductor current iLa, and the switch voltage vS2 decreases. The switch current iSa falls down to zero and the switch voltage vSa rises to the auxiliary capacitor voltage Va .

The body diode of the switch S2 is conducted for carrying the differential current without strain. Besides, the auxiliary inductor voltage vLa is equal to -Vo , and the current iLa linearly decreases. The energy stored in the auxiliary inductor La starts to discharge into the output voltage Vo as freewheeling.

Mode 5 [t4 –t5]: At t5 , the switch S2 is turned ON with ZVS upon the condition that the auxiliary inductor current iLa is still larger than the secondary inductor current iL2 . The auxiliary inductor current iLa continuously decreases with the slope -Vo/La . After the current iLa is smaller than the secondary inductor current iL2 , the switch current iS2 is positive. By the same way, the switch current iS1 becomes positive as well as iS2 . During modes 4 to 5 (t = t3 – t5), the time interval can be written as (dd + ddc2)TS . The auxiliary inductor current iLa and the secondary inductor current iL2 can be expressed as

$$i_{La}(t) = \frac{[(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_{a2})T_S - V_o(t - t_3)]}{L_a} \quad (17)$$

$$i_{L2}(t) = (I_{L2} - 0.5\Delta i_{L2}) + \frac{V_2(t - t_3)}{L_2}. \quad (18)$$

Mode 6 [t5 –t6]: At t5 , the auxiliary inductor current iLa is equal to zero. Substituting iLa(t5) = 0 into (17), the relation between the voltages Va and Vo can be derived as

$$(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_{a2}) = V_o(d_d + d_{dc2}). \quad (19)$$

In this mode, the parasitic capacitor of the primary diode Da1 is charged by the output voltage Vo with a small reverse-recovery current.

Mode 7 [t6 –t7]: At t6 , the diode voltage vDa1 is rising to the output voltage Vo , the secondary auxiliary diode Da2 is conducted for receiving the auxiliary inductor current iLa to charge the auxiliary capacitor.

Mode 8 [t7 –t8]: At t7 , the auxiliary inductor current iLa returns to zero. The switches S1 and S2 are continuously conducted. Mode 8 is similar to mode 1.

Mode 9 [t8 –t9]: At t8 , the switch S1 is turned OFF, the switch voltage vS1 is rising to the auxiliary capacitor voltage Va , and the auxiliary switch voltage vSa is decreasing to zero. The body diode of the auxiliary switch Sa is conducted for carrying the primary inductor current iL1 to charge the auxiliary capacitor.

The auxiliary inductor current iLa linearly increases with the slope (Va - Vo)/La . Continuously, the primary auxiliary diode Da1 is conducted.

Mode 10 [t9 –t10]: At t9 , the auxiliary switch Sa is turned ON with ZVS. After the auxiliary inductor current iLa increases to be larger than the primary inductor current iL1 , the auxiliary switch current iSa becomes positive.

The discharging current from the auxiliary capacitor together with the primary inductor current iL1 releases the stored energy to the output voltage Vo.

Mode 10 [t9 –t10]: At t9 , the auxiliary switch Sa is turned ON with ZVS. After the auxiliary inductor current iLa increases to be larger than the primary inductor current $iL1$, the auxiliary switch current iSa becomes positive. The discharging current from the auxiliary capacitor together with the primary inductor current $iL1$ releases the stored energy to the output voltage Vo . During modes 9to10 (t=t8– t10), the time interval can be written as $(dd + da1)TS$. The auxiliary

inductor current iLa and the primary inductor current $iL1$ can be expressed as auxiliary switch Sa is charged by the auxiliary inductor current iLa .At the same time, the energy stored in the parasitic capacitor of the switch S1 will release to the output voltage Vo via the inductor current iLa . The switch current iSa falls down to zeroand the switch voltage vSa rises to the auxiliary capacitor voltage Va . Similar to mode 4, both the switches' currents $iS1$ and $iS2$ are negative.

The energy stored in the auxiliary inductor L_a starts to discharge into the output voltage V_o as freewheeling.

Mode 12 [t11–t12]: At t11, the switch S1 is turned ON with ZVS. The auxiliary inductor current i_{La} continuously decreases with the slope $-V_o/L_a$. After the current i_{La} is smaller than the primary inductor current i_{L1} , the switch current i_{S1} is positive. By the same way, the switch current i_{S2} becomes positive as well as i_{S1} . During modes 11 to 12 ($t = t_{10} \sim t_{12}$), the time interval can be written as $(d_d + d_{dc1})T_S$. The auxiliary inductor current i_{La} and the primary inductor current i_{L1} can be expressed

$$i_{La}(t) = \frac{[(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_{a1})T_S - V_o(t - t_{10})]}{L_a} \quad (24)$$

$$i_{L1}(t) = (I_{L1} - 0.5\Delta i_{L1}) + \frac{V_1(t - t_{10})}{L_1} \quad (25)$$

Mode 13 [t12–t13]: At t12, the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} is equal to zero. Substituting $i_{La}(t_{12}) = 0$ into (24), the relation between the voltages V_a and V_o can be derived as

$$(V_a - V_o)(d_d + d_{a1}) = V_o(d_d + d_{dc1}). \quad (26)$$

Mode 13 is similar to mode 6 as well as the reverse-recovery time of the primary auxiliary diode Da_1 . Mode 14 [t13–t14]: At t13, the diode voltage v_{Da1} is rising to the output voltage V_o , and the secondary auxiliary diode Da_2 is conducted for receiving the auxiliary inductor current i_{La} to charge the auxiliary capacitor. According to the volt-second balance theory [20], the voltage second productions of the inductors L_1 and L_2 in a switching period should be equal to zero. Thus, one can obtain Assume that the dead-time duty cycle d_d is much smaller than the duty cycles of the switches d_1 and d_2 , the relationships of the voltages in (19), (26), (27c), and (27d) can be rewritten as

$$V_o = \frac{(1 - d_1)V_a}{(1 + d_{dc1} - d_1)} = \frac{(1 - d_2)V_a}{(1 + d_{dc2} - d_2)} \quad (28a)$$

$$V_a = \frac{V_1}{(1 - d_1)} = \frac{V_2}{(1 - d_2)} \quad (28b)$$

Equations (30c) and (31) state that the proposed converter can simultaneously boost both input power sources with different voltage levels to a stable output

voltage via controlling the driving signals of the switches T1, T2, and Ta. Moreover, there exists only one pair of the duty cycles d_1 and d_2 according to specific input voltages. Note that the driving signal Ta is composed of T1 and T2 as shown in Fig. 5. First, one should make up the inverse signals of T1 and T2 as $\overline{T1}$ and $\overline{T2}$. Then, the inverse signals $\overline{T1}$ and $\overline{T2}$ are processed via delay time functions to synthesize the signals T_1 and T_2. In the driving circuit, the control signals T_1 and T_2 are passed through logic OR gate IC to compose the driving signal Ta for the auxiliary switch. In this study, a high-efficiency ZVS dual-input converter is investigated. The proposed converter utilizes the primary and secondary input circuits to be connected in series and operates in continuous conduction mode (CCM). The phenomenon of a high reverse-recovery current in a traditional step-up converter will be greatly alleviated via the utilization of an auxiliary inductor in series connected with a diode when the diode current falls to zero. If the primary and secondary input circuits are changed to connect in parallel, the primary inductor L1 and the secondary inductor L2 can be operated in DCM. In this case, the control signals for the primary and secondary input circuits are different from the ones for these two input circuits connected in series. The control signals for the primary and secondary input circuits connected in parallel can be widely designed without regard to the series-inductor problem. Moreover, it would reduce the inductor volume and save two level shifter circuits for the floating switches. However, the primary inductor L1 and the secondary inductor L2 operated in DCM would cause the inductor currents i_{L1} and i_{L2} with higher peak values, so that the lifetime of the input power source (e.g., battery module or FC) will be degenerated. Besides, the DCM operation is not suitable for a high-power application.

IV. CONCLUSION

The effectiveness of this converter is also verified by the experimental results. In the single power-supply state, the property of ZVS turn ON of all switches guarantees that switching losses can be reduced. In the dual power-supply state, the conduction loss can be effectively reduced by topological design of series connection of two input circuits. Besides, the reverse-recovery currents of the diodes are slight as well as the switching losses of the switches are effectively

reduced. The maximum efficiency of the proposed converter operated in both operational states is higher than 95%. This new converter topology provides designers with an alternative choice to simultaneously convert hybrid power sources. In addition, the proposed high-efficiency dual-input converter also can work well in high-power level applications because the switching losses can be greatly reduced due to the ZVS property. In general, the ground leakage current would be harmful to high-power nonisolated PV applications due to the presence of a parasitic capacitance between the PV cells and the metal frame of the PV panel, usually connected to earth. A two-stage PV ac-module application including a nonisolated high step-up dc/dc converter and a newly designed H6-type dc/ac inverter to feature high efficiency over a wide load range, low ground leakage current, no need for split capacitors, and low-output ac-current distortion. If the proposed ZVS dual-input converter in this study is used for nonisolated PV applications, the ground leakage current issue due to the high-frequency voltage swing between the two negative terminals of the input sources also may cause safety and electromagnetic interference (EMI) problems because the input power sources do not share the same ground. These problems could be solved by the adoption of an EMI filter.

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Increasing speed with Low-Power Multiplier

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design exploration of a spurious-power suppression technique (SPST) which can dramatically reduce the power dissipation of combinational VLSI designs for multimedia/DSP purposes. The proposed SPST separates the target designs into two parts, i.e., the most significant part and least significant part (MSP and LSP), and turns off the MSP when it does not affect the computation results to save power.

There are different entities that one would like to optimize when designing a VLSI circuit. These entities can often not be optimized simultaneously, only improve one entity at the expense of one or more others. The design of an efficient integrated circuit in terms of power, area, and speed simultaneously, has become a very challenging problem. Power dissipation is recognized as a critical parameter in modern the objective of a good multiplier is to provide a physically compact, good speed and low power consuming chip. To save significant power consumption of a VLSI design, it is a good direction to reduce its dynamic power that is the major part of total power dissipation. In this paper, we propose a high speed low-power multiplier adopting the new SPST implementing approach. This multiplier is designed by equipping the Spurious Power Suppression Technique (SPST) on a modified Booth encoder which is controlled by a detection unit using an AND gate. The modified booth encoder will reduce the number of partial products generated by a factor of 2. The SPST adder will avoid the unwanted addition and thus minimize the switching power dissipation. In this project we used Models for logical verification, and further synthesizing it on Xilinx-ISE tool using target technology.

Keywords-Booth encoder; low power; spurious power suppression technique (SPST); SPST-Adder.

1. INTRODUCTION

Power dissipation is recognized as a critical parameter in modern VLSI design field. To satisfy MOORE'S law and to produce consumer electronics goods with more backup and less weight, low power VLSI design is necessary.

Fast multipliers are essential parts of digital signal processing systems. The speed of multiply operation is of great importance in digital signal processing as well as in the general purpose processors today, especially since the media processing took off. In the past multiplication was generally implemented via a sequence of addition, Subtraction, and shift operations. Multiplication can be considered as a series of repeated additions. The number to be added is the multiplicand, the number of times that it is

added is the multiplier, and the result is the product. Each step of addition generates a partial product. In most computers, the operand usually contains the same number of bits. When the operands are interpreted as integers, the product is generally twice the length of operands in order to preserve the information content. This repeated addition method that is suggested by the arithmetic definition is slow that it is almost always replaced by an algorithm that makes use of positional representation.

It is possible to decompose multipliers into two parts. The first part is dedicated to the generation of partial products, and the second one collects and adds them.

II. Proposed Low-Power Multiplier

Figure 1: Proposed high performance low power equipped multiplier

The proposed SPST-equipped multiplier is illustrated in fig-1.

III. Partial Product generation

Modified Booth Encoder

In order to achieve high-speed multiplication, multiplication algorithms using parallel counters, such as the modified Booth algorithm has been proposed, and some multipliers based on the algorithms have been implemented for practical use. This type of multiplier operates much faster than an array multiplier for longer operands because its computation time is proportional to the logarithm of the word length of operands.

Modified Booth's algorithm

- Insert 0 on the right side of LSB of multiplier.
- Divide the multiplier into overlapping groups of 3-bits.
- If the number of multiplier bits is odd, add an extra 1 bit on left side of MSB.
- Determine partial product scale factor from modified booth encoding table.
- Compute the Multiplicand Multiples
- Sum Partial Products.
- When new partial product is generated, each partial product is added 2 bit left shifting in regular sequence.

Booth multiplication is a technique that allows for smaller, faster multiplication circuits, by recoding the numbers that are multiplied. It is possible to reduce the number of partial products by half, by using the technique of modified Booth recoding algorithm. The

basic idea is that, instead of shifting and adding for every column of the multiplier term and multiplying by 1 or 0, we only take every second column, and multiply by ± 1 , ± 2 , or 0, to obtain the same results. The advantage of this method is the halving of the number of partial products. To recode the multiplier term, we consider the bits in blocks of three, such that each block overlaps the previous block by one bit. Grouping starts from the LSB, and the first block only uses two bits of the multiplier. Fig-2 shows the grouping of bits from the multiplier term for use in modified booth encoding.

Figure 2: Illustration of multiplication using modified Booth encoding.

Figure 3: Grouping of bits from the multiplier term

Block	Re - coded digit	Operation on X
000	0	0 X
001	+1	+1 X
010	+1	+1 X
011	+2	+2 X
100	-2	-2 X
101	-1	-1 X
110	-1	-1 X
111	0	0 X

Table-1

The encoding of the multiplier Y, using the modified booth algorithm, generates the following five signed

digits, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2. Each encoded digit in the multiplier performs a certain operation on the multiplicand, X, as illustrated in Table-1.

Fig-3 shows a computing example of Booth, multiplying two numbers, "2AC9" and "006A". The shadow denotes that the numbers in this part of Booth multiplication are all zero so that this part of the computations can be neglected. Saving those computations can significantly reduce the power consumption caused by the transient signals.

According to the analysis of the multiplication shown in fig-3, we propose the SPST-equipped modified-Booth encoder, which is controlled by a detection unit. The detection unit has one of the two operands as its input to decide whether the Booth encoder calculates redundant computations.

Figure 4: detection logic circuits using an AND gate

Fig-4 shows the booth partial product generation circuit. It includes AND/OR/EX-OR logic. From one of the two operands, e.g., the operand A, the partial product (PP) candidate generator generates five candidates of the partial products, i.e., -2A, -A, 0, A, 2A, which are then selected according to the Booth encoding results of the other operand, i.e., the operand B. Meanwhile, the detection unit has the second one of the two operands, i.e., the operand B in this case, as its input to decide whether the Booth encoder includes redundant computations.

Figure 5: SPST equipped modified Booth encoder

As shown in Fig-5, the latches can, respectively, freeze the inputs of MUX-4 to MUX-7 or only those of MUX-6 to MUX-7 when the PP4 to PP7 or only the PP6 to PP7 are zeros to reduce the transition power dissipation. Such cases occur frequently in wireless multimedia-data coding like texture coding, orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing, and filter designs.

Proposed SPST

We explore five cases of 16-bit additions as shown in Fig-6. The cases of exchanging the operands A and B in additions lead to the same spurious transitions with those shown in Fig-6.

Hence, there is probably no other case beyond these

Figure 6: Low power adder/subtractor adopting the SPST

five based on this design. The first case illustrates a transient state in which spurious transitions of carry signals occur in the MSP, although the final result of the MSP is unchanged. Meanwhile, the second and third cases describe situations involving one negative operand adding another positive operand without and with carry-in from the LSP, respectively. Moreover, the fourth and fifth cases demonstrate the addition of two negative operands without and with carry-in from the LSP, respectively.

In those cases, the results of MSP are predictable; therefore, the computations in MSP are useless and can be neglected. Eliminating those spurious computations not only can save the power consumption inside the adder/subtractor in the current stage but also can decrease the glitching noises which cause power wastage inside the arithmetic circuits in the next stage. From the analysis of Fig-6, we are motivated to propose the SPST that separates the adder/subtractor into two parts and then latches the input data of the MSP whenever they do not affect the computation results.

SPST equipped Adder/Subtractor

A 16-bit adder/subtractor design based on the proposed SPST is shown in the Fig-7. In this, the 16-bit adder/subtractor is divided into MSP and LSP at the place between the 8th bit and the 9th bit. The adder subtractor is divided into two parts, the most significant part (MSP) and the least significant part (LSP). The MSP of the original adder/subtractor is modified to include detection logic circuits, data controlling circuits, sign extension circuits, logics for calculating carry in and carry out signals. Latches implemented by simple AND gates are used to control the input data of the MSP. When the MSP is necessary, the input data of MSP remain the same as usual, while the MSP is negligible, the input data of the MSP become zeros to avoid switching power consumption.

To know whether the MSP affects the computation results or not, we need a detection logic unit to detect the effective ranges of the inputs. The Boolean logical equations shown below express the behavioral principles of the detection logic unit in the MSP circuits of the SPST-based adder/subtractor:

Where $A[m]$ and $B[n]$ respectively denote the m th bit of the operands A and the n th bit of the operand B , and A_{MSP} and B_{MSP} respectively denote the MSP parts, i.e. the 9th bit to the 16th bit, of the operands A and B . When the bits in A_{MSP} and/or those in B_{MSP} are all ones, the value of A_{and} and/or that of B_{and} respectively become one, while the bits in A_{MSP} and/or those in B_{MSP} are all zeros, the value of A_{nor} and/or that of B_{nor} respectively turn into one. Being one of the three outputs of the detection logic unit, $close$ denotes whether the MSP circuits can be neglected or not.

When the two input operand can be classified into one of the five classes as shown in fig-6, the value of $close$ becomes zero, which indicates that the MSP circuits can be closed to save power dissipation. This design intends to close the MSP circuits by feeding zero inputs into them, which may freeze the switching activities in the MSP circuits to avoid dynamic power consumption. The ways to compensate for the sign bits of the computing results are also shown in case 4 in Fig-6. In equation (7) and

(8), $CLSP$ denotes the carry propagated from the LSP circuits.

From the derived Boolean equations (1) to (8), the detection logic unit of the SPST is designed as shown in fig-8, which can determine whether the input data of MSP should be latched or not. Moreover, we add three 1-bit to control the assertion of the close, sign, and Carr-ctrl signals in order to further decrease the glitch signals occurred in the cascaded circuits

$$A_{MSP} = A[15:8]; B_{MSP} = B[15:8] \quad (1)$$

$$A_{and} = A[15].A[14] \dots A[8] \quad (2)$$

$$B_{and} = B[15].B[14] \dots B[8] \quad (3)$$

$$A_{nor} = \overline{A[15] + A[14] + \dots + A[8]} \quad (4)$$

$$B_{nor} = \overline{B[15] + B[14] + \dots + B[8]} \quad (5)$$

$$Close = (A_{and} + A_{nor}).(B_{and} + B_{nor}) \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} carr - ctrl &= \overline{C_{LSP}} \times \overline{A_{and}} \times A_{nor} \times B_{and} \times \overline{B_{nor}} \\ &+ \overline{C_{LSP}} \times A_{and} \times \overline{A_{nor}} \times \overline{B_{and}} \times B_{nor} \\ &+ C_{LSP} \times \overline{A_{and}} \times A_{nor} \times \overline{B_{and}} \times B_{nor} \\ &+ C_{LSP} \times A_{and} \times \overline{A_{nor}} \times B_{and} \times \overline{B_{nor}} \\ &= \overline{C_{LSP}} \times (\overline{A_{and}} \times B_{and} + A_{and} \times \overline{B_{and}}) \\ &\times (A_{and} \times B_{and} + A_{and} \times B_{nor} + A_{nor} \times B_{and} \\ &+ A_{nor} \times B_{nor}) + C_{LSP} \\ &\times (A_{and} \times B_{and} + \overline{A_{and}} \times \overline{B_{and}}) \\ &\times (A_{and} \times B_{and} + A_{and} \times B_{nor} + A_{nor} \times B_{and} \\ &+ A_{nor} \times B_{nor})(C_{LSP} \oplus A_{and} \oplus B_{and}) \\ &\times (A_{and} + A_{nor}) \times (B_{and} + B_{nor}) \\ &= (C_{LSP} \oplus A_{and} \oplus B_{and}) \times (A_{and} + A_{nor}) \\ &\times (B_{and} + B_{nor}) \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} sign &= \overline{C_{LSP}} \times (\overline{A_{and}} \times A_{nor} \times B_{and} \times \overline{B_{nor}} + A_{and} \\ &\times \overline{A_{nor}} \times \overline{B_{and}} \times B_{nor} + A_{and} \times \overline{A_{nor}} \\ &\times B_{and} \times \overline{B_{nor}}) \\ &+ C_{LSP} \times A_{and} \times \overline{A_{nor}} \times B_{and} \times \overline{B_{nor}} \\ &= \overline{C_{LSP}} \times (\overline{A_{and}} \times B_{and} + A_{and}) \\ &+ C_{LSP} \times A_{and} \times B_{and} \\ &= \overline{C_{LSP}} \times (A_{and} + B_{and}) + C_{LSP} \times A_{and} \times B_{and} \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Based on Figs -7 and 8, the timing issue of the SPST is analyzed as follows.

Figure 7: Booth partial product selector logic.

- 1) When the detection-logic unit turns off the MSP: At this moment, the outputs of the MSP are directly compensated by the SE unit; therefore, the time saved from skipping the computations in the MSP circuits shall cancel out the delay caused by the detection-logic unit.
- 2) When the detection-logic unit turns on the MSP: The MSP circuits must wait for the notification of the detection-logic unit to turn on the data latches to let the data in. Hence, the delay caused by the detection-logic unit will contribute to the delay of the whole combinational circuitry, i.e., the 16-bit adder/subtractor in this design example.

Figure 9: Data-controlling components of the SPST Where PS denotes pseudo summations as shown in (a) Data-latch design. (b) SE circuits. (c) SE circuits designed using OR

- 3) When the detection-logic unit remains its decision: No matter whether the last decision is turning on or turning off the MSP, the delay of the detection logic is negligible because the path of the combinational circuitry (i.e., the 16-bit adder/subtractor in this design example) remains the same.

Fig-9 shows the data-controlling components of the SPST, where Fig-9(a) shows the design of the data latch. The SE circuits can be intuitively implemented by multiplexers to compensate for the sign signals of the MSP, as shown in Fig-9(b).

The input data of the SE circuits are pseudo summations (PS) from the MSP adder/subtractors. We further have two more approaches besides using multiplexers to optimize the SE circuits. One approach uses simple OR gates, as shown in Fig-9(c). The other adopts Complementary Pass-transistor Logics (CPLs) as shown in Fig-9(d). Both of these approaches can help realize the needed SE circuits.

IV. Simulation results and Discussions

In this project we are examining the performance of the proposed high speed low power multiplier. This multiplier can be implemented using Verilog-HDL coding. In order to get the power report and delay report we are synthesizing this multiplier using Xilinx. Simulations results correspond to the multiplier are given in fig-10 and 11.

./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/multiplier	0064	0064
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/multiplierand	04C9	04C9
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final1	1AA6E	1AA6E
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final2	10537	10537
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final3	10537	10537
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final4	05592	05592
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final5	00000	00000
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final6	00000	00000
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final7	00000	00000
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./ppa_out_final8	00000	00000
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./close1	0	0
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./close2	0	0
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp1	1AA6E	1AA6E
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp2	10537	10537
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp3	10537	10537
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp4	05592	05592
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp5	00000	00000
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp6	00000	00000
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp7	00000	00000
./top_complex_mult/./top_multiplier/./booth_encoder/./pp8	00000	00000

Figure 10: Simulation result of Booth-Encoder

CONCLUSION:

This work presents the designing of a 16x16 multiplier with low-power technique called SPST. A Modified Booth Encoder circuit is used for this Multiplier architecture. Compared to other circuits, the Booth multiplier has the highest operational speed and less hardware count.

The presented low-power technique called SPST and the theoretical analysis of the SPST are fully discussed. The proposed SPST can obviously decrease the switching (or dynamic) power dissipation, which comprises a significant portion of the whole power dissipation in integrated circuits. And simulation results for Booth Encoder and SPST-adder equipped Multiplier are shown.

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Analysis of Knee Joint

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ABSTRACT

Knee joint is an important part of human body. Failure of knee joint may occur mainly because of surface to surface contact of femoral and tibial surfaces owing to the dry out of bursae fluid. The damaged surfaces must be replaced by artificial implants made of metals, ceramics, or composite materials. This process is known as total knee replacement. The failure of bearing component in knee implant is due to high stresses at the contact regions of femoral component and polyethylene insert causes wear and decreases the life of the implant. The stiffness of artificial implants is around 110 GPa to 210 GPa, while that of the human bone is around 17 GPa. This increases the stress shielding effect. To reduce stress shielding effect an implant material should have the stiffness value nearer to human bone. This reduces the effect of stress shielding between the bone and implant.

Keywords: Knee Joint, Femoral and Tibial component, Stress shielding effect

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid Prototyping (RP), also known as Additive Manufacturing (AM), is a totally automatic process of manufacturing objects directly from their CAD models. With the help of RP technology 3D models can be easily generated a layer by layer deposition process. The 3D CAD data is sliced into 2D layers and realized one layer at a time, making it simple to construct a 3D model and manufacture. A study conducted by Milan *et al.* [1] in 2011 reported in that about 800,000 knee joint replacements are carried out per year worldwide. Nagarjan *et al.* [2] studied different rapid prototyping technologies used in medical applications. Gibson *et al.* [3] did some case studies on the applications of RP technology in medicine. Jeng-Nan lee *et al.* [4] studied the application of Rapid Prototyping technology and multi axis machining for fabrication of femoral component of the knee prosthesis. Juan Felipe *et al.* [5] designed and manufactured a skull implant by Titanium alloy. Milan *et al.* [1] studied on the production of medical implants by using rapid prototyping technology and investment casting technology. Niinomi *et al.* [10] studied on preventing stress shielding between the implant and the bone. B.R Levine *et al* [11] studied on clinical performance

of porous tantalum in orthopaedic surgery which is having a young's modulus of 3 Gpa having high volumetric porosity of 70-80% and excellent biocompatibility.

II. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HUMAN BONE

Human bone is an isentropic, heterogeneous and viscoelastic material which should withstand the weight of the body and stabilize the body. The mechanical properties of the bone are tabulated in Table 1.

Property	Longitudinal	Transverse
Young's modulus (MPa)	17,000	11,500
Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	133	51
Ultimate compressive strength (MPa)	193	133
Ultimate strain	3.1%	0.7%

Table 1: Mechanical properties of bone [8]

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The failure of knee joint replacement is because of wear between the knee joint components (Femoral component, PE insert and Tibial Tray). The early detection of contact stresses in the components prevents wear and increases the life of knee joint replacement. Tomasoet, al [9e] conducted

experiments on knee joint component to find the contact stresses at different stages of gait cycle in between Femoral component, Tibial Tray and PE insert. The femoral component and Tibial Tray is made of Cobalt chromium and bearing component is made of Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene. Vertical load is applied on the model at various flexion angles from 15° – 60° as follows:

Flexion angle (°)	Load applied (N)
15	2200
45	3200
60	2800

CAD model of Knee Joint

3D geometrical model of knee joint implant is designed using Unigraphics NX7.5 software. The dimensions of femoral component are taken from the femur bone. The geometrical model of femoral component, tibial components is shown in the Fig 1.

a) Femoral component

b) Tibial(UHMWPE) component

c) Tibial baseplate component

Figure 1: Components of Knee joint implant

The assembly of knee joint implant consists of femoral component; tibial UHMWPE component and tibial base plate are shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 2: Assembly of improved knee implant

Analysis of Knee Joint; Mesh development:

The knee joint model is meshed with h-adaptive technique, using TET10 element, shown in the Fig. 3

Figure 3: Mesh of Model 1knee joint implants

Materials and their properties:

Materials: The materials used in knee joint replacement surgery must have certain properties like:

- Biocompatibility,
- Non-corrosive,
- Non-toxic and
- Anti-allergic.

The following are some materials which used in knee joint implants by researchers and medical practitioners:

1. Cobalt chromium alloy (CoCrMo)
2. Titanium alloy's
 - i. Ti-6Al-4V
 - ii. Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.6Zr also known as TNTZ etc.
3. Stainless steel 316L
4. Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE)
5. Porous Tantalum

Properties:

The properties of materials are tabulated in Table 2

Material	Density (Kg/m ³)	Youngs modulus (Gpa)	Poissons ratio	Tensile Yield strength (Mpa)	Ultimate tensile strength (Mpa)
CoCr	7990	200	0.3	560	1000
Ti6Al4V	4430	113.8	0.36	880	950
TNTZ	6075	50	0.36	800	820
SS 316L	7990	193	0.3	290	558
UHMW PE	926	0.69	0.45	21	48
Tantalum	16650	3.5	0.34	51	110

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The knee joint implant is made of titanium alloy, to reduce the stress shielding effect at the implant. Finite Element Analysis is performed to determine the contact stresses between Femoral component & PE insert and the stress shielding effect in between

the bone and the Femoral component. In this process, two cases were studied.

Case 1: Implant made of Titanium alloy (Ti-6Al-4V) and Tantalum.

Case 2: Implant made of Titanium alloy Titanium β -alloy (TNTZ) and Tantalum

The contact stresses between Femoral component and PE insert for above two cases are obtained at different flexion angles and are compared with the experimental results [9]. From the results it is found that, the contact stresses are less compared to the experimental results. This proves that the knee joint model is best and increases life of the knee joint implant. This indicates reduction in stress shielding effect and bone resorption between the implant and the bone.

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a) Ti6Al4V + Ta

b) Ti6Al4V + Ta

Figure 4: Comparison of contact stresses between FC and PE insert for Experiment and FEM

a) Cocr and Ti6Al4V+Ta

b) Cocr and Ti6Al4V+Ta

Figure 5: Comparison of contact stresses on Femoral component

Optimum Adaptive Beamforming Techniques

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ABSTRACT

Smart antennas possess the capability of suppressing jamming signal, so they can improve signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR). Array processing utilizes information regarding locations of signal to aid in interference suppression and signal enhancement and is considered promising technology for anti-jamming. In this paper we studied three beam forming algorithms, Least Mean Square (LMS) algorithm, Optimized-LMS algorithm and Recursive Least Squares (RLS) algorithm. Simulation results are presented to compare the ability of these three algorithms to form beam in the direction of desired signal and place null in the direction of interference signal. Dependency of these algorithms on SNR and SIR is also analyzed. It has been found that RLS algorithm is best suited for anti-jamming applications.

Keywords: SINR, SIR, RLS, LMS

1. INTRODUCTION

Potential jamming in military and critical civilian applications has been a major concern for system designers. And usual filtering techniques are not helpful as the jamming signal and desired signal are of same frequency. Various methods have been adopted to avoid jamming; including frequency hopping but it requires excessive bandwidth. Spatial filtering can solve the problem [10] over head without the need of additional bandwidth as signals are filtered on basis of their direction of arrival.

Non-blind algorithms as discussed in this paper require the information of desired signal but blind algorithms such as Constant Modulus Algorithm (CMA) and MUSIC algorithm can estimate the Direction of Arrival (DOA) of the source signal, and then this direction information can be utilized in non-blind beam forming algorithms to form beam in the estimated direction. LMS algorithm is known for its simplicity and robustness. The computation complexity of LMS algorithm is $O(M)$. While it lacks in convergence speed several modifications to the algorithm are proposed including Optimized-LMS [2] Variable Step Size LMS (VSS-LMS) algorithms [6, 7, 1, 3], variable-length LMS algorithm [7], transform

domain algorithms [6], and recently CSLMS algorithm [9]. Optimized-LMS algorithm modifies the conventional LMS algorithm with optimized step size and is studied in detail in this paper. The computational complexity of Optimized-LMS is also $O(M)$. RLS algorithm usually converges with order of magnitude faster than LMS algorithm but the price paid is added complexity. Several variants of RLS algorithm are also proposed one of which is GVFF (Gradient based Variable Forgetting Factor)-RLS [5]. The complexity of RLS algorithm is $O(M^2)$.

Figure 1. Least Mean Square (LMS) Algorithm

In Fig. 1 the outputs of the individual sensors are linearly combined after being scaled with corresponding weights optimizing the antenna array to have maximum gain in the direction of desired signal and nulls in the direction of interferers.

For beam former the output at any time k , $y(k)$ is given by a linear combination of the data at M antennas, with $\mathbf{u}(k)$ being the input vector and $w(k)$ being the weight vector

$$y(k) = W^H(k)\mathbf{u}(k)$$

where $W(k) = \sum_{k=0}^{M-1} w_k$
 and $\mathbf{u}(k) = \sum_{k=0}^{M-1} u_k$

The signal received at time index k is

$$\begin{aligned} r(k) &= u_1(k-1)w_1(m) + \dots \dots + u_l(k-l)w_l(k) + n(k) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^l u_j(k-j)w_j + n(k) \\ &= \mathbf{u}^T(k)W(k) + n(k) \end{aligned}$$

The output $y(k)$ of the adaptive filter is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} y(k) &= d_1(k-1)w_1(k) + \dots \dots + d_l(k-l)w_l(m) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^l d_j(k-j)w_j(k) \\ &= D^T(k)w(k) \end{aligned}$$

In practice, the adaptive filter can only adjust $w(k)$ such that $y(k)$ closely approximates desired signal over time. Therefore, the instantaneous estimated error signal needed to update the weights of the adaptive filter is

$$\begin{aligned} j(k) &= p(k)e^T(k)e(k) \\ e(k) &= r(k) - y(k) \\ &= r(k) - D^T(k)w(k) \end{aligned}$$

This priori error signal, $e(k)$ is used to minimize the estimator error by adaptive updating of filter weights.

2.1 Least Mean Squares (LMS) Algorithm

The LMS algorithm is based on the stochastic gradient and is given by [12]

$$\begin{aligned} e(k) &= \mathbf{u}^T(k)w(k) + z(k) - \mathbf{u}^T(k)h(k) \\ w(k+1) &= w(k) + \eta\mathbf{u}(k)e(k) \end{aligned}$$

where η is step size, $\mathbf{u}(k)$ is the transmitted diagonal matrix at sampling time k , $W(k)$ is the adaptive filter coefficient, and $e(k)$ is the estimation error. The filter coefficients are updated using an estimate of the cost function gradient, $[\eta\mathbf{u}(k)e(k)]$. In all practical applications, the signals involved might be corrupted by noise. When the noise is present in the received sequence, interference will also in the coefficients adaption process through the term $[\eta\mathbf{u}(k)e(k)]$. As a result, where the distribution of the noise is highly impulsive, the LMS scheme might have low convergence and lower steady state MSE performance. The step size parameter, η determines the convergence rate of the algorithm and higher value provides faster convergence. However, if η exceeds certain bound then the algorithm will diverge. As the bound on η is not known a priori and is dependent on the various statistics

2.2 Normalized LMS (NLMS) Algorithm

The main problem of the LMS CE algorithm is that it is sensitive to the scaling of its input signals. This makes it very hard to choose η that guarantees stability of the algorithm. The NLMS is a variant of the LMS algorithm that solves this problem by normalizing with the power of the input signal. The NLMS algorithm can be summarized as [11]:

$$w(k+1) = w(k) + \eta e(k) [\mathbf{u}^T(k)\mathbf{u}(k)]^{-1} \mathbf{u}(k)$$

when a constant scalar step size is employed in the LMS are NLMS algorithm, there is a trade off among the steady state error-convergence towards the true channel coefficients, which avoids a fast convergence when the step size is preferred to be small for small output estimation error. In order to guarantee the algorithm to be convergent, the range of step size is specified but the choice of optimal learning step size has not been appropriately addressed. In order to deal with these troubles, one key idea is to exploit varying step size during adaptation.

2.3 Recursive Least Squares (RLS) Algorithm

To combat the channel dynamics, the RLS based CE algorithm is frequently used for rapid convergence and improved MSE performance. The standard RLS algorithm is

$$e(k) = \mathbf{u}^T(k)w(k) + z(k) - \mathbf{u}^T(k)w(k)$$

$$R(k) = \lambda^{-1}P(k-1) - \lambda^{-1}R(k)\mathbf{u}^T(k)P(k-1)$$

$$w(k+1) = w(k) + \mathbf{u}(k)e(k)R(k)$$

Where λ is the exponential forgetting factor with $0 < \lambda < 1$. The smaller value of λ leads to faster convergence rate as well as larger fluctuations in the weight signal after the initial convergence. On the other hand, too small λ value makes this algorithm unstable. Subsequently, it requires best possible forgetting factor such that the estimator error is decreased.

Although a lot of modified CE algorithm has been studied on employing adaptive forgetting factor and parallel forgetting factor, the CE performance is severely degraded in highly dynamic fading channel even when the forgetting factor is well optimized [13].

3. SIMULATION RESULT

A linear 10 element array is simulated in MATLAB to compare results of LMS, Optimized-LMS and RLS algorithm. Spacing between adjacent elements of array equals one half of the wavelength.

Figure2. Adaptive beam forming using LMS Algorithm

Figure3. Adaptive beam forming using NLMS Algorithm

Figure4. Adaptive beam forming using RLS Algorithm

Figure5. Comparison of SNR vs BER for Adaptive beam forming using LMS, NLMS and RLS

4. CONCLUSION

By analyzing the graphs, we observed that RLS algorithm provides fastest convergence, Optimized LMS algorithm also shows fast convergence but LMS algorithm lacks the convergence speed. In beam forming results, RLS showed the best beam forming capability placing deeper nulls in case of all the three interference positions i.e 40±, 60± and 90±. The significant difference between the results of LMS and Optimized-LMS in case of beam forming was the presence of many minor lobes in Optimized-LMS. The dependency on SNR and SIR showed that in better conditions i.e., high SNR and SIR Optimized-LMS showed the best results. But in poor conditions i.e low SNR and SIR its performance deteriorates. LMS and RLS almost showed equal dependency on SNR and SIR. As the recent developments in digital signal processor (DSP) kits and field-programmable gate arrays (FPGA) have made it possible to implement RLS algorithms in real time systems, and complexity to an extent is not a problem anymore. So RLS algorithm is proposed as it provides deeper nulls in the direction of interferences and faster convergence.

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Telugu Document Image Segmentation Methods

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ABSTRACT

The image segmentation is typically used to trace the object and boundaries such as line and curves in an image. The segmentation of the text reliability is necessary to perform the classification and Recognition. The main aim of segmentation is to partition the document image into various homogeneous regions such as text block, image block, line and word. Image segmentation is the front-stage processing of image compression. We hope that there are three advantages in image segmentation. The first is the speed. The second is good shape connectivity of its segmenting result. The third is good shape matching. Besides, we introduce many segmenting methods including iterative threshold technique, black pixels method and laplacian method for telugu document images.

Keywords: Edge Detection algorithm Preprocessing, Image acquisition. Image segmentation, histogram

I. INTRODUCTION

As the technology is enhancing in day to day life, there is huge amount of increase in the number of documents on the web. There is a need for an application that facilitates the user with an efficient retrieval of the information that is needed. Search engines are the key to finding specific information on the vast expanse of the World Wide Web. A search engine is a program that searches documents for specified keywords and returns a list of the documents where the keywords were found. The keywords to be searched for are given as query and the search engine gives the list of the documents having a match with the keywords in the query based on certain algorithms. The search engine also ranks the documents such that the more relevant documents are placed first in the results retrieved. For that segmentation of document images is to be done.

Modern technology has made it possible to produce, process, transmit and store digital images efficiently. Consequently the amount of visual information is increasing at an accelerating rate in many diverse

application areas. The large amount of these image data are related to text. The information is stored in

the form of digital versions and in document management system. Document image retrieval systems are utilized in many organizations which are using document image databases extensively. To fully exploit this different document image segmentation techniques are used.

When we refer to a paper document it is distinguished by the fact that it is on paper. However the notion of digital document is one which digital systems can understand and present to the user in an articulated manner. There are several types of documents which present information to a person that can be conceived and comprehended. Documents can be primarily divided into three different categories and they are Online: Documents that fall into the online paradigm consist of online handwriting that consist handwriting data captured

by a digitizer that captures handwriting of a writer. These digitizers are specialized devices that capture a writer's ink information his speed the pressure applied etc. which can be later used for further processing.

Offline: The least common denominator for handwriting is the paper and pen. Offline documents we do not access to information such the speed or pressure with which the writer must have written. Handwriting data in both online or offline could have cursive, discrete or mixed. Handwritten notes are examples of offline documents.

Printed: Printed documents contain textual information which is scanned copies from a book. The textual content in books is in the printed form following a specific font style font analysis. Such processing includes thresholding to reduce a gray scale or color image to binary image, reduction of noise to reduce extraneous data and thinning and region detection to enable easier subsequent detection of pertinent features and objects of interest, size and maintaining a standard uniformity across all pages. These are typically referred to as document images and could also contain images or pictures in addition to textual content. OCRs are used to extract the textual content from these documents, Books, Journals, articles, news papers; magazines are some of the examples of a printed document. Some of the popular digitizers for both offline and printed documents include the digital cameras, hand held and flat bed scanners etc.

Segmentation is to subdivide an image into its component regions or objects. It should stop when the objects of interest in an application have been isolated. Segmentation algorithms generally are based on one of 2 basis properties of intensity values

Discontinuity: to partition an image based on sharp changes in intensity (such as edges)

Similarity: to partition an image into regions those are similar according to a set of predefined criteria.

More precisely, image segmentation is the process of assigning a label to every pixel in an image such that

pixels with the same label share certain characteristics.

The result of image segmentation is a set of segments that collectively cover the entire image, or a set of contours extracted from the image (edge detection). Each of the pixels in a region is similar with respect to some characteristic or computed property, such as color or intensity, or texture. Adjacent regions are significantly different with respect to the same characteristic(s). When applied to a stack of images, typical in medical imaging, the resulting contours after image segmentation can be used to create 3D reconstructions with the help of interpolation algorithms like marching cubes.

The first segmentation method is Mean Gray Level., Edge Pixels, Iterative Selection and Percentage of Black Pixels.

Mean Gray Level: Mean Gray Level Algorithm is simply applied by summing up all the pixel values in the image and then taking the mean of it to obtain the threshold.

Percentage of Black Pixels: Assuming that percentage of black pixels is a constant for some types of images, lower pixel values up to the number of assumed pixels are segmented as background or black.

Edge pixels: Laplacian is calculated for each pixel and then histogram of pixels with large laplacians is created. Using this new histogram a threshold can be detected using any of the previous methods.

Iterative thresholding: In this method a threshold is iteratively calculated and refined by consecutive passes through the image.

The simplest method of image segmentation is called the thresholding method. This method is based on a clip-level (or a threshold value) to turn a gray-scale image into a binary image. There is also balanced histogram thresholding.

The key of this method is to select the threshold value (or values when multiple-levels are selected). Several popular methods are used in industry including the maximum entropy method, Otsu's method maximum variance), and k-means clustering.

Histogram-based methods are very efficient when compared to other image segmentation methods because they typically require only one pass through the pixels. In this technique, a histogram is computed from all of the pixels in the image, and the peaks and valleys in the histogram are used to locate the clusters in the image. Color or intensity can be used as the measure.

A refinement of this technique is to recursively apply the histogram-seeking method to clusters in the image in order to divide them into smaller clusters. This is repeated with smaller and smaller clusters until no more clusters are formed. One disadvantage of the histogram-seeking method is that it may be difficult to identify significant peaks and valleys in the image.

Histogram-based approaches can also be quickly adapted to occur over multiple frames, while maintaining their single pass efficiency. The histogram can be done in multiple fashions when multiple frames are considered. The same approach that is taken with one frame can be applied to multiple, and after the results are merged, peaks and valleys that were previously difficult to identify are more likely to be distinguishable. The histogram can also be applied on a per pixel basis where the information result is used to determine the most frequent color for the pixel location. This approach segments based on active objects and a static environment, resulting in a different type of segmentation useful in video tracking.

Edge detection is a well-developed field on its own within image processing. Region boundaries and edges are closely related, since there is often a sharp adjustment in intensity at the region boundaries. Edge detection techniques have therefore been used as the base of another segmentation technique. The edges identified by edge detection are often disconnected. To segment an object from an image however, one needs closed region boundaries. The desired edges are the boundaries between such objects or spatial axons. Segmentation methods can also be applied to edges obtained from edge detectors. Region growing methods mainly rely on the assumption that the neighbouring pixels within one region have similar values. The common procedure is to compare one pixel with its neighbours. If a similarity criterion is satisfied, the

pixel can be set belong to the cluster as one or more of its neighbours. The selection of the similarity criterion is significant and the results are influenced by noise in all instances. We can conquer the noise problem easily by using some mask to filter the holes or outlier. Therefore, the problem of noise actually does not exist. In conclusion, it is obvious that the most serious problem of region growing is the power and time consuming

Algorithm: Iterative thresholding

1. Assume that the four corner points of the image are background pixels (part of segment 0), and set μ_0 to the average grey value of these four pixels. Assume all of the other pixels are object pixels, and set μ_1 to their average grey value.
2. Set the threshold t to $t = 1/2 (\mu_0 + \mu_1)$, and segment the image.

3. Recomputed μ_0 and μ_1 , the mean of the original grey values of the two segments.
4. Go to step 2 and iterate until the threshold value no longer changes (or no longer changes significantly).

Iterative threshold method

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, telugu document image are segmented by using iterative threshold method, Mean gray level, detection method, laplacian method and percentage of black pixels are proposed.

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Mean gray level method

Edge pixels

Multiuser Detection in Shadowed Fading Channels with Impulsive Noise

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ABSTRACT

In direct sequence-code division multiple accesses systems (DS-CDMA), the signals are transmitted over multipath channels that introduce fading. Multipath fading along with multiple access interference and inter-symbol interference degrades the system performance. Further, simultaneous presence of multipath fading and shadowing leads to worsening of wireless channels. Moreover, experimental results have confirmed the presence of impulsive noise in wireless mobile communication channels. Hence, this paper presents a technique for multiuser detection in DS-CDMA systems over shadowed fading channels in presence of impulsive noise. Approximate expression for average probability of error of an M -decorrelator is derived, for the demodulation of binary phase shift keying (BPSK) signals over shadowed fading channels, by modeling the channel with generalized K (GK) distribution. A new M -estimator is proposed for robustifying the detector and its performance is also studied and analyzed by evaluating probability of error with the derived expression. Simulation results reveal that the proposed multiuser detector performs better in fading and shadowing with heavy-tailed impulsive noise.

Keywords: Multiuser detection; fading channel; impulsive noise; GK distribution; probability of error.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent research has explored the potential benefits of evolutionary optimization algorithms and their application to multiuser detection (MUD) for direct-sequence code division multiple access (DS-CDMA) systems [1]-[4]. An adaptive robust MUD technique for CDMA by implementing Huber's M -estimator using genetic algorithm (GA) is presented in [3] and shown that it is robust against heavy-tailed impulsive noise. Recently, particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm has been applied for the MUD [4] to detect received data bit by optimizing an objective function.

The generalized- K (GK) fading channel has been received considerable attention as it can provide a good fit to different fading environments such as Nakagami- m and Rayleigh-Lognormal [5]. Experimental results have confirmed the presence of heavy-tailed impulsive noise in outdoor mobile

communication channels, in radar and sonar systems and in indoor wireless communication channels [6].

Hence, this paper presents the implementation and performance analysis of proposed based M -estimator [7], [10], which performs well in the heavy-tailed impulsive noise, using PSO algorithm.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider an L -user synchronous CDMA system, where each user transmits information by modulating a PN sequence over a single-path GK fading channel. The received signal over one symbol duration can be modeled as [8]

$$r(t) = \Re \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} b_l(i) \alpha_l(t) e^{j\phi(t)} s_l(t - iT_s - \tau_l) \right\} + n(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\Re\{\cdot\}$ denotes the real part, M is the number of data symbols per user in the data frame of interest, T_s is the symbol interval, $\alpha_l(t)$ is the time-varying fading gain of the l^{th} user's channel, $\phi(t)$ is the time-

varying phase of the l^{th} user's channel, $b_l(i)$ is the i^{th} bit of the l^{th} user, $s_l(t)$ is the normalized signaling waveform of the l^{th} user and $n(t)$ is assumed as a zero-mean complex two-term non-Gaussian noise [9].

For synchronous case (i.e., $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = \dots = \tau_L = 0$), assuming that the fading process for each user varies at a slower rate than the magnitude and phase can taken to be constant over the duration of a bit, the received signal can be expressed in matrix notation as [9]

$$\underline{r}(i) = \underline{A}\underline{\theta}(i) + \underline{w}(i) \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{r}(i) \triangleq [r_1(i), \dots, r_N(i)]^T$, $\underline{w}(i) \triangleq [w_1(i), \dots, w_N(i)]^T$

and $\underline{\theta}(i) \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} [b_1(i)g_1(i), \dots, b_L(i)g_L(i)]^T$. Here, $w_n(i)$ is a sequence of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) complex random variables whose in-phase and quadrature components are independent non-Gaussian random variables, $g_l(i)$ is the l^{th} channel fading coefficient and

$$\underline{A} \triangleq [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_L] \text{ with } a_l \triangleq [a_1^l, a_2^l, \dots, a_N^l].$$

It is assumed that the signal of each user arrives at the receiver through an independent, single-path fading channel. For the shadowed fading channels, $\alpha_l(i)$ are i.i.d. random variables with GK distribution given by [12]

$$p_{\alpha}(\alpha_l) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(\mu)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \right)^{m+\mu} \alpha_l^{\frac{m+\mu}{2}-1} K_{m-\mu} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \alpha_l \right) \quad (3)$$

where, m is the Nakagami fading parameter that determines the severity of the fading, μ represents the shadowing levels, Ω_0 is the average SNR in a shadowed fading channel, $K_{\xi}(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function [9]

In M-estimates, unknown parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_L$ are solved by minimizing a sum of function, $\rho(\cdot)$ of the residuals [9]

$$\hat{\underline{\theta}} = F(\theta_l(i)) = \arg \min_{\underline{\theta} \in \mathbb{C}^L} \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \rho \left[\Re \left(\underline{r}_n(i) - \sum_{l=1}^L [\underline{A}]_{nl} \theta_l(i) \right) \right] + \rho \left[\Im \left(\underline{r}_n(i) - \sum_{l=1}^L [\underline{A}]_{nl} \theta_l(i) \right) \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

where $\rho(\cdot)$ represents a specific penalty function that is symmetric positive-definite with a unique minimum at zero, and is chosen to be less increasing than square, $r_n(i)$ and $\theta_l(i)$ are the n^{th} and l^{th} elements of the vectors $\underline{r}(i)$ and $\underline{\theta}(i)$ respectively, $[\underline{A}]_{nl}$ is the nl^{th} element of the matrix \underline{A} , and $\Im(\cdot)$ denotes imaginary part. This paper considers the modified-Hampel based M-estimator to implement an M-decorrelating detector with penalty function [7]

$$\rho_{MH}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x^2}{2} & \text{for } |x| \leq a \\ \frac{a^2}{2} - a|x| & \text{for } a < |x| \leq b \\ -\frac{ab}{2} \exp\left(1 - \frac{|x|^2}{b^2}\right) + d & \text{for } |x| > b \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where a , b and d are constants that depend on the robustness of the estimator [7].

It is assumed that the signal of each user arrives at the receiver through an independent, single-path fading channel. For the shadowed fading channels, $\alpha_l(i)$ are i.i.d. random variables with GK distribution given by [8]

$$p_{\alpha}(\alpha_l) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(\mu)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \right)^{m+\mu} \alpha_l^{\frac{m+\mu}{2}-1} K_{m-\mu} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \alpha_l \right) \quad (6)$$

where, m is the Nakagami fading parameter that determines the severity of the fading, μ represents the shadowing levels, Ω_0 is the average SNR in a shadowed fading channel, $K_{\xi}(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function [9].

III. AVERAGE PROBABILITY OF ERROR FOR M-DECORRELATOR

In this section, the proposed M-estimator is presented and the average probability of error is derived for a single-path shadowed fading channel.

A) M-estimator

An M-estimator is, a generalization of usual maximum likelihood estimates, used to estimate the unknown parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_L$ (where $\theta = Ab$) by minimizing a sum of function $\rho(\cdot)$ of the residuals [4]

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathcal{R}^L} \sum_{j=1}^N \rho \left(r_j - \sum_{l=1}^L s_j^l \theta_l \right) \quad (7)$$

where ρ is a symmetric, positive-definite function with a unique minimum at zero, and is chosen to be less increasing than square and N is the processing gain. An influence function $\psi(\cdot) = \rho'(\cdot)$ is proposed (as shown in Fig. 1), such that it yields a solution that is not sensitive to outlying measurements, as [6]

$$\psi_{PRO}(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{for } |x| \leq a \\ a \operatorname{sgn}(x) & \text{for } a < |x| \leq b \\ \frac{a}{b} x \exp\left(1 - \frac{x^2}{b^2}\right) & \text{for } |x| > b \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Influence function of M-estimator.

where the choice of the constants a and b depends on the robustness measures.

B) Average probability of error

The asymptotic probability of error for the class of decorrelating detectors, for large processing gain N , is given by [4]

$$P_e^l \equiv \Pr(\hat{\theta}_l < 0 | \theta_l > 0) = Q \left(\frac{A_l}{v \sqrt{[R^{-1}]_{ll}}} \right) \quad (8)$$

where $Q(x)$ is the Gaussian Q -function defined by

$$Q(x) = \int_x^\infty \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp(-\xi^2/2) d\xi, \quad x \geq 0,$$

$$v^2 = \frac{\int \psi^2(u) f(u) du}{\left[\int \psi'(u) f(u) du \right]^2} \quad (9)$$

and $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{S}$ with \mathbf{S} is an $N \times L$ matrix of columns a_i . Average probability of error can be obtained by averaging the conditional probability of error (15) over the PDF, (10), of generalized K distribution as [7]

$$\overline{P_e^l} = F \cdot \int_0^\infty x^{\left(\frac{m+\mu}{2}-1\right)} Q \left(\frac{x}{v \sqrt{[R^{-1}]_{ll}}} \right) K_{m-\mu} \left(2 \sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} x \right) dx \quad (10)$$

where $F = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(\mu)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \right)^{m+\mu}$. Using the well

known upper-bound approximation, called Chernoff bound, to $Q(x)$, given by

$$Q(x) \leq \frac{1}{2} e^{-x^2/2} \quad (11)$$

the integral, I_1 , of (15) can be expressed as

$$I_1 = \int_0^\infty x^{\left(\frac{m+\mu}{2}-1\right)} \exp\left(\frac{-x^2}{v^2 [R^{-1}]_{ll}}\right) K_{m-\mu} \left(2 \sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} x \right) dx \quad (12)$$

Now, by using [Eq. 6.631.3, 9] in solving (17), the average probability of error can be written as

$$\overline{P_e^1} = F \cdot \frac{1}{2} \alpha^{-0.5l} \beta^{-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{1+d+l}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{1-d+l}{2}\right) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{\beta^2}{8\alpha}\right) W_{-0.5l,d}\left(\frac{\beta^2}{4\alpha}\right)$$

where $d = m - \mu$, $l = \frac{m+\mu}{2} - 1$, $\alpha = \frac{1}{v^2 [R^{-1}]_{11}}$ and

$\beta = 2\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}}$ and $W_{\lambda,\gamma}(\cdot)$ is the Whittaker function [9].

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the performance of M -decorrelator is presented by performing Monte Carlo simulations by computing (18) for different values of Nakagami fading parameter and different shadowing levels. It is assumed that $\Omega_0 = 10$ dB in the simulations. Performance of decorrelating detector with different influence functions is shown in Fig. 2, Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. In Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 ($\epsilon = 0.01$ & $\kappa = 100$), the average probability of error versus the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) corresponding to the user 1 under perfect power control of a synchronous DS-CDMA system with six users ($L = 6$) and a processing gain, $N = 31$ is plotted for $m = \mu = 1$ and $m = \mu = 2$ respectively. Similarly, in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 ($\epsilon = 0.1$ & $\kappa = 100$), average probability of error is plotted for $m = \mu = 1$ and $m = \mu = 2$ respectively. Simulation results show that the proposed M -estimator based detector performs well in the heavy-tailed impulsive noise compared to linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber and Hampel estimators.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Multiuser detection in DS-CDMA systems over fading and shadowing channels under impulsive noise environment is presented. An approximate closed-form expression for average probability of

error of the decorrelating detector to detect BPSK (13) signals is derived. An M -estimator based multiuser detector is proposed and its probability of error is computed using the expression derived. Simulation results show that the proposed multiuser detector offers significant performance gain over the linear multiuser detector and the minimax decorrelating detector with Huber and Hampel M -estimators, in heavy-tailed impulsive noise.

Fig.1 Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\epsilon = 0.01$, $m = 1$, $\mu = 1$.

Fig. 2. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\epsilon = 0.01$, $m = 1$, $\mu = 1$.

Fig. 3. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0.01$, $m = 2$, $\mu = 2$.

Fig. 4. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in asynchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$, $m = 1$, $\mu = 1$.

Fig. 5. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in asynchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$, $m = 2$, $\mu = 2$.

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A Robust clustering Method for Multispectral Remote Sensing Image Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Methods of Detection of Multi spectral remote sensing Images are becoming more popular due to the progresses in spatial resolution of satellite imagery. This paper presents detection of multispectral remote-sensing images corrupted by noise using robust clustering method without any training data. First enhancement of color separation of satellite image using decorrelation stretching is carried out and then the regions are grouped into a set of clusters. Simulation results are provided to demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed method for detection of Multi spectral remote sensing Images.

Keywords: Decorrelation, LANDSAT imagery, Spatial resolution, Support Vector Machines.

1. INTRODUCTION

The process of image segmentation (such as pixel based, contour based, region based, model based, color based and hybrid, etc.) is defined as the search for homogenous regions in an image and later the classification of these regions. It also means the partitioning of an image into meaningful regions based on homogeneity or heterogeneity criteria [1]. Multispectral image delivers a great source of data for studying spatial and temporal changeability of the environmental factors. It can be utilized in a number of applications which consists of reconnaissance, making of mapping products for military and civil use, assessment of environmental damage, nursing of land use, radiation level check, urban planning, growth directive, soil test and crop outcome increment . One major area where we use multispectral image is in the process of classification and mapping of vegetation over large spatial scales, as the remote sensing data delivers very good coverage, mapping and classification of land cover features like vegetation, soil, water and forests. This behaves like a replacement for the normal classification techniques, which necessitates expensive and time-intensive field surveys.

Purposes of classification of LANDSAT images is to identify Land use and land cover (LULC) Vegetation types, Geologic terrains, Mineral exploration, Alteration mapping, etc. LANDSAT 7 was launched in April, 1999. LANDSAT carries two multispectral sensors. The first is the Multi-Spectral Scanner (MSS) which acquires imagery in four Spectral bands: blue, green, red and near infrared. The second is the Thematic Mapper (TM) which collects seven bands: blue, green, red, near-infrared, two mid- infrared and one thermal infrared. The MSS has a spatial resolution of 80 meters, while that of the TM is 30 meters. Both sensors image a 185 km wide swath, passing over each day at 09:45 local time, and returning every 16 days. With LANDSAT 7, support for TM, imagery is to be continued with the addition of a co-registered 15 m panchromatic band [4].

Multispectral image classification can be considered as a combined project of both image processing and classification methods. Usually, image classification, in the process of remote sensing is the method of referring pixels or the basic units of an image to the classes. It is mostly likely to create groups of similar pixels found in image data into classes that match the informational categories of user interest by matching the pixels to one another and to those of the said

identity. Many techniques of image classification have been introduced and numerous areas like image analysis and pattern recognition use the vital term, classification.

Image segmentation is a process of partitioning image pixels based on selected image features. The pixels that belong to the same region must be spatially connected and have the similar image features. If the selected segmentation feature is color, an image segmentation process would separate pixels that have distinct color feature into different regions, and, simultaneously, group pixels that are spatially connected and have the similar color into the same region.

Classification of multispectral remotely sensed data is computed with a special attention on uncertainty computation in the land-cover maps. An efficient technique for classifying the multispectral satellite images into land cover and land use sectors using SVM. The proposed classification technique comprises of segmentation using clustering technique, training data selection for SVM and classification using trained SVM. Multispectral images cannot be fed directly into the SVM for training and testing. The input image is subjected to a set of pre-processing so that the image gets transformed suitably for segmentation.

This paper deals with statistical cluster analysis in the potential presence of contaminations. Detection of multispectral remote-sensing images corrupted by noise using Support Vector Machines is proposed in this paper.. Simulation results are provided to demonstrate the effectiveness of proposed algorithm.

II. PROPOSED K-MEANS CENTRE BASED CLUSTERING

Define a d-dimensional set of n data points $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ as the data to be clustered and a d-dimensional set of k centers $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k\}$ as the clustering solution that an iterative algorithm refines. Now we can define the steps of a general model of iterative, center-based clustering as [6]

1. Initialize the algorithm with guessed centers C.
2. For each data point x_i , compute its membership $m(c_j | x_i)$ in each center c_j nad its weight $w(x_i)$.

3. For each center c_j recompute its location from all data points x_i according to their memberships and weights:

$$c_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n m(c_j | x_i) w(x_i) x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n m(c_j | x_i) w(x_i)}$$

4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until convergence.
5. Further, the entire process can be summarized in the following steps

Step 1: Read the image

Step 2: For color separation of an image apply the Decorrelation stretching.

Step 3: Convert Image from RGB Color Space to L*a*b* Color Space.

Step 4: Classify the Colors in 'a*b*' Space Using proposed K-Means Clustering.

Step 5: Label Every Pixel in the Image Using the Results from K-MEANS.

Step 6: Create Images that Segment the Image by Color.

Step 7: Segment the Nuclei into a Separate Image.

Furthermore, the k-means algorithm partitions data into k disjoint subsets or clusters with common characteristics. The solution is then a set of k-centers, each of which is located at the centroid of the data for which it is the closest center. The objective function that the k-means algorithm optimizes, i.e., the classical least squares (LS) technique uses the solution corresponding to

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \min_{j \in \{1, \dots, k\}} \|x_i - c_j\|^2 \quad (1)$$

or

$$\min_c \sum_{i=1}^N r_i^2 \quad (2)$$

It was realized that the LS technique is extremely sensitive to noise and outliers. Therefore many robust methods were developed in statistics to overcome this [7-9].

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

Various experiments were carried out using K-means clustering based image analysis for LANDSAT images and results are summarized in Fig1 to Fig 4. In Fig 5, error analysis of the proposed SVM method is shown and these results demonstrate that multispectral remote sensing image corrupted with noise analysis can be carried out with to maximum accuracy.

Fig.1 (a) & (b) Original Image & its Histogram, Fig.1 (c) & (d) Decoorelated Image & its Histogram

Fig.2 (a) & (b) Objects in cluster 1 (multi spectral remote sensing Image without noise is considered) & its Histogram, Fig.2 (c) & (d) Objects in cluster 1 (multi spectral remote sensing Image with noise is considered) & its Histogram.

Fig. 3 (a) & (b) Objects in cluster 2 (multi spectral remote sensing Image without noise is considered) & its Histogram, Fig. 3 (c) & (d) Objects in cluster 2 (multi spectral remote sensing Image with noise is considered) & its Histogram.

Fig. 4 (a) & (b) Objects in cluster 3 (multi spectral remote sensing Image without noise is considered) & its Histogram, Fig. 4 (c) & (d) Objects in cluster 3 (multi spectral remote sensing Image with noise is considered) & its Histogram.

Fig5. Error Analysis for the considered 3 clusters (Blue, Green, Red indicates cluster 1, cluster 2 and cluster3, respectively).

IV. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, robust clustering based algorithm for detection of Multi Spectral Remote sensing Images corrupted with noise is proposed analyzed. Simulation results are also provided, which demonstrate the efficiency of proposed algorithm for image analysis for extracting and updating geographical information though considered LANDSAT Images are corrupted with noise

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Adaptive Channel Estimation For SCFDMA System

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ABSTRACT

Third generation partnership project (3GPP) long term evolution (LTE) uses single carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) in uplink transmission and orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) scheme for the downlink. A variable step size based least mean squares (LMS) algorithm is formulated for a single carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) system channel estimation (CE). The weighting coefficients on the channel condition can be updated using this unbiased CE method. Channel and noise statistics information are not essential. Rather, it uses a phase weighting scheme to eliminate the signal fluctuations due to noise and decision errors. The convergence towards the true channel coefficient is guaranteed.

Keywords: Channel estimation, SC-FDMA, LMS

I. INTRODUCTION

Wide demand on high data rates in wireless communication systems has arisen in order to support broadband services. The Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Long Term Evolution (LTE) radio access standard provides peak data rates of 75 Mb/s on the uplink and 300 Mb/s on the downlink. In LTE standard orthogonal frequency-division multiple accesses (OFDMA) is used on the downlink. This supports different carrier bandwidths (1.25–20 MHz) in both frequency-division duplex (FDD) and time-division duplex (TDD) modes. In OFDMA each user is provided with a unique fraction of the system bandwidth. OFDMA combines scalability, multipath robustness, multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) compatibility [1], thereby making it adaptive for wideband wireless accessibility.

OFDMA, being sensitive to frequency offset and phase noise, accurate frequency and phase synchronization is needed. In addition, OFDMA is characterized by a high transmit PAPR, and for a given peak power limited amplifier this results in a lower mean transmit level. For these reasons, OFDMA is not well suited to the uplink

transmission. Hence, LTE proposed, single carrier FDMA (SC-FDMA), also known as discrete Fourier transform (DFT) pre coded OFDMA, for the uplink. PAPR reduction in SCFDMA is motivated by a desire to increase the mean transmit power, improve the power amplifier efficiency, increase the data rate, and reduce the bit error rate (BER) and energy consumption [4]. SC-FDMA ensures high data rate transmission, utilizing single carrier in frequency domain equalization. In algorithm is proposed for LTE uplink channel impulse response (CIR) knowledge of the channel.

2.1 Baseband System Model

At the transmitter side, a baseband modulator transmits the binary input to a multilevel sequences of complex numbers $m_1(q)$ in one of several possible modulation formats including binary phase shift keying (BPSK), quaternary PSK (QPSK), 8 level PSK (8-PSK), 16-QAM, and 64-QAM. These modulated symbols perform an N-point discrete Fourier transform (DFT) to produce a frequency domain representation. The DFT followed by IDFT in a distribution-FDMA (DFDMA) or localization-FDMA (LFDMA) subcarrier mapping setup operates as efficient implementation to an interpolation filter.

In distributed subcarrier mode, the outputs are allocated equally spaced subcarriers, with zeros occupying the unused subcarrier in between. While in localized subcarrier mode, the outputs are confined to a continuous spectrum of subcarriers. Except the above two modes, interleaved subcarrier mapping mode of FDMA (IFDMA) is another special subcarrier mapping mode [12], [13]. The difference between DFDMA and IFDMA is that the outputs of IFDMA are allocated over the entire bandwidth; whereas the DFDMA's outputs are allocated every several subcarriers.

2.2 Channel Model

Channel model is a mathematical representation of the transfer characteristics of the physical medium. These models are formulated by observing the characteristics of the received signal. According to the documents from 3GPP, in the mobile environment, radio wave propagation can be described by multipaths which arise from reflection and scattering. If there are l distinct paths from transmitter to the receiver, the impulse response of the wide-sense stationary uncorrelated scattering (WSSUS) fading channel can be represented as

$$w(\tau, t) = \sum_{j=0}^{l-1} w_j(t) \delta(\tau - \tau_j)$$

where fading channel coefficients $w_j(t)$ are the wide sense stationary i.e. $w_j(t) = w(m; j)$, uncorrelated complex Gaussian random paths gains at time instant t with their respective delays τ_j , where $w(m; j)$ is the sample spaced channel response of the l^{th} path during the time k , and $\delta(\bullet)$ is the Dirac delta function. Based on the WSSUS assumption, the fading channel coefficients in different delay taps are statistically independent. And has an autocorrelation function given by

$$E[w(k, j)w^T(n, j)] = \sigma_w^2(j) J_0[2\pi f_d T_f (k - n)]$$

where $w(n; j)$ is a response of the l^{th} propagation path measured at time n , $\sigma_w^2(J)$ denotes the power of the channel coefficients, f_d is the Doppler frequency in Hertz, T_f is the symbol duration in seconds, and $J_0(\bullet)$ is the zero order Bessel function of the first kind

III. PROPOSED ADAPTIVE CE ALGORITHM

The signal $s(k)$ is transmitted via a time-varying channel $w(k)$, and corrupted by an observation noise $n(m)$ before being detected in a receiver. The signal received at time index k is

$$\begin{aligned} r(k) &= s_1(k-1)w_1(m) + \dots + s_l(k-l)w_l(k) + n(k) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^l s_j(k-j)w_j + n(k) \\ &= S^T(k)W(k) + n(k) \end{aligned}$$

Where $s_j(k-j)$, $j=1,2,\dots,l$ are transmitted signal vectors at time m , l is the distinct paths from transmitter to the receiver, $w(m)$ is the channel coefficients at time m , and $n(k)$ is the noise with zero mean and variance σ^2 . After processing some intermediate steps (synchronization, remove CP, DFT, and de mapping), the decision block reconstructs the detected signal to an approximate modulated signal and its phase. The output $y(k)$ of the adaptive filter is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} y(k) &= d_1(k-1)h_1(k) + \dots + d_l(k-l)h_l(m) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^l d_j(k-j)h_j(k) \\ &= D^T(k)h(k) \end{aligned}$$

where $d_j(k-j)$, $j=1,2,\dots,l$ are detected signal vectors at time

$$k \dots D(k) = \text{diag}[d_1(k-1), d_2(k-2), \dots, d_l(k-l)].$$

In this problem formulation, the ideal adaptation procedure would adjust $w_j(k)$ such that $w_j(k)=h_j(k)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. In practice, the adaptive filter can only adjust $w(k)$ such that $y(k)$ closely approximates desired signal over time. Therefore, the instantaneous estimated error signal needed to update the weights of the adaptive filter is

$$\begin{aligned} j(k) &= p(k)e^T(k)e(k) \\ e(k) &= r(k) - y(k) \\ &= r(k) - D^T(k)h(k) \end{aligned}$$

This priori error signal, $e(k)$ is used to minimize the estimator error by adaptive updating of filter weights.

3.1 Least Mean Squares (LMS) Algorithm

The LMS algorithm is based on the stochastic gradient and is given by [10]

$$e(k) = S^T(k)w(k) + z(k) - S^T(k)h(k)$$

$$h(k+1) = h(k) + \eta s(k)e(k)$$

where η is step size, $S(k)$ is the transmitted diagonal matrix at sampling time k , $h(k)$ is the adaptive filter coefficient, and $e(k)$ is the estimation error. The filter coefficients are updated using an estimate of the cost function gradient $[\eta s(k)e(k)]$.

In all practical applications, the signals involved might be corrupted by noise. When the noise is present in the received sequence, interference will also in the coefficients adaption process through the term $[\eta s(k)e(k)]$. As a result, where the distribution of the noise is highly impulsive, the LMS scheme might have low convergence and lower steady state MSE performance. The step size parameter, η determines the convergence rate of the algorithm and higher value provides faster convergence. However, if η exceeds certain bound then the algorithm will diverge. As the bound on η is not known a priori and is dependent on the various statistics

3.2 Normalized LMS (NLMS) Algorithm

The main problem of the LMS CE algorithm is that it is sensitive to the scaling of its input signals. This makes it very hard to choose η that guarantees stability of the algorithm. The NLMS is a variant of the LMS algorithm that solves this problem by normalizing with the power of the input signal. The NLMS algorithm can be summarized as [7]:

$$h(k+1) = h(k) + \eta e(k) [S^T(k)S(k)]^{-1} S(k)$$

when a constant scalar step size is employed in the LMS are NLMS algorithm, there is a trade off among the steady state error-convergence towards the true channel coefficients, which avoids a fast convergence when the step size is preferred to be small for small output estimation error. In order to guarantee the algorithm to be convergent, the range of step size is specified but the choice of optimal learning step size has not been appropriately addressed. In order to

deal with these troubles, one key idea is to exploit varying step size during adaptation.

3.3 Recursive Least Squares (RLS) Algorithm

To combat the channel dynamics, the RLS based CE algorithm is frequently used for rapid convergence and improved MSE performance [9]. The standard RLS algorithm is

$$e(k) = S^T(k)w(k) + z(k) - S^T(k)h(k)$$

$$R(k) = \lambda^{-1}P(k-1) - \lambda^{-1}R(k)S^T(k)P(k-1)$$

$$h(k+1) = h(k) + S(k)e(k)R(k)$$

Where λ is the exponential forgetting factor with $0 < \lambda < 1$. The smaller value of λ leads to faster convergence rate as well as larger fluctuations in the weight signal after the initial convergence. On the other hand, too small λ value makes this algorithm unstable. Subsequently, it requires best possible forgetting factor such that the estimator error is decreased. Although a lot of modified CE algorithm has been studied on employing adaptive forgetting factor and parallel forgetting factor, the CE performance is severely degraded in highly dynamic fading channel even when the forgetting factor is well optimized [11].

IV. SIMULATION RESULT

The performance of the proposed CE algorithm is compared with the fixed step size LMS algorithm [6], NLMS algorithm [7], VSS-LMS algorithm [8], and RLS algorithm subjected to a Rayleigh fading environment. The simulation parameters are listed in table1. The BER is a significant performance parameter for quality measurement recovered data in wireless communication effect of the proposed CE in terms of BER compared with existing estimators. It is evident that the proposed CE algorithm outperforms the existing.

V. CONCLUSION

A time-varying step size LMS channel estimation scheme is proposed so as to combat channel dynamics and support broadband multimedia access. The weighting coefficients are updated automatically, despite the unavailability of channel information. Besides signals fluctuations due to noise decision errors can be nullified by the phase weighting scheme. Thus the algorithm guarantees convergence towards accurate channel coefficient. Even though, the proposed CE technique requires little bit computational complexity, the advantage of convergence towards true channel coefficient as well as BER performance could be of relevant use in future mobile communications which allow broadband multimedia access, anywhere, and anytime wireless communication.

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Closed Loop Quasi-Orthogonal STBC for Multiple Transmitters and Multiple Receivers

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents how to design Quasi-Orthogonal Space Time Block Coding for multiple transmitting antennas and one receiver with feedback. Multipath wireless environment creates difficulty because of diversity at multiple receivers and multiple transmitters. Diversity is reduced by using Quasi-Orthogonal STBC. For simplicity we considered four transmitters and one receiver. The diversity is achieved by reducing the non-zero off diagonal terms of quasi orthogonal matrix and by reducing the number of phase rotations at the transmitter. The phase rotations are achieved by single phase and two phase methods with low number of feedback bits. In this paper We concluded that two bit feedback is better than three bit feedback which is achieved by calculation of BER (bit error rate). These techniques are effective over fading channels and indoor wireless networks with low data rate systems .with this method we can achieve low-complexity and full diversity.

Keywords: Full diversity, Space time Block Codes, Bit Error Rate. Phase feedback method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Severe attenuation in a multipath wireless environment creates extreme difficulty for the receiver to determine the transmitted signal unless the receiver is provided with some form of diversity. Such diversity can be achieved by deploying multiple antennas at the transmitter and/or the receiver. Multiple antenna techniques have been of great interest in recent times, because of their ability to support higher data rates than single-antenna systems. It is generally impractical to deploy multiple antennas at the receiver because receivers should be small. Quasi-Orthogonal STBC proposed by Papadias [6], and independently by Jafarkhani [8] for the enhancement of link layer performance has a number of features such as it enables a significant portion of the open loop channel capacity and it requires simple receiver processing. In the case of quasi-orthogonal four transmit and one receive antenna, diversity gain decreases due to non-zero ortho diagonal elements in matrix .In this paper we investigate two transmitter preprocessing schemes to

orthogonalize the QO-STBC proposed by Toker[4]. A phase feedback method is used to rotate the transmitted signals from certain antennas in a prescribed way based upon partial transmitter channel state information (CSI), which is fed back from the transmitter. The rest of the paper is organized as follows:

II. QUASI-ORTHOGONAL STBC

Orthogonal Space-Time Block coding is a transmit diversity method that has the potential to enhance the forward capacity. A quasi orthogonal code could provide full code rate, but at the expense of loss in diversity. This extended to construct the code for four data symbols is as follows

$$x_{quasi} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & x_4^* \\ -x_2^* & -x_1^* & -x_4 & x_3 \\ -x_3^* & x_4^* & x_1 & x_2 \\ x_4 & -x_3 & -x_2 & x_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The code rate is

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \\ r_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & x_4 \\ -x_2^* & -x_2^* & -x_4^* & x_3^* \\ -x_3^* & x_4^* & x_1^* & x_2^* \\ x_4 & -x_3 & -x_2 & x_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} h_1 \\ h_2 \\ h_3 \\ h_4 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

For simplicity, considering four transmitters and one receiver in a flat fading environment, by taking the complex conjugate of the second and third row of the matrix (2).the received signal vector can be written explicitly in terms of the transmitted symbols as follows

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2^* \\ r_3^* \\ r_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 & h_2 & h_3 & h_4 \\ h_2^* & -h_1^* & h_4^* & -h_3^* \\ -h_3^* & -h_1^* & -h_2^* & -h_4^* \\ h_4 & -h_3 & -h_2 & h_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2^* \\ v_3^* \\ v_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= h_1 x_1 + h_2 x_2 + h_3 x_3 + v_1 \\ r_2^* &= h_2^* x_1 + h_1^* x_2 + h_4^* x_3 + v_2^* \\ r_3^* &= h_3^* x_1 + h_4^* x_2 - h_1^* x_3 + v_3^* \\ r_4 &= h_4 x_1 - h_3 x_2 - h_2 x_3 + v_4 \\ r &= Hx + v \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where h_i and $v_i, i=1; 2; 3; 4$ are the complex channel impulse response coefficients and zero-mean, circularly symmetric, complex valued Gaussian noise terms with variance σ^2_n

$$\alpha = |Re\{h_1^* h_4 - h_2^* h_3\}| \quad (5)$$

Respectively. Matched filtering is performed by pre multiplying by H^H , therefore we get Matched filtering is performed by pre multiplying by H^H , therefore we get

$$H^H r = H^H H x + H^H v \quad (6)$$

$$\check{r} = \Delta x + \check{v} \quad (7)$$

where $(.)^H$ represents Hermitian transpose in equation

$$\Delta = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & 0 & 0 & \alpha \\ 0 & \gamma & 0 & \alpha \\ 0 & -\alpha & \gamma & 0 \\ \alpha & 0 & 0 & \gamma \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

After match filtering at the receiver some non-zero off diagonal terms exist which reduce the diversity gain of the code. For example, the fourth symbol

interferes with the first symbol, the second symbol interferes with the third symbol.

Where

$$\gamma = |h_1^2| + |h_2^2| + |h_3^2| + |h_4^2| \quad (9)$$

and

$$\alpha = Re\{h_1^* h_4 - h_2^* h_3\}, Re \quad (10)$$

Denotes the real operator.

III. ORTHOGONALIZATION BY PHASE FEEDBACK METHOD

The non-zero ortho-diagonal elements in matrix (2) reduce the diversity gain and the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the receiver. The signals transmitted from certain antennas can be modified by rotating with proper phase angle such that the magnitude of the ortho diagonal elements α is minimized.

Fig 1: Four transmit and one receive antennas, showing the fading Channel coefficients and the additive white Gaussian noise

IV. TWO PHASE FEEDBACK

If the first and second terms in the brackets in equation (3) are multiplied by a phasor, it is possible to make α zero. Assuming that the signals from the third and fourth antennas are rotated by μ and \hat{A} respectively, which is equivalent to multiplying the

first and second term in equation (11) by $e^{-j\theta}$ and $e^{-j\phi}$ respectively

$$\alpha = \text{Re}\{h_1^* h_4 e^{-j\theta} - h_2^* h_3 e^{-j\phi}\} \quad (11)$$

Let $k = h_1^* h_4$ and $\lambda = h_2^* h_3$

$$\alpha = |k| \cos(\theta + \angle k) - |\lambda| \cos(\theta + \angle \lambda) \quad (12)$$

where j and L denote the absolute value and the angle (arctan) operators, respectively. Since $\alpha = 0$ has infinite solutions for Θ and Φ The solutions

$$\theta = \arccos\left(\frac{\lambda}{k} \cos(\theta + \angle \lambda)\right) - \angle k \quad (13)$$

Provided that

$$\varphi \in \begin{cases} (0, 2\pi) & \text{where } \lambda < k \\ (\pi - \xi - \angle \lambda, \xi - \angle \lambda) & \\ (2\pi - \xi - \angle \lambda, \pi + \xi - \angle \lambda, \text{otherwise} & \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Where

$$\xi = \arccos(|k|/|\lambda|)$$

where $|k|$ and L denote the absolute value and the angle (arctan) operators, respectively. Since $\alpha = 0$ has infinite solutions for Θ and Φ The solutions are

$$\theta = \arccos\left(\frac{\lambda}{k} \cos(\phi + \angle \lambda)\right) \quad (15)$$

Provided that

$$\varphi \in \begin{cases} (0, 2\pi) & \text{where } \lambda < k \\ (\pi - \xi - \angle \lambda, \xi - \angle \lambda) & \\ (2\pi - \xi - \angle \lambda, \pi + \xi - \angle \lambda, \text{otherwise} & \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $\xi = \arccos(|k|/|\lambda|)$

V. SINGLE PHASE FEEDBACK

The number of feedback bits required from the receiver to the transmitter has to be small because of practical constraints. Reduction in feedback bits can be achieved by reducing the number of phase rotations at the transmitter antennas. There are two methods proposed by Taker [10], [11]

Which are as follows?

1. one way to reduce the amount of information needed to be fed back is to rotate the signal of one antenna only.
2. Another way is to quantize the feedback phase information according to the number of feedback bits

available. It is possible to reduce the off diagonal terms of the matrix just by rotating a single antenna instead of rotating two antennas. For example rotations applied only at the fourth antenna, the coupling term α can be rewritten as

$$\alpha = \text{Re}\{h_1^* h_4 e^{-j\theta} - |h_2^* h_3|\} \quad (17)$$

$$= |k| \cos(\theta + \angle k) - \lambda_{real}$$

Where $K = h_1^* h_4$, $\lambda = h_2^* h_3$, λ_{real} (18)

Is the real part of λ and $|k|$ is the absolute value from the above equation it is clear that the cosine wave is a function of θ scaled by $|k|$, phase shifted by $\angle k$ and biased by λ_{real} under the condition

$$|\lambda_{real}| \leq |k|, \alpha = 0$$

has two solutions for

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\theta_1} &= \arccos(\lambda_{real}/|k|) - \angle k \\ \theta_{\theta_2} &= -\arccos(\lambda_{real}/|k|) - \angle k \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

On the other hand, if $|\lambda_{real}| > |k|$ there is no solution for $\alpha = 0$ and $|\alpha|$ can only be minimized at the following phase value

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= \{-\angle k \mid |\lambda_{real}| > |k|, \} \\ \Phi &= \{\pi - \angle k \mid -|\lambda_{real}| > |k|, \} \end{aligned}$$

With the minimum value

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} -\lambda_{real} + |k|, & |\lambda_{real}| > |k| \\ -\lambda_{real} - |k|, & |\lambda_{real}| > |k| \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

VI. QUANTIZATION

In practice only a finite number of bits is allowed for the feedback, which we assume to equal to P bits. For the single antenna phase adjustment, the discrete estimated feedback formation corresponding to the phase μ will be

$$\text{an element of the set } \theta \in \Omega = \frac{2\pi n}{2^P}, 2^P - 1$$

$$\theta = \text{argmin}(|h_1^* h_4 e^{-j\theta} - h_2^* h_3|)$$

Similarly, for the dual antenna phase adjustment, the discrete estimated feed-back information for the phases θ and ϕ are the elements of the set

$$\{\bar{\theta}, \bar{\phi}\} \in \Omega \frac{2\pi n}{2^p - 1}, n=0,1,2,3,\dots,2^p - 1$$

and are computed as

$$\{\bar{\theta}, \bar{\phi}\} = \underset{\theta, \phi}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left(\left| \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} (h_1^* h_n) e^{j\theta} \right|^2 - \left| \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} (h_1^* h_n) \right|^2 \right) \quad (21)$$

VII. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The results depicted in Figure are a comparison between the open loop quasi-orthogonal four transmit and one receives antennas and closed loop quasi-orthogonal four transmit and one receives antennas. A Rayleigh fading channel is used for simulation and it can be seen that at a BER of 10^{-3} ; the performance improvement of the feedback scheme is approximately 2:53dB compared to the open loop scheme. The feedback method is successful in reducing the ortho-diagonal terms of the matrix shows both the one phase feedback method and two phase feedback method. It is observed that the performance gain between the three bit feedback and the two bit feedback is only 0:43dB, so to use 2 bit feedback appears to be good. Due to practical limitations, a finite number of bits is allowed for the feedback.

Fig 2: The BER performance comparisons between the two transmit antennas, four transmit antennas with open loop and two phase feedback schemes.

Fig 3: The BER performance comparisons between the two transmit antennas; four transmit antennas with open loop, two phase feedback scheme and one phase feedback schemes.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The proposed closed loop quasi-orthogonal space frequency block code-OFDM can achieve both full code rate and full diversity. By using antenna selection method and phase rotation method, we can minimize the or diagonal terms of the matrix

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BIOGRAPHY

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Low Power Multiplier to Reduce Switching Activities Using Bypassing Technique

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ABSTRACT

Multipliers and adders are the basic circuits required for implementing any Arithmetic and logic functions in VLSI. Many of the real-time applications like the arithmetic operations in Microprocessor, the filter designing in Signal processing require the multipliers. As the multipliers play a major role in the VLSI designing the power consumption related to them is a parameter to be thought of. To achieve such power reduction, modifications are made to conventional multiplier architecture and low power multiplier architecture is proposed using a technique called bypassing in this work. This proposed architecture removes the unnecessary switching activities responsible for power consumption and also eliminates unnecessary iteration done in the conventional multiplier whenever a zero is encountered in the multiplier.

Index Terms – low power, multiplier, shift-and-add, ring counter, feeder.

INTRODUCTION

As the scale of integration keeps growing, more and more sophisticated signal processing systems are being implemented on a VLSI chip. These signal processing applications not only demand great computation capacity but also consume considerable amount of energy. For portable applications where the power consumption is the most important parameter, one should reduce the power dissipation as much as possible. One of the best ways to reduce the dynamic power dissipation is to minimize the total switching activity, i.e., the total number of signal transitions of the system.

Multiplier is one of the most important arithmetic circuits used in multimedia, and digital signal processing such as discrete cosine transform, fast Fourier transform. Because of its massive usefulness lots of algorithms are developed to improve constraints like power and speed. Multiplication consists of three major steps:

- 1) Partial products recoding and generating;
- 2) Reducing the partial products by partial product reduction schemes to two rows; and
- 3) Adding the remaining two rows of partial products by using a carry-propagate adder to obtain the final product.

In this work, we propose modifications to the conventional architecture of the shift-and-add radix-2 multipliers to considerably reduce its energy consumption.

A. Conventional Shift and Add Multiplier: Conventional shift-and-add multiplier, which multiplies A by B architecture is shown in FIG1. There are six major sources of switching activity in the multiplier. These sources, which are marked with ovals in the figure, are:

- (1) shifting value of B register,
- (2) counter activity,
- (3) adder activity,
- (4) 0 and A switching between in the multiplexer,
- (5) multiplexer select activity,
- (6) partial product shifting.

Note that the activity of the adder consists of required transitions (when $B(0)$ is nonzero) and unnecessary transitions (when $B(0)$ is zero).

By minimizing any of these switching activity sources, it can lower the power consumption. Since some of the nodes have higher capacitance, reducing their switching will lead to more power reduction. As an example, the selector line of the multiplexer $B(0)$ which is connected to K gates for a K -bit multiplier. If we somehow eliminate this node, power saving can be achieved. Next, we describe how we minimize or possibly eliminate these sources of switching activity.

Figure1: Architecture of conventional shift and add multiplier with major source of switching activity

I. The Proposed Low Power Multiplier: BZFAD

To derive low-power architecture, we concentrate our effort on eliminating or reducing the sources of the switching activity discussed in the previous section. The proposed architecture which is shown in Figure 2 is called BZ-FAD.

A. Shift of the B Register

In the traditional architecture (see Fig. 1), to generate the partial product, $B(0)$ is used to decide between A and 0 . If the bit is "1", A should be added to the previous partial product, whereas if it is "0", no addition operation is needed to generate the partial product. Hence, in each cycle, register B should be shifted to the right so that its right bit appears at $B(0)$; this operation gives rise to some switching activity.

To avoid this, in the proposed architecture (see Fig. 2) a multiplexer $M1$ with one-hot encoded bus selector chooses the hot bit of B in each cycle. A ring counter is used to select $B(n)$ in the n th cycle. As will be seen later, the same counter can be used for block $M2$ as well. The ring counter used in the proposed multiplier is noticeably wider (32 bits versus 5 bits for a 32-bit multiplier) than the binary counter used in the conventional architecture; therefore an ordinary ring counter, if used in BZ-FAD, would raise more transitions than its binary counterpart in the conventional architecture. To minimize the switching activity of the counter, we utilize the low-power ring counter.

To avoid this, in the proposed architecture (Fig 2) a multiplexer ($M1$) with one-hot encoded bus selector chooses the hot bit of B in each cycle. A ring counter is used to select $B(n)$ in the n th cycle. As will be seen later, the same counter can be used for block $M2$ as well. The ring counter used in the proposed multiplier is noticeably wider (32 bits vs. 5 bits for a 32-bit multiplier) than the binary counter used in the conventional architecture; therefore an ordinary ring counter, if used in BZ-FAD, would raise more transitions than its binary counterpart in the conventional architecture. To minimize the switching activity of the counter, we utilize the low-power ring counter.

Fig 2: BZFAD Architecture

II. Shifting of PP Register

In the conventional architecture, the partial product is shifted in each cycle giving rise to transitions. Inspecting the multiplication algorithm reveals that the multiplication may be completed by processing the most significant bits of the partial product, and hence, it is not necessary for the least significant bits of the partial product to be shifted. We take advantage of this observation in the BZ-FAD architecture. Notice that in FIG 2 for P_{low} the lower half of the partial product, we use $_$ latches. These latches are indicated by the dotted rectangle M2 in Fig. 2. In the first cycle, the least significant bit PP (0) of the product becomes finalized and is stored in the right-most latch of P_{low}. The ring counter output is used to open (unlatch) the proper latch. This is achieved by connecting the S/ \sim H line of the nth latch to the nth bit of the ring counter which is "1" in the nth cycle. In this way, the nth latch samples the value of the nth bit of the final product (see Fig. 2).

In the subsequent cycles, the next least significant bits are finalized and stored in the proper latches. When the last bit is stored in the left-most latch, the higher and lower halves of the partial product form the final product result. Using this method, no shifting of the lower half of the partial product is required. The higher part of the partial product, however, is still shifted. Comparing the two architectures, BZ-FAD saves power for two reasons: first, the lower half of the partial product is not shifted, and second, this half is implemented with latches instead of flip-flops. Note that in the conventional architecture (see Fig. 1) the data transparency problem of latches prohibits us from using latches instead of flip-flops for forming the lower half of the partial product. This problem does not exist in BZ-FAD since the lower half is not formed by shifting the bits in a shift Register.

In brief, from the six sources of activity in the multiplier, we have eliminated the shift of the B register, reduced the activities of the right input of the adder, and lowered the activities on the multiplexer select line. In addition, we have minimized the activities in the adder, the activities in the counter,

and the shifts in the PP (partial product) register. The proposed architecture, however, introduces new sources of activities. These include the activities of a new multiplexer which has the same size as that of the multiplexer of the conventional architecture.

III. Reducing Switching Activity of the Adder:

In the conventional multiplier architecture (see Fig. 1), in each cycle, the current partial product is added to A (when B (0) is one) or to 0 (when B (0) is zero). This leads to unnecessary transitions in the adder when B (0) is zero. In these cases, the adder can be bypassed and the partial product should be shifted to the right by one bit. This is what is performed in the proposed Architecture which eliminates unnecessary switching activities in the adder.

As shown in Fig. 2, the Feeder and Bypass registers are used to bypass the adder in the cycles where B (n) is zero. In each cycle, the hot bit of the next cycle (i.e., B (n+1)) is checked. If it is 0, i.e., the adder is not needed in the next cycle, the Bypass register is clocked to store the current partial product. If B(n+1) Is 1, i.e., the adder is really needed in the next cycle, the Feeder register is clocked to store the current partial product which must be fed to the adder in the next cycle. Note that to select between the Feeder and Bypass registers we have used NAND and NOR gates which are inverting logic, therefore, the inverted clock (\sim Clock in Fig. 3) is fed to them. Finally, in each cycle, B (n) determines if the partial product should come from the Bypass register or from the Adder output.

Fig 3. Adder with Registers

Feeder and bypass registers are used to optimize the adder operation. In every cycle, the partial product obtained in the previous cycle is available at the input of these two registers. A clock gating structure is given to feeder and bypass registers. The clock gator performs the following functions. Feeder is clocked if LSB of 'B' obtained by using the low power ring counter is equal to '1'. Bypass is clocked if LSB of 'B' obtained by using the low power ring counter is equal to '0'. Thus the current partial product is stored either in feeder or in bypass register.

IV. Critical Path Analysis

By comparing the two architectures, it is observed that in BZ-FAD, the value of B does not contribute to the critical path whereas in the conventional multiplier, it should first settle since B(0) is required for the multiplexer to select either A or zero. In BZ-FAD, "A" has already settled and only the output of the Feeder register which is the other input to the adder needs to settle. Next, we consider the BZ-FAD MUX1, whose select signal does not contribute to the critical path. This is because the adder in the BZ-FAD, in contrast to the conventional architecture, can begin its work independent of multiplexer MUX1.

In fact, while the adder is busy with performing the addition, there is enough time for the ring counter and multiplexer M1 to deliver the value of the next hot bit. All delays in this path are shorter than the adder delay and, hence, do not increase the delay of BZ-FAD. The synthesis timing reports estimates the critical path delay for the BZ-FAD and the conventional multipliers to be 6.599 and 6.472 ns, respectively, which agrees with the above discussion. The slight difference between the reported delays originates from the fact that the input clock signal to the Feeder and Bypass registers pass through a NAND and a NOR gate in the BZ-FAD architecture.

V. Simulation results

Both the architectures, conventional shift and add multiplier and Bypass zero feed a direct multiplier are implemented in VHDL and are simulated using

Xilinx in simulator and the results obtained are shown in following sections.

A. Conventional Multiplier output

The simulation result for 8 bit multiplier using conventional architecture is highlighted in Figure 5.1. The inputs given are 00001111(15) and 000000111(7). Multiplier is shifted in each cycle and the corresponding partial products are formed. The conventional multiplier uses a binary counter. From the simulation results, it can be seen that the output of multiplier comes out to be 000000001101001(105).

1. Simulation results of conventional multiplier

B. BZFAD multiplier output

The simulation result for 8 bit multiplier using low power architecture is shown in Figure 5.2. The inputs given are 00001111(15) and 00000110(6). The multiplication operation is performed using the BZFAD architecture. The low power multiplier uses a low power ring counter. From the simulation results, it can be seen that the output comes out to be 000000001011010(90)

2. Simulation results of BZFAD multiplier

C. Device utilization summary

TABLE I DEVICE UTILIZATION SUMMARY OF CONVENTIONAL MULTIPLIERS

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)			
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slices	81	990	8%
Number of Slice Flip Flops	88	1920	4%
Number of 4 input LUTs	123	1920	6%
Number of bonded I/Os	94	83	100%
Number of DCMs	1	24	4%

TABLE II Device utilization summary of BZFAD multiplier

Device Utilization Summary			
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slice Flip Flops	55	1,920	2%
Number of 4 input LUTs	91	1,920	4%
Logic Distribution			
Number of occupied Slices	64	960	6%
Number of Slices containing only related logic	64	64	100%
Number of Slices containing unrelated logic	0	64	0%
Total Number of 4 input LUTs	123	1,920	6%
Number used as logic	91		
Number used as a route-thru	32		
Number of bonded I/Os	68	66	100%
I/Os Flip Flops	8		
Number of BUFGMUXs	1	24	4%

D. Timing summary

- 1). Conventional multiplier minimum period= 6.599 ns
- 2). BZFAD multiplier minimum period= 6.472 ns.

TABLE III. Summary of Simulation Results

Multiplier type	Conventional	BZFAD
Vendor	Xilinx	Xilinx
Device and family	Spartan 3E	Spartan 3E
Power dissipation	34mW	27Mw

VII. Conclusion

In this project, sources of power dissipation in VLSI circuits are studied and methods to reduce power dissipation are explained. Switching activity is found to be active source of power dissipation in conventional shift and add architecture. A low power architecture known as Bypass Zero Feed A Direct (BZFAD) architecture is proposed. Both the architectures are implemented using VHDL in Xilinx and results thus obtained are analyzed. The proposed architecture reduced the power dissipated by 20% compared to conventional multiplier architecture.

VIII. Future Scope

The project can be implemented on CADENCE or SYNOPSIS tool to obtain more reliable power

calculations. Multiplier architectures other than shift and add multiplier can be implemented, analyzed and compared with one another to select an appropriate architecture for our purpose. Apart from switching activity other sources of power dissipation can be considered and addressed.

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Implementation of AES-GCM encryption algorithm for high performance and low power architecture Using FPGA

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ABSTRACT

Evaluation of the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) algorithm in FPGA is proposed here. This Evaluation is compared with other works to show the efficiency. Here we are concerned about two major purposes. The first is to define some of the terms and concepts behind basic cryptographic methods, and to offer a way to compare the myriad cryptographic schemes in use today. The second is to provide some real examples of cryptography in use today. The design uses an iterative looping approach with block and key size of 128 bits, lookup table implementation of S-box. This gives low complexity architecture and easily achieves low latency as well as high throughput. Simulation results, performance results are presented and compared with previous reported designs. Since its acceptance as the adopted symmetric-key algorithm, the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and its recently standardized authentication Galois/Counter Mode (GCM) have been utilized in various security-constrained applications. Many of the AES-GCM applications are power and resource constrained and requires efficient hardware implementations. In this project, AES-GCM algorithms are evaluated and optimized to identify the high-performance and low-power architectures. The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is a specification for the encryption of electronic data. The Cipher Block Chaining (CBC) mode is a confidentiality mode whose encryption process features the combining (“chaining”) of the plaintext blocks with the previous Cipher text blocks. The CBC mode requires an IV to combine with the first plaintext block. The IV need not be secret, but it must be unpredictable. Also, the integrity of the IV should be protected. Galois/Counter Mode (GCM) is a block cipher mode of operation that uses universal hashing over a binary Galois field to provide authenticated encryption. Galois Hash is used for authentication, and the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) block cipher is used for encryption in counter mode of operation. To obtain the least-complexity S-box, the formulations for the Galois Field (GF) sub-field inversions in GF (2^4) are optimized. By conducting exhaustive simulations for the input transitions, we analyze the synthesis of the AES S-boxes considering the switching activities, gate-level net lists, and parasitic information. Finally, by implementation of AES-GCM the high-performance GF (2^{128}) multiplier architectures, gives the detailed information of its performance. An optimized coding for the implementation of Advanced Encryption Standard-Galois Counter Mode has been developed. The speed factor of the algorithm implementation has been targeted and a software code in Verilog HDL has been developed. This implementation is useful in wireless security like military communication and mobile telephony where there is a grayer emphasis on the speed of communication.

Index Terms— Cipher blocks chaining, GaliosField, Advanced Encryption Standard, finite field, Galois/Counter Mode, high performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Data Encryption Standard (DES) is the most common SKC scheme used today; DES was designed by IBM in the 1970s and adopted by the National Bureau of Standards (NBS) [now the National Institute for Standards and Technology (NIST)] in 1977 for

commercial and unclassified government applications. DES is a block-cipher employing a 56-bit key that operates on 64-bit blocks. Symmetric-key ciphers use the same key for encryption and decryption, or to be more precise, the key used for decryption is computationally easy to compute given the key used for encryption. In turn, symmetric-key

ciphers fall into two categories: block ciphers and stream ciphers. Stream ciphers encrypt the plaintext one bit at a time, in contrast to block ciphers, which operate on a block of bits of a predefined length. Most popular block ciphers are DES, IDEA and AES, and most popular stream cipher is RC6. DES has a complex set of rules and transformations that were designed specifically to yield fast hardware implementations and slow software implementations. The Advanced Encryption Standard-Galois/Counter Mode (AES-GCM) provides authentication and confidentiality for sensitive data simultaneously. In the AES-GCM, data confidentiality is provided by the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). This paper explores the area-throughput trade-off for an ASIC implementation of the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). Different pipelined implementations of the AES algorithm as well as the design decisions and the area optimizations that lead to a low area and high throughput AES encryption processor are presented. With loop unrolling and outer-round pipelining techniques, throughputs of 30 Gbits/s to 70 Gbits/s are achievable in a 0.18- μ m CMOS technology. Moreover, by pipelining the composite field implementation of the byte substitution phase of the AES algorithm (inner-round pipelining), the area consumption is reduced up to 35 percent. By designing an offline key scheduling unit for the AES processor the area cost is further reduced by 28 percent, which results in a total reduction of 48 percent while the same throughput is maintained. Therefore, the over 30 Gbits/s, fully pipelined AES processor operating in the counter mode of operation can be used for the encryption of data on optical links. The authentication of the AES-GCM is provided by the Galois/Counter Mode (GCM) using a universal hash function. The AES-GCM has been used for a number of applications such as the new LAN security standard WLAN 802.11ae (MACSec) and Fibre Channel Security Protocols (FC-SP). Moreover, it has been utilized in a number of cores from industry. In addition, two AES-GCM software-based implementations have been presented. Among the transformations in the AES encryption, the SubBytes (S-boxes) is the only non-linear one, requiring the

highest area and consuming much of the AES power. Therefore, the performance metrics of the S-boxes affect those for the entire AES encryption significantly. For low-complexity implementations, the S-box can be realized using logic gates in composite fields. These S-boxes can also be pipelined for achieving high performance. On the other hand, the S-boxes based on look-up tables (LUTs) could be area-efficient when implemented utilizing the memory resources available on FPGAs. In this paper, logic-gate optimizes and comprehensive synthesis of more than 40 different S-boxes are used for deriving their performance metrics. This paper presents the area-throughput trade-offs of a fully pipelined, ultra high speed AES encryption processor. Different pipelined architectures that can achieve the required throughput for the above application and the area optimization opportunities for such designs are explored.

II. Galois/Counter Mode of Operation (GCM)

By definition, the Galois/Counter Mode is a block cipher mode of operation that uses universal hashing over a binary Galois field whose purpose is to provide authenticated encryption. This paper proposes an efficient solution to combine Rijndael encryption and decryption in one FPGA design, with a strong focus on low area constraints. The proposed design gets into the smallest Xilinx FPGAs3, deals with data streams of 208 Mbps, uses 163 slices and 3 RAM blocks and improves by 68% the best-known similar designs in terms of ratio Throughput=Area. They also proposed implementations in other FPGA Families (Xilinx Vertex-II) and comparisons with similar DES, triple-DES and AES implementations. It can achieve data rates of 21.3 Gbps in Vertex-II FPGAs. The encryption/decryption mode can be changed on a cycle-by-cycle basis with no dead cycles. For the AES, the best similar RAM-based solution unrolls the 10 cipher rounds and pipelines them in an encryption-only process. This implementation in a Vertex-E FPGA produces a throughput of 11.8 Gbps and allows the key to be changed at every cycle. This DES implementation reaches higher throughput than the corresponding

AES implementation. The input and output for the AES algorithm each consist of sequences of 128 bits (digits with values of 0 or 1). These sequences will sometimes be referred to as blocks and the number of bits they contain will be referred to as their length. The Cipher Key for the AES algorithm is a sequence of 128, 192 or 256 bits. Other input, output and Cipher Key lengths are not permitted by this standard. The bits within such sequences will be numbered starting at zero and ending at one less than the sequence length (block length or key length). The number i attached to a bit is known as its index and will be in one of the ranges $0 \leq i < 128$, $0 \leq i < 192$ or $0 \leq i < 256$ depending on the block length and key. For the AES algorithm, the length of the input block, the output block and the State is 128 bits. This is represented by $N_b = 4$, which reflects the number of 32-bit words (number of columns) in the State. For the AES algorithm, the length of the Cipher Key, K , is 128, 192, or 256 bits. The key length is represented by $N_k = 4, 6, \text{ or } 8$, which reflects the number of 32-bit words (number of columns) in the Cipher Key. For the AES algorithm, the number of rounds to be performed during the execution of the algorithm is dependent on the key size. The number of rounds is represented by N_r , where $N_r = 10$ when $N_k = 4$, $N_r = 12$ when $N_k = 6$, and $N_r = 14$ when $N_k = 8$.

A. GCM Encryption and Decryption - Inputs and Outputs

Encryption: The GCM encryption routine expects four inputs:

- A secret key K , to be used with the underlying block cipher. AES is defined to support key lengths of 128-, 192- or 256-bits long.
- An initialization vector IV that (in principle) can be of any length between 1 and 2^{64} bits.
- A plaintext P that can be of any length between 0 and $(2^{39} \otimes 256)$ bits.
- Additional authenticated data AAD that can be of any length between 0 and 2^{64} bits.

This procedure has two outputs:

- A cipher text C that has the same length as the input plaintext P .
- An authentication tag T , which in our case is of length exactly 128 bits.

Below we denote the GCM encryption routine (using AES) by

$$(C, T) := \text{GCM-AES-enc}(K; IV, P, AAD)$$

The security of GCM relies on the secret key being secret, and on the IV being used as a nonce. That is, GCM only offers security as long as the same value for the IV is never used for encryption of more than one plaintext under the same key.

Decryption: The GCM decryption routine has five inputs:

- the key K ,
- initialization vector IV ,
- cipher text C ,
- additional authenticated data AAD , and
- tag T , all as above.

Its output is either the plaintext P as above, or the special signal fail (indicates that the inputs are not authentic). Below we denote the GCM decryption routine (using AES) by

$$P/\text{fail} := \text{GCM-AES-dec}(K; IV, C, AAD, T)$$

A cipher text C , initialization vector IV , additional authenticated data A and tag T are authentic for key K when they are generated by the encrypt operation with inputs K , IV , A and P , for some plaintext P . The authenticated decrypt operation will, with high probability, return **FAIL** whenever its inputs were not created by the encrypt operation with the identical key. The additional authenticated data A is used to protect information that needs to be authenticated, but which must be left unencrypted. When using GCM to secure a network protocol, this input could include addresses, ports, sequence numbers, protocol version numbers, and other fields that indicate how the plaintext should be handled, forwarded, or processed. In many situations, it is desirable to authenticate these fields, though they must be left in the clear to allow the network or system to function

properly. When this data is included in the AAD, authentication is provided without copying the data into the cipher text. The primary purpose of the IV is to be a nonce, that is, to be distinct for each invocation of the encryption operation for a fixed key. It is acceptable for the IV to be generated randomly, as long as the distinctness of the IV values is highly likely. The IV is authenticated, and it is not necessary to include it in the AAD field. Both confidentiality and message authentication is provided on the plaintext. The strength of the authentication of P, IV and A is determined by the length t of the authentication tag. When the length of P is zero, GCM acts as a MAC on the input A. The mode of operation that uses GCM as a stand-alone message authentication code is denoted as GMAC.

B. ENCRYPTION

Let n and u denote the unique pair of positive integers such that the total number of bits in the plaintext is $(n - 1)128 + u$, where $1 \leq u \leq 128$. The plaintext consists of a sequence of n bit strings, in which the bit length of the last bit string is u, and the bit length of the other bit strings is 128. The sequence is denoted $P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{n-1}, P_n^*$, and the bit strings are called data blocks, although the last bit string, P_n^* , may not be a complete block. Similarly, the cipher text is denoted as $C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{n-1}, C_n^*$, where the number of bits in the final block C_n^* is u. The additional authenticated data A is denoted as $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_{m-1}, A_m^*$, where the last bit string A_m^* may be a partial block of length v, and m and v denote the unique pair of positive integers such that the total number of bits in A is $(m - 1)128 + v$ and $1 \leq v \leq 128$. The authenticated encryption operation is defined by the following equations:

$$H = E(K, 0^{128})$$

$$Y_0 = \begin{cases} IV \parallel 0^{31}1 & \text{if } \text{len}(IV) = 96 \\ \text{GHASH}(H, \{\}, IV) & \text{Otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Otherwise.

$$Y_i = \text{incr}(Y_{i-1}) \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

$$C_i = P_i \oplus E(K, Y_i) \quad \text{for } i = 1 \dots n - 1$$

$$C_n^* = P_n^* \oplus \text{MSB}_u(E(K, Y_n))$$

$$T = \text{MSB}_t(\text{GHASH}(H, A, C) \oplus E(K, Y_0))$$

Successive counter values are generated using the function $\text{incr}()$, which treats the rightmost 32 bits of its argument as a nonnegative integer with the least significant bit on the right, and increments this value modulo 2^{32} . More formally, the value of $\text{incr}(F \parallel I)$ is $F \parallel (I + 1 \bmod 232)$. The encryption process is illustrated in Figure 1.

C. GCM encryption operation

As the name suggests, GCM mode combines the well-known counter mode of encryption with the new Galois mode of authentication. The key feature is that the Galois field multiplication used for authentication can be easily computed in parallel thus permitting higher throughput than the authentication algorithms that use chaining modes, like CBC. The GF(2^{128}) field used is defined by the polynomial $x^{128} + x^7 + x^2 + 1$. The function GHASH is defined by $\text{GHASH}(H, A, C) = X_{m+n+1}$, where H is a string of 128 zeros encrypted using the block cipher, A is data which is only authenticated (not encrypted), C is the cipher text, m is the number of 128 bit blocks in A, n is the number of 128 bit blocks in C (the final blocks of A and C need not be exactly 128 bits), and the variable X_i for $i = 0, \dots, m + n + 1$ is defined as

$$X_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } i = 0 \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (X_{i-1} \oplus A_i) \cdot H \\ \text{for } i = 1 \dots m - 1 \\ (X_{m-1} \oplus (A_m^* \parallel 0^{128-v})) \cdot H \\ \text{for } i = m \end{array} \right. \\ (X_{i-1} \oplus C_i) \cdot H \\ \text{for } i = m + 1 \dots m + n - 1 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$(X_{m+n-1} \oplus (C_m^* \parallel 0^{128-u})) \cdot H$$

for $i = m + n$

$$(X_{m+n} \oplus (\text{len}(A) \parallel \text{len}(C))) \cdot H$$

for $i = m + n + 1$.

where v is the bit length of the final block of A , u is the bit length of the final block of C , and \parallel denotes concatenation of bit strings.

Figure 1: The authenticated encryption operation.

For simplicity, a case with only a single block of additional authenticated data (labeled Auth Data 1) and two blocks of plaintext is shown. Here E_K denotes the block cipher encryption using the key K , mult_H denotes multiplication in $GF(2^{128})$ by the hash key H , and incr denotes the counter increment function.

Figure 2: The authenticated decryption operation, showing the same case as in Figure 1.

Figure 3 :A hardware implementation of GCM, showing the different data paths through the circuit.

D. MULTIPLICATION IN $GF(2^{128})$

The multiplication operation is defined as an operation on bit vectors in order to simplify the specification. This definition corresponds to the particular choice of the field representation used in GCM. Each element is a vector of 128 bits. The i^{th} bit of an element X is denoted as X_i . The leftmost bit is X_0 , and the rightmost bit is X_{127} . The multiplication operation uses the special element $R = 11100001 \parallel 0^{120}$, and is defined in Algorithm 1. The function $\text{right shift}()$ moves the bits of its 7

Algorithm 1 Multiplication in $GF(2^{128})$. Computes the value of $Z = X \cdot Y$, where X, Y and

```

 $Z \in GF(2^{128})$ .
 $Z \leftarrow 0, V \leftarrow X$ 
for  $i = 0$  to 127 do
    if  $Y_i = 1$  then
         $Z \leftarrow Z \oplus V$ 
    end if
    if  $V_{127} = 0$  then
         $V \leftarrow \text{right shift}(V)$ 
    else
         $V \leftarrow \text{right shift}(V) \oplus R$ 
    end if
end for
return  $Z$ 
    
```

argument one bit to the right. More formally, whenever $W = \text{right shift}(V)$, then $W_i = V_{i-1}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 127$ and $W_0 = 0$.

Authenticated encryption and decryption are the two functions within the GCM. The authenticated encryption performs two tasks; encrypting the confidential data and computing and authentication tag. The authenticated decryption function decrypts the confidential data and verifies the tag. The data flow of the authenticated encryption is shown in Fig. 3. As seen in this figure, the mechanism for the confidentiality of data is a variation of the block cipher counter mode of operation, denoted by GCTR_K (Galois Counter with the key K). Then, the function GCTR_K performs the block cipher counter mode with the Initial Counter Block (ICB) and its increments ($\text{CB}_2 - \text{CB}_i$) and the plaintext blocks ($P_1 - P_i$) as the inputs.

Figure 4 The GCM authenticated encryption data flow.

Galois Hash (GHASH_H) function is constructed by $\text{GF}(2^{128})$ multiplications with a fixed parameter, called the hash subkey (H). The GHASH_H function calculates

$$\sum_{j=1}^n X_j H^{n-j+1} = X_1 \cdot H^n \oplus X_2 \cdot H^{n-1} \oplus \dots \oplus X_n \cdot H, \quad (1)$$

where X_1 to X_n are the n , 128-bit blocks of the input. It is noted that the hash subkey is generated by applying the AES to the zero block, i.e., $0 = (0, 0 \dots 0) \in \text{GF}(2^{128})$. Then, the GHASH_H function calculates (1). All the arithmetic operations in (1), i.e., additions, GF

multiplications, and exponentiations are performed over $\text{GF}(2^{128})$ constructed by the irreducible polynomial $P(x) = x^{128} + x^7 + x^2 + x + 1$. As seen in Fig. 3.2, the total number of input blocks to GHASH_H is $n = m + i + 1$, where m and i are the number of blocks for the additional authenticated data ($A_1 - A_m$) and the output of GCTR_K , respectively. Eventually, the authentication tag T with length of t bits is derived. In the authenticated decryption, the same GHASH_H procedure is performed on the authenticated data and ciphertext blocks to verify the tag.

III. HIGH PERFORMANCE GCM PARALLEL ARCHITECTURE

High-performance parallel architectures for GCM improve the throughput and the latency of the structures for GHASH_H . They also remove the need for consecutive $\text{GF}(2^{128})$ multiplications with H for deriving (1). Because of the low complexity of the implementations of these exponents, we take advantage of these low-cost hash subkey powers in the proposed high-performance architectures. We utilize the powers in the form of H^{2^j} to obtain the other powers of the hash subkey with the least number of GF multiplications over $\text{GF}(2^{128})$ for proposed architectures. For instance, we derive $H^4 = H^2 \times H$ or $H^6 = H^4 \times H^2$. This architecture is based on the composite field $\text{GF}((2^4)^2)$. Algorithm 1 is used for obtaining the key formulation for the proposed GHASH_H function. Although there is no restriction in choosing q , i.e., the number of parallel adder-multipliers, we use $q = 2^j$, $1 \leq j \leq \log_2(n)$. This leads to lower number of clock cycles and higher throughput needed for the implementations.

Algorithm 1 The proposed high-performance approach for implementing the GCM.

Inputs: $X_p \in \text{GF}(2^{128})$, $1 \leq p \leq n$, and $H^{2^j} \in \text{GF}(2^{128})$,

$0 \leq j \leq \log_2(q)$.

Output: $\text{GHASH}(X, H) = \sum_{j=1}^n X_j H^{n-j+1}$.

1: for $i = 1$ to q do

2: $\text{temp}_i \leftarrow X_i$

```

3:   for j = 1 to (n/q) - 1 do
4:       tempi = (tempi × Hq ⊕ Xi+jq)
5:   end for
6: Let q - i + 1 = (a0(i), . . . , alog2(q)(i))2
7:   tempi = tempi × (Ha0(i)q × H2 × . . . × Ha(i)log2(q))
8:   end for
9: GHASH(X, H) = Σqi-1 tempi
10: return GHASH(X, H).
    
```

In Algorithm1, the output GHASH(X,H) is obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & X_1 \cdot H^q \times \dots \times H^q \oplus X_2 \cdot H^q \times \dots \times H^q \times H^{q-1} \oplus \dots \\
 & \oplus X_j \cdot H^q \times \dots \times H^q \times H^{q-j+1} \oplus \dots \\
 & \oplus X_q \cdot H^q \times \dots \times H^q \dots \oplus X_n H, \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where all operations are performed over GF(2¹²⁸) constructed by the irreducible polynomial P(x) = x¹²⁸ + x⁷ + x² + x + 1 and ⊕ comprises 128 XOR gates.

One can re-write (1) so that only the exponentiations of the hash subkey to the powers of 2 in the form of H^{2ⁱ} are utilized. This method of exponentiation is based on the binary exponentiation. As seen from this algorithm, for the exponentiations H^{q-i+1}, 1 ≤ i ≤ q, one can use the binary representation of q - i + 1 as (a₀⁽ⁱ⁾, . . . , a_{log₂(q)⁽ⁱ⁾})₂. The hardware implementation of Algorithm 1 has been presented in Fig. 4.1. For implementing Algorithm 1 in hardware, in total, (n/q) + log₂(q) clock cycles are needed. For the first (n/q) - 1 clock cycles, the GF (2¹²⁸) multiplications by H^q are performed. This is achieved by a simple control unit selecting H^q. Then, for the next log₂(q) clock cycles, the other exponentiations are used. These include the powers of the hash subkey in the form of H^{2ⁱ} and a number of field elements 1 = (0, 0... 1) ∈ GF (2¹²⁸) for bypassing the GF (2¹²⁸) multiplication operations. We note that if n is not a multiple of q, one need to add q - mod (n, q) blocks containing 0 = (0, 0... 0) ∈ GF (2¹²⁸) to the beginning of the n blocks to

make the total blocks processed multiple of q. Performing this, the hash computation can be done normally based on the presented procedure. Finally, in one clock cycle, the result becomes Σ^{n_j-1} X_jH^{n-j+1}.

Figure 5. The hardware architecture of the proposed high performance GCM GHASH_H function

GF (2¹²⁸) Multipliers for the GCM - Different types of GF (2¹²⁸) multipliers are utilized in the literature for implementing the GF (2¹²⁸) multiplications in (1). The multiplications have been performed using bit-parallel, digit-serial, and hybrid multipliers in composite fields. The efficiency of different multipliers, including the sub-quadratic ones, are compared. A high-speed AES-GCM core has been presented. It is noted that the considered GF (2¹²⁸) multipliers in these works include the Mastrovito multiplier with quadratic space complexity, the Karatsuba-Ofman multiplier and the GF (2¹²⁸) multiplier. We have considered the bit-parallel GF (2¹²⁸) multiplier which has quadratic hardware complexity. It is noted that this GF (2¹²⁸) multiplier has lower timing complexity compared to the sub-quadratic hardware complexity GF (2¹²⁸) multipliers. However, we note that according to the latency of the proposed architectures, i.e., (n/q) + log₂(q), increasing the number of parallel structures (q) results in having higher throughputs. Fig.5 presents the proposed architecture for the AESGCM for q = 8 parallel structures. The AES-128 pipeline registers are shown by dashed lines in Fig. 4.5. As seen in this figure, 10 clock cycles are needed for obtaining the cipher text. After these first 10 clock cycles, the results are obtained after each clock cycle. According to Fig. 5, 8

parallel AES-128 structures are implemented as part of $GCTR_K$ to provide inputs to $GHASH_H$. As seen in this figure, the function $GCTR_K$ performs the AES counter mode with the Initial Counter Block (ICB) and its one-increments (CBi). Moreover, $q = 8$ increments (using INC 8 module) and the plaintext blocks (P_i) are used as the inputs. It is assumed that the data is encrypted and the IV in the GCM is 96 bits which is recommended for high throughput implementation

Figure 6. The proposed AES-GCM high-performance architecture for $q = 8$ ($\text{mod}(n, q) = 0$).

The architecture shown in Fig. 5 assumes that the number of blocks n is a multiple of the number of parallel structures q and there is no additional authenticated data (AAD). In case that n is not a multiple of q , one can append $q - \text{mod}(n, q)$ zero blocks at the beginning of the blocks for which hash is computed. This is done by adding a masking gate along the dotted line as shown in Fig. 4.5. Moreover, in this case, the counter blocks and accordingly P_i 's in Fig. 5 start from the $q - \text{mod}(n, q) + 1$ column, i.e., the first actual input block. We also note that in case AAD is present, additional multiplexers are placed at the output of the GCTR block in Fig. 4.5 along the dotted line so that instead of encrypted data, the AAD is fed to the architecture. When the AAD is done, the counter blocks provide the encrypted data. Finally, in Fig. 5 and as the last processed block, the output of the

GCTR block in the rightmost column is masked and L_A, c (number for n) is fed (using an extra multiplexer which is not shown in Fig. 5 for the sake of brevity). $AES_K(J_0)$ and $H = AES_K(0)$ can be also obtained or pre-computed in Fig. 5. The results of our synthesis for the AES-GCM using the FPGA Vertex Xilinx tool are shown in the results. The synthesis are based on the case for $q = 8$ parallel addition-multiplications using the bit-parallel GF (2^{128}) multiplier which has quadratic hardware complexity. For achieving low hardware complexity for the AES-GCM, we have also synthesized six different steps for the Karatsuba-Ofman multipliers.

Figure 7(a) Cascade, (b) parallel, and (c) hybrid realization methods for hashSub key exponentiations

IV. GCM-AES BLOCK SPECIFICATION

GCM-AES (Galois Counter Mode – Advanced Encryption Standard) is an authenticated encryption mode designed by David McGrew and John Viega. This aims to explore hardware implementation of GCM-AES mode of operation specifically targeting FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Arrays). The aim of such an implementation is to benchmark GCM-AES on FPGA in terms of area, power and speed. GCM-AES has been implemented as a full duplex block which means that the design consists of separate encryption-authentication and decryption-verification blocks. Thus, it can carry out encryption-authentication and decryption-verification operations simultaneously.

Encryption and Authentication Block

- GCM-AES encryption block works on one single frame (Message + AAD) at any given time. A frame consists of one or more AAD blocks or zero or more message blocks. Specifically, the

encryption block works on one message block or AAD block at any time.

- The default block length is 128 bits.
- A single control word starts the operation of GCM-AES encryption block with the Setup phase. This phase is done once per frame. After twenty clock cycles of latency incurred from the setup phase, the encryption block is ready to accept a message or AAD block.
- The encryption block expects one or more AAD blocks where the last AAD's block length need not be 128 bits. It should however be a multiple of a byte. Similarly, the encryption block expects zero or more message blocks where the last message block length need not be the default block length. It should as well be a multiple of a byte.
- The design requires one or more AAD blocks to be input first and then zero or more plain text blocks.
- The current implementation is capable of handling any message or AAD blocks per frame. It takes 10 clock cycles to encrypt a message block (default block length or less than that) with 10 cycle AES-128 implementation when the corresponding encrypted cipher text is produced. The GCM-AES encryption block relies on AES-128 encryption block for encryption and Galois Field multiplication for authentication. Galois Field Multiplier used in this implementation produces result in 8 clock cycles. Cipher text is not produced in case of AAD block.
- The length of the frame does not need to be known by the encryption block. The encryption block works on a frame with the following format:

Figure 7. The AES-128 structure for (a) simple loop, (b) unrolled pipelined, and (c) unrolled sub-pipelined architectures

Decryption and Verification Block

- 1 The GCM-AES decryption block is similar to GCM-AES encryption block. Thanks to Counter Mode. Tag calculation is exactly the same as GCM-AES encryption. The computed tag is compared against the provided tag. If the tags match, decrypted plain texts are considered valid.
- 2 The GCM-AES decryption block works on the similar frame format as GCM-AES encryption block where now Message Blocks are replaced by zero or more Cipher text blocks.

GCM-AES Encryption and Authentication

Figure 8 Interface diagram GCM-AES Encryption block

GCM-AES design as described is coded in Verilog hardware descriptive language HDL. All simulations are done in Modelsim-Altera 6.5e (Quartus II 10.0sp1) Starter Edition Modelsim. XILINX ISE 9.2 is used for FPGA design flow using VirtexE technology (Family = VirtexE, Device = XCv400e, Package = bg560, Speed = -8).

V. RESULTS

We used test case for GCM-AES Encryption-Auth simulations. It is reproduced here for convenience

K = feffe9928665731c6d6a8f9467308308

P = d9313225f88406e5a55909c5aff5269a

86a7a9531534f7da2e4c303d8a318a72

1c3c0c95956809532fcf0e2449a6b525

b16aedf5aa0de657ba637b39A

AAD= feedfacedeadbeeffeedfacedeadbeefabaddad2

IV = cafebabefacedbaddecaf888

The corresponding cipher text and Tag is

CT = 42831ec2217774244b7221b784d0d49c

e3aa212f2c02a4e035c17e2329aca12e

21d514b25466931c7d8f6a5aac84aa05
1ba30b396a0aac973d58e091

All simulations are done in Mentor Graphic's Modelsim. The design is mapped to FPGA belonging to VirtexE technology (Family = VirtexE, Device = XCv400e, Package = bg560, Speed = -8). Synthesis is performed by using Xilinx Synthesis Tool (XST).

Figure 8 Simulation of GCM-AES Enc-Auth block

Figure 8 shows simulation of GCM-AES Encryption-Authentication block. Decryption-Verify block is exactly the same. Thus, only simulation of Encryption-Authentication block suffices.

The synthesis report generated is shown below.

Figure 9 Synthesis report of GCM-AES Enc-Auth block

Figure 10 Floor plan design of GCM-AES Enc-Auth block

Figure 11 FPGA Schematic of GCM-AES Enc-Auth block

Table 1 Description of GCM-AES Encryption block

dii_data dii stands for data input interface.	Input	128	Data input that is either Nonce, message or AAD block
dii_data_vld	Input	1	When asserted (=1), dii_data contains either message or AAD block
dii_data_type	Input	1	When asserted, dii_data contains AAD block. When deasserted (=0), dii_data contains message block
dii_data_size	Input	4	Describes the size of valid dii_data. It ranges from 0-15 where 0 indicates valid message consists of 1 byte in the LSB of dii_data and 15 indicate full block length. Its value may change from 15 on the last message or AAD block
dii_data_last_word	Input	1	When asserted, dii_data contains the last message or AAD block
dii_data_not_ready	Output	1	It is asserted by the GCM-AES indicating that it currently in the Setup phase or working with one message or AAD block and cannot accept an additional message or AAD block.
cii_ctl_vld cii stands for control input interface	Input	1	When asserted, starts the execution of GCM-AES encryption block and triggers Setup phase
cii_IV_vld	Input	1	When asserted, dii_data contains IV value
cii_K	Input	128	It contains secret key used in GCM-AES block
Out_data	Output	128	It contains either the cipher text or Tag_data
Out_vld	Output	1	When asserted, it indicates Out_data contains cipher text
Out_data_size	Output	4	It describes the number valid bytes in Out_data
Out_last_word	Output	1	It describes whether the cipher text is the last cipher text
Tag_vld	Output	1	When asserted, Out_data contains Tag data.

PIN	Direction	Size (bits)	Description
clk	Input	1	Design clock
reset	Input	1	Design reset

VI CONCLUSION and FUTURE SCENARIO

In this project, we have obtained optimized building blocks for the AES-GCM to propose efficient and high performance architectures. For the AES, through logic gate minimizations for the inversion in GF (2⁴), the areas of the S-boxes have been reduced. We have also evaluated and compared the performance of different S-boxes using Xilinx tool. Furthermore, through exhaustive searches for the input patterns,

Message length in Bytes
AAD length in Bytes
Key
Nonce
Message Block 1
Message Block 2
:
Message Block N
AAD Block 1
AAD Block 2
:
AAD Block M

We have performed simulation-based results using modelsim tool for different S-boxes to reach more accurate results compared to the statistical methods. We have also proposed high-performance and efficient architectures for the GCM. For the case study of $q = 8$ parallel structures in GHASH_H, we have performed a hardware complexity reduction technique for the hash subkey exponentiations, having their timing complexities intact. Based on the available resources and performance goals to achieve, one can choose the proposed AES-GCM architectures to fulfill the constraints of different applications.

In future the performance of the proposed efficient architectures for the AES-GCM and their fault detection approaches can be benchmarked using application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) and field-programmable gate array (FPGA) hardware platforms. Larger devices can be chosen to have enough number of slices needed. Another future work for the FPGA platform can be explored noting that the AES is utilized for bit stream security mechanisms. Specifically, the AES decryption is hardware-implemented in many recent FPGAs. Incorporating the proposed hardware countermeasures and evaluating their effectiveness in counteracting internal/malicious faults on FPGAs would be an interesting future research topic. Finally, one can work on devising reliable architectures for the recently standardized GCM, which provides data authentication to block ciphers such as the AES. To the best of my knowledge, the aforementioned

research on reliability of these architectures will be carried out for the first time.

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Energy Efficient Reversible logic Design for Code Converters

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a new 3×3 reversible logic gates for application in optimized code converters. An optimum reversible logic design for different code converters such as BCD to Excess-3, Excess-3 to BCD, Binary to Gray and Gray to Binary is achieved by using the proposed reversible logic gates. It was shown that the proposed design leads to the reduction of power consumption compared with conventional logic circuits. This optimization is achieved by minimizing number of logic gates, garbage values and input constants.

Keywords- code converters; garbage values; reversible logic gates;

1. INTRODUCTION

Power consumption plays a significant role in the present day VLSI technology. So energy efficiency has become main concern in the portable equipments to get better performance with less power dissipation [1]. Reversible logic has received significant attention in recent years to achieve optimum power consumption [2]. Reversible computing is a model of computing where the computational process to some extent is reversible, i.e., time-invertible. In a computational model that uses transitions from one state of the abstract machine to another, a necessary condition for reversibility is that the relation of the mapping from states to their successors must be one-to-one. Reversible computing is generally considered an unconventional form of computing. Broadly, there are two different levels of reversible computing: Logically reversible computing means computing in such a way that it always remains possible to efficiently reconstruct the previous state of the computation from the current state. Doing this enables thermodynamically reversible computing which generates no (or very little) new physical entropy, and is thus energy efficient [2].

Recently, in [3-4], reversible logic gates and reversible circuits for realizing different code converters like BCD to Excess-3, Excess-3 to BCD, Binary to Gray and Gray to Binary was proposed and it was shown that the proposed design leads to the reduction of power

consumption compared with conventional logic circuits, the design proposed was implemented with Feynman gate (FG) and URG gates described in [4].

In this paper, new reversible logic gates for optimization of power consumption are proposed and designed. This optimization of power is obtained by minimizing number of garbage values, input constants and finally number of logic gates. Further, reversible code converters for binary to gray, gray to binary, BCD to excess-3 and excess-3 to BCD with proposed reversible logic gates are implemented and compared with earlier designs [4].

2. Proposed Reversible Logic Gates

Basic concepts of reversible logic gates and various reversible logic gates proposed are discussed in this section. An $n \times n$ reversible gate can be represented as [4]

$$\begin{aligned} IV &= (A, B, C, \dots) \\ OV &= (P, Q, R, \dots) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where IV and OV are input and output vectors. truth tables of proposed gates are listed in Table I to Table V.

I. TRUTH TABLE OF NG1 GATE

Inputs			Outputs		
A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	1
0	1	1	0	1	0
1	0	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	1	0
1	1	0	1	0	0
1	1	1	1	0	1

II. TRUTH TABLE OF NG2 GATE

Inputs			Outputs		
A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	1
0	1	1	0	1	0
1	0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	1	0	0
1	1	0	1	1	0
1	1	1	1	1	1

III. TRUTH TABLE OF NG3 GATE

Inputs			Outputs		
A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	1
0	1	1	0	1	0
1	0	0	1	1	0
1	0	1	1	0	1
1	1	0	1	0	0
1	1	1	1	0	0

IV. TRUTH TABLE OF NG4 GATE

Inputs			Outputs		
A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0
0	1	0	0	1	1
0	1	1	0	1	0
1	0	0	1	1	1

Inputs			Outputs		
A	B	C	P	Q	R
1	0	1	1	1	0
1	1	0	1	0	0
1	1	1	1	0	1

V. TRUTH TABLE OF NG5 GATE

Inputs			Outputs		
A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	1	1
0	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	0	1
1	0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	1	1	0
1	1	0	1	0	0
1	1	1	1	1	1

Existing reversible gates and proposed reversible logic gates are listed in Table VII and VIII respectively (shown at the end of the paper).

Few frequently used codes in digital systems are Binary, Binary Coded Decimal, Excess-3, Gray, ASCII etc. A code converter can be implemented by using a circuitry of AND, OR and NOT gates. In the following section few code converters are designed and implemented using the reversible logic gates described in Table I and II.

3. Reversible Binary to Gray and Gray to Binary Converter

Fig. 1 and 2 shows the circuit diagrams of reverse Binary to Gray and Gray to Binary code converter respectively. Here 'G' represents the garbage value. In the designing of Binary to Gray Code Converter one garbage value is generated, no. of input constants is zero and no. of reversible logic gates required is two. Thus with the proposed reversible gates a Gray to Binary Code Converter can be developed in such a way that the no. of input constants and generated garbage values are zero and no. of gates used is two.

Further, the no. of input constants, garbage values generated and no. of reversible logic gates are used to implement these code converters are less when compared to the conventional reversible logic gates [4-5].

Figure1: Circuit diagram of Reversible Binary to Gray Code Converter.

Figure2: Circuit diagram of Reversible Gray to Binary Code Converter.

4. Reversible BCD to Excess-3 and Excess-3 to BCD Converter

Fig. 2 (a) and (b) shows the circuit diagrams of Reverse BCD to Excess-3 and Excess-3 to BCD converter respectively. In designing of BCD to Excess-3 code converter ten garbage values are generated, no. of input constants is three and no. of reversible logic gates required is six. Thus with the proposed reversible gates a Excess-3 to BCD Code Converter is designed in such a way that the no. of input constants is three, generated garbage values are seven and no. of gates used is five.

Further, the no. of input constants, garbage values generated and no. of reversible logic gates are used to implement these code converters are less when compared to the previous designs [4-5].

Figure3: Circuit diagram of Reversible BCD to Excess-3 Code Converter.

Figure4: Circuit diagram of Reversible Excess-3 to BCD Code Converter.

5. Performance Analysis

The performance of the design is based on the number of gates, number of garbage (unused terminals) values and number of constants. Table IX provides a summary of the proposed design. It is observed from Table IX that the proposed design achieves optimization by minimizing the number of gates, garbage values and input constants when compared to earlier designs described in [4-5].

VI. PROPOSED DESIGN

Reversible Code Converters	No. of gates	No. of garbage values	No. of input constants
Binary to Gray	2	1	0
Gray to Binary	2	0	0
BCD to Excess-3	6	10	3
Excess-3 to BCD	5	7	3

VII. EXISTING REVERSIBLE LOGIC GATES

Gate	Diagrammatic representation	Inputs	Outputs
Feynman Gate		A, B	P, Q $P = A$ $Q = A \oplus B$
Toffoli Gate		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = B$ $R = AB \oplus C$
Fredkin Gate		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = A'B \oplus AC$ $R = A'C \oplus AB$
Peres Gate		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = A \oplus B$ $R = AB \oplus C$
URG Gate		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = C \oplus AB$ $Q = B$ $R = C \oplus (A + B)$
HNG Gate		A, B, C, D	P, Q, R, S $P = A$ $Q = B$ $R = A \oplus B \oplus C$ $S = (A \oplus B)C \oplus AB \oplus D$

VIII. PROPOSED REVERSIBLE LOGIC GATES

Gate	Diagrammatic representation	Inputs	Outputs
NG1		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = A \oplus B$ $R = A \oplus B \oplus C$

Gate	Diagrammatic representation	Inputs	Outputs
NG2		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = B$ $R = A \oplus B \oplus C$
NG3		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = A \oplus B$ $R = B \oplus C$
NG4		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = A \oplus B$ $R = \overline{AB \oplus C}$
NG5		A, B, C	P, Q, R $P = A$ $Q = A' B \oplus C$ $R = AB' \oplus C$

6. Concluding Remarks

New reversible logic gates were proposed in this paper and reversible circuits for realizing different code converters like Binary to Gray, Gray to Binary, BCD to Excess-3 and Excess-3 to BCD were analyzed. The proposed design is optimum in terms of the reduction of power consumption compared with previous logic circuits, i.e., the proposed design increases the energy efficiency by minimizing no. of gates, garbage values and input constants.

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A Robust Channel Estimation for SCFDMA System

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a robust technique is proposed for a single carrier frequency division multiple access system channel estimation in flat- fading non- Gaussian channels. Further, A new M-estimator is proposed for the robustification of the proposed detector. Simulation results are also provided to demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed detector over the least squares, Huber and Hampel based detectors in flat- fading non- Gaussian channels.

Keywords: Channel estimation, Fading channels, M-estimator, SC-FDMA.

I. INTRODUCTION

I. INTRODUCTION

Wide demand on high data rates in wireless communication systems has arisen in order to support broadband services. The Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Long Term Evolution (LTE) radio access standard provides peak data rates of 75 Mb/s on the uplink and 300 Mb/s on the downlink. In LTE standard orthogonal frequency-division multiple accesses (OFDMA) is used on the downlink. This supports different carrier bandwidths (1.25–20 MHz) in both frequency-division duplex (FDD) and time-division duplex (TDD) modes. In OFDMA each user is provided with a unique fraction of the system bandwidth. OFDMA combines scalability, multipath robustness, multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) compatibility [1], thereby making it adaptive for wideband wireless accessibility.

OFDMA, being sensitive to frequency offset and phase noise, accurate frequency and phase synchronization is needed. In addition, OFDMA is characterized by a high transmit PAPR, and for a given peak power limited amplifier this results in a lower mean transmit level. For these reasons, OFDMA is not well suited to the uplink

transmission. Hence, LTE proposed, single carrier FDMA (SC-FDMA), also known as discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) pre coded OFDMA, for the uplink. PAPR reduction in SCFDMA is motivated by a desire to increase the mean transmit power, improve the power amplifier efficiency, increase the data rate, and reduce the bit error rate (BER) and energy consumption [4]. SC-FDMA ensures high data rate transmission, utilizing single carrier m frequency domain equalization. In algorithm is proposed for LTE uplink channel impulse response (CIR) knowledge of the channel.

II. CHANNEL MODEL

At the transmitter side, a baseband modulator transmits the binary input to a multilevel sequences of complex numbers $m_1(q)$ in one of several possible modulation formats including binary phase shift keying (BPSK), quaternary PSK (QPSK), 8 level PSK (8-PSK), 16-QAM, and 64-QAM. These modulated symbols perform an N-point discrete Fourier transform (DFT) to produce a frequency domain representation. The DFT followed by IDFT in a distribution-FDMA (DFDMA) or localization-FDMA (LFDMA) subcarrier mapping setup operates as efficient implementation to an interpolation filter. In distributed subcarrier mode, the outputs are allocated equally spaced subcarriers, with zeros

occupying the unused subcarrier in between. While in localized subcarrier mode, the outputs are confined to a continuous spectrum of subcarriers. Except the above two modes, interleaved subcarrier mapping mode of FDMA (IFDMA) is another special subcarrier mapping mode [12], [13]. The difference between DFDMA and IFDMA is that the outputs of IFDMA are allocated over the entire bandwidth, whereas the DFDMA's outputs are allocated every several subcarriers. The response of the wide-sense stationary uncorrelated scattering (WSSUS) fading channel can be represented as

$$w(\tau, t) = \sum_{j=0}^{l-1} w_j(t) \delta(\tau - \tau_j) \quad (1)$$

where fading channel coefficients $w_j(t)$ are the wide sense stationary i.e. $w_j(t) = w(m; j)$, uncorrelated complex Gaussian random paths gains at time instant t with their respective delays τ_j , where $w(m; j)$ is the sample spaced channel response of the l^{th} path during the time k , and $\delta(\bullet)$ is the Dirac delta function. Based on the WSSUS assumption, the fading channel coefficients in different delay taps are statistically independent. And has an autocorrelation function given by

$$E[w(k, j)w^T(n, j)] = \sigma_w^2(j) J_0[2\pi f_d T_f (k - n)] \quad (2)$$

Where $w(n; j)$ is a response of the l^{th} propagation path measured at time n , $\sigma_w^2(J)$ denotes the power of the channel coefficients, f_d is the Doppler frequency in Hz, T_f is the symbol duration in seconds, and $J_0(\bullet)$ is the zero order Bessel function of the first kind(4).

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The signal $s(k)$ is transmitted via a time-varying channel $w(k)$, and corrupted by an observation noise $n(m)$ before being detected in a receiver. The signal received at time index k is

$$\begin{aligned} r(k) &= s_1(k-1)w_1(m) + \dots + s_l(k-l)w_l(k) + n(k) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^l s_j(k-j)w_j + n(k) \\ &= S^T(k)W(k) + n(k) \end{aligned}$$

Where $s_j(k-j)$, $j=1,2,\dots,l$ are transmitted signal vectors at time m , l is the distinct paths from transmitter to the receiver, $w(m)$ is the channel coefficients at time m , and $n(k)$ is the noise with zero mean and variance σ^2 . After processing some intermediate steps (synchronization, remove CP, DFT, and de mapping), the decision block reconstructs the detected signal to an approximate modulated signal and its phase. The output $y(k)$ of the adaptive filter is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} y(k) &= d_1(k-1)h_1(k) + \dots + d_l(k-l)h_l(m) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^l d_j(k-j)h_j(k) \\ &= D^T(k)h(k) \end{aligned}$$

Where $d_j(k-j)$, $j=1,2,\dots,l$ are detected signal vectors at time

$$k \dots D(k) = \text{diag}[d_1(k-1), d_2(k-2), \dots, d_l(k-l)]$$

In this problem formulation, the ideal adaptation procedure would adjust $w_j(k)$ such that $w_j(k)=h_j(k)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. In practice, the adaptive filter can only adjust $w(k)$ such that $y(k)$ closely approximates desired signal over time. Therefore, the instantaneous estimated error signal needed to update the weights of the adaptive filter is

$$\begin{aligned} j(k) &= p(k)e^T(k)e(k) \\ e(k) &= r(k) - y(k) \\ &= r(k) - D^T(k)h(k) \end{aligned}$$

This priori error signal, $e(k)$ is used to minimize the estimator error by adaptive updating of filter weights. $w(i) = [w_0(i), \dots, w_{N-1}(i)]^T$ is the channel noise vector during the i^{th} symbol interval. $w(i)$ are assumed to be independent and identically distributed random variables with non-Gaussian distribution.[]

$$(1 - \varepsilon)f(0, \sigma_1^2) + \varepsilon f(0, \sigma_2^2) \quad (12)$$

Several different classes of robust methods (such as M, L, R estimators, and the least median of squares method) exist [7-9]. In this paper, M-estimator based robust clustering technique is proposed. The M-estimators try to reduce the effect of outliers by

Fig. 2 Probability of error versus SNR for the considered detectors in Gaussian noise.

Fig. 3 Probability of error versus SNR for the considered detectors in non-Gaussian noise.

Fig. 4 Probability of error versus SNR for the considered detectors in non-Gaussian noise.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a robust detection technique is proposed to estimate channel parameters when the

signal is corrupted with non-Gaussian noise. A new M-estimator is proposed. Simulation results are also provided. These simulation results prove that the proposed detector outperforms Least Squares, Huber and Hampel based detectors in non-Gaussian flat-fading channels.

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Intelligent Gesture Controlled Robot

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ABSTRACT

Today human machine interaction is moving away from mouse and pen and is becoming pervasive and much more compatible with the physical world. With each passing day the gap between machines and humans is being reduced with the introduction of new technologies to ease the standard of living. Gestures have played a vital role in diminishing this abyss Robots of the future should communicate with humans in a natural way. Hence, we are especially interested in hand motion based gesture interfaces. The purpose of this study was to present a reliable means for human-computer interfacing based on hand gestures made in three dimensions, which could be interpreted and adequately used in controlling a remote robot's movement. In this paper we discuss the development of a novel architecture of an intelligent robot working on hand gesture control and not by the usual method of keypad. The locomotion of the robot is controlled by a MCU (microcontroller Unit).

Keywords –gesture control, Accelerometer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans are anxiously working on finding new ways of interacting with machines. However, a major breakthrough was observed when gestures were used for this interaction. A gesture is a form of non verbal communication in which visible bodily actions communicate particular messages. It comprises of sound, light variation or any type of body movement. Based upon the type of gestures, they have been captured via Acoustic (sound), Tactile (touch), Optical (light), Bionic and Motion Technologies through still camera, data glove, Bluetooth, infrared beams etc. Motion Technology has succeeded in drawing the attention of researchers from different parts of the world. The accelerometer circuit can be freely rotated in space, temporarily varying 3-dimensional signal data is obtained from the 3-axis acceleration sensor. This data is transmitted to a robot via Im324 Module. Further, it is processed by a microcontroller embedded on the robot for its desirable motions. In these contexts, a robot is an analogy for any machine that is controlled by man varying from a simple toy to heavy machinery.

Robots have even replaced humans in performing various tasks that they are unable to perform due to physical disability, size limitation or extreme environments.

II. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The present structure of the project involves the method of controlling the robot using hand gestures as commands. The control of the locomotion of the wheelchair is presently done by microcontroller (MCU-8 Prototyping Platform). The following block diagram shows how the entire system works using the hand gesture method.

Fig: Block diagram for the hand gesture method of control

As we can see from the above block diagram the robot works on the hand gestures. The MCU-8 prototyping platform is an open source prototyping platform which runs on embedded C structure. The platform is extremely powerful and easy to use with several inbuilt functions and a powerful microcontroller. Atmel 89s52 which is an 8-bit CISC-based microcontroller. It combines 8 KB of ISP flash memory with read-while-write capabilities, 32 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, serial programmable USART, three timer/counters, internal and external interrupts, SPI serial port, programmable timer with internal oscillator, and five software selectable power saving modes.

HAND GESTURE MODULE

The hand gesture module has been prepared by using a triple axis accelerometer sensor (ADXL 335). The relatively low cost sensor provides the data

Block diagram of Accelerometer sensor to Microcontroller module

for the orientation of the hand and therefore helps in recognizing the gestures. The accelerometer sensor senses the accelerating force (acceleration due to gravity org) and thus gives a particular voltage for the x, y and z coordinate orientation. The data can be observed in integer format through the serial port of MCU on the computer's serial monitor and accordingly the orientations of the hand can be sorted out. The basic working block diagram of the accelerometer sensor:

Hand Position	Direction of Motion	Thresholded values of ADXL335
	Forward	$x \geq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \leq -1230 \ \& \ z \geq 1295$
	Right	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \leq -1230 \ \& \ z \geq 1295$
	Left	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \geq 280$ $\& \ z \leq -1230 \ \& \ z \geq 1295$
	Back	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \leq 230$
	Stop	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \geq 295$

Table of accelerometer threshold values for different hand orientation

The accelerometer sensor has specific values which are read as analog inputs by the microcontroller. The data obtained from the accelerometer for the various orientations of the hand gave us the readings to decide the threshold value for each x, y and z coordinate reading:

LOCOMOTION

For the locomotion of the robot we have used general DC motors as part of the model for the project. The motors are controlled by the bidirectional motor driver IC – L293D. The motor driver is connected through the microcontroller on the robot which sends the signal to the driver for the various conditions. For smooth turning during the motion of the robot we have used the method of PWM. The Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) allows the microcontroller to send the power to the motor driver in small packets over high frequency. The constant ON and OFF states actually helps to conduct smooth turning motion. The following figure shows an example graph of the PWM duty cycles for varying efficiency output supplies:

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All the components after integration give us the working skeleton model for the robot. The robot model works perfectly according to the hand gestures. The various gestures were tested and the outputs were studied to check if the right codes were transmitted. Therefore the project is seen to be working successfully with an artificial human-machine interaction system.

IV. APPLICATIONS

Through the use of gesture recognition, remote control with the wave of a hand of various devices is possible. Gesture controlling is very helpful for handicapped and physically disabled people to achieve certain tasks, such as driving a vehicle. Gestures can be used to control interactions for entertainment purposes such as gaming to make the game player's experience more interactive or immersive.

V. CONCLUSION

Enormous amount of work has been done on gesture controlling of robots. In this paper, various methodologies have been analyzed and reviewed with their merits and demerits under various operational and functional strategies. Thus, it can be concluded that features like user friendly interface, light weight and portability has overtaken the sophistication of technologies like programmable glove etc., making them obsolete. Although recent researches in this field have made wireless gesture controlling a ubiquitous phenomenon, it needs to acquire more focus in relevant areas of applications like home appliances, wheelchairs, artificial nurses, table top screens etc. in a collaborative manner.

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Visual based an Intelligent Robotic Control System using ARM7 Microcontroller

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present application field of service robots i.e., to interacting of two sensor systems to control of a robot one proposed system consists of acoustic sensor the function of this sensor is to receive and identifies or acknowledged the oral commands and other one is sensor of visual type that receives and identifies the commands (i.e., instructions) based on the Mexican sign language. According to the simulation either visually or acoustically the multimodal interface of the robot is able to find the weight of each sensors contribution to perform a particular task. By observing the sensor system separately based on an oral commands and sight indications. The capability of a machine was found to be approximately 85.35% and observed 90% task finishing for the systems in several types.

1. INTRODUCTION

From its beginnings, robotics has been an important assistive technology for the human being, making possible the existence of constant production lines with minimum error rates for the realization of repetitive tasks. This is an example of industrial robots, which although they provide a service to the human being, cannot be classified as service robots. According to the International Federation of Robotics (IFR) [1] a service robot is defined as: a robot that works autonomously either partially or totally, and that performs useful services for the well being of humans and equipments. These robots can have mobility and the capacity to manipulate objects.

Thus, the application field of service robots can be classified in:

- Applications of service for human beings (personal protection and assistance of handicapped people, etc.).
- Applications of service for equipments (maintenance, repairs, cleaning, etc.).
- Other autonomous tasks (surveillance, transportation, inspection, etc.).

The autonomy capacity required for such systems is obtained by means of a control system able to interact with the environment of application. To accomplish this, the system must have sensors to perceive the events that occur in the environment, and actuators/mechanisms to react and realize modifications to it.

This work is focused in developing tasks of service robotics for the human being, looking for the robotic system to be controlled by means of natural language represented in acoustic form (speech) and visual form (signs). Hence, the service robot must interpret visual and acoustic commands to perform a task. The tasks to be performed are considered to be simple in order to be arranged in sequences to accomplish more complex tasks such as to "serve a glass with water" and "take it to" a particular work space or person.

Our advances towards this system are presented in this paper, which is structured as follows: in Section II a review of related studies to this problem is presented, while in Section III the details of the design of the visual and acoustic sensor systems are presented; in Section IV are presented the design details of the integrated multimodal system, whose results are presented and discussed in Section V; finally in Section VI we present our conclusions and future work.

2. Research review

Communication between humans is performed by means of voice and gestures. Unfortunately, robots cannot understand these human natural languages. Thus, a mechanism is necessary for the robot to understand these languages as a human does. To accomplish this, many research projects have been developed to perform communication between humans and robots. Among those projects we can mention to Posada-Gomez et al. [2] that controlled a wheelchair with hand signals. Such equipment has also been controlled by Hashimoto et al. [3] by tracking other signals such as ocular movements, while Alcubierre et al. [4] used spoken commands.

A project more related to the focus of our work is presented by Bohme et al. [5] that developed the multimodal control of a service robot for a shop. This robot was used as an informative kiosk which was able to locate a user by processing audio signals in addition to perceived visual information. On the other hand there are developments for companion robots (i.e., Aibo, Robosapien, etc.). In this field we can mention to Weitzenfeld et al. [6] that controlled a group of Aibo robots to play football by means of spoken commands and visual feedback.

The list of examples can be very extensive, and thus, we comment on two last projects that use acoustic and visual information for multimodal interaction: (1) the Golem robot [7], developed at the Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico (UNAM), which is able to receive complex spoken instructions and establish a dialog with a user based on that information; and (2) Rackham [8], which was developed at the Laboratoire d'Analyse et d'Architectures des Systemes (LAAS) in France. Rackham receives spoken commands to guide visitors towards the different areas of a museum.

3. Sensor systems

3.1 Signs recognition system

In order to develop in a satisfactory manner the sign recognition system, this was developed in different stages: imaging, segmentation, obtaining the descriptor form, learning patterns by the neural network and recognition. Relation among these stages is shown in the flowchart of Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Structure of the sign recognition system.

In the paragraphs below we will briefly explain each of the stages mentioned above.

© Obtaining images

In Fig. 2 the 23 symbols that were used, from the 27 that comprise the alphabet of the MSL, are presented. We choose those whose shape was different from each other and image sequences were not considered.

Figure 2. The 23 symbols of the MSL alphabet.

The images of the signs were taken using a uniform background. Additionally, the user wore a garment that let uncover only the hand in order to avoid interference by objects in the wrist (watch, bracelets, etc.). This ensured that the region of interest to be processed belonged only to the hand.

We used four different sets similar to that shown in Where c is a constant and x is the parameter to be varied to obtain different intensities in the image that is being processed. The parameter x was varied in a random way in order to obtain different light variation for the input image. In evaluating Eq. (1) we have that, if $x < 1$, the image is darker, and if $x > 1$, is bright (see Fig. 3).

© Segmentation

The first step in the realization of the sign recognition system was the image segmentation by active contours [9]. These contours shape the boundaries between the object, background and other objects in the image. Also allow extraction of the contours of the objects of interest based on models that use a priori information on the shape of objects. These techniques are much more robust to the presence of noise, and allow more complex image segmentation. In this paper, snakes were used to perform segmentation (segmentation by region [10]).

Figure 3. Examples for several power settings.

In Fig. 4 an example is presented of the different transitions of the snake for the image of MSL symbol representing the letter "y".

Figure 4. Different snake transitions (a) initial snake and (d) final contour (e) contour of sign.

© Descriptor

Since the snake as result gives us the edge of the object, the shape signature [11] was used as descriptor. In our

Fig. 2, each with a different background. These four image sets served to create a database of images by varying their parameters using a photometric filter. The used filter was a power function of the form shown in Eq. 1.

$$f(x) = cex \quad 0.9 \leq x \leq 1.1 \quad (1)$$

case, the object is the shape of the hand with one sign of the MSL alphabet (Fig. 4).

The signature of the object is done by calculating the distances from the object's center of gravity to each one of the points that form the boundary. This yields a histogram of distances as shown in Fig. 5 which is the histogram contour for the symbol shown in Fig. 4(e). This histogram consisted of 360 different values which was the input vector for training the neural network.

© Neural network: learning

We used a neural network composed of three layers with the following configuration: an input layer of 360 neurons, an intermediate layer of 23 neurons, and one neuron in the final layer.

In this case, the input vectors are formed by histograms of the shape signature descriptor. Each input vector is associated with an output label ranging from number 1 to 23. Therefore there is an output of 23 different values, one for each symbol used of the MSL alphabet.

Figure 5. Shape signature of the symbol that represents the letter "y": (a) in the learning phase, (b) in the recognition phase. There are significant differences between both histograms.

Back propagation was used as the network training algorithm due to fast convergence and robustness over other type of training algorithms [12]. Some of the parameters used for this training were: (1) learning rate of 0.01; a maximum of 9000 iterations; and minimum error of 1e-10.

The time it took to the neural network to learn the pattern vectors and their association with 23 patterns goal was 316 seconds.

© Sign Recognition Performance

We tested the neural network before and after training to observe how the recognition of the symbols of the MSL varied. Fig. 6(a) shows the graph which was obtained with initial values for the weights of the neural network. In "circles" are shown the expected values, and in "stars" those obtained from the output of the network by presenting the symbols of the MSL alphabet. After training the system's new graphics were obtained, showing the patterns of Fig. 6(b).

To evaluate the recognition system, a series of different images from those learned by the system were used. By comparing the histograms of learning with the histogram of the symbol to recognize, it was observed some variation while there were many values in the histogram that matched. This makes the neural network to recognize the symbol smoothly as expected.

Recognition tests were performed for all the symbols in the MSL alphabet. The system was tested 30 times for each symbol, and the following was observed:

The symbols that were always properly recognized were those that represented the letters a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, m, n, o, r, u, v, x, y.

- The system confused certain symbols, and the letters l, p, s, and w, were recognized correctly in about 50% of the experiments. The overall recognition rate was 90%.

Figure 6. Neural network output: (a) before training, (b) after training.

It is now common practice to build HMMs at the phonetic level instead of at the word level. A phoneme is a sub-word unit that forms a word, for example, the word HELLO is formed by the sequence of phonemes /hh/, /eh/, /l/, /oh/. A Lexicon, or Phonetic Dictionary, is used in this case to establish the sequence of phonemes that define each word in a vocabulary. In our case, we defined a sequence of phonemes for each word of the control sentences associated to 12 symbols of the MSL (see Table 3). The Transcribe Mex [15] tool was used to define the phoneme sequences for the vocabulary words of the application. Because of limited

3.2 Speech recognition system

The structure of the Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) system is presented in Fig. 7, and each component is explained below.

© Acoustic Models and Lexicon

Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) were used to model the acoustic features of the user's voice. These models were standard three-state left-to-right HMMs with eight Gaussian components per state. The front-end used 12 MFCCs plus energy, delta, and acceleration coefficients [13, 14].

Figure 7. Structure of the speech recognition system.

availability of Mexican speech corpora, we developed a Speaker Dependent (SD) ASR system trained with speech samples from a single speaker. For multi-user purposes, Maximum Likelihood Linear Regression (MLLR) [14] was performed to adapt this system for its use by other users. The training corpora of the SD ASR system consisted of a selection of a short narrative, 16 phonetically balanced sentences, and 30 words with presence of contrast phonemes. This text corpus was uttered 5 times by a male speaker to provide speech corpora, which was labeled at the phonetic and word levels using the software Wave surfer for supervised

training. By using the sequences of phonemes established in our Lexicon we expanded these word labels into their corresponding phoneme labels. The supervised training of the acoustic models was performed by using Baum- Welch re-estimation of the HMMs with the acoustic data and the corresponding phoneme labels.

© *Language Model*

The control sentences were defined for manipulation of objects (robot arm “Cube” tasks) and movement of the platform (robot platform “Bot” tasks). The sentences for manipulation have the following structure: *Device + Task + Object*. Here, *Device* defines the identifier of the robotic element to be controlled (Cube or Bot), *Task* identifies the kind of action to perform over an *Object* (the element to be manipulated). Hence, sentences such as those presented in Fig. 8 were modeled by the grammar.

Figure 8. Sentences for manipulation tasks.

Sentences to control the movement of the platform, or to give more details about the task, had the following structure: *Device + Task + Configuration*.

Figure 9. Sentences for manipulation tasks and settings.

As shown in Fig. 9, Configuration adds parameters to the Task given to the robotic element. In this way, the

grammar allows recognition of simple and more complex commands. We used word bigrams for the Language Model and 32 possible sentences were used for this purpose. Initially we used a vocabulary of 202 different Mexican words to build these sentences. HTK Toolkit [14] was used for language and acoustic modeling, implementation of the search algorithm (i.e., speech recognition function, Viterbi Decoding) and evaluation of performance.

© *Speech Recognition Performance*

Initially the system was tested with the training corpus to verify the accurate modelling of phonemes and stability of the baseline system. The metric of performance was % Word Accuracy (%WAcc) which is defined as:

$$\%WAcc = (N-D-S-I)/N \quad (2)$$

Where *N* is the number of words in the reference (correct) sentences, and *S*, *D* and *I* are the number of words substituted, deleted, and inserted in the recognized sentences. Hence, this measure considers the different kind of errors which can change the meaning of a recognized sentence, compromising the ability of the robot to accomplish the desired task.

As presented in Table 1, the recognizer had a %WAcc of 98.45%, which is consistent with a SD system tested with the corpus used for training. If this metric were lower that would mean that the samples have significant variations in pronunciation and thus the resulting system will not be stable. As we focus on using this recognizer with different users, the SD recognizer alone will not perform efficiently with other users except for the user that provided his voice for the training corpus. The stability of the baseline system allows the use of a speaker adaptation technique to adjust the system to other’s speaker’s voice, and thus, make it multi-user.

Table 1. Performance of the baseline recognizer tested with the training corpus.

N	D	S	I	%Wacc
1418	9	12	1	98.45

Maximum Likelihood Linear Regression (MLLR) was the adaptation technique used for this system, and is based on the assumption that a set of linear transformations can be used to reduce the mismatch between a baseline HMM model set and the speech samples from a different speaker. In this work, these transformations were applied to the mean and variance

parameters of the Gaussian mixtures of the SD HMMs. The adaptation speech consisted in a set of 16 phonetically balanced sentences which were uttered by the user once before starting to use the recognizer. The adapted system was tested using the set of control commands defined for this work (see Table 3) with two users (a male and female student) across ten sessions. In each session, all 12 sentences were read by the test users (thus, there were 120 test sentences for each user), and we recorded the number of instances where %WAcc = 100% as we are interested in precise recognition of commands. As presented in Table 2 the adapted system achieved around 95% of recognition for complete commands.

Table 2. Performance of the adapted recognizer tested with control commands.

User	Fails/Total	% Success
Male Student	4/120	96.67
Female Student	7/120	94.17

4. Multimodal recognition system

The structure of the integrated recognition system is shown in Fig.10. As presented, both recognition systems receive input data where each one processes the signal that was designed to detect. Each recognition block generates an output with a likelihood, which is then weighted jointly with the other’s system to allow mutual help in the decision task to perform an action in case that there is uncertainty. In total, 12 control commands were considered for the bimodal system. These are presented in Table 3.

Figure 10. Multimodal recognition system structure.

Table 3. Control Tasks: * represents composite actions (control of both, the robot’s arm – Cube- and the robot’s platform – Bot).

	MSL Symbol	Action/Task
1	h	BOT MOVE FORWARD QUICKLY TWO METERS
2	a	BOT MOVE BACKWARDS SLOWLY
3	m	BOT TURN NINETY DEGREES TO THE LEFT
4	n	BOT TURN FORTY FIVE DEGREE S TO THE RIGHT
5	u	CUBE SERVE BOTTLE
6	v	CUBE TAKE GLASS
7	o	BOT GO OUT BY DOOR ONE
8	s	BOT GET IN BY DOOR TWO
9	y	BOT SERVE COUP *
10	g	BOT MOVE FORWARD SLOWLY TWO METERS
11	c	CUBE HOME
12	B	BOT STOP *

The recognizers’ outputs can either help to each other (similar decision) or interfere to each other (different decision). Hence, weighting each other’s contribution to the accurate decision task is important. The form in which the system’s weighting is performed to know if they mutually help or interfere to decision taking is as follows:

- Each sensor system votes for a particular action according with the output probability of each recognizer.
- If both systems vote for the same action, then both systems help to each other. However, if both vote for different actions, then both interfere to each other.

Both responses are added together until the system converges towards a unique response. This sum is performed incrementally in time. Thus, the multimodal system delivers an action when such sum is higher than (or equal) to an established limit. In this case, this limit was set to 95%.

In Fig. 11(a) in t_0 all actions have the same occurrence probabilities. This changes in t_1 (Fig. 11(b)) because at this moment the system has already processed some signals (speech, signs) via the recognition system. Thus, the probabilities are modified in function of the probabilities provided by the recognizers. This

continues until the multimodal system converges towards a single action. In case that both systems vote for a different action, the process starts with equal occurrence probabilities for each action defined in Table 3. In t_1 the probabilities are updated and the corresponding probabilities to the voted actions (in this example, 3 and 5), are modified. This is shown in Fig. 11(b), where action 3 has a probability of 65% and action 5 has 85%.

Figure 11. Occurrence probabilities in (a) t_0 , and (b) t_1 .

As shown in Fig. 12, by weighting these probabilities we have an occurrence probability of 20% for the action that initially was higher (in this case, action 5). As it was presented, action 3 influenced in a negative way the action 5, reducing its value. Additionally, the probability of the action 3 is decreased because it affected the other action.

Figure 12. Updated probabilities after weighting.

The probabilities for the other actions are also updated and all are decreased. Because the predominant action's probability does not reach the established limit, the system iterates and requests the user (via speech synthesis) to provide again the control command to validate, or discard, the decoded command. Fig. 13 shows the evolution of the system for actions (a) 5 and (b).

Figure 13. Decision to execute (a) action 5 (u) after 4 iterations, and (b) action 6 (v) after 3 iterations.

5. Performance of the multimodal system

As presented in Table 3, 12 control actions were considered for the service robot. Each action has associated a spoken sentence and a sign of the MSL alphabet as presented in Table 3. To verify that the system performed the desired action, a graphical user interface was designed in Matlab © which processed the probabilities of the acoustic and visual signals to assign weights and generate an output (see Section 4). This implementation allowed the iterative reception and processing of speech signals and visual MSL signs until the multimodal system achieved convergence towards a maximum value over a defined limit. This limit is reached when the weighing was higher or equal to 95%.

Although many tests were performed for each of the actions defined in Table 3, only one of the m is shown. The action used to show the performance of the multimodal interaction is 6 (v) which is equivalent to the command "CUBE TAKE GLASS". In Fig. 13(b), the evolution of the system to perform action 6 (v) is shown. It is observed that the system requires only a few iterations to appropriately weight the probabilities generated by the recognition systems and to decide which action is to be executed. Also, the system converges to action 6 (v) which is the correct result. The implementation of the multimodal interaction system was tested with the simulation software Roboworks © which was developed by the University of Texas. In Fig. 14 is shown the simulation of the action 6(v).

Figure 14. Simulated execution of action 6 (v).

The tests for all control commands were performed 30 times, obtaining a successful completion rate of 95.60%. It is important to mention that lighting affected the segmentation, producing confusions which lead to

failures and delays in obtaining the desired result. However this is part of our future research that is presented in the next section.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper a multimodal system to control a service robot was presented. This system was built with two main blocks to process acoustic and visual commands (speech, signs). The proposed system was validated by means of implementation in a simulation environment. The robot was constituted by a mobile platform – Bot and by a 6 DOF arm – Cube, which as a whole is able to perform easy tasks. The simulation was performed with 12 different tasks, where two of them required coordination of both, the platform and the arm. The multimodal system performed tasks with a completion rate of 95.60 %, which was considered to be robust enough to allow interaction in closed environments. Among the future research and expectations for this work we present the following:

- Implementation of the multimodal system in the real robotic system.
- To use a network of sensor devices to synchronize the received signals.
- To modulate the lighting by using a different scheme to RGB such as the CielAB system.

Implementation of recognition of MSL signs that have movement (i.e., dynamic signs instead of static signs). This would increase the range of applications and tasks to be executed by the service robot.

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A Novel High Performance 64-bit MAC Unit with Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier

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ABSTRACT

A Novel High Performance Design of 64 bit Multiplier-and-Accumulator (MAC) Unit is implemented in this paper by using Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier and Carry Save Adder. MAC unit performs many important Arithmetic and other operations in many of the digital signal processing (DSP) applications. This 64-bit MAC Unit is suitable to use in 64-bit DSP Processors. The Project is coded in Verilog-HDL. The Power Dissipation of entire MAC Unit is 182.312 mW.

Key words— Modified Wallace Multiplier, Carry Save Adder, Multiplier and Accumulator (MAC), Digital Signal Processor (DSP), Verilog-HDL.

I. Introduction

MAC Unit is a common step in many Digital Signal Processing (DSP) applications involving multiplications and/or accumulations. Modern computers have high performance dedicated MAC unit consisting of Multiplier, adder and an accumulator register to store the result [1]. Particularly this MAC Unit is used for high performance digital signal processing systems. Where, the DSP applications include Digital Filtering, Convolution, and Computing of Inner Products. This MAC Unit is Isolated from CPU so that operations such as multiplications and/or additions are done separately, by reducing the CPU Load. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) Operations are performed by MAC Unit because FFT requires addition and/or Multiplication operations [2].

A MAC unit consists of a multiplier, adder and an accumulator containing the sum of the previous successive products. The MAC Unit obtain inputs from the memory location such as RAM and given to the Multiplier. MAC Unit is used in DSP Applications that uses discrete cosine transform (DCT) or discrete wavelet transforms (DWT). Where, Multiplication is accomplished by repetitive application of addition,

the speed of the multiplication and addition arithmetic determines the execution speed and performance of the entire Calculation.

The functionality of the MAC unit enables high-speed filtering and other processing which are typical for DSP applications. Particularly, in applications like optical Communication Systems which is based on DSP, require extremely fast processing of huge amount of digital data.

The Design of MAC Unit in this Paper Consists of 64 bit Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier, 128 bit Carry Save Adder (CSA) and 129 bit Accumulator.

This Paper is divided into Five Sections. In the First section the introduction about MAC unit is discussed. In the Second section the detailed operation of MAC unit is described. The Third section deals with the basic building blocks of MAC Unit. In the Fourth section, Results and Comparisons of various MAC units are given. Finally the Conclusion is made in the Fifth section.

II. MAC UNIT

The Multiplier-Accumulator (MAC) operation is the key operation not only in DSP applications but also in multimedia information processing and various other applications. As mentioned above, MAC unit consist of multiplier, adder and register/accumulator.

In this paper, we used 64 bit modified Wallace multiplier. The MAC Unit take inputs from the memory location such as RAM and given to the multiplier block. This is very useful in 64 bit digital signal processor. The inputs which is being fed from the memory location is 64 bit. When the input is given to the multiplier it starts computing value for the given 64 bit input and hence the output will be 128 bits. The multiplier output is given as the input to carry save adder (CSA) which performs addition. The function of the MAC unit is given by the following equation

$$Y = \sum_{i=0}^{63} A_i \times B_i \quad (1)$$

where, A_i & B_i are two 64 bit input Operands, Y is the output of MAC Unit and i is a 64 bit value. This Equation performs Summation of partial products.

The Carry Save Adder (CSA) produces 129 bit output. Since, one bit is for the carry (128 bits + 1 bit). Then, the output of CSA is given to the accumulator register. The accumulator used is designed with Parallel in Parallel out (PIPO) Type [3]. Because the CSA Produces output in Parallel form and also the bits are huge. PIPO register is used where the input bits are given in parallel and output is taken in parallel. The output of the accumulator register is taken out or fed back as one of the input to the CSA. Fig. 1 shows the basic architecture of MAC unit.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of MAC Unit.

III. Modified Wallace Multiplier And Carry Save Adder

A Wallace tree is an efficient hardware implementation of a digital circuit that multiplies two integers. The Wallace tree has three steps: Multiply (that is - AND) each bit of one of the arguments, by each bit of the other. Secondly, reduce the number of partial products to two by layers of full and half adders. Finally, Group the wires in two numbers, and add them with a conventional adder. The Benefit of Wallace Tree is that there are only few layers and thereby reducing the propagation delay. But, As the number of bits to multiply increases, no. of adders (full adders & half adders) increases thereby increasing propagation delay [4].

In this Paper, Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier is proposed where no. of half adders get reduced and therefore circuit complexity reduces, power dissipation also decreases at a reduced propagation delay. Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier has three stages, to achieve the desired functionality. Initially, the $N \times N$ Product Matrix is formed and rearranged to take the shape of inverted pyramid. Secondly, the rearranged product matrix is grouped into non-overlapping group of three parts. Single bit and two bits column in the group will be passed to the next stage and three bits column is given to a full adder circuit[5]. The number of rows (R) in each stage of the reduction stage is calculated as

$$R_{i+1} = 2 [R_i / 3] + R_i \text{ Mod } 3 \quad (2)$$

If $R_i \text{ Mod } 3 = 0$, Then

$$R_{i+1} = 2 [R_i / 3] \quad (3)$$

If the Calculated value from the above equation for number of rows in the each stage in the 2nd phase and the number of rows that are formed in each stage of 2nd phase does not match, only then the Half Adder will be used [6].

The Final Product of the 2nd Stage will be in the Height of two bits and passed on to the 3rd Stage. During the Third Stage the Output of Second Stage is then given to the carry propagation adder to generate the final output.

Figure 2: A 10-bit Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier.

Thus 64 bit Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier is constructed and the total number of stages in the second phase is ten. As per the equation the number of row in each of the ten stages was calculated and the use of half adders was restricted only to the Tenth stage. The total number of half adders used in the second phase is eight and the total number of full adders that was used during the second phase is slightly increased that in the Conventional Wallace Tree Multiplier [7].

Since, the 64 bit Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier Representation is very difficult, A Typical 10 bit by 10 bit reduction example is as shown in Figure 2. the Modified Wallace Tree shows better Performance when CSA is used in final stage instead of Ripple Carry Adder (RCA)[8].

The Carry Save Adder (CSA) is a type of Digital Adder, used to compute the sum of three or more number of bits in binary form. CSA gives less propagation delay and the Glitching problem in RCA is also avoided. Since, the Representation of 128 bit CSA is very difficult, A Typical example of 8 bit CSA is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: A Typical 8-bit Carry Save Adder

Here, we compute the sum of two 128 bit binary numbers so 128 half adders at the first stage is required instead of 128 full adders. Since, we add bits of two binary numbers only [9].

If, P and Q are two 128 bit numbers then it produces the partial products and carry S_i and C_i respectively.

Where,

$$S_i = P_i \oplus Q_i$$

$$C_i = P_i \cdot Q_i$$

However, a CSA Produces all the output values in parallel. so that, the computation time is reduced compared to RCA. Also, Parallel in Parallel Out (PIPO) is used in Accumulator Stage [10].

IV. RESULTS

The Design is developed using Verilog - HDL and Synthesized using Xilinx 13.2 ISE.

As a previous work different MAC Units were developed using different combination of multipliers and adders. A Comparison of different multipliers used such as

- (i) Modified Booth Algorithm,
- (ii) Dadda Multiplier,

(iii) Wallace Multiplier.

The different adders used are

- (i) Carry Save Adder,
- (ii) Carry Select Adder.

The Area, Power Dissipation and Delay comparison of different MAC Units are shown in Figure 4 as a graph and in tabular form in Table 1.

Figures 4 and 5 shows the cell area and total power dissipation of different MAC unit. These figures clearly indicates that the MAC unit which are developed using Wallace Tree Multiplier Requires less area, dissipate less power and also delay caused by it is also less when compared other MAC unit which are done either by Modified Booth or Dadda multiplier. Hence a 64 bit MAC unit is designed using Modified Wallace Multiplier and Carry Save Adder.

The simulation waveform result of 64 bit MAC unit in shown in the figure 6. In the simulation result it is observed that there is a delay by one clock cycle, this is because it takes some time to compute since the multiplier used here is 64 bit and the adder used here is 128 bits.

No	MAC NAME	Area Report		Delay (ps)
		Cells	Cell Area (μm^2)	
1	Multiplier Adder Modified Booth Carry Look Ahead (MCLMAC)	221	7677	4995
2	Multiplier Adder Wallace Multiplier Carry Look Ahead (WCLMAC)	90	4398	3084
3	Multiplier Adder Dadda Multiplier Carry Select (DCEMAC)	183	7637	4125
4	Multiplier Adder Modified Booth Carry Save (MCSMAC)	185	6819	4545
5	Multiplier Adder Wallace Multiplier Carry Save (WCSMAC)	61	2947	1026

Table 1: Area and Delay Comparison of MAC Units

Figure 4: Graph Comparison of Cell Area in μm^2

Figure 5: Comparison of Total Power Dissipation in mW.

Sl.No	MAC NAME	Power Report		
		Leakage	Dynamic	Total
1	MCLMAC	252	1812909	1813161
2	WCLMAC	132	903720	903852
3	DCEMAC	260	1721111	1721371
4	MCSMAC	218	1517795	1518013
5	WCSMAC	79	435399	435478

Table 2: Power Dissipation of Different MAC Units

Figure 6: Simulation Waveform of 64-bit MAC Unit

V. CONCLUSIONS

Hence, a High Performance 64 bit MAC Unit is designed and implemented using Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier and Carry Save Adder. When compared to all other MAC Units which are developed earlier using different combinations of multipliers and adders, the designed Modified Wallace Tree Multiplier offers High Performance with Less Area, Less Power Dissipation with Less Propagation Delay, which further increases the overall speed of MAC Unit. This MAC Unit is designed using Verilog - HDL and Synthesized using Xilinx 13.2 ISE.

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Web Server Implementation for Embedded Home Automation by Using IP Protocol

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ABSTRACT

Web access functionality is embedded in a device to enable low cost widely accessible and enhanced user interface functions for the device. A web server in the device provides access to the user interface functions for the device through a device web page. A web server can be embedded into any appliance and connected to the Internet so the appliance can be monitored and controlled from remote places through the browser in a desktop.

Key Words — Ethernet, Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), Internet Protocol (IP), Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP), Protection diode.

I. Introduction

This technique is to control the devices or equipment's from the remote place through a web page. Here all the devices, which are to be controlled, are connected to the relays (acts as switches) on the web server circuit board. The web-server circuit is connected to LAN or Internet. The client or a person on the PC is also connected to same LAN or Internet. By typing the IP-address of LAN on the web browser, the user gets a web page on screen; this page contains all the information about the status of the devices. The user can also control the devices interfaced to the web server by pressing a button provided in the web.

The Block diagram shown in the fig 1 gives an overview of the interconnection between various devices in the design. The resources of the Micro Controller are used in such a way that simultaneous processing of information from the various sensors and also to send/receive data over the internet via the Ethernet Controller is made possible. The full 8-bit operation of both the Micro Controller and the Ethernet Controller ensures no queuing up of data received from the internet. This is also

complemented by the high speeds at which both the devices operate.

The Micro Controller forms the central part of the design where the respective Sensors/Actuators are connected to the electronic equipments to perform the necessary functions. The Micro tiobe programmed at any point of time without affecting other components. This feature is used to change the contents of the flash memory where the web pages are stored. The Analog circuitry around the Ethernet Controller mainly consists of the isolation transformer and LEDs to indicate the status of the network link.

Figure 1. Module wise Block Diagram.

II. Methods

a) Overview of the System

The aim of the project is to control the devices or equipment's from the remote place through a web page. Here all the devices, which are to be controlled, are connected to the relays (acts as switches) on the web server circuit board. The web-server circuit is connected to LAN or Internet. The client or a person on the PC is also connected to same LAN or Internet. By typing the IP-address of LAN on the web browser, the user gets a web page on screen; this page contains all the information about the status of the devices. The user can also control the devices interfaced to the web server by pressing a button provided in the web page.

b) Ethernet

The name comes from the physical concept of the ether. It defines a number of wiring and signaling standards for the physical layer, through means of network access at the Media Access Control (MAC)/Data Link Layer, and a common addressing format. On top of the physical layer Ethernet stations communicate to each other by sending each other data packets, small blocks of data that are individually sent and delivered.

Ethernet is standardized as IEEE 802.3. The combination of the twisted pair versions of Ethernet for connecting end systems to the network, along with the fiber optic versions for site backbones, is the most widespread wired LAN technology. It has been in use from around 1980 to the present, largely replacing competing LAN standards such as token ring, FDDI, and ARCNET. In recent years, Wi-Fi, the wireless LAN standardized by IEEE 802.11, is prevalent in home and small office networks and augmenting Ethernet in larger installations.

10Base-T provides Manchester-encoded 10-Mbps bit-serial communication over two unshielded twisted-pair cables. Although the standard was designed to support transmission over common telephone cable, the more typical link configuration is to use two pair of a four-pair Category 3 or 5 cable, terminated at each NIC with an 8-pin RJ-45 connector (the MDI), as shown in Fig 5 Because each active pair is configured as a simplex link where transmission is in one direction only, the 10Base-T physical layers can support either half-duplex or full-duplex operation.

c) Transmission Control Protocol (TCP)

TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) was specifically designed to provide a reliable end-to-end byte stream over an unreliable internetwork. An internetwork differs from a single network because different parts may have widely different topologies, bandwidths, delays, packet sizes, and other parameters. TCP was designed to dynamically adapt to properties of the internetwork and to be robust in the face of many kinds of failures.

Figure 2. TCP header

Figure 2 shows the layout of a TCP segment. Every segment begins with a fixed-format, 20-byte header. The fixed header may be followed by header options. After the options, if any, up to 65,535 - 20 - 20 = 65,495 data bytes may follow, where the first 20 refer to the IP header and the second to the TCP header. Segments without any data are legal and are commonly used for acknowledgements and control messages.

d) Internet Protocol (IP)

An appropriate place to start our study of the network layer in the Internet is the format of the IP datagram's they. An IP datagram consists of a header part and a text part. The header has a 20-byte fixed part and a variable length optional part.

The header format is shown in Fig. 3. It is transmitted in big-endian order: from left to right, with the high-order bit of the Version field going first. (The SPARC is big endian; the Pentium is little-endian.) On little endian machines, software conversion is required on both transmission and reception.

Figure 3. IP header

e) IP Addresses

Every host and router on the Internet has an IP address, which encodes its network number and host number. The combination is unique: in principle, no two machines on the Internet have the same IP address. All IP addresses are 32 bits long and are used in the Source address and Destination address fields of IP packets. It is important to note that an IP address does not actually refer to a host. It really refers to a network interface, so if a host is on two networks, it must have two IP addresses. However, in practice, most hosts are on one network and thus have one IP address.

Figure 4. IP address

For several decades, IP addresses were divided into the five categories listed in Fig. 4.17. This allocation has come to be called glassful addressing. It is no longer used, but references to it in the literature are still common. We will discuss the replacement of glassful addressing shortly. For example every web server has a unique address so that other computers connected to the internet know where to find it on the vast network. The IP (Internet Protocol) address looks something like this: 69.93.141.146.

Web hosts rent out space on their web servers to people or businesses to set up their own websites. The web server allocates a unique website address to each website it hosts.

When you connect to the internet, your personal computer also receives a unique IP address assigned by your ISP (internet service provider). This address identifies your computer's location on the network. When you click on a link to visit a website, like www.wisegeek.com, your browser sends out a request to wise Geek's IP address. This request includes return information and functions like a postal letter sent across town, but in this case the information is transferred across a network. The communiqué passes through several computers on the way to wise GEEK, each routing it closer to its ultimate destination.

When your request reaches its destination, the web server that hosts wise Geek's website sends the page in HTML code to your IP address. This return communiqué travels back through the network. Your computer receives the code and your browser interprets the HTML code then displays the page for you in graphic form.

The more powerful the server, the faster it can serve up website pages. Slower, smaller servers may result in frustrating lag time for viewers. High traffic can also slow servers that are not powerful enough to handle high volumes of data exchange. This lag time should be a concern if you are shopping for a web host. Most web hosts have a page dedicated to sharing technical information about their web server, including speed, capacity, network configuration and other details.

f) Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP)

The transfer protocol used throughout the World Wide Web is HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol). The HTTP is an application level protocol. It is a generic, stateless, object oriented protocol that can be used for many tasks, such as name servers and distributed object management systems, through extension of its request methods (commands). It uses a client-server relationship and is based on a stream-oriented transport layer, such as TCP. Today, the most important use is transferring HTML documents with multimedia contents between Internet servers and clients (WWW). It works with the principle of request and response. The simplest case is that a client establishes a connection to a server and requests a content referred by a Uniform Resource Identifier (URL) that specifies the path and name of the resource. Commonly, this is done by navigating

with the web browser. These URLs are structured like a file path. After decoding the request, the server starts transferring the resource to the client. The requests (also called methods) are sent as simple ASCII strings with a trailing carriage return (CR) and line feed (LF). The response from a server contains some header lines. Each one has a CR and LF at its end. An additional CR and LF at the end of the last line of the header indicate that the data is following. In most cases, this will be an HTML page or a picture file. After transferring the content, the connections usually closed again.

g) Drive Circuit and Protection Diodes for Relays

The coil of a relay passes a relatively large current, typically 30mA for a 12V relay, but it can be as much as 100mA for relays designed to operate from lower voltages. Hence a CB amplifier is used to achieve the current rating of the relay.

Transistors and ICs must be protected from the brief high voltage produced when a relay coil is switched off. The diagram shows how a signal diode (e.g. 1N4148) is connected 'backwards' across the relay coil to provide this protection.

Current flowing through a relay coil creates a magnetic field which collapses suddenly when the current is switched off. The sudden collapse of the magnetic field induces a brief high voltage across the relay coil which is very likely to damage transistors and ICs. The protection diode allows the induced voltage to drive a brief current through the coil (and diode) so the magnetic field dies away quickly rather than instantly. This prevents the induced voltage becoming high enough to cause damage to transistors and ICs.

Figure 5. Drive circuit and protection diodes for relays

h) CIRCUIT DETAILS

Ethernet is the most common Local Area Network (LAN) technology in use today. On top of the Physical Layer Ethernet stations communicate to each other by sending data packets. Each Ethernet station is given a single 48-bit MAC address, which is used both to specify the destination and the source of each data packet. As with other IEEE 802 LANs, each Ethernet station is given a single 48-bit MAC address, which is used both to specify the destination and the source of each data packet. Network interface cards (NICs) or chips normally do not accept packets addressed to other Ethernet stations. Adapters generally come programmed with a globally unique address but this can be overridden either to avoid an address change when an adapter is replaced or to use locally administered addresses. Serial Ethernet Board has 28-pin ENC28J60 10Base-T Controller with on board Media Access Control and Physical layer, 8KB of buffer RAM and Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) communication

Note 1: Ferrite Bead should be rated for at least 100 mA.
 2: Required only if the microcontroller is operating at 5V.

III. Conclusions

Embedded web servers are an integral part of an embedded network. Embedded Servers in our project can be used to change the status of the various Gadgets connected to the kit by means of Internet.

The embedded web server design includes a complete web server with TCP/IP support and Ethernet interface. It provides the software for automatic configuration of the web server in the network. The embedded web server reference design includes complete source code written in c-language. A comprehensive model of the embedded web server has been designed using Pic. We can reduce the power consumption by making use of a different kind of microcontroller called the AVR, which makes use of only 3.3v power supply. This design is a quick start to embedded web servers.

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Tollgate based on web of things

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ABSTRACT

The electronic toll assortment system (ETC) collection wireless communication system to execute the automated payments of transportation fee no end a toll gate in categorical ways that. This paper presents the planning and development of car plate recognition for machine-driven toll assortment. Car place recognition (LPR) is that the extraction of automobile plate info from a picture since it's easier and quicker than the conventional token based mostly price ticket system; it's all the potential to interchange the prevailing system. Moreover, it saves users valuable time by reducing the queue length before of the toll counter. It's accustomed pay the quantity mechanically and open & shut the toll gate mechanically. A registration number plate is installed on every vehicle. A recognition device at the gate reads this information from the vehicle and compares it with the data inside the electronic information service and permits the access consequently by gap the gate. This information is utilized to print a daily or monthly bill for toll assortment from the vehicles. This model has low quality and takes fewer times in terms of automobile plate segmentation and character recognition. We tend to aim to collection the time consumed to pay the toll gate quantity and additionally to help the RTO, department of local government to trace the vehicle, simply in case} if it completely was taken or used for any illegal activities. Nevertheless as we tend to ar progressing to increase the protection options inside the toll gate as a result of currently a day's toll gate ar the door to the foremost cities. If we tend to increase the protection inside the toll gate section mechanically the protection inside town are enlarged. The planned collection has been designed exploitation very (high-speed integrated circuit) hardware description language (VHDL) and simulated. Finally, it's downloaded {in a | during a | in an exceedingly in a terribly} very field programmable gate array (FPGA) chip and tested on some given situations. The FPGA implementation is administrated in one of the applying area automatic toll collection.

Keywords: License plate recognition, Pressure sensor ,Gas Sensor

I. Introduction

In our daily life we are seeing toll gate. We are going to pay certain amount to the government in form of tax through this toll gate. We can see this toll gates being placed in some national high ways etc., So in order to pay tax we are normally going to pay in form of cash, but instead of that as the technology is growing we can make use of smart card which is nothing but like a memory card in which we are going to store the details of particular person and

certain amount. The main objective of this project is to pay the toll gate tax using smart card. Smart card

must be recharged with some amount and whenever a person wants to pay the toll gate tax, he needs to insert his smart card and deduct amount using keypad. By using this kind of projects there is no need to carry the amount in form of cash and so we can have security as well. These electronic toll Collection systems are a combination of completely automated toll collection systems (requiring no

manual operation of toll barriers or collection of tolls) and semi-automatic lanes. Various traffic and payment data are collected and stored by the system as vehicles pass through. The different technologies involved are logically integrated with each other but remain flexible for upgrades. They also include sophisticated video/image capturing equipment for full-time violation enforcement.

AUTOMATIC car place recognition (LPR) plays a crucial role in various applications like unattended parking heaps security management of restricted areas traffic enforcement congestion rating and automatic toll assortment. Attributable to totally different operating environments, LPR techniques vary from application to application. Point able cameras produce dynamic scenes after they move. A dynamic scene image could contain multiple car places or no license plate the least bit. Moreover, after they do seem in a picture, license plates could have impulsive sizes, orientations and positions. And, if complicated backgrounds area unit concerned, detective work license plates will become quite an challenge. Typically, Associate in Nursing LPR method consists of 2 main stages (1) locating license plates and (2) distinctive license numbers. Within the 1st stage, car place candidates' area unit determined supported the options of license plates. Options ordinarily used are derived from the car place format and therefore the alphanumeric characters constituting license numbers. The options concerning car place format embody form, symmetry height-to dimension magnitude relation color texture of achromatic color abstraction frequency and variance of intensity values Character options embody line blob the sign transition of gradient magnitudes, the ratio of characters the distribution of intervals between characters and therefore the alignment of characters. In reality, atiny low set of sturdy, reliable, and easy-to-detect object options would be adequate.

The car place candidates determined within the locating stage area unit examined within the identification number identification stage. There are unit 2 major tasks concerned within the identification stage, variety separation and variety recognition. Variety separation has within the past been accomplished by such techniques as projection morphology relaxation labeling, connected elements and blob coloring. Since the projection methodology assumes the orientation of a car place is thought and

therefore the morphology methodology needs knowing the sizes of characters. A hybrid of connected elements and blob coloring techniques is taken into account for character separation. For this, we tend to developed our own character recognition technique, that is predicated on the disciplines of each artificial neural networks and mechanics.

License Plate Recognition:

Most of the quantity plate detection algorithms fall in additional than one class supported totally different techniques. To sight vehicle variety plate following factors ought to be considered:

- (1). Plate size: a plate will be of various size in a very vehicle image.
- (2). Plate location: a plate will be settled anyplace within the vehicle.
- (3). Plate background: A plate will have totally different background colours supported vehicle sort. as an example a government vehicle variety plate may need totally different background than different public vehicles.
- (4). Screw: A plate might have screw which may be thought-about as a personality.

A number plate will be extracted by mistreatment image segmentation technique. There ar various image segmentation strategies accessible in numerous literatures. In most of the strategies image binarization is employed. Some authors use Otsu's technique for image binarization to convert color image to grey scale image. Some plate segmentation algorithms ar supported color segmentation. A study of car place location supported color segmentation is mentioned. within the following sections common variety plate extraction strategies ar explained, that is followed by elaborate discussion of image segmentation techniques adopted in numerous literature of ANPR or LPR.

Fig1: License Plate recognition

The templates that square measure almost like the registration number plate character is known by the comparison method with the character hold on within the information. Extracted registration number plate characters could have some noise or they'll be broken. The extracted characters could in addition be inclined. example matching may be a straightforward and straightforward technique in recognition. The similarity between character and therefore the example is measured. example matching is performed once resizing the extracted character into an identical size. each example scans the character column by column to calculate the normalized cross correlation. The example with the most price is that the foremost similar one. example matching is useful for recognizing single-font, rotated, broken, and fixed-size characters. If a personality is completely totally different from the example, the example matching produces incorrect recognition result. Among the disadvantage of recognizing inclined characters is solved by storing several templates of an identical character with totally different inclination angles.

Database Image

Block Diagram for Toll Gate System:

Fig: 4New Toll Gate system

Fig2: Input Images

Fig3: Different Template Images

The planned system makes certain that the traffic at the toll gates is efficient and security is additionally gift. The tax that is collected is predicated on the load carried by the vehicle. Through this technique we will additionally determine taken vehicles. The reading the knowledge from vehicle plate recognition system, computer compares the information within the info and permits the access consequently by opening/closing the gate. This knowledge is employed to print a daily or monthly bill for toll assortment from the vehicles. this fashion even taken vehicles is known.

The pressure of the vehicle is obtained victimization the pressure sensing element and consequently the pressure of the vehicle is showed on the display. A counter is employed to count the quantity of vehicles. the quantity on the idea of weight & the count of vehicles is additionally displayed on the screen. the quantity to be paid is mechanically deduced from the various checking account.

If a vehicle carries any reasonably gas that shouldn't be carried, the gas sensing element detects the gas within the vehicle. just in case if there's any reasonably gas that's detected, the RF transmitter is employed to alert the close police headquarters associated an alarm is enabled to alert the encircling

areas. After wards motor one is employed to shut the gate and at the same time motor two is employed to drag up the spikes so as to puncture the vehicle.

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PRESSURE SENSOR

A piezoelectric sensor as shown in **figure 5** is a device that uses the piezoelectric effect to measure pressure, acceleration, strain or force by converting them to an electrical charge. Here a simple pressure sensor is used to protect door or window. It generates a loud beep when somebody tries to break the door or window. The alarm stops automatically after three minutes. The circuit uses a piezo element as the pressure sensor.

Piezo buzzer exploits the piezoelectric property of the piezo electric crystals. The piezoelectric effect may be direct piezoelectric effect in which the electric charge develops as a result of the mechanical stressor reverse or indirect piezoelectric effect (Converse piezoelectric effect) in which a mechanical force such as pressure develops due to the application of an electric field.

Fig5: Piezo electric sensor

A typical example of direct piezoelectric effect is the generation of measurable amount of piezoelectricity when the Lead Zirconate Titanate crystals are deformed by mechanical or heat stress. The Lead Zirconate Titanate crystals also shows indirect piezoelectric effect by showing pressure when an electric potential is applied.

OPERATION

Operation of pressure sensor is very simple. Here we have two plates that is one is input plate and the other is output plate, whenever pressure is applied as shown in **figure 6** then these two plates come into contact we get voltage as a output then this output is send to the FPGA in turn it shows the weight of the vehicles is shown in the display as per our project. Accordingly toll tax is calculated. It is made up of a piezoelectric crystal. Depending on how a piezoelectric material is cut, three main modes of operation can be distinguished into transverse, longitudinal, and shear.

Figure 6 Pressure sensor operation

GAS SENSOR

The Flammable Gas and Smoke sensors can detect the presence of combustible gas and smoke at concentrations from 300 to 10,000 ppm. Owing to its simple analog voltage interface, the sensor requires one analog input pin from the FPGA.

Fig7:Gas Sensor (type-MQ2)

The product can detect the pressure of the smoke and send the output in the form of analog signals. Our range can function at temperature ranging from -20 to 50 degree Celsius and consume less than 150 mA at 5V.

Sensitive material of MQ-2 gas sensor in the figure is SnO₂ (Tin dioxide), which with lower conductivity in clean air. When the target combustible gas exist, the sensor's conductivity is higher along with the gas concentration rising.

MQ-2 gas sensor has high sensitivity to LPG, Propane and Hydrogen, also could be used to Methane.

STRUCTURE AND CONFIGURATION

Structure and configuration of MQ-2 gas sensor is shown as figure, sensor composed by micro AL₂O₃ ceramic tube, Tin Dioxide (SnO₂) sensitive layer, measuring electrode and heater are fixed into a crust made by plastic and stainless steel net. The heater provides necessary work conditions for work of sensitive components. The enveloped MQ-2 has 6 pin, four of them are used to fetch signals, and other two are used for providing heating current.

WIRELESS COMMUNICATION MODULE:

A general RF communication block diagram is shown in figure8 Since most of the encoders/decoders/microcontrollers are TTL compatible and mostly inputs by the user will be given in TTL logic level. Thus, this TTL input is to be converted into serial data input using an encoder or a microcontroller. This serial data can be directly read using the RF Transmitter, which then performs ASK (in some cases FSK) modulation on it and transmit the data through the antenna. In the receiver side, the RF Receiver receives the modulated signal through the antenna, performs all kinds of processing, filtering, demodulation, etc and gives out a serial data. This serial data is then converted to a TTL level logic data, which is the same data that the user has input.

Fig8: RF communication block diagram

Results:

Fig9: Before Segmentation Number Plate

Fig10: After Segmentation Number Plate

Fig11: Number Plate Recognition

Fig12: After Matching

CONCLUSION:

Motive of this projected system is to detect the images of the vehicle plate accurately. The automated real-time vehicle plate recognition system has been demonstrated to provide correct identification of vehicles captured images from the camera. The system has been shown to be robust to lighting variations, headlight dazzle, and partial vehicle obscuration. The next stage of development will involve increasing the vehicle coverage of the reference database and further trials at sites including parking facilities and public highways.

FUTURE WORK:

The future analysis of AVPR ought to focus on multistyle plate recognition, video-based AVPR mistreatment temporal information, multiplates process, high definition plate image process, ambiguous-character recognition, and so on. In four important factors were planned to identify the multistyle license plate problem: license plate rotational angle, character line number, the alphanumerical varieties used and character formats

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Implementation of Effective Area Architectures for CSLA

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ABSTRACT

In the design of Integrated circuit area occupancy plays a vital role because of increasing the necessity of portable systems. Carry Select Adder (CSLA) is a fast adder used in data-processing processors for performing fast arithmetic functions. From the structure of the CSLA, the scope is reducing the area of CSLA based on the efficient gate-level modification. In this paper 16 bit, 32 bit, 64 bit and 128 bit Regular Linear CSLA, Modified Linear CSLA, Regular Square-root CSLA (SQRT CSLA) and Modified SQRT CSLA architectures have been developed and compared. However, the Regular CSLA is still area-consuming due to the dual Ripple-Carry Adder (RCA) structure. For reducing area, the CSLA can be implemented by using a single RCA and an add-one circuit instead of using dual RCA. Comparing the Regular Linear CSLA with Regular SQRT CSLA, the Regular SQRT CSLA has reduced area as well as comparing the Modified Linear CSLA with Modified SQRT CSLA; the Modified SQRT CSLA has reduced area. The results and analysis show that the Modified Linear CSLA and Modified SQRT CSLA provide better outcomes than the Regular Linear CSLA and Regular SQRT CSLA respectively. This project was aimed for implementing high performance optimized FPGA architecture Model.

Keywords: Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), Area efficient, Carry Select Adder (CSLA), Square-root CSLA (SQRT CSLA).

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, dc-dc converters with steep voltage ratio are usually required in many industrial applications. For example, the front-end stage for clean-energy sources, the dc back-up energy system for an uninterruptible power supply (UPS), high-intensity discharge lamps for automobile headlamps, and, finally, the telecommunications industry [1]-[3]. The conventional boost converters cannot provide such a high dc voltage gain, even for an extreme duty cycle. It also may result in serious reverse-recovery problems and increase the rating of all devices. As a result, the conversion efficiency is degraded and the electromagnetic interference (EMI) problem is severe under this situation [4]. In order to increase the conversion efficiency and voltage gain, many modified boost converter topologies have been investigated in the past decade [5]. In dc-dc

converters with high voltage gain, there are several requirements such as high voltage gain low reverse-recovery loss, soft-switching characteristic, low-voltage stress across the switches, electrical isolation, continuous input current, and high efficiency. In order to meet these requirements, various topologies are introduced. In order to extend the voltage gain, the boost converters with coupled inductors are proposed in [6] and [7]. The voltage gain is extended but continuous input current characteristic is lost and the efficiency is degraded due to hard switching of power switches. In [8], a step-up converter based on a charge pump and coupled

Inductor is suggested. Its voltage gain is around 10 but its efficiency is not high enough due to the switching loss. In [9], a high-step-up converter with

coupled inductors is suggested to provide high voltage gain and a continuous input current. However, its operating frequency is limited due to the hard switching of the switches. In [10], a new boost converter with a ripple free input current was suggested. In the new boost converter, an extra LC circuit with coupled inductors was utilized. The ripple component of the input current was reduced by carefully designing the parameters of the coupled inductor. Coupled inductor can serve as a transformer to extend the voltage gain in non-isolated DC/DC converters. The coupled inductor has two windings. The primary winding serves as the similar function as the filter inductor. The second winding operates as a voltage source in series to the power branch. The voltage gain can be extended by a proper turn's ratio design of the coupled inductor. However, the efficiency could not be improved due to the switching losses of the power switch. To increase the efficiency and power conversion density, the soft-switching technique is required in DC/DC converters. In [11]–[16], various soft-switching techniques are suggested.

Generally, there is a tradeoff between soft-switching Characteristic and high voltage gain. It is because an inductor that is related with soft-switching limits the voltage gain. In order to solve these problems, a zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) dc–dc converter with high voltage gain is proposed. As shown in Fig. 1, it consists of a ZVS boost converter stage to make the input current continuous and provide ZVS functions. In Fig. 2 ZVS boost converter and ZVS half-bridge converter stage to provide high voltage gain and continuous input current, soft switching operation. Since single power processing stage can be a more efficient and cost-effective solution, both stages are merged and share power switches to increase the system efficiency and simplify the structure. Since both stages have the ZVS function, ZVS operation of the power switches can be obtained with wider load variation. Moreover, due to the ZVS function of the boost converter stage, the design of the half-bridge converter stage can be focused on high voltage gain. Therefore, high voltage gain is easily obtained. ZVS operation of the power switches reduces the switching loss during the switching transition and improves the overall efficiency. The theoretical analysis is verified by a 100W experimental prototype with 24–396 V conversion.

II. Analysis of Proposed Converter

A ZVS boost converter with a coupled inductor is proposed. The ZVS characteristic of the proposed boost converter reduces the switching losses and raises the overall efficiency. Moreover, since the ZVS characteristic is achieved by adding an additional winding to the boost inductor, there is only one magnetic component. The reverse-recovery of the auxiliary diode is alleviated due to the leakage inductance of the coupled inductor. The theoretical analysis is verified by a 100W experimental prototype with 24V-to-86V conversion.

ZVS DC-DC Converters with high voltage gain was proposed in this project which consists of ZVS Boost converter and ZVS Half bridge converter. Analysis of the proposed converter with design parameters are shown below.

Fig.1 ZVS Boost Converter

Fig.2 Proposed soft-switching dc–dc converter with high voltage gain

The equivalent circuit of the proposed converter is shown in Fig.2 The ZVS boost converter stage consists of a coupled inductor L_c , the lower switch Q_1 , the upper switch Q_2 , the auxiliary diode D_a , and the dc-link capacitor C_{dc} . The diodes D_{O1} and D_{O2} represent the intrinsic body diodes of Q_1 and Q_2 . The capacitors C_{O1} and C_{O2} are the parasitic output capacitances of Q_1 and Q_2 . The coupled inductor L_c is modeled as the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} , the

leakage inductance L_{k1} , and the ideal transformer that has a turn ratio of $1:n_1$ ($n_1 = N_{s1}/N_{p1}$). The ZVS half-bridge converter stage consists of a transformer T, the switches Q1 and Q2, the output diodes Do1 and Do2, the dc blocking capacitors C_{B1} and C_{B2} , and the output capacitor C_o . The transformer T is modeled as the magnetizing inductance L_{m2} , the leakage inductance L_{k2} , and the ideal transformer that has a turn ratio of $1:n_2$ ($n_2 = N_{s2}/N_{p2}$). The theoretical waveforms of the proposed converter are shown in Fig. 3. The switches Q1 and Q2 are operated asymmetrically and the duty ratio D is based on the switch Q1. The operation of the proposed converter in one switching period T_s can be divided into seven as shown in Fig. 4. Just before Mode 1, the upper switch Q2, the auxiliary diode Da, and the output diode D_{o1} are conducting. The magnetizing current i_{m1} of L_c arrives at its minimum value I_{m12} and the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} arrives at its maximum value I_{Da} . The current i_L has its maximum value I_{L1} .

Fig.3 Equivalent circuit of the proposed soft-switching dc-dc converter

Mode 1 [t_0, t_1]: At t_0 , the upper switch Q2 is turned OFF. Then, the capacitor C_{Q2} starts to be charged and the voltage V_{Q2} across Q2 increases toward V_{dc} . Simultaneously, the capacitor C_{Q1} is discharged and the voltage v_{Q1} across Q1 decreases toward zero. With an assumption that the output capacitances C_{Q1} and C_{Q2} of the switches are very small and all the inductor currents are not changed, the transition time interval T_{t1} can be considered as follows

$$T_{t1} = t_1 - t_0 = \frac{(C_{Q1} + C_{Q2}) V_{dc}}{I_{L1} + (n_1 + 1) I_{Da} - I_{m12}} \quad (1)$$

Mode 2 [t_1, t_2]: At t_1 , the voltage V_{Q1} across the lower switch Q1 becomes zero and the body diode D_{Q1} is turned ON. Then, the gate signal for Q1 is applied. Since the current has already flown through the body diode D_{Q1} and the voltage V_{Q1} is maintained as zero before the switch Q1 is turned ON, the zero-voltage turn-ON of Q1 is achieved.

Since the voltage v_{p1} across the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} is V_{in} , the magnetizing current i_{m1} increases linearly from its minimum value I_{m2} as follows:

$$i_{m1}(t) = I_{m12} + \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m1}} (t - t_1) \quad (2)$$

Since the voltage v_{Lk1} across the leakage inductance L_{k1} is $-(n_1 V_{in} + V_{dc})$, the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} linearly decreases from its maximum value I_{Da} as follows:

$$i_{Da}(t) = I_{Da} - \frac{n_1 V_{in} + V_{dc}}{L_{k1}} (t - t_1) \quad (3)$$

From (2) and (3), the input current i_{in} is determined as follows:

$$i_{in}(t) = i_{m1}(t) - i_{p1}(t) = i_{m1}(t) - n_1 i_{Da}(t) = I_{m12} - n_1 I_{Da} + n_1 \frac{n_1 V_{in} + V_{dc}}{L_{k1}} (t - t_1) + \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m1}} (t - t_1) \quad (4)$$

Since v_{p2} is $-(V_{dc} - V_{CB1})$ and v_{Lk2} is $V_{CB2} + n_2 V_{in}$, the magnetizing current i_{m2} and the diode current $i_{D_{o1}}$ are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = I_{m21} - \frac{V_{dc} - V_{CB1}}{L_{m2}} (t - t_1) \quad (5)$$

$$i_{D_{o1}}(t) = -i_{CB2}(t) = I_{D_{o1}} - \frac{V_{CB2} + n_2 V_{in}}{L_{k2}} (t - t_1) \quad (6)$$

In this mode, the primary current i_{p2} , the coupled inductor current i_L , and the switch current i_{Q1} can be obtained from

$$i_{p2}(t) = n_2 i_{CB2}(t) \quad (7)$$

$$i_L(t) = i_{m2}(t) - i_{p2}(t) \quad (8)$$

$$i_{Q1}(t) = i_{in}(t) - i_{Da}(t) - i_L(t) \quad (9)$$

Mode 3 [t_2, t_3]: At t_2 , the current i_{CB2} changes its direction. The output diode current $i_{D_{o1}}$ decreases to zero and the diode D_{o1} is turned OFF. Then the output diode D_{o2} is turned ON and its current increases linearly. Since the current changing rate of D_{o1} is controlled by the leakage inductance L_{k2} of the transformer T, its reverse-recovery problem is alleviated. Since V_{p2} is the same as in Mode 2 and V_{Lk2} is $n_2 V_{in} + V_{CB2} - V_{O}$, the current i_{m2} and the diode current $i_{D_{o2}}$ are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = i_{m2}(t) - \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m2}} (t - t_2) \quad (10)$$

$$i_{D_{o2}}(t) = i_{CB2}(t) = \frac{V_{CB2} + n_2 V_{in} - V_{O}}{L_{k2}} (t - t_2) \quad (11)$$

The currents i_{p2} , i_L , and i_{Q1} can be obtained from the same relations in Mode 2. In this mode, the voltages V_{p1} and V_{Lk} are equal to those in Mode 2. Therefore, the magnetizing current i_{m1} , the auxiliary current i_{Da} , and the input current i_{in} change with the same slopes as in Mode 2.

Mode 4 [t3, t4]: At t3, the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} decreases to zero and the diode Da is turned OFF. Since the changing rate of the diode current i_{Da} is controlled by the leakage inductance L_{k1} of the coupled inductor L_c its reverse recovery problem is alleviated. Since the voltage v_{p1} across the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} is the input voltage V_{in} , the magnetizing current i_{m1} increases linearly with the same slope as in Modes 2 and 3 as follows:

$$i_{m1}(t) = i_{m1}(t_3) + \frac{V_{in}}{L_{m1}}(t - t_3) \quad (12)$$

Since the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} is zero, the input current i_{in} is equal to the magnetizing current i_{m1} . At the end of this mode, the magnetizing current i_{m1} arrives at its maximum value I_{m11} . Since the voltages V_{p2} and V_{Lk2} are not changed in this mode, the slopes of the current i_{m2} , i_{CB2} , and i_L are not changed.

Mode 5 [t4, t5]: At t4, the lower switch Q1 is turned OFF. Then, the capacitor C_{Q1} starts to be charged and the voltage V_{Q1} across Q1 increases toward V_{dc} . Simultaneously, the capacitor C_{Q2} is discharged and the voltage V_{Q2} across Q2 decreases towards zero. With the same assumption as in Mode 1, the transition time interval T_{t2} can be determined as follows:

$$T_{t2} = t_5 - t_4 = \frac{(C_{Q1} + C_{Q2}) V_{dc}}{I_{L2} + I_{m11}} \quad (13)$$

Mode 6 [t5, t6]: At t5, the voltage V_{Q2} across the upper switch Q2 becomes zero and the body diode D_{Q2} is turned ON. Then, the gate signal is applied to the switch Q2. Since the current has already flown through the body diode D_{Q2} and the voltage V_{Q2} is maintained as zero before the turn-ON of the switch Q2, the zero-voltage turn-ON of Q2 is achieved. Since the voltage V_{p1} across the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} is $-(V_{dc}-V_{in})$, the magnetizing current i_{m1} decreases linearly from its maximum value I_{m11} as follows:

$$i_{m1}(t) = I_{m11} - \frac{V_{dc}-V_{in}}{L_{m1}}(t - t_5) \quad (14)$$

Since the voltage V_{Lk1} across the leakage inductance L_k is $n_1(V_{dc}-V_{in})$, the auxiliary diode current i_{Da} linearly increases from zero as follows:

$$i_{Da}(t) = \frac{n_1(V_{dc}-V_{in})}{L_{m1}}(t - t_5) \quad (15)$$

From (14) and (15), the input current i_{in} is determined as

$$i_{in}(t) = I_{m11} - \frac{(V_{dc}-V_{in})}{L_{m1}}(t - t_5) - n_1^2 \frac{(V_{dc}-V_{in})}{L_{k1}}(t - t_5) \quad (16)$$

Since the voltage V_{p2} is $V_{CB1} (= D V_{in} / (1-D))$ and V_{Lk2} is $-(V_o-V_{CB2} + n_2DV_{in}/(1-D))$, the magnetizing current i_{m2} and the diode current i_{D02} are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = -I_{m22} + \frac{DV_{in}}{L_{m2}(1-D)}(t - t_5) \quad (17)$$

$$i_{D02}(t) = i_{CB2}(t) = I_{D02} - \frac{V_o - V_{CB2} + (n_2DV_{in}/(1-D))}{L_{k2}}(t - t_5) \quad (18)$$

Mode 7 [t6, t7]: At t6, the current i_{CB2} changes its direction. The output diode current i_{D02} decreases to zero and the diode D_{02} is turned OFF. Then the output diode D_{01} is turned ON and its current increases linearly. Similar to D_{01} , the current changing rate of D_{02} is controlled by the leakage inductance L_{k2} of the transformer T and its reverse-recovery problem is alleviated. Since v_{p2} is the same as in Mode 6 and V_{Lk2} is $V_{CB2} - n_2DV_{in}/(1-D)$, the current i_{m2} and the diode current i_{D02} are given by

$$i_{m2}(t) = i_{m2}(t_6) + \frac{DV_{in}}{L_{m2}(1-D)}(t - t_6) \quad (19)$$

$$i_{D01}(t) = -i_{CB2}(t) = \frac{V_{CB2} - (n_2DV_{in}/(1-D))}{L_{k2}}(t - t_6) \quad (20)$$

The currents i_{p2} and i_L can be obtained from the same relations in Mode 2. In this mode, the voltages V_{p1} and V_{Lk1} are equal to those in Mode 6. Therefore, the magnetizing current i_{m1} , the auxiliary current i_{Da} , and the input current i_{in} change with the same slopes as in Mode 2.

Fig.4 Theoretical waveforms

Fig.5 Modes of Operation

III. CHARACTERISTIC AND DESIGN

PARAMETERS:

1. Voltage Gain of the Boost Converter Stage:

Referring to the voltage waveform V_{p1} in Fig. 4, the volt second balance law gives

$$V_{in}DT_s - (V_{dc} - V_{in})(1 - D)T_s = 0. \quad (21)$$

From (21), the voltage gain of the proposed ZVS boost converter stage is obtained by

$$\frac{V_{dc}}{V_{in}} = \frac{1}{1 - D} \quad (22)$$

Which is the same as that of the conventional CCM boost converter.

2. Auxiliary Diode Current Reset Timing Ratio d_1 :

By applying the volt-second balance law to the voltage waveform V_{Lk1} , the auxiliary diode current reset timing ratio d_1 is

$$d_1 = \frac{n_1 D(1 - D)}{n_1(1 - D) + 1} \quad (23)$$

3. Maximum Auxiliary Diode Current I_{Da} :

From Modes 6 and 7, the maximum auxiliary diode current I_{Da} is obtained by.

$$I_{Da} = \frac{n_1 D V_{in} T_s}{L_{k1}} \quad (24)$$

4. DC-Blocking Capacitor Voltage V_{CB1} :

Referring to the voltage waveform v_{p2} in Fig. 4, the volt second balance law gives

$$V_{CB1}(1 - D)T_s - (V_{dc} - V_{CB1})DT_s = 0 \quad (25)$$

From (22) and (25), the dc-blocking capacitor voltage V_{CB1} is obtained by

$$V_{CB1} = \frac{D V_{in}}{1 - D} \quad (26)$$

5. Maximum Output Diode Currents I_{Do1} and I_{Do2} :

From Modes 2 and 7, the maximum output diode current I_{Do1} can be written as follows:

$$I_{Do1} = \frac{n_2 V_{in} + V_{CB2}}{L_{k2}} d_2 T_s = -V_{CB2} + \frac{(n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D))}{L_{k2}} \quad (27)$$

$$I_{Do2} = \frac{n_2 V_{in} + V_{CB2} - V_o}{L_{k2}} (D - d_2) \quad (28)$$

$$T_s = V_o - V_{CB2} + \frac{(n_2 D V_{in} / (1 - D))}{L_{k2}} d_3 T_s \quad (29)$$

6. Output Voltage V_o of the Half-Bridge Converter Stage:

From (27) and (29), the dc-blocking capacitor voltage V_{CB2} and the output voltage V_o can be derived as follows:

$$V_{CB2} = \frac{D - d_2 - (D/(1 - D))d_3}{1 - D + d_2 - d_3} \cdot n_2 V_{in} \quad (30)$$

$$V_o = \frac{D - d_2 - (D/(1 - D))d_3}{(D - d_2 + d_3)(1 - D + d_2 - d_3)} \cdot n_2 V_{in} \quad (31)$$

7. Output Diode Current Reset Timing Ratios d_2 and d_3 :

Since the average value of the current i_{CB2} should be zero, the following relation can be obtained:

$$(1 - D + d_2 - d_3) I_{Do1} = (D - d_2 + d_3) I_{Do2} \quad (32)$$

From (27) to (32), the relation between d_2 and d_3 is obtained by

$$\frac{d_2}{d_3} = \frac{D}{1 - D} \quad (33)$$

Since the average value of the current i_{m2} is zero, its peak values I_{m21} and I_{m22} have the same value as follows:

$$I_{m21} = I_{m22} = \frac{D V_{in} T_s}{2 L_{m2}} \quad (34)$$

From Fig.4, the output current I_o can be represented by

$$I_o = (1 - D + d_2 - d_3) \frac{I_{Do1}}{2} = (D - d_2 + d_3) \frac{I_{Do2}}{2} \quad (35)$$

From (27), (28), (33), and (37), d_2 and d_3 are obtained by

$$d_2 = \alpha D \quad (36)$$

$$d_3 = \alpha(1 - D) \quad (37)$$

$$\alpha = 1/2 \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{8 L_{k2} I_o}{n_2 V_{in} D T_s}} \right) \quad (38)$$

8. Voltage Gain M of the Proposed DC-DC Converter:

From (22), (31), (36), and (37), the voltage gain M of the proposed converter is given by

$$M = \frac{V_o}{V_{in}} = \frac{n_2 D(1-2\alpha)}{(D(1-2\alpha) + \alpha)(1-\alpha - (1-2\alpha)D)} \quad (39)$$

9. Input Current Ripple:

The input current ripple Δi_{in} can be written by

$$\Delta i_{in} = I_{m11} - I_{m12} + n_1 I_{Da} = \frac{n_1^2 L_{m1} + L_{k1}}{L_{m1} L_{k1}} \cdot D V_{in} T_s \quad (40)$$

To reduce the input current ripple below a specific value I^* , the magnetizing inductance L_{m1} should satisfy the following condition:

$$L_{m1} > \frac{1}{(I^* / D V_{in} T_s) - (n_1^2 / L_{k1})} \quad (41)$$

10. ZVS Conditions:

As is seen in Fig. 3, both the boost converter stage and the half-bridge converter stage have ZVS function. From Fig. 3, the ZVS condition for Q2 is given by

$$I_{m11} + I_{L2} = I_{m11} + I_{m22} + n_2 I_{Do2} > 0. \quad (42)$$

Since the current values I_{m11} , I_{m22} , and I_{Do2} have positive values, the ZVS condition for Q2 is always satisfied. Similarly, for ZVS of Q1, the following condition should be satisfied:

$$I_{m21} + n_2 I_{Do1} + (n_1 + 1) I_{Da} - I_{m12} > 0 \quad (43)$$

The terms I_{m21} and $n_2 I_{Do1}$ are from the half-bridge converter stage and the terms $(n_1 + 1) I_{Da}$ and I_{m12} are from the boost converter stage. If the boost converter stage is designed to satisfy the above inequality (43) regardless of the status of the half bridge converter stage, ZVS of the proposed converter is always accomplished. In this case, the leakage inductance L_{k1} of the coupled inductor L_c should satisfy the following condition

$$L_{k1} < \frac{(n_1 + 1) n_1 D V_{in} T_s}{P_o / V_{in}} \quad (44)$$

Where P_o is the output power and the minimum value I_{m12} of the magnetizing current i_{m1} is approximated as P_o / V_{in} .

Fig.6 Measured Efficiency

Fig.7 MATLAB Simulation circuit

Simulation Results:

Fig 8.1 I_{in} , I_{Da} , V_{Q1} Waveforms

Fig 8.2 V_{Q1} , I_{Q1} , V_{GS1} Waveforms

Fig 8.3 I_L , V_{Q1} , I_{CB1} Waveforms

Fig 8.4 I_{D02} , I_{D01} , V_{Q1} Waveforms

Fig 8.5 I_{Q2} , V_{GS2} , V_{Q2} Waveforms

Fig 8.6 Output voltage
Waveform

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig.9 Hardware Implementation

A 100W prototype of the proposed converter is made and tested. The power circuit setup is shown in Fig 4.1. Various parameters used in designing the power circuit are as shown the Table 1.

Parameter	Value
Power	100W
V_{in}	24V
V_{out}	396V
Coupled inductor(L_c)	800 μ H /16.75 μ H
L_{m1} / L_{lk1}	
Transformer(T) L_{m2} / L_{lk2}	474 μ H / 170 μ H
C_{dc} (Electrolytic capacitor)	470 μ F/100V
Inductor Core for coupled inductor(L_c)	ETD49
Inductor Core for transformer(T)	ETD44
$N_1, N_2(L_c)$	90,45turns
$N_1, N_2(T)$	22,132turns
D_{01}, D_{02}	MUR460(2)
C_{B1}	6.6 μ F
C_{B2}	2.2 μ F
C_o Electrolytic capacitor	220 μ F
Q_1, Q_2	IRF640N
D_a	MUR460

Table.1 Specifications of prototype

The power is tested in laboratory with the diode bridge rectifier output as input to the converter. Power to control circuit is given from regulated power supply. The waveforms are captured from the oscilloscope and the results are shown in the following section.

V. CONCLUSION

A ZVS dc-dc converter with high voltage gain was suggested. It can achieve ZVS turn-ON of two power switches while maintaining CCM. In addition, the reverse-recovery characteristics of the output diodes were significantly improved by controlling the current changing rate with the use of the leakage inductance of the transformer. The proposed converter presents a higher efficiency and a wider ZVS region compared to other soft-switching converters due to the ZVS boost converter stage. Therefore, the proposed ZVS boost converter is suitable for industrial applications that require a step-up function and a continuous input current characteristic.

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Phase-Shifted (PS)PWM DC–DC Converter With ZCS Active Rectifier for EV Battery Chargers

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ABSTRACT

A phase shift soft-switching PWM dc–dc converter suitable for electric vehicle battery charging systems is presented in this paper. Wide range soft-switching operations are achievable from full load to no load by effectively utilizing the parasitic inductances of the high frequency transformer in the dc–dc converter. In addition, no circulating current occurs in both of the primary and secondary side full bridge circuits; thereby, the related idling power can be minimized. As a result, high efficiency power conversion can be maintained owing to the full range soft-switching operation and wide range output power and voltage regulations. Its operating principle is presented on the basis of theoretical analysis and simulation results, and the design procedure of the circuit parameters of the dc–dc converter is described.

Keywords— DC–DC converter, phase shift pulse width modulation (PS-PWM), soft switching, zero voltage soft switching (ZVS), zero current soft switching (ZCS), ZCS active rectifier, no circulating current, EV battery charger.

1. INTRODUCTION

Power conversion systems in electric vehicles (EVs) usually use a high energy battery pack to store energy for the electric traction system. Switch-mode HF-link (HF-isolated) dc–dc power converters serve as an essential power interface connecting the grid with the onboard electric power supply in a battery charging system for EVs including plug-in HEVs (PHEVs) as introduced in Fig. 1 [1]. Voltage-source full-bridge soft-switching PS-PWM dc–dc converters are suitable for the battery chargers due to the high power, low electromagnetic interference noise emissions and applicability of versatile output power regulation schemes. The phase shift power regulation strategy is useful for the HF-link dc–dc power converter with a galvanic isolation due to precise generations of the switching signal patterns for the semiconductor power devices.

The most remarkable method in high-power isolated applications is Phase Shifted (PS) Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) method, which provides all of the switches to operate with ZVS without any additional auxiliary switches. The parasitic capacitance energy is discharged by the leakage inductance, and the

MOSFET turns on with zero voltage transition (ZVT). Insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) is preferred over MOSFET at high voltage and high-power levels in industrial applications. Low $R_{DS(on)}$ MOSFETs are quite expensive compared to the IGBTs with equivalent current and voltage ratings. The choice of IGBT over MOSFET is mandatory due to non availability of high voltage and high-current MOSFET devices in some applications. An external snubber capacitor is connected in parallel to each IGBT in order to decrease turn-off losses, in case the IGBT is used in the phase shifted full bridge (PSFB) pulse width modulation (PWM) converter.

Fig.1. Battery charging system architecture for EVs/PHEVs.

In the grid-connected battery charging system, the HF-link dc-dc converter has a function of controlling the battery voltage in a wide range with respect to the intermediate dc-link voltage which is regulated by the ac-dc rectifier. In addition, high efficiency and high reliability are essentially required in the HF-link dc-dc converter in order to enhance the total performances of the battery charging system.

The HF-link dc-dc converter is more advantageous in terms of the compact size and light weight of transformer as well as wide-range output power and voltage regulations due to a higher resolution in a controller processing. The typical soft-switching PS-PWM dc-dc converters are based on the primary-side phase shift (PPS) scheme, as depicted in Fig. 2, which have been developed not only for the automotive electric power systems but also for the variety of the industrial power conversion equipments. In contrast to the simplicity on the main circuit and controller, occurrence of large circulating currents and its relevant power losses are the technical issues inherent to the conventional PPS-PWM dc-dc converters in Fig. 3 [2]–[13]. In addition, ZVS ranges of the active switches especially for the active switches of the lagging phase legs in the primary-side inverter are severely limited. Besides that, the rectifier diodes in the secondary-side circuit suffer from reverse recovery currents, so that the power consuming RCD passive snubbers are necessary for protecting them from the voltage surges and the parasitic ringing. As a result, the conversion efficiency decreases and the higher switching frequency operations that are essential for achieving the high power density cannot be performed in reality.

In order to overcome the disadvantages of the conventional ZVS PPS-PWM dc-dc converters, a variety of soft-switching PPS-PWM dc-dc converters have been developed in the past decades, as summarized.

Fig. 2. A conventional ZVS PPS-PWM dc-dc converter.

Fig. 3. A circulating current pathway in the conventional ZVS PPS-PWM dc-dc converter.

Fig. 4. soft-switching SPS-PWM dc-dc converter with ZCS active rectifier.

The improved soft-switching PPS-PWM dc-dc converters are classified into capacitor and diode-assisted regenerative snubbers [14], [15], switched capacitor active clamped circuit [16], [17], mode changeable active clamped circuit [18], primary-side saturable reactors [19], primary-side voltage-blocking capacitor [20], tapped-inductor filter [21], and primary-side additional resonant pole-assisted circuit [22]. Although the circulating current can be eliminated to some extent and the soft-switching limitations of the lagging phase leg can be mitigated, additional power devices and passive components are indispensable in the improved soft-switching PPS-PWM dc-dc converters. The additional magnetic components as well as capacitors cause power losses especially in the light load conditions, and are obstacles for achieving high efficiency and high power density whereas increasing a cost in developing those dc-dc converters. Furthermore, the soft-switching operations cannot be ensured over the wide range of load conditions, i.e., from full load to no load.

The ZVS SPS-PWM dc-dc converter with ZVS active rectifier, as depicted in Fig. 6 (a), which is more suitable for high output voltage applications, can reduce the circulating current of the primary-side inverter, but that

of the secondary-side rectifier still remains [23], [24]. The ZVS SPS-PWM dc–dc converter with saturable reactor-assisted ZCS rectifier in Fig. 6 (b) has been developed by the authors [25]. In this unique dc–dc converter, the circulating currents can be eliminated in both of the primary and secondary-side power circuits. However, the additional magnetic switches are required to control the B–H curves of the saturable reactors with high sensitivity; thereby, the circuit and system configuration might be complicated.

In order to overcome the drawback of the saturable reactor- assisted type, the ZVS SPS-PWM dc–dc converter with ZCS active rectifier deriving from the circuit topology of Fig. 6(b) has been by the authors in [26]. The soft- switching dc–dc converter can eliminate the circulating current completely; thereby, the relevant conduction power losses can be minimized without any additional passive component. Moreover, the primary-side and secondary-side active switches can operate in ZVS and ZCS for the entire load range, respectively.

Fig.6. Soft-switching SPS-PWM dc–dc converters: (a) ZVS active rectifier-assisted type [23], [24], and (b) saturable reactor-assisted ZCS rectifier type [25].

The soft-switching ranges on both the primary side inverter and the secondary-side rectifier in the soft-switching dc–dc converter can be extended owing to the unique current commutation process attained by the SPS-PWM scheme.

It is a remarkable feature of the soft-switching SPSPWM dc–dc converter that full-range soft-switching operations can be realized by employing the reverse conduction blocking active switches for the controlled-side leg of the rectifier. Thus, no auxiliary switch and magnetic component is required; thereby, a power density of the HF-link dc–dc converter could be improved. Furthermore, the wide-range output power and output voltage regulations can be realized by a relatively small range variation of phase shift angle. As a result, high efficiency power conversion can be expected as well as performance improvement of the battery voltage controller, which is preferable for an EV battery charging system. Although the basic and conceptual research has been reported in [26], application specific performance evaluations on the soft-switching SPS-PWM dc–dc converter including the analysis on soft switching range and the steady-state power regulation characteristics have not been evaluated in-depth in the past relevant work. The main objective of this paper is to originally demonstrate the operation principle, more detailed analysis on the soft-switching operations, and circuit design guideline of the soft-switching SPS-PWM dc–dc converter, and prove its practical effectiveness in an experiment with considerations specifically for EV battery charger applications [27]–[29]. In addition, the performances of the soft-switching SPSPWM dc–dc converter for battery charging operations are evaluated by modeling a typical constant current and constant voltage (CCCV) mode in the experiment. Furthermore, a power loss analysis is carried out for evaluating the unique circuit topology and providing more practical ideas to construct the soft-switching SPS-PWM dc–dc converter.

This paper is organized as follows. The circuit configuration and operation principle together with the soft-switching conditions are explained in Section II. The soft-switching ranges, i.e., ZVS in the primary-side HF inverter and ZCS in the secondary-side active rectifier are theoretically analyzed in Section III, where the circuit design procedure is also described. In addition, the output power and output voltage versus phase shift angle characteristics are demonstrated by theoretical analysis and its simulation results in Section IV. The performances on the output power and output voltage regulations as well as the full-range soft switching operations are actually verified by experimental results based on the prototype provided in Section V, and effectiveness of the soft-switching SPS-PWM dc–dc converter herein is evaluated from a practical point of view.

II. CIRCUIT DESCRIPTION AND OPERATION PRINCIPLE

A. Circuit Configuration

The circuit configuration of the soft-switching

SPS-PWM dc-dc converter is depicted in Fig.4. In the primary-side full bridge inverter, the lossless snubbing capacitors C1-C4 operate with the series inductor L_s including the leakage inductance L_k ; then, ZVS turn-off and ZVS & ZCS (ZVZCS) turn-on operations can be attained all in Q1-Q4. The secondary-side rectifier consists of the hybrid legs of the reverse blocking active switches Q5 and Q6 and diodes D7 and D8. The output power and output voltage can be regulated by changing the phase shift angle φ (phase shift interval $t_\varphi = (\varphi/360) \cdot T$) between Q5 and Q6 as synchronous switches with respect to Q1-Q4.

The features and outstanding advantages of the soft switching dc-dc converter are summarized as follows.

- The output power and output voltage are regulated by the active switch-mode rectifier operating at ZCS.
- No additional magnetic component and capacitor is necessary as compared to the improved soft-switching PPSPWM dc-dc converters mentioned previously. This is advantageous for achieving high power density together with a light and compact size while decreasing a cost of development.
- No circulating current and the relevant power loss occur in both of the primary and secondary-side power stages over the wide load range.
- Full-range soft-switching operations can be achieved in all of the switching power devices.
- A wide-range power regulation can be attained with the small phase shift angle variations.
- The output power can be regulated linearly with the phase shift angle; thereby, the control system is simpler than that of the conventional ZVS PS-PWM dc-dc converters.
- The ZCS active rectifier-assisted SPS-PWM scheme can be widely applied for other converter topologies such as half-bridge and center-tapped rectifier.

B. Operation Principle

The relevant operating waveforms of the soft switching dc-dc converter are depicted in Fig.5. In addition, its switch mode transitions and equivalent circuits during one switching cycle are illustrated in Fig. 6. The operation mode of the soft-switching dc-dc converter treated herein is divided into the 12 submodes. The positive and negative half-cycle transitions are symmetrical; therefore, only the positive half-cycle operation is explained as follows. Note here that the output smoothing inductor L_o is large enough to establish $i_o(t) = I_o$ in the secondary-side circuit.

Mode 0 [$t < t_0$], <steady-state power transfer mode>

The primary-side active switches Q2 and Q3 are on state,

While the active switch Q6 and the diode D7 in the secondary-side rectifier are on-state. During this mode, the electric power from the input voltage source V_{in} is delivered to the load R_o .

Mode 1 [$t_0 \leq t < t_1$], <Q2 & Q3 ZVS turn-off mode>

From the steady-state negative half-cycle in the periodical circuit operation, the gate signals for S2 and S3 are removed simultaneously at $t = t_0$. Then, the lossless snubbing capacitors C2 and C3 are charged by the inverter current i_p ; accordingly, the voltages v_{Q2} and v_{Q3} across Q2 and Q3 rise gradually due to charging of C2 and C3.

$$v_{Q2,Q3}(t) = \frac{i_{mp} + I_o/a}{2C_r}(t - t_0) \quad (1)$$

$$v_{Q1,Q4}(t) = V_{in} - v_{Q2,Q3}(t) \quad (2)$$

At the same time, the voltages v_{Q1} and v_{Q4} across Q1 and Q4 decrease gradually from V_{in} to zero by discharging of C1 and C4. In this interval, the voltages across the primary-side active switches are expressed by defining $C_r = C1 = C2 = C3 = C4$ as During this interval, the primary-side inverter current $i_p(t)$ begins to decline from the negative peak current $i_p(t_0)$ as Expressed by

$$i_p(t) = \frac{V_{in}}{L_s}(t - t_0) + i_p(t_0). \quad (3)$$

The soft-switching conditions in the primary-side active switches are expressed as

$$\frac{1}{2}L_s\{i_p(t_0)\}^2 \geq 2C_r V_{in}^2. \quad (4)$$

removed, and the ZCS turn-off commutation can be achieved in Q6 . In order to achieve the ZCS turn-off commutation, the turn-off timing in Q6 is required to be delayed by t_{ex} against the turn-off timing of Q1 , Q4. Using (6), t_{ex} is expressed by

$$t_{ex} \geq \frac{aL_s}{V_{in}} I_o. \tag{9}$$

Mode 5 [t4 ≤ t < t5],<Q5 ZCS turn-on / ZCS turn-off mode>

The gate of S5 is supplied at t = t4 ; then, is as well as ip increases gradually due to the effect of Ls . Thus, the ZCS turn-on commutation can be performed in Q5.

During this interval, ip and is can be defined, respectively, as

$$i_p(t) = \frac{V_{in}}{L_s}(t - t_4) + i_p(t_4) \tag{10}$$

$$i_s(t) = a(i_p - i_m). \tag{11}$$

The HF transformer secondary-side current is gradually commutates to Q5 ; thereby, the current iD7 through D7 begins to decline.

Mode 6 [t5 ≤ t < t6],<D7 positive half-cycle steady-state power transfer mode>

The inverter current ip corresponds with im at t = t5. Then, the current iD7 through D7 naturally decays to zero owing to the effect of Ls ; thereby, ZCS turn-off operation can be realized in D7 . After the moment, the power is delivered from Vin to the load Ro and the circuit operations get into the negative half cycle. At this time, ip is denoted as

$$i_p(t) = \frac{V_{in} - aV_o}{L_s}(t - t_5) + i_p(t_5). \tag{12}$$

Fig.6 .Mode transitions and switching-mode equivalent circuits during one switching cycle.

Parameter	Symbol	Value unit
Input dc voltage rating	V_{in}	260 V
Output power rating	$P_{o,rating}$	1 kW
Switching frequency	f_s	50 kHz
Loss-less snubbing capacitors	$C_r(C_1 - C_4)$	3 nF
Auxiliary capacitor for DC magnetization protecting	C_a	30 μF
Rated load resistance	R_o	40 Ω
Output smoothing capacitor	C_o	1500 μF
Output smoothing inductor	L_o	620 μH
Additional series inductor	L_a	30 μH
HF transformer turns ratio	$a = N_p/N_s$	8 / 8
HF transformer magnetizing inductance	L_m	230 μH
HF transformer leakage inductance	L_k	1.2 μH
HF transformer series inductance	$L_s(= L_a + L_k)$	31.2 μH

TABLE I: CIRCUIT PARAMETERS AND SPECIFICATIONS

III. ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF SOFT-SWITCHING RANGE.

The primary-side inverter voltage and current waveforms of the conventional ZVS PPS-PWM dc-dc converter and the proposed soft-switching SPS-PWM dc-dc converter are depicted in Figs. 10 and 11, respectively. Note in these figures that the time origin to is set to be 0 for simplifying the explanations below.

The primary-side inverter peak current $i_p(0)$ of both PPS-PWM and SPS-PWM dc-dc converters is generally expressed as

$$i_p(0) = i_{mp} + \frac{I_o}{a} \tag{13}$$

Fig.7. Primary-side voltage and current waveforms of HF transformer in the proposed soft-switching SPS-PWM dc-dc converter ($t\phi$: phase-shift interval).

Fig. 8. Gate pulses sequences for the primary-side ZVS and secondary-side ZCS operations for the fullload condition (no phase-shifting; $t\phi = 0$).

The switching waveforms of the active switches and the rectifying diodes are under the condition of $P_o = 60\text{ W}$ and $\phi = 117^\circ$. It can be actually confirmed from those results that ZVZCS turn-on and ZVS turn-off in the primary-side active switch Q1, ZCS turn-on/off in the secondary-side active switch Q5, and ZCS turn-on/off commutations in the rectifying diode D8 can be actually attained.

Fig. 9. Voltage and current waveforms of HF transformer windings at $\phi = 117^\circ$ and $P_o = 60\text{ W}$: (a) Primary-side. (b) Secondaryside (100 V/div, 2 A/div, 2 μs /div).

CONCLUSION

The secondary-side phase shift (SPS) PWM soft-switching dc-dc converter applicable for EV battery chargers has been presented in this paper. The wide-range softswitching operations of the proposed soft-switching SPS-PWM dc-dc converter have been clarified with the theoretical analysis and simulation results, and then, the circuit design guidelines have been originally described, which contributes for engineers in actually developing the soft-switching dc-dc converter herein.

The performances of the soft-switching dc-dc converter are evaluated using simulation model of the 1 kW-50 kHz. It can be actually demonstrated that the wide-range soft-switching can be attained

from the heavy load to light load. In addition, it has been confirmed that the output power can be controlled from full load to no load with a relatively small variation of the phase shift angle. Those unique characteristics provide high performances for the dc-dc converter applied for the EVs/PHEVs battery chargers.

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Locking and Unlocking of Theft Vehicles Using CAN

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ABSTRACT

Avoiding Vehicle Theft is making buzz in present automobile industry. Design and development of a theft control system for an automobile, can be achieved by making use of GPS feature of mobile phone. The developed system makes use of an mobile phone that is embedded in the vehicle with an interfacing to Engine Control Module(ECM) through Control Area Network (CAN) Bus, which is in turn, communicated to the ECM. The vehicle being stolen can be stopped by using GPS feature of mobile phone and this information is used by the owner of the vehicle for future processing. The owner sends the message to the mobile which is embedded in the vehicle which has stolen which in turn controls the vehicles engine by locking the working of the engine immediately. The developed system accept the message and broadcasted to the Vehicle Network through CAN Bus. The engine can be unlocked only by the owner of the vehicle by sending the message again. The goal behind the design is to develop security for vehicles and embedded system to communicate with engine of the vehicle.

Keywords: Controller Area Network Bus ; Engine Control Unit; Vehicle Network ; Mobile Phone ; GPS ; GSM ; Theft Control Unit

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's Automobiles, invariably comply with digital control systems as a consequence of constant growth in technology. Recent Vehicles contains large number of Electronic Control Systems and already there are large numbers of Electronic Control Units present [1]. The growth of automotive electronics is the result parties of the customers wish for better safety and greater comfort and also for other requirements like improved emission control and reduced fuel consumption.

Electronic Control Units (ECUs) are increasingly being deployed in automobiles to control one or more electronic subsystems to realize various functions .When someone drives a car there are many signals that are passed between the various ECU's embedded inside the car. Output signals from an Electronic Control Unit contain information about the current state of the car as the driver interacts continuously with the car.

A modern day automobiles can consists up to 80 ECU's, sensing and taking tabs of the various parameters of the automobiles [2]. This rapid and complex exchange of signals ensures the proper functioning of the car.

Automotive industry uses Controller Area Network (CAN) as the in-vehicle network for the Engine Management, the body electronics like door and roof control, air conditioning and lighting as well as for the entertainment control. Nowadays all most all car manufacturers have also started implementing CAN based vehicle automation.CAN networks used in engine management to connect several ECUs [2].

A vehicle tracking system combines the installation of an electronic device in a vehicle, or fleet of vehicles, with purpose -designed computer software atleast at one operational base to enable the owner to track the vehicle's location. Collecting data in the process from the field and deliver it to the base of operation. The terms cover a range of products

which, by use of communications technology, or a combination of technologies, identify a stolen vehicle and its real-time location and present this information to a Systems Operating Centre (SOC) or to the police. Tracking systems also continue to update the data and differentiate between a particular stolen vehicle and all other vehicles, which may or not be stolen. It is recognized that such systems may be a facility within fleet management/logistics systems or part of services known as vehicle telemetric. Modern vehicle tracking systems commonly use GPS technology for locating the vehicle and also other types of automatic vehicle location technology can also be used. Vehicle information can be viewed on electronic maps via the Internet or specialized software.

II. CONTROLLER AREA NETWORK (CAN) BUS

Controller Area Network (CAN) is a serial data communications bus for real-time applications, developed by engineers at Bosch [5]. Evaluated existing serial bus systems regarding their possible use in passenger cars and found that none of the available network protocols were able to fulfill the requirements of the automotive applications in 1980's. CAN is based on the "broadcast communication mechanism", which is based on a *message-oriented transmission protocol*. The Controller Area Network (CAN) is used in a broad range of embedded as well as automation control systems. Application of CAN includes in the area of CAN in cars & Truck Engine, Maritime Applications, Avionics System Networks, Building Automation etc.

A. CAN Network in Automobiles

The use of a CAN Bus in Automobiles makes it possible to network electronic devices such as control units or intelligent sensors, provides the following advantages for the Vehicles as an overall system:

- 1) Data exchange between control units take place on a uniform platform. This platform is called a protocol. The CAN Bus acts as a so-called data highway.
- 2) Systems involving several control units, e.g. ESP, can be implemented efficiently.
- 3) System expansions are easier to implement in the form of optional extras.

- 4) The CAN Bus is an open system which permits adaptation to various transmission media such as copper or optical fiber cables.
- 5) Control units are diagnosed via the K-wire. Inside the car, diagnosis already takes place via the CAN Bus in some cases (for example the airbag and the door control unit). In this context, this is called a "virtual K-wire". In future cars, there will be no K-wire.
- 6) A cross-system diagnosis is possible across several control units.

Fig. 1 Overview of Controller Area Network.

Fig. 1 shows that the CAN network topology, follows the bus network topology, which gives it the advantage of easily adding new CAN nodes to an existing network. Furthermore, the standardization of the protocol means all ECUs will conform to the CAN standards while transmitting data. Note that in the Figure 2 all CAN nodes are fitted with a mandatory transceiver chip that connects it to the CAN bus.

B. CAN Principle

CAN is based on the "broadcast communication mechanism". This means that all nodes can "hear" all transmissions. There is no way to send a message to just a specific node; all nodes will invariably pick up all traffic. The CAN hardware, however, provides local filtering so that each node may react only on the interesting messages. Therefore, CAN is based on a message-oriented transmission protocol. Every message has a message identifier, which is unique within the whole network since it defines the priority of the message. The basic system of CAN in any vehicles is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2 Information Exchange of a message on the CAN Bus Broadcast Principle)

Exchange of information is referred to as messages. Any control unit can send or receive messages. A message contains physical values such as the engine speed (2000 rpm, 1800 rpm). The engine speed in this case, is represented as a binary value as shown in Figure 2. For example: The engine speed of 1800 rpm is represented as 00010101 in binary notation. Before sending, the binary value is converted into a serial bit stream called as CAN Message. The bit stream is sent over the TX line (transmit line) to the transceiver. The transceiver converts the bit stream into voltage values which are then sent over the CAN Bus line one by one. In the reception process, voltage values are converted back into a bit stream by the transceiver and sent over the RX line (receive line) to the control units. The control units then convert the serial binary values back into messages. For example: (the value 00010101 is converted back to the engine speed 1800 rpm). A message sent is received by all control units by administering message broadcast by using CAN protocol. The idea is derived from a transmitter which broadcasts a program me which any tuner (receiver) can receive. The broadcasting process ensures that all control units connected to the bus have the same information status.

The control unit receives signals from the sensors, processes them and passes them on to the actuators. The main components of a control unit are: a microcontroller with input and output memories and a program memory. The sensor values received by the controller, e.g. engine temperature or engine speed, are interrogated at regular intervals and stored in the input memory in their order of occurrence. This process corresponds to the principle of a mechanical step-by-step system with a rotating input selector switch. The microcontroller links the input values based on the program configuration. The results of this process are stored in each output memory and from there, they are sent to each of the actuators. In order to process CAN messages, each control unit has an additional CAN memory area for received and sent messages. The CAN module controls the data transfer process for CAN messages. It is divided into two sections, the receive section and the send section. The CAN module is connected to

the control unit via the receive mailbox or the send mailbox. It is normally integrated in the chip of the control unit microcontroller.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Commercially available anti-theft vehicular systems are very expensive. The paper act towards with the design & development of a Theft Control System for an automobile, which is being used to prevent or control the theft of a vehicle. The developed system makes use of an embedded system and n GSM /GPS technology. The proposed system, installed in the vehicle can be easily controlled by the owner of the vehicle by sending a message from his/her mobile to the vehicle engine by interfacing with CAN bus and GSM modem.

Once, the vehicle is being stolen, the information is being used by the vehicle owner for further

processing, where by sitting at a remote place, a message is sent to the interfacing GSM modem that is interfaced with the ECU which is installed in the vehicle. By reading the signals received by the mobile, the engine is locked automatically and speed of the vehicle reduced to zero. Again it will come to the normal condition only after entering a secured password by the owner of the vehicle.

The main idea behind the design is to introduce the Mobile technologies into the embedded system. The designed unit is very cost effective. The entire designed unit is on a single chip (ECU). When the vehicle is stolen, owner will send a message to the mobile which is embedded in the car showing the exact location using GPS. To stop the vehicle, owner sends a message to control system placed in vehicle as an ECU that automatically stops the flow of the fuel in the vehicle by sending message through CAN Bus thus automatically engine speed reduce to zero.

Many modern vehicle tracking devices combine both active and passive tracking abilities. The proposed system is very reliable, when a cellular network is available and a tracking device is connected it transmits data to a server; when a network is not available the device stores data in internal memory and will transmit stored data to the server later when the network becomes available again.

Vehicle tracking has been accomplished by installing a box into the vehicle, either self-powered with a battery or wired into the vehicle's power system. For detailed vehicle locating and tracking it is still the predominant method but many companies are increasingly interested in the emerging cell phone technologies that provide tracking of multiple entities, such as both a salesperson and their vehicle. These systems also offer tracking of calls, texts and Web use and generally provide a wider range of options.

A. Existing System

Unit racking Vehicle Tracking Unit has the ability to integrate the GPS tracking system with existing vehicle alarm or provide alarm features when someone is tampering with owner vehicle. It allows detecting the security threat before the vehicle is driven away and gives the ability to track the vehicle over the internet.

The ability to track the vehicle over the internet is done by utilizing Global Positioning Satellites. Data

such as Global Position, Speed Velocity and Time (PVT) are transmitted over the Cellular network. The information transmitted from the tracking device is disseminated and stored on your private confidential account or sent over the wireless network. The data is cross referenced on a street level map for viewing. The positioning information provided is cross reference to the closest geographic address and displayed in residential / commercial address format.

B. Drawbacks of Existing System

The main disadvantage of the existing system is that the system provides only a broad layout of the geographical address, providing and does not provide street wise address. Speed of the vehicle and engine is no way controlled by the existing systems, thus exposing the vulnerability of a system that provides only tracking.

C. Theft Control Unit (TCU)

The proposed theft control system retrieves a geographical address and provides a facility to control the further movement of the vehicle. The system is intended to provide a feature that would control the speed of the vehicle by (engine lock/unlock) only upon receipt of a predefined code from the owner, who may be at a remote place by using mobile phone technology.

IV. DESIGN & DEVELOPMENT OF TCU

The block diagram of the proposed system is as shown in Fig. 3. The design & development of the proposed system carried out in two modules, first the design of module to retrieve the location and second module to control the vehicle engine by either to lock or unlock the engine by sending ON/OFF message from the user to the Theft Control Unit. Fig. 3 accomplishes the various control units of the vehicles are connected to one another through CAN Bus. The Theft Control Unit locks/unlocks the vehicle engine by sending text message through mobile to CAN Bus from the owner's mobile through GSM.

A. Location Retrieval of the Vehicle

Location of the vehicle is a two way process. Initially latitude and longitude of the vehicle is to be obtained from the satellites. Obtained latitude and longitude is used for further computation of geographical address by invoking geocoder. The owner can

retrieve the location only upon sending a solitary message. This solitary message is set by the owner before deploying the system. Retrieval of the vehicle's location is explained in the activity diagram shown in Fig. 4.

Only upon receipt of corresponding message code, the application would start the service. As an acknowledgement, the owner is sent with latitude, longitude and the geographical address. Mobile network is a matter of concern as only in presence of substantial network coverage solitary message and its receipt is possible. Design of location retrieval module takes into consideration both the network factor and user code authentication. Only upon receiving an authenticated code that has been defined earlier, the owner is sent the location. Hence user code authentication is also considered.

B. Ignition/fuel flow Control of the Vehicle

Design of ignition/fuel flow control module involves a stimulus to drive the process. This stimulus is obtained through an owner's message. Upon receiving the location of the vehicle, the owner can either stop or start the ignition of the engine. The design parameter that is considered in this module is receiving a message from the owner to perform further action. Another design parameter considered is authenticating the genuine nature of the message. Design involves processing the message only if it is from the owner. Even if the locking code is known to others, locking cannot be performed. Owner thus has a discrete control over the ignition of the engine. The crux of the design involves controlling the ignition the engine being at a remote place by sending a message.

Fig. 4. Activity Diagram to Retrieve the Location of the Vehicle

Fig. 5. Block Diagram of the engine ignition control module

Upon receiving the message and verifying its authentication, the micro controller installed on the vehicle would send a signal to the relay to lock or unlock the engine. A SIM card on GSM module installed on the vehicle would receive the message

and would forward it to the micro controller. A MAX232 would perform the action of both driver and receiver to forward the message to and from the micro controller as shown in Fig. 5. An LCD display is used to notify the changes. Corresponding messages would be display on the LCD when a new message is received, when locking or starting the engine is performed. This kit however is not essential for actual deployment of the system and is used only for demonstration purpose.

V. EXPERIMENTED RESULTS

The results are obtained after carrying out the experimentation by using the following hardware components. The component includes Android Based Phone, ARM Controller, Relay Circuit, GSM Module, and LCD Display. Fig. 6 shows ARM Controller, Relay circuit, GSM Module and LCD Display are interfaced on a single board and embedded on single board which is embedded to a vehicle as a control unit. The relay is connected to the Vehicle Engine Unit of the Automobile.

Fig. 6. Hardware Kit embedded to the vehicle

When “OFF” message sent by the owner of the vehicle to the mobile embedded in the control unit, the controller displays the message in the LCD as shown in Fig. 7(a) and invokes the relay that is connected to the vehicle engine which will stop fuel flow thus locking the vehicle engine by sending message through the CAN Bus in the CAN readable format. Similarly when “ON” message sent by the owner of the vehicle to the mobile embedded in the control unit, the controller displays the message in the LCD as shown in Fig. 7(b) and invokes the relay that is connected to the vehicle engine which will in turn allows the fuel flow by unlocking the vehicle engine by sending message through CAN Bus.

(a) (b)

Fig. 7. (a) LCD displaying “ENGINE OFF” message, (b) LCD displaying “ENGINE ON” message.

The values of the vehicle like Speed, Rpm, Gear and Signal are analyzed along with the experiment conducted and these values are recorded in the form of table as shown below.

TABLE 1: shows the values of speed, rpm, and gear values of vehicle when signal 0 and 1 are sent

Speed	Rpm	GEAR	Signal
0	90	10	0
10	95	10	0
15	100	10	0
20	150	10	0
20	200	10	0
20	250	10	0
20	300	10	0
20	350	10	0
20	90	20	0
25	95	20	0
30	100	20	0
0	150	20	1
0	200	20	1
0	250	20	1
0	300	20	1
0	350	20	1
0	90	30	1
0	95	30	1
0	100	30	1
0	150	30	1
0	200	30	1
60	250	30	0
65	300	30	0
65	350	30	0
40	90	40	0
50	95	40	0
60	100	40	0
70	150	40	0
80	200	40	0
0	250	40	1
0	300	40	1
0	350	40	1
0	90	50	1
0	95	50	1
0	100	50	1
0	150	50	1
90	200	50	1
100	250	50	0
110	300	50	0
120	350	50	0

Fig. 8. Graph representing Engine status of a vehicle

Messages “OFF” and “ON” are converted into signal 1 and 0. When signal=1, it means engine is locked, speed of the vehicle is reduced to zero irrespective of drivers input. If the signal=0, it means engine is unlocked it behaves normally as per the drivers input. This illustrated by plotting a graph as shown in Fig. 8 by the considering the values present in Table 1. When engine is in normal condition, speed of the vehicle depends on drivers input but when the engine is locked, speed of the vehicle is 0 but it cannot be changed by the drivers input.

Fig. 9. Location details received on owner mobile

The Fig. 9 shows the typical message sent by the Android mobile to the owner mobile when there is a network, by invoking Vanet app in Android mobile and hence displaying the location in terms of latitude, longitude and geo-graphical address of the location.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Proposed System Theft Control Unit can be implemented in any automobiles as one of the vehicle’s electronic control unit which will be connected to the CAN Bus as one more node. The developed system is less expensive vehicle tracking control system that could be implemented on any vehicle since the system is developed by using mobile and GSM technology which is operated by sending and receiving messages. The vehicle engine ignition system can be controlled by reading the message received.

The system consists of two modules one is GSM module and the other is Android module. The owner of the vehicle interacts with GSM module by sending and receiving messages. The Android module uses GPS system to retrieve the location details of the vehicle. So that the owner can get location details and using which the owner could track the vehicle easily. GSM module is the simple communication channel that uses existing network providers. So, mobile network is essential for the functioning of the system.

Theft Control Unit installed, controls the vehicle engine unit when it receives message through from owner through CAN Bus. Since the CAN Bus is used as in-vehicle network, the transfer of data from one unit to another unit reliable and efficient. Therefore, the integrated system handles different functions such as locking vehicle engine by stopping fuel flow in to the engine, getting location details through GPS network and sending it to owner of the vehicle.

The Proposed system can be deployed on any automobile, less expensive and ignition of an engine can be controlled being at the remote place, encompasses some advantages of the system. Therefore, the Mobile based Vehicle Theft control Unit (TCU) provides an easier and featured tracking system. Also helps the owner of the vehicle to have an easy remote control of the theft vehicle.

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HIGH PERFORMANCE IMPLEMENTATION OF IDEA CRYPTOGRAPHIC ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

Cryptography is the science of keeping communication secure, so that eavesdroppers cannot decipher the transmitted messages. The transmission speeds of core networks require hardware based cryptographic modules, since software based cryptography cannot meet the required throughput requirements. Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) are ideal components for fast cryptographic algorithms. The large capacities of FPGAs enable the fitting of fully pipelined algorithms on a single chip. The reprogram ability of FPGAs enables using the same hardware platform as a cryptographic engine for a multitude of communication protocols. This paper shows the implementation of the IDEA (International Data Encryption Algorithm) one of the strongest secret-key block ciphers. The algorithm process data in 16-bit sub blocks and can be fully pipelined.

Keywords: Participants, Encryption, Decryption, Algorithm(s), Plaintext, Ciphertext, Public key, Private key.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Motivation

The aim of cryptography is to make it intractable to retrieve the data without the knowledge of a secret piece of information which is usually called a key. All cryptography algorithms can be divided into two categories: symmetric algorithms and asymmetric algorithms.

The original message before encrypted is denoted as plaintext, the message after being encrypted as cipher text, and the way to break cipher text as cryptanalysis. A symmetric cryptography usually encrypts plaintext by using permutation, substitution, and XOR operations.

IDEA becomes one of the most popular symmetric cryptography and has been widely used in the internet security scheme. For example, Pretty Good Privacy (PGP), a well-known internet security protocol, has adopted IDEA as its message encryption scheme.

1.2 Cryptography

Cryptography is the science of using mathematics to encrypt and decrypt data. Cryptography enables you to store sensitive information or transmit it across insecure networks (like the internet) so that it cannot be read by anyone except the intended recipient. While cryptography is the science of securing data, cryptanalysis is the science of analyzing and breaking secure communication. 1.2.1 Types of Cryptography

There are several ways of classifying cryptographic algorithms. These are categorized based on the number of keys that are employed for encryption and decryption. The two types of algorithms that will be discussed are

- Secret Key Cryptography: Uses a single key for both encryption and decryption.
- Public Key Cryptography: Uses one key for encryption and another for decryption.

Cryptography algorithms use either symmetric keys, also called secret keys or asymmetric keys, also called public keys.

Figure 1.1. Encryption and Decryption with a Symmetric Cipher

Figure 1.2. Encryption and Decryption with a Public Key Cipher

1.3 Field Programmable Gate Arrays

FPGA is a semiconductor device containing programming logic components and programmable interconnects. The programmable logic components can be programmed to duplicate the functionality of basic logic gates such as AND, OR or complex combinational function such as decoder or simple math functions. In most of the FPGAs, these programmable logic blocks also include memory elements, which may be simple FFs or complete block of memories.

There are two basic categories of FPGAs on the market today: 1. SRAM-based FPGAs and 2. antifuse-based FPGAs. In the first category, Xilinx and Altera are the leading manufacturers in terms of number of users, with the major competitor being AT&T. For antifuse-based products, Actel, Quick logic and Cypress, and Xilinx offer competing products.

II. International Data Encryption Algorithm

IDEA is the name of the patented and universally applicable block encryption algorithm, which permits the effective protection of transmitted and stored data against unauthorized access by third parties. With a key of 128 bits in length, IDEA is far more secure than the widely known DES based on a 56-bit key. The fundamental criteria for the development of IDEA were military strength for all security requirements and easy hardware and software implementation. The algorithm is used worldwide in various banking and industry applications

2.1 Architecture

IDEA encrypts 64-bit plaintext blocks into 64-bit cipher text blocks using a 128-bit input key K. The algorithm consists of eight identical rounds followed by an output transformation. Each round uses six 16-bit sub keys $K_i(r)$, $1 \leq i \leq 6$, to transform a 64-bit input X into an output of four 16-bit blocks, which are then input to the next round. All sub keys are derived from the 128-bit input key K. The sub key derivation process is different in decryption mode from the encryption mode, but otherwise encryption and decryption are performed with identical hardware.

Bruce Schneier, author of Applied Cryptography, broke this cipher down into 14 steps. So in each round, the sequence goes as follows:

1. Multiply X1 and the first sub key
2. Add X2 and the second sub key
3. Add X3 and the third sub key
4. Multiply X4 and the fourth sub key
5. XOR the results of steps 1 and 3
6. XOR the results of steps 2 and 4
7. Multiply the result of step 5 with the fifth sub key
8. Add the results of steps 6 and 7
9. Multiply the results of step 8 with the sixth sub key
10. Add the results of steps 7 and 9
11. XOR the results of steps 1 and 9
12. XOR the results of steps 3 and 9

13. XOR the results of steps 2 and 10
14. XOR the results of steps 4 and 10

This is basically the algorithm in a nutshell, but it's not finished yet, there is still some swapping that needs to get accomplished.

15. The results of the algorithm will be in order, 11, 12, 13, and 14. Swap the 2 inner blocks so that it would read 11, 13, 12, and 14.

Now you are ready to move onto the next iteration of the algorithm, don't forget to change the keys, now instead of using keys 1 through 6, now the keys will be 7 through 12. The swapping step (step 15) happens on all rounds except for the eighth round, which the inputs are used for the final transformation. The final Transformation goes as follows:

1. Multiply X1 and the first sub key
2. Add X2 and the second sub key
3. Add X3 and the third sub key
4. Multiply X4 and the fourth sub key

Now, keep in mind that the 'first' sub key (mentioned above) is actually the fifty third sub key and that the fourth sub key is actually the fifty-sixth sub key.

IDEA requires fifty-two 16 bit sub keys. These are generated from a key of 128 bits, the bits are divided into blocks of 16 and the first 6 are taken, these are keys 1 through 6. The 128 bit key is then shifted 25 bits to the left and relocked. The second set of keys is taken. This process is repeated until all 52 keys are generated. The reason for the shift of the bits being 25 is to simply ensure that there is no repetition occurring. It would take 128×25 shifts before the key is repeated in its entirety. Next, plaintext comes in 64 bit blocks. The computational path of the overall IDEA encryption algorithm is shown in the Figure.2.1.

The plaintext is broken into four 16 bit sub-blocks (for ease of reference I will refer to these as X1, X2, X3, and X4). These blocks are the input to the algorithm. The bits are then manipulated (XOR, addition, multiplication) and between rounds the second and third (X2 and X3) are swapped. This process is repeated 8 times, each time incorporating 6 of the 52 keys. Finally the four sub-blocks are combined with the four final keys in an output transformation.

2.2 Basic Operations used in IDEA

The following are the three major operations associated with IDEA algorithm:

1. XOR: Bit-by-bit exclusive-OR, denoted as \oplus .
2. Modulo addition: Addition of integers modulo 2^{16} (modulo 65536) with inputs and outputs treated as unsigned 16-bit integers. This operation is denoted as \boxplus .
3. Modulo multiplication: Multiplication of integers modulo $2^{16} + 1$ (modulo 65537) with inputs and outputs treated as unsigned 16-bit integers. This operation is denoted as \odot .

2.3 Encryption, Decryption schemes and Sub key generation

The IDEA (International Data Encryption Algorithm) encrypts the 64-bit plaintext in to 64-bit cipher text using 128-bit secret key. The overall IDEA encryption and decryption consists of eight rounds followed by an output transformation. There are eight full rounds followed by an output transformation.

Figure.2.1 the IDEA Cryptographic Algorithm

Stage	Encryption	Equivalent to	Decryption
Round1	$Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 Z_4$ $Z_5 Z_6$	$Z[1..96]$	$Z_{49}^{-1}(-Z_{50})(-$ $Z_{51})Z_{52}^{-1}Z_{47}Z_{48}$
Round2	$Z_7 Z_8 Z_9 Z_{10}$ $Z_{11} Z_{12}$	$Z[97..128;2$ $6..89]$	$Z_{43}^{-1}(-Z_{45})(-$ $Z_{44})Z_{46}^{-1}Z_{41}Z_{42}$
Round3	$Z_{13} Z_{14} Z_{15}$ $Z_{16} Z_{17} Z_{18}$	$Z[90..128;1.$ $.25;51..82]$	$Z_{37}^{-1}(-Z_{39})(-$ $Z_{38})Z_{40}^{-1}Z_{35}Z_{36}$
Round4	$Z_{19} Z_{20} Z_{21}$ $Z_{22} Z_{23} Z_{24}$	$Z[83..128;1.$ $.50]$	$Z_{31}^{-1}(-Z_{33})(-$ $Z_{32})Z_{34}^{-1}Z_{29}Z_{30}$
Round5	$Z_{25} Z_{26} Z_{27} Z_{28}$ $Z_{29} Z_{30}$	$Z[76..128;1.$ $.43]$	$Z_{25}^{-1}(-Z_{27})(-$ $Z_{26})Z_{28}^{-1}Z_{23}Z_{24}$
Round6	$Z_{31} Z_{32} Z_{33}$ $Z_{34} Z_{35} Z_{36}$	$Z[44..75;10$ $1..128;1..36]$	$Z_{19}^{-1}(-Z_{21})(-$ $Z_{20})Z_{22}^{-1}Z_{17}Z_{18}$
Round7	$Z_{37} Z_{38} Z_{39}$ $Z_{40} Z_{41} Z_{42}$	$Z[37..100;1$ $26..128;1..2$ $9]$	$Z_{13}^{-1}(-Z_{15})(-$ $Z_{14})Z_{16}^{-1}Z_{11}Z_{12}$
Round8	$Z_{43} Z_{44} Z_{45}$ $Z_{46} Z_{47} Z_{48}$	$Z[30..125]$	$Z_7^{-1}(-Z_9)(-Z_8)Z_{10}^{-1}$ $Z_5 Z_6$
Transformation	$Z_{49} Z_{50} Z_{51}$ Z_{52}	$Z[23..86]$	$Z_{13}^{-1}(-Z_2)(-Z_3)Z_4^{-1}$ Z_1

Figure.2.2 The diagram of IDEA structure

2.3.2 Sub key generation

IDEA then takes 64-bit data blocks as input and produces 64-bit output data blocks. When encrypting data, IDEA first divides the 64-bit input data into four 16-bit data blocks, and uses six sub keys of the 52 generated sub keys to encrypt the four blocks in every round. The final transformation stage is identical to the transformation in each run except it utilizes the last four sub keys of the 52 generated sub keys. In summary, IDEA encrypts 64-bit plaintext with 52 16-bit sub keys to generate the corresponding cipher text with the same size as plaintext. The decryption scheme is the same as encryptions except it utilizes a different set of sub keys generated from the key of IDEA.

Each round can be divided in to 7 sub rounds. Each round uses six 16-bit sub keys generated from the original key.

2.3.1 The Structure of IDEA

The basic Structure of IDEA consists of eight full rounds followed by an output transformation is show in Figure 2.2. The 64-bit plaintext is divided in to 4 16-bit sub blocks and these blocks are encrypted using 128-bit key and results the cipher text. The structure also consists of key generation logic. This algorithm uses 52 sub keys which must be generated from the input 128-bit key. Each round consists of three basic operations and the first round output is connected as the input to the second round, then second round output is connected as the input to the third round and so on.

The 52 encryption sub keys Z_i , where $1 \leq i \leq 52$, are generated as follows. The first eight 16-bit encryption sub keys are retrieved directly from the original 128-bit key. That is, the first 16-bit of the 128-bit key is Z_1 , and the next 16-bit is Z_2 , and so on. After the first eight sub keys are taken out, a circular left shift of 25 bit positions is applied to the key, and the next eight keys are extracted from the resultant new key.

Decryption sub keys are generated according to its encryption sub keys in reverse sequence. That is, the first four sub keys used in the first round's transformation of the decryption process are derived from the four sub keys used in the final transformation of the encryption process, and the two sub keys used in the first round's MA of the decryption process are derived from the two sub keys used in the final round's MA of the encryption process, and so on.

Table 2.1: Encryption and decryption sub keys, $(-Z_i)$ denotes the additive inverse of Z_i , and Z_i^{-1} denotes the multiplicative inverse of Z_i .

Table 2.1. Shows the encryption and decryption sub keys generated from the 128-bit input key.

III. The Pipelined IDEA

The pipelining is a technique used in the design of computers and other digital electronic devices to increase their instruction throughput (the number of instructions that can be executed in a unit of time).

3.1 Concept of Loop Unrolling

Loop unrolling is the main compiler technique that allows reconfigurable architectures achieve large degrees of parallelism. Loops that do not carry dependencies from earlier iterations can theoretically be fully unrolled to achieve maximum parallelism.

3.2 Implementation of Pipelining Concept

To improve the speed of IDEA function, one should take advantage of the concept of pipeline. Pipelining is an implementation technique which allows multiple instructions to be overlapped in an execution, much like to an assembly line in industry.

3.3 Limitations for Throughput

With the introduction of million-gate FPGAs, the implementation of fully unrolled secret-key cryptographic algorithms became feasible. If the entire algorithm with full inner and outer loop pipelining fits on a single FPGA, the limiting factor for throughput is the achieved clock rate as follows:

$$\text{Throughput} = \text{block size} \times \text{clock rate}$$

Since the block size of IDEA is fixed at 64 bits, a 100 MHz clock rate implies a throughput of 6.4 Gbps.

3.4 Security Analysis

IDEA has a key length of 128 bit's, this is double the size of DES, if one was performing an exhaustive key search on the algorithm it would take 340282366920938463463374607431768211456 encryptions to recover.

V. Conclusion and Future Scope

5.1 Conclusion

The design and implementation of the IDEA algorithm on a single XC2VPX20-7FF896 proves that entire unrolled and pipelined complex cryptographic functions can be implemented on a single FPGA. The

limiting factors in achieving maximal throughput are the block size of the algorithm and the clock rate.

5.2 Future scope

An interesting research area is partial reprogram ability applied to cryptography. This is especially true for algorithms, which process data in small-sized blocks, whose other input is directly computed from the session key.

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